

Lexicological Studies in Old Literary Tibetan with Etymological Notes

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Introduction

“Lexicological Studies in Old Literary Tibetan with Etymological Notes” (LS) provides analytical information and etymological notes on the lexemes included in the Old Tibetan Dictionary (otdict.com). It complements the latter and contains only additional sources, whereas the principal sources of information are provided in the dictionary. The lexicological studies were undertaken within two projects financed by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (BI 1953/1-1 & BI 1953/1-2) in years 2017–2020 and 2020–2022. Unless otherwise stated, reconstructed forms quoted after STEDT are to be taken with a grain of salt. If not otherwise stated, all passages have been checked against scans available on IDP and Gallica. Transliteration follows (Bialek 2020b). Old Tibetan inscriptions have been transliterated after Richardson (1985), Li/Coblin (1987), and Iwao/Hill/Takeuchi (2009). Transliteration of western sources has been adjusted.

k

ke ke ru (#394)

D: 30b: skt. *kakkatara* / *karkketana*: white precious stone.

(Richardson 1972: 35, fn. 74) apparently some precious hard stone; (Uebach and Zeisler 2008: 320, fn. 21) renders skt. *karketana* 'cat's eye'; (Dotson 2009b: 60) chrysoberyl; p. 133, fn. 365: a white chrysoberyl, the word is borrowed from the Sanskrit *karketana*.

Objects referred to by the term *ke ke ru* had a greater value than those of turquoise (Or.8212/187: 58–61). The report from Or.8212/187: 58–9 is repeated in the OTC where grand councillor Dbays Snañ-bžer Zla-brcan is said to have been granted *nor bu rin po che yi yi ge* 'a letter of precious jewel' (PT 1287: 384). Accordingly, *ke ke ru* can be identified as a kind of precious jewel. I deem it controversial to establish the identity of *ke ke ru* solely on the basis of the meaning of the Skt. *karketana* 'quartz' (NWS). It is obvious that *ke ke ru* cannot be a direct loanword from Sanskrit; the forms are too divergent. It is more probable that *ke ke ru* was borrowed from another language which in turn borrowed the term from Sanskrit. The most plausible candidate for the donor language of OLT *ke ke ru* seems Chinese. I refrain from translating the term due to the doubts concerning its identity.

kwa ču khar (#726) 'stronghold of Kwa-ču'

bkay (#773) 'HON word; ¹behest; ²order'

In the OTA, *bkay* occurs in three types of phrase:

bkay scald 'gave order' (ITJ 750: 154, 155, 223, 238, 245, 250; Or.8212/187: 14, 21, 61)

bcan poe bkas bčad lit. 'decided by *bcan po*'s order' (ITJ 750: 121)

bcan po bkas 'by *bcan po*[s] order' (ITJ 750: 299, 305)

I consider the third phrase to be an abbreviated form of the second one, following the formalisation and standardisation of the administrative language of the Empire. Worth noting is the loss of the genitive marker after *bcan po*. This can be a feature of the formal language.

bkay was derived from *kha* 'mouth' by means of prefix *b-* (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))).

bkay gyod (#391) 'HON accusation'

WtS: 191a: Streit, Prozeß, Anklage; CM: 11b: *bkay čhad*; *khrims ñes*.

DTH: 48: la querelle; (Richardson 1985: 160) charge, accusation; (Li and Coblin 1987: 179) Li: =*bkay bkyon* reprimand, punishment; Coblin: guilt, penalty; (Richardson 1998b: 266) imputation; (Denwood 1999: 90) punishment; (Dotson 2009b: 116) accusation; p. 257: charge; (Hill 2011b: 14) allegation; p. 35: accusation; CM: 11b: *bkay čhad*; *bkay ñes*.

The term *bkay gyod* occurs only once in the OTA-I but it is known from several Central Tibetan inscriptions:¹

¹ The clause of the Lho-brag inscription which contains the compound is not fully legible and therefore omitted from the following survey.

(1)

(21) *zla goñ gī bu cha rgyud gyis // bcan poe* (22) *ža sñar // glo ba ma riñs na / noñs* (23) *myig gžan čī byuñ yañ ruñ / srog* (24) *srid la myī dbab par // [bkay gyod gyī (25) chigs]_{ABS} čī la bab pa las // [bkay gyod]_{ABS}* (26) *na gčīg gis smad čīñ bskyuñ bar* (27) *gnañ ño // (Žol N)*

Should the line of the descendants of Zla-goñ not become disloyal towards the *bcan po*, whatever other offence attempts may have appeared, [it is] allowed that, in order not to threaten (lit. cast upon) [their] life or sway, the accusation, while being each time (lit. with one time, *na gčīg gis*) diminished, shall be reduced upon the words of accusation have appeared on whatever [issue].

(2)

(61) *bu cha ypheld gyī nañ nas la la žig // bcan po* (62) *ža sñar glo ba riñs yañ dag par gyurd na gañ* (63) *ñes paḡi sgor / bkay gyod rmaḡo // pu nu po gžan /* (64) *khrin la myī gdags srog srid la myī dbab par gnañ* (65) *ño // (Žol N)*

If someone from among the descendants should become actually disloyal towards the *bcan po*, the accusation shall be investigated exclusively from the one who has committed the offence.² It is not allowed to relate any other *pu nu po* to *khrin* nor to threaten [their] life or sway.

(3)

snañ bzañ ydus koñ gi bu cha yphel (43) *rgyud kyī bran žiñ / ybrog sog chal las scogs pa / naḡ žar rabs čhad daḡ / bka* (44) *gyod la thogs na yañ / phyag tu myī bžes / gžan myī sbyin / (Žwa W)*

Even if [his] family should ever become extinct or [they] should be involved in an accusation, slaves, fields, summer pastures, straw-lands, and forests, among others, of the descendants of Snañ-bzañ Ydus-koñ, should not be confiscated (lit. seized to the authorities' hand) nor given to others.

(4)

ma ñes par srog srid la dku (29) *dañ gnod pa byed pa žig yod na / su la bab [kyañ r]uñ / dkuḡ* (30) *ba dañ / pheḡu paḡi ño khar myī dor ba / dku ba du gtogs pa //* (31) *bka gyod la gdags par gnañ ba dañ / (Žwa E)*

If there is a one [single person] tricking and harming [their] life or property without there being any [other] offence [on their side], whoever it may be, it is allowed to charge (lit. bind to accusation) the one who belongs to tricksters [and] does not despise the tricksters and the *pheḡu pas*.

To summarise, *bkay gyod* occurs in the following phrases:

<i>bkay gyod</i>		<i>gyod</i>		
<i>bkay gyod la</i>	<i>čhags</i>			
<i>bkay gyod</i>	<i>smad čīñ bskyuñ</i>	<i>gyod</i>	<i>bskyuñ</i>	<i>Žwa W 40</i>

² *gañ ñes paḡi sgor* means literally 'at the door of the one who has committed an offence'.

<i>bkaḡ gyod</i>	<i>rma</i>	<i>gyod</i> (myi) <i>rmas</i>	PT 1055: 42, 88; PT 1283: 229; ITJ 742: 24 ³
<i>bka gyod la</i>	<i>gdags / thogs</i> ⁴	<i>gyod la ḡdogs/myi gdags</i>	PT 1283: 584; Žwa W 39
<i>bkaḡ gyod gyī chigs</i>			

I have added analogous phrases with *gyod* so that there can be no doubt that *gyod* is the syntactic head of *bkaḡ gyod*. Regarding its meaning, from Žol (and possibly also Žwa W) it occurs that *bkaḡ gyod* was related to an offence against a *bcan po*, but in Žwa E it is mentioned following an offence towards descendants of Myaṅ Snaṅ-bzaṅ Ḳdus-koṅ, the grandfather of Myaṅ Tiṅ-ṅe-ḡjin who was the beneficiary of the edict perpetuated in the Žwa inscriptions. The passage is obscure on that matter but the use of the honorific *bkaḡ gyod* suggests that in fact (and against all previous interpretations) an offence against either the *bcan po* or other authorities is meant. Such an offence under normal circumstances would bring consequences to the whole family not sparing anybody. The edict guarantees special rights to those descendants of Myaṅ Snaṅ-bzaṅ Ḳdus-koṅ who have not committed any offence against the *bcan po* and neither their life nor sway is endangered in case one of their relatives incurs a penalty.

bkaḡ gyod was a technical term from the legal practice of the Tibetan Empire. Authorities could relate (*ḡdogs*; lit. attach) one to *bkaḡ gyod*, investigate (*rma*), or reduce (*smad*, *bskyuṅ*) it. A person could be involved (*čhags*, *thogs*, lit. attached) in a *bkaḡ gyod*. *bkaḡ gyod* ensued from some kind of illegal action against a *bcan po* (disloyalty, offence, trickstery, or harm), and could have serious consequences, including confiscation of wealth and possibly also execution of the person (*srog srid la dbab*). Accordingly, I translate the term as ‘accusation (in consequence of an illegal action against a *bcan po*)’ and the collocation **bkaḡ gyod ḡdogs* as ‘to charge’, lit. ‘to bind sb. to an accusation’.

bkaḡ grims (#758) ‘HON sovereign law’

Mvy: 5307: *maryādām vyavasthāpayanti* (s.v. *khirms kyi skabs su ni bkaḡ khirms bčāḡ*); Desg: 28a: *lex, loi* (s.v. *bkaḡ khirms*); Sch: 11a: *ein Gesetz* (s.v. *bkaḡ khirms*); Cs: 101a: *a law* (s.v. *bkaḡ khirms*); Jä: 12a: *Gesetz, Gebot* (s.v. *bkaḡ khirms*); J: 12b: *law, commandment* (s.v. *bkaḡ khirms*); D: 61a: *a law, commandment* (s.v. *bkaḡ khirms*); GC: 26a: *khirms yig lta bu* (s.v. *bkaḡ khirms*); BYD: 18b: *bkaḡ grims kyi yi ge = bkaḡ khirms kyi yi ge = bkaḡ khirms kyi yig čha*; Gs: 26b: *hon. a law, an edict* (s.v. *bkaḡ khirms*); BTC: 69a: *khirms* (s.v. *bkaḡ khirms*); WtS.3: 191b: *bkaḡ khirms* ‘gesetzliche Anordnung, Gesetz’ (3: 190b); CM: 11b: *rgyal pos bkas bčad paḡi khirms* (s.v. *bkaḡ khirms*).

(Thomas 1936: 283) law; p. 286, fn. 22: ordinance-usage; DTH: 31: *la loi*; TLTD.3: 113: law; (Uray 1972b: 27) law; (Uray 1975: 161) lois; (Richardson 1990b: 50) code of law; (Dotson 2007a: 25) law; (Dotson 2007b: 39) official law; p. 69: law (honorific); (Dotson 2009b: 85) the laws; p. 257: official law; variant of *bkaḡ khirms*; (Hill 2011b: 26) the laws; (Scherrer-Schaub 2012: 230) the [Code of] Law.

Following previous studies, I identify the second syllable with the lexeme *khirms*, CT ¹right, not in the abstract sense in which the word is generally understood with us, but in more or less concrete applications, such as administration of justice, law, judgment, sometimes also implying custom, usage, duty; ²law; ³administration of justice; ⁴action, lawsuit; ⁵use, custom,

³ Compare also *gyod smed* (= CT *rmed*) in ITJ 738: 3v71.

⁴ I understand *thogs* as an intransitive equivalent of *ḡdogs* (cf. CDTD.V: 556) and a near-synonym of *čhags* ‘to be attached (to sth.)’.

usage' (J: 50b). The honorific classifier *bkay* indicates that a *bcan po* was involved in the legislation process that resulted in *bkay khrims*. Accordingly, I translate the lexeme as 'sovereign law',⁵ in order to distinguish it from *khrims* that might have been passed by local authorities.

bkay tañ (#404) 'HON decree'

Cs: 53b: command, precept; Sch: 228b: od[er] *thañ* Befehl, Vorsicht; p. 10b: = *bkay scal*, *bkay luñ* ein gesprochenes Wort, ein gegebener Befehl, eine erlassene Verordnung od[er] Vorschrift; Jä: 13a: Befehl, Edict; J: 13b: order, edict; Desg: 445a: *mandatum*, *edictum*, ordre, édit; D: 63a: *bkay thañ* = *bkay luñ* order; edict; written order; command; commandment; precept; BTC: 71b: lo rgyus sam. kha čhems; Gs: 28b: biography, testament, the writings of a deceased author; WtS.4: 196a: Erlaß.

DTH: 40: réglementation; p. 190: = *bkay thañ*; (Karmay 2007: 244) *bkay thañ* = *bkay thañ yig* record, proceedings; (Dotson 2009b: 257) document, testament.

bkay tañ seems to be a *hapax legomenon* in OLT but *bkay thañ* is well known in lexicographical sources on CT although it appears that the sole source for the provided glosses was *Bkay yañ dag payi chad ma las mdo btus pa* (D 4352, *sna chogs*, čo 173v1–203v7; *apud* BCRD) attributed to Khri Sroñ-lde-brcan. According to BCRD, this is the only canonical text in which the honorific occurs and thus six times. In ITJ 750 the formation is attested in the annual entry for the winter of the year 702/3:

(1)

yum yon čañ do na bźugs (142) *čĩñ* / *yđun ma yañ yon čañ dor bsduste* / *šĩd gyi bkay tañ čhen po bor* (ITJ 750)

While the mother was abiding in *Yon-čañ-do*, the council, also convened at *Yon-čañ-do*, issued a great **decree** concerning (lit. of) funeral ceremonies.

bkay tañ was issued during the winter council and therefore the effective force behind the event was not the *bcan po* himself, although we can assume that it concerned if not the *bcan po* then at least the royal family – the term is clearly an honorific. Secondly, *bkay tañ* is determined by *šĩd*, a morpheme well known from funeral context (see below). In previous studies the reading **šĩñ* was preferred instead of the clearly visible *-d*:

Fig. 1. *šid* in ITJ 750: 142

The final consonant can be compared with *-ñ* of *bkay tañ* and, on the other hand, with *d-* of *dor*, both occurring in the same line of the text:

Fig. 2. *tañ* in ITJ 750: 142

⁵ I understand *sovereign* here as an adjective with the meaning 'possessing supreme or ultimate power' (OED: 1381a).

Fig. 3. *dor* in ITJ 750: 142

The following translations have been previously proposed for the clause in question:

“La grande réglementation des forêts fut établie.” (DTH: 40)

“They abolished the great wooden document(s) [in favor of paper].” (Dotson 2009b: 101)⁶

In addition, (Bsod-nams-skyid 1992: 76, fn. 69) paraphrase the clause as: *śiñ las bzos paḡi bkay khrims kyī yi ge čhen po bkrams pa*.

I deem the ‘correction’ of *śid* to *śiñ* unwarranted. As against Dotson’s statement that “funerary practices might not have come the (sic) jurisdiction of the political council” (Dotson 2009b: 102, fn. 215), the following quotation suggests the contrary to have been the case:

(2)

dgun ḡdun (301) *dra byer ḡdus / bruñ pa žaň tre goň phyuň ste / čog ro rma goň bčug pa daň / seň go ḡphan la skyes phyuň ste / myaň* (302) *ḡdus khoň bčug paḡi rcis bgyīste / jo mo khri bcun gyī mdad btaň* (ITJ 750)

The winter council convened at Dra-bye [and], having made an account of the dismissal of *bruñ pa žaň* Tre-goň, the installation of Čog-ro Rma-goň [in his place], and of the dismissal of Seň-go ḡphan-la-skyes and the installation of Myaň ḡdus-khoň [in his place], organised the funeral ceremony for *jo mo* Khri-bcun.

That preparations of *bcun po*’s funeral fell under the jurisdiction of the council is very probable. The heir to the throne usually could not take care of the preparations himself because he was too young, frequently an infant. On the other hand, entrusting a single person, for instance a grand councillor, with the related duties entailed the risk of his misusing the power in a moment that is always critical for any hereditary political system. Thus, I consider the reading *śid* correct and translate it as ‘funeral ceremony’ (see s.v.).

Another crucial issue for the interpretation of the clause is the meaning of the verbal phrase *bkay taň bor*. In (Bialek 2018a: 1.374) I proposed rendering *bor* as ‘issued’, arguing that the verb is “a ‘verbaliser’ similar to the CT *ḡdebs* or MT *rgyab* (all three verbs, apart from being used as verbalisers in different periods of Tibetan language, share the core meaning of ‘to throw, to cast’)” (ibid., pp. 374–5, fn. 5). I have also argued that the use of a concrete verbaliser (i.e. a light verb) was fixed and therefore we find *byaň bu ḡbor* but *khram ḡdebs*, even though in terms of the physical characteristics and functions of their referents both *byaň bu* and *khram* were wooden devices used for keeping records. It follows that the base lexeme from which *bkay taň* was derived must have been a one that could function as a direct object of *bor*. No such a compound as *!thaň byaň* seems to have ever existed. However, some of the

⁶ Dotson notices that his translation is problematic just as the correction of *śid* to *śiñ* is and proposes four alternatives: “they made/abolished the great funerary/wooden documents” (ibid., p. 102, fn. 215), depending on the interpretation of *śid/śiñ* and the verb *bor*.

lexicographical sources gloss *bkay thañ* as an honorific of *thañ yig* (cf., e.g., J: 228b, s.v. *thañ*). As far as I was able to ascertain *thañ yig* occurs only twice in OLT documents: Or.15000/35: v1 & ITN 1429A: 1, but unfortunately without a verb. On the other hand, in CT we find compounds that have *yig* as their second constituent and in addition function as direct objects of the verb *bor*, for instance, *bčay yig bor* (for other examples see BCRD & BDRC). On these grounds, I reconstruct *bkay tañ* as an honorific of *thañ yig* ‘decree’, lit. ‘a written document [containing] jurisdictions’.⁷

bkay nan (#788) ‘HON instruction’

J: 13b: C[entral Tibet] **ka nán*, instruction (s.v. *bkay*); BTC: 75a: ¹do gal čhen pos ydoms paŷi bkay; ²bkay bkyon; BTK: 28, fn. 1: *bkay nan te bkay bkyon no* (s.v. *bkay nand*); Gs: 29a: criticism (from superiors); WTS.4: 198a: resp. strenger Befehl; CM: 12a: *bkay brda nan mo. bkay brda bcan bčun čan*.

DTH:52: *hâte*; TLTD:III: 113a: stern command; (Takeuchi 1995: 241) edict, proclamation; (Dotson 2009b: 125) commandment; p. 257: condemnation, suppression.

In OLT, *bkay nan* is attested in three different contexts:

I. Direct object of *scald*

(1)

stams las čhad pa/ bla nas bkay nan scald par ji gnañ žes/ (PT 1297.2: 4)

“Would [you] allow that the authorities give *bkay nan* to those who are being persecuted?”⁸

(2)

myi mčhi[r] myi [r]uñ bar bkay nan scal čin/ chal byir mčhis nas/ (Or.15000/119r: 1–2)⁹

Being given the *bkay nan* that [it] would not be correct not to come, [I] came to Chal-byi.

(3)

sman yar myi mčhir myi ruñ bar bkay nan scald/ (Or.15000/119v: 5)¹⁰

[They] gave the *bkay nan* that it would not be correct for the medicine not to arrive here.

(4)

blon pal sum gyis/ bkay nan scal te/ ydi [n]¹¹ stag bor la brjañ ba/ (ITN 245r: 1)

Councillor Pal-sum gave *bkay nan*; [these] were sent to Stag-bor.

II. Direct object of *mjad*

(5)

⁷ For this interpretation compare *thañ khram* ‘a tally of jurisdiction’ (Bialek 2018a: 2.139ff.) A comprehensive analysis of the semantics of *thañ* can be found in (Bialek 2018a: 1.499ff.)

⁸ On double object constructions ‘DO[REC/BEN]_{ABS} IO[THEM]_{ABS} V’ with verbs of giving, see (Bialek 2023b: 31f.) In rendering *stams las čhad* as ‘to be persecuted’ I follow Coblin’s interpretation of *stams las gčod* as ‘to persecute, turannize’ (Coblin 1991b: 527b) which is based on Chinese equivalents. The meaning of *stams* remains unknown.

⁹ For slightly different transliterations see TLTD.2: 159 and (Takeuchi 1998: 60, text 181).

¹⁰ For slightly different transliterations see TLTD.2: 159 and (Takeuchi 1998: 60, text 181).

¹¹ [n] is tentatively reconstructed following Thomas (TLTD.2: 356) but the letter cannot be identified any more.

blon čhen po man čhad bro scalte/ bkay nan čen pho mjad nas/ (ITJ 750: 305–6)

Having sworn (lit. bestowed an oath) [all] from grand councillors downward, [the *bcan po*] prepared a great *bkay nan*.

(6)

śi sos kyi gla dgra čhud ma ychal bar gyis śig par ydrul ba las bkay nan ma mjad par gsol// (Or.15000/497r: 8–9)¹²

Upon travelling so that the wages for *śi sos* were made without the enemy willing to enter (?), [I] request that, no *bkay nan* is prepared.

(7)

śiñ śan_{du} droñs śig par bkay nan bla nas mjad_{par} thug_s rje čhen po [g]zīgs// (Or.15000/90: 7–8)
Look graciously so that the *bkay nan* is prepared by the authorities that [barley] is conveyed to Śiñ-śan (=Mazār-Tāgh).

III. Modifier in a determinative phrase

(8)

rgya drug yjañ las scogs pa mthayī rgyal po// bar du čhab srid la sdo žiñ rcol/ ba kun kyañ/ bkay nan gyī mthu dañ/ rlabs gyīs/ bthul bas nī re thag bčad/ (ITJ 751: 36v2–3)

Because [they] also tamed the border kings of the Chinese, the Dru-gu, the Yjañ and others (all those who were endeavouring for and were posing threat to the realm in the middle) through the impression and power of [their] *bkay nan*, [they] dashed [their] hopes.

The use of *bkay nan* with *scald* parallels the verb phrase *bkay scald* of the OTA allowing us to see in *bkay nan* an attributive compound with the noun *bkay* as its head and the syllable *nan* probably representing another word that functions as attribute of *bkay*. This is confirmed by the lack of words in *-nan* with verbs of giving, such as *ybul* or *gsol*. However, in OLT corpus, *bkay* is not recorded as direct object of *mjad*.¹³ The diverging phraseology suggests that *bkay nan* in *bkay nan scal* might be a different formation than *bkay nan* in *bkay nan mjad*. This assumption is additionally supported by the phrase *bkay non* (sic) *mjad* in the following two passages:

(9)

srog srid la/ dmaḡ bar byed pa žīg yod na/ bkay non bla nas mjad par gnañ ño// (Žol N 56–8)

It is granted that, if there is anybody doing harm to [their] life or dominion, the authorities will prepare a *bkay non*.

(10)

gžan gyīs mnar taḡ/ staḡs las čhad na/ bka non bla nas mjad pa dañ/ (Žwa W 35–6)

Should [they] have suffered through others or have been persecuted, a *bka non* will be prepared by the authorities.

¹² The translation is largely tentative. For a slightly different transliteration, see TLTD.2: 147.

¹³ We only find *bkay gros mjad* (PT 1287: 204; ITJ 737.3: 15), the honorific equivalent of *gros* 'advice' attested with the verb *byed* (OTDO, *passim*).

In yet another context, we find the string *bkay nan thur*:

(11)

bla na[s] bkay nan thur drags s{t}e mchi[---] (Or.8212/187: 92)

The order, being a harsh punishment, came from the authorities.

OLT possesses two analogously formed compounds which are both nouns: *nan thur* (see s.v.) and *non thur*; cf.:

(12)

slan čhad ybañs kyi (r7) ldum ra yphrog čin ycher myi gnañ bar// non thur gyī phyag rgya č gnañ žes gsol pa las// (PT 1085; *apud* OTDO)

[They] requested: “Would [you] grant [us] a document (bearing an official seal)¹⁴ of *non thur* so that it is not allowed later to rob and damage subjects’ gardens?”

Although the latter is a *hapax legomenon* (PT 1085: r7),¹⁵ it seems that the compounds have complementary distribution; they do not share any collocations. They were most probably distinct compounds. The meaning of *nan thur* has been reconstructed as *‘punishment’ (see s.v.), whereas the meaning of *non thur* seems to be different and I think it might have been something like *‘strict instruction; monition; monitory letter’, i.e. a formal notice admonishing a person to refrain from doing something specified, or commanding a person to do something specified. In later lexicographical sources, we observe an apparent conflation of *nan thur* and *non thur*, maybe facilitated by the fact that both formed complex lexical units with *bkay*. Dictionaries provide only the form *nan thur* (or its variants *nan tur* and *nan stur*) but ascribe to it two different meanings: 1. punishment; and 2. instruction.

bkay nan scal has clearly negative connotation; I interpret *bkay nan* here as an appositive compound of the underlying structure **bkay nan thur*, lit. ‘an order that is a punishment’ (see s.v. *nan thur*). Its actual meaning seems to have been ‘reprimand’, or similar. This however must be a compound distinct from *bkay nan* in *bkay nan mjad* with its rather neutral emotional load. Judging by its context, *bkay nan* in (8) must be the same word. *bkay non mjad* in (9) & (10) requires the meaning ‘monition’. We can summarise the analysis as follows:

<i>nan thur</i>	‘punishment’	(11) & s.v. <i>nan thur</i>	
<i>non thur</i>	‘monition; monitory letter’	(12)	
<i>bkay nan scal</i>	‘reprimand’	(1)–(4)	< * <i>bkay nan thur</i>
<i>bkay nan mjad</i>	‘instruction’	(5)–(7)	< * <i>bkay non thur</i>
<i>bkay nan gyi</i> NP	‘instruction’	(8)	< * <i>bkay non thur</i>
<i>bkay non mjad</i>	‘monition; monitory letter’	(9)–(10)	

In conclusion, OLT had originally two distinct compounds *nan thur* and *non thur*. The former formed an appositional compound *bkay nan* ‘reprimand’, whereas the latter received an honorific equivalent *bkay non* ‘instruction’. Our sources indicate that already by the mid-8th c.

¹⁴ For this meaning of *phyag rgya*, see (Takeuchi 1995: 259).

¹⁵ In Or.15000/467: v3 & v5 we find *non* in otherwise the same linguistic context, which fact suggests that it should be emended with *non thur*.

the forms were confused (see *bkay nan* for *bkay non* in ITJ 750: 306 for the year 746/7).¹⁶ In addition, the meaning of *bkay nan* evolved from ‘monition; monitory letter’ to ‘instruction’ with less negative connotation. (1) is an example difficult to interpret for the meaning ‘instruction’ seems to better fit the context but the verb is *scald*. This passage might present a case of collocational conflation due to the merger of *bkay nan* with *bkay non* after which *bkay nan* in the meaning ‘instruction’ could also be used with *scald*. In general, the situation seems very complicated and requires further in-depth study, including early post-imperial sources.

bkay só (#405) ‘HON code of law’

DTH: 63: compulsory contribution; pp. 69–70: apparently = ‘[special] command tax’, i.e. a special levy at the outset of the new reign; (Dotson 2007b: 29) dice edict; (Dotson 2009b: 129) dice edict; p. 257: proclamation (?); (Walter 2009: 183) dice edict; (Dotson 2011a: 83, fn. 9) a dice edict that comes from the centre of the empire, but it also carries with it a sense of something approaching ‘amnesty’. It is not exactly a reprieve or a pardon, but rather extends the possibility of such to certain cases where punishment would otherwise be a certainty, and thus offers defendants the possibility of being let off the hook by a roll of the dice; (Dotson 2015b: 283, fn. 1) proclamation, literal ‘dice edict’.

In (Bialek 2018a: 2.35, fn. 2) I stated that *bkay só* might be an honorific of *só chigs* ‘dice code’. ITJ 740 contains one phrase with both formations:

(1)

stagī loyī bkay só byuñ beyi só chīgs gyi zūs lan / pho brañ nas mchīspa (l. 238, *apud* OTDO)
answers of a dice code of the code of law of the tiger year that arrived from the court

The literal translation of the part *stagī loyī bkay só byuñ beyi só chīgs* would be ‘dice code of the code of law that occurred in the year of the tiger’. From this we can infer that *bkay só* was issued once a year and that it consisted of smaller units that were called *só chigs*. Accordingly, I interpret *bkay só* as a ‘code of law’ composed of at least several dice codes (*só chigs*, eleven in the case of ITJ 740), that is laws that could be implemented by means of dice. The honorific classifier *bkay* might have been added to stress that codes of law were issued by official institutions only and had an over-regional character. In addition, the above passage uses the verb *byuñ* in connection with *bkay só*. This allows us to reconstruct *pyuñ* in Or.8212/187: 18 as **byuñ*.

bkug (#393) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ¹to summon; ²to subjugate; to subject (with *ybañs su*)’

In the OTA-I the agent argument of *bkug*, if mentioned, is always a human being. The verb occurs in the following collocations:

AGENT	PATIENT	OBL	V	
	<i>žañ žuñ thaṃs čad</i>	<i>ybañsu</i>	<i>bkug</i>	PT 1288: 13–4
HUMAN _{ERG}	<i>glo bo dañ rcañ rhyay</i>		<i>bkug</i>	PT 1288: 21–2
	<i>pha los</i>		<i>bkug</i>	ITJ 750: 59, 213
	<i>myī mañ po</i>		<i>bkug</i>	ITJ 750: 124
	<i>pha los mañ pho</i>		<i>bkug</i>	ITJ 750: 182
	<i>pha los čen po</i>		<i>bkug</i>	ITJ 750: 294–5

¹⁶ Alternatively, this change could have been introduced into the text by a later copyist.

ce čī man čad ybañsu brkug Or.8212/187: 22

The examples leave no doubt that the object of *bkug* must have referred to humans, specifically collectives of humans.¹⁷

Regarding the meaning of the verb, we have to differentiate between two instances depending on the legal status of the population towards which the action was directed. Basically, when a foreign population (Žaň-žuň, Glo-bo, Rcaň-rhyaḡ, Ce-či) was meant to be included in the Tibetan Empire, *bkug* denoted their subjugation under the sway of the Tibetan *bcan po*.¹⁸ On the other hand, when a Tibetan or foreign but already subjugated population (*pha los, myi*) was referred to, the action was rather that of summoning, i.e. ordering the respective group to be present.¹⁹

bkum (#403) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [PAT]_{ABS} 'to kill'

[C] *gum*

In the OTA *bkum* is attested with the following arguments:

AGENT	PATIENT	
[---]	[---]	PT 1288: 5
	<i>bal po yu sna kug tī</i>	PT 1288: 12
<i>thoň myis</i>	<i>kam khri bzaň bye ḡday</i>	PT 1288: 25
	<i>(dug ma maň po)</i>	ITJ 750: 93
	<i>guň rton</i>	ITJ 750: 121
	<i>rgya maň po</i>	ITJ 750: 122
	<i>khu ḡbyur lod bcan</i>	ITJ 750: 144
	<i>ldeg ren pa log pa rnams</i>	ITJ 750: 151–2
	<i>rgya</i>	Or.8212/187: 6
	<i>khu ḡbyur lod bcan</i>	Dx.12851v: 2

With one exception, the agent argument is never stated and the patient argument in absolutive has always a human referent. The case marking of the agent argument is supported by data from other OLT sources:

(1)

mon ka ḡi ni stag čhig pa /

stag bkum nī [zu ces]_{ERG} bkum / [...]

rcaň braň nī ya stod kyi

A lone tiger of Mon-ka –

[One] killed the tiger. Zu-ce killed [it].

In Rcaň-braň, of the highs

¹⁷ Ce-či seems to have been understood as a toponym by Thomas (DTH: 63) and Dotson (Dotson 2009b: 129). However, the complement *ybañsu* clarifies that humans must have been meant.

¹⁸ The collocation *ybañsu bkug*, lit. 'subjugated as subjects', can also, for the sake of conciseness, be rendered as 'subjected', i.e. it describes the action of bringing so. under one's control. Strictly speaking, in Or.8212/187: 22 the verb used is *brkug*. It seems that the prefix *-r-* was just a scribal error, in which Or.8212/187 abounds. Since I was not able to trace any other case of *brkug* or *'rkug* in OT documents, which could shed more light on the issue, I leave this question open and treat *brkug* as synonymous with *bkug*.

¹⁹ The action undertaken towards suitable commoners from among the Žaň-žuň and Mard peoples (ITJ 750: 213) should be interpreted as summoning rather than subjugation. The described events took place in 719/20, that is, long time after the subjugation of the Žaň-žuň. If Mard = Ladakh, in the 8th century Ladakh and the territory of the Žaň-žuň were perceived of as integral parts of the Empire.

thañ prom nī rgod ldiñ bay // A white-winged one, a soaring vulture –
rgod bkum nī [zu ces]_{ERG} bkum // (PT 1287: 221–2) [One] killed the vulture. Zu-ce killed [it].

(2)

[bdagis]_{ERG} pha bkum nas // (PT 1287: 326)
 I killed my father.

The argument structure [AGT]_{ERG} [PAT]_{ABS} agrees with data from CT and modern dialects (cf. CDTD.V: 226).

bkye (#409) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to send’

In the OTA *bkye* occurs only with a THEME argument which in both cases in *riñ lugs* ‘messenger’. The clauses lack the AGENT argument and so the argument structure of the verb must be complemented from other sources, cf.:

(1)

[lha nmams kyis]_{ERG} sprul pa mañ po bkye yo // (PT 981: r91)
 Deities sent many magical transformations.

bkyon (#408) ‘scorching criticism; accusation’

WtS.4: 215b: tadeln, schelten, zurechtweisen, beschuldigen, anfeinden.

(Richardson 1952a: 22) = *bkaγ bkyon*, Bell: rebuke; the word is used often in the Tun huang Annals and Chronicle in connection with the disgrace of ministers; (Chang 1959: 131) disgrace; (Beckwith 1993: 106, fn. 135) disgrace.

I assume that OLT *bkyon* is related to CT *bkyon* ‘to beat; *bkaγ bkyon pa* resp[ectful] to chastise with words, to scold’ (J: 14b). The OLT form *bkyon* has been preserved in modern dialects in the complex honorific *bkaγ bkyon*: Sapi, Khalatse [kabkjon], Nurla, Leh [kapkjon], Shigatse [kāpcǝ], Rmastod [kaptɕon] ‘scolding’ (CDTD: 152). In OLT *bkyon* occurs as a verb or as a noun. In the latter case it can be either the subject of the verb *bab* (√*bab*) or the object of *phab* (√*pab*). The latter usage can be compared with CT *skyon γbebs* glossed by Jäschke as ‘to charge one with a crime, to calumniate’ (32a, s.v. *skyon*).

In OLT, *bkyon* as a verb is attested, e.g., in:

(1)

*dbyī chab kyī bu cha la la žig gis / ma bsams ste sñi[n] (282) riñs na yañ // [gañ sñiñ riñs pa]_{ABS} ñi
 ce yi sgor myi bkyon re // [gžan blo la ma gthogs pa rnam[s] (283) la]_{ALL} / bkyon re /* (PT 1287)
 Should any descendant of Dbyi-chab, not having intended, ever become disloyal, [one] denounces the one who became disloyal in the presence (*sgor*) of *ñi ce*.²⁰ [One] shall not condemn others who were not involved in the plan.

²⁰ Whatever its meaning, *ñi ce* seems to be based on *ñid* ‘self’. The second constituent may be identical with *che* as quoted by Jäschke from Balti ‘sex **p’ó-t’sē*, *mó-t’sē**, male, female sex’ (J: 450b, s.v. *che*). However, I doubt that the meaning ‘sex’ given by Jäschke is the original one. Tibetan writers explain *ñi ce* as ‘ñi che. ñin gañ gi che las med pa’ (BYD: 179b), ‘phyogs reγam čuñ zad kyī don te’ (DSM: 212a), ‘ñi

(2)

žañ snañ la [*bcan po*]_{ABS} myi *bkyon du bkyon žes byas so* // (PT 1287: 309)

To Žañ-snañ [he] said: “Does [one] severely criticise the *bcan po* or not?”

These two passages provide us with two seemingly distinct argument structures of the verb:

1. HUM_{ABS} *bkyon*

2. HUM_{ALL} *bkyon*

Since in OLT no intransitive verb is allowed to have its sole argument in allative, we can be sure that *bkyon* was a transitive verb. I read *la* in PT 1287: 283 as a partitive allative, meaning that the referent was not completely affected by the action (see (Bialek 2023b: 26ff.)) This interpretation agrees with the content of the clause that states that those not involved in disloyalty shall not be condemned. The clause negates (*re*) condemnation and therefore the patient-referent could not be affected by the action. From other similar usages of *re* in PT 1287 we infer that it was applied either after v1 or v3 of transitive verbs, whereas the converb *bkyon tam* (ITJ 737.1: 343, *apud* OTDO) attests to the underlying **bkyond*.

In OLT, not only disloyal ones could be exposed to *bkyon* but also a *bcan po*. At least in the latter case it is rather improbable that *bkyon* denoted an action that was carried out in the presence of the patient-referent of the verb; it is hardly imaginable that a subject could scold a *bcan po* in public. Therefore I propose interpreting *bkyon* in a more general way as ‘to severely criticise’. In legal context, this sense might have evolved towards ‘to denounce, to condemn’. This agrees with the fact that in several cases in the OTA-I *bkyon* followed after sb. had become disloyal to the *bcan po*. Therefore, I interpret *bkyon* as denoting an action of publicly declaring somebody to be evil and condemning the person.

In the OTA-I *bkyon* is used only as a noun in the collocations *bkyon bab* and *bkyon phab*. In accordance with the above analysis, I suggest translating them as ‘came under scorching criticism’ and ‘passed scorching criticism on; to denounce’ respectively.²¹ I understand the noun *bkyon* as derived by conversion from the original v3 of the verb.

Below I present contextual analyses of the passages from the OTA-I in order to provide additional information on legal and social aspects of the actions denoted by *bkyon bab* and *bkyon phab*.

(3)

che). kher rkyañ’ (BNY: 157, fn. 30), ‘ñi che ste ydir (PT 1287:282 – JB) kher rkyañ ñam ñuñ śos kyi don’ (STK: 172, fn. 18).

²¹ The phrases have been differently understood previously: *bkyon bab* ‘khrims čhad phog pa’ (BTK: 14, fn. 1), ‘to be disgraced’ (Hill 2011b: 12); *bkyon phab* ‘to indicate for crimes’ (Beckwith 1993: 61, fn. 41), ‘an archaic form often used in inscriptions and Dunhuang documents to denote the act of punishing or condemning, particularly with regard to people being executed by royal order’ (Wangdu and Diemberger 2000: 11–2), ‘executed’ (Wangdu and Diemberger 2000: 36), ‘this phrase, *bkyon phab*, indicates the disgrace of a minister and the end of his career, often resulting in death’ (Dotson 2009b: 92, fn. 173), ‘to be disgraced, lit. ‘to bring reprimands down upon’ {Dotson, 2009b #419: 257; Dotson does not distinguish between the intransitive *bkyon bab* and transitive *bkyon phab*}, ‘to bring down reprimands on someone’ (Hill 2011b: 28).

[---] *bkyon phab nas bkumo / mkhar sdur ba bśīg go / (PT 1288: 5)*

After [they] had passed scorching criticism [---], [they] killed [him].

The passage is incomplete. On the basis of an account from the OTC, Dotson reconstructed the name of the person denounced as Myañ Mañ-po-rje Žañ-snañ (Dotson 2009b: 81). In the preceding line we read that somebody (the name is not preserved) became disloyal (l. 4). Dotson related the two events to each other. Indeed, in PT 1287 we read: *myañ gis kyañ glo ba riñste / bkyon phab pay / (260) yīn no / 'Myañ [Mañ-po-rje Žañ-snañ], having become disloyal, was denounced (lit. was the one on whom one had passed scorching criticism).'*

(4)

ra sañ rje spuñ rye ryuñ dañ / khu khri sña dgru zuñ la bkyon bab (73) ste / (ITJ 750)

Spuñ-rye-ryuñ, the lord of the Ra-sañ, and Khu Khri-sña Dgru-zuñ came under scorching criticism.

These events concern the winter of 678/9, whereas two years later, during the winter council of 680/1, wealth of Khu Khri-sña Dgru-zuñ and Ra-sañ-rje Spuñ-rye-ryuñ was confiscated (ITJ 750: 75–6). The reasons for the accusation are unknown.

(5)

deyi dgun mgar la bkyon phab ste (ITJ 750: 128)

That winter, [they] passed scorching criticism on the Mgar family.

The accusation took place in the winter 698/9 and in the winter 699/700 wealth of the denounced (*bkyon bab*) was confiscated.

(6)

deyi rjes la gliñ riñs cal du khu mañ po rje lha zuñ (155) la bkyon phab / (ITJ 750)

After that, at Gliñ-riñs-cal, [they] passed scorching criticism against Khu Mañ-po-rje Lha-zuñ.

(7)

ɣdun ma / na mar du ɣbon da rgyal bcan zuñ dañ / blon čhen pho khri gzigs gyis bsduste / lho ɣdus sregs (158) la bkyon phab / (ITJ 750)

The council, *dbon* Bcan-zuñ, the king of the Dags-po, and grand councillor [Dbays] Khri-gzigs [Žañ-ñen] convened at Na-mar, passed scorching criticism on Lho ɣdus-sregs.

The accusation of Khu Mañ-po-rje Lha-zuñ occurred in the winter 705/6,²² shortly after he had been nominated a grand councillor (ITJ 750: 154). In the next year Lho ɣdus-sregs was denounced. Their wealth was confiscated during the same summer council of 707/8.

(8)

čhog ro khoñ ge la bkyon bab / (ITJ 750: 180)

Čhog-ro Khoñ-ge came under scorching criticism.

(9)

²² It is also mentioned in PT 1287: 107–8.

dbays stag sgra khoñ lod la bkyon phab nas / (ITJ 750: 249)

[They] passed scorching criticism on Dbays Stag-sgra Khoñ-lod.²³

The reasons for a denouncement are only vaguely expressed as 'becoming disloyal'. The consequences of a denouncement differed: from death (PT 1288: 5), to banishment of servants, to wealth confiscation. A denouncement could affect the whole family, as was the case with Mgar, but also single persons; although Čhog-ro Khoñ-ge was denounced in 711/2, other members of the family could still serve the *bcan po* in convening councils (ITJ 750: 182–3), functioning as *mñan* (ITJ 750: 227–9) or as a private councillor of the Chinese princess Kim-šeñ *koñ co* (ITJ 750: 257–8).

bkyon bab (#411) 'Adj at fault; N one at fault'

The compound *bkyon bab*, an OLT *dis legomenon*, can be juxtaposed with the verbal phrases *bkyon ybab* 'for scorching criticism to come down' and *bkyon ybebs* 'to pass scorching criticism' (see s.v. *bkyon*). The confiscation of wealth addressed to in both passages with *bkyon bab* concerned persons of whom we read in the preceding annual entries:

(1)

deyi dgun mgar la bkyon phab ste (ITJ 750: 128)

That winter, [they] passed scorching criticism on the Mgar family.

(2)

deyi rjes la gliñ riñs cal du khu mañ po rje lha zuñ la bkyon phab / (ITJ 750: 154–5)

After that, at Gliñ-riñs-cal, [they] passed scorching criticism against Khu Mañ-po-rje Lha-zuñ.

(3)

yduñ ma/ na mar du ybon da rgyal bcan zuñ dañ / blon čhen pho khri gzigz gyis bsduste / lho ydus sregs la bkyon phab / (ITJ 750: 157–8)

The council, *dbon* Bcan-zuñ, the king of the Dags-po, and grand councillor [Dbays] Khri-gzigz [Žaň-ñen] convened at Na-mar, passed scorching criticism on Lho Ydus-sregs.

In all three passages the transitive verb *phab* is used. It appears that after criticism was passed, the person concerned was perceived as being at fault.

In its first occurrence in the OTA-I (l. 131) *bkyon bab* is a modifier in a determinative phrase connected to the head via genitive clitic, whereas in the second case (l. 162) it functions as an attribute to an NP. Presuming that l. 131 is not distorted,²⁴ it is more plausible to posit the development from the adjectival to the nominal meaning. Accordingly, I propose interpreting *bkyon bab* as a subject-incorporate compound (cf. (Bialek 2018a: 1.199)) derived from the verbal phrase *bkyon bab*, lit. 'for scorching criticism to have come down'. The semantic

²³ The accusation of Dbays Stag-sgra Khoñ-lod is also mentioned in PT 1287: 110–1.

²⁴ We could think of the reconstruction **mgar bkyon bab*, by analogy with *khu dañ lho bkyon bab*.

development can be reconstructed as ‘for scorching criticism to have come down’ > Adj ‘at fault’ > N ‘one at fault’.

bkral (#410) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to distribute’

[C] *khral*

The meaning ‘to explain, comment, illustrate’ (J: 100b) attested in most dictionaries for *ygrel* (v2 *bkral*) is secondary. The primary meaning has been preserved in some NW dialects: Balti ‘to divide (among people), to apportion, to distribute’, Kargil/Tshangra/Chiktan ‘to distribute’, Nurla ‘to distribute, to divide (among people)’ (CDTD.V: 262). The semantic change can be compared to that of Ger. *auslegen*, orig. ‘to lay sth. out’ > ‘to explain’.²⁵ The verb is unanimously glossed as cEA which agrees with the argument structure of the verb in OLT, cf.:

(1)

[*myi rma bu ldam śad gyis*]_{ERG} *g.yag śa ni lhu ru bkrald* (ITJ 731: r118; *apud* OTDO)

The man, the son of man, Ldam-śad distributed yak’s meat in portions.²⁶

rkañ ton (#396) ‘*rkañ*-conscription’

In connection with the morpheme *rkañ*, we observe that Ch. character 武 *wǔ* ‘military; martial, warlike’ is composed of 止 *zhǐ* ‘foot’ under 戈 *gē* ‘dagger-axe’ (Halliday 1985: 17). Although (Bialek 2018a: 1.284ff.) reconstructed *rkañ* as denoting a land unit, this is certainly the same word as in *rkañ pa* ‘foot; leg’.

sku sruñs (#786) ‘life guards’

Mvy: 3722: talavargaḥ = *sku sruñs/sku bsruñs/skru sruñ*; GC: 43b: rgyal poḡi sku sruñ dmag mi (s.v. *sku sruñ*); BTC: 125a–b: ¹skuḡi ñen kha las skyob pa; ²sku sruñ mkhan (s.v. *sku sruñ ba*).

D: 91b: or *sku bsruñs pa* attendant; waiter; body-guard (s.v. *sku bsruñs*); Gs: 59a: ¹security guard, bodyguard; ²v[erb]a[ctive] to protect, shield, safeguard (s.v. *sku sruñ*); WtS.5: 285b: auch *sku sruñ*, *sku bsruñ*, *sku bsruñs* Leibwache; CM: 19b: skuḡi ñen kha las skyob mkhan.

DTH: 42: gardes du corps; (Tucci 1956b: 81–2, fn. 1) the *sku sruñ* regiments are so disposed as to form a kind of protection on the four sides of Dbus, which was the residence of the Bcan po, *mñay bdag* and therefore the center of the state; the *sku sruñ* of Dbu ru were on the east, those of G.yo ru provided to the defence of the North, those of G.yas of the West, those of the supplementary banner of the South; (Uray 1960b: 31) royal bodyguard; (Richardson 1985: 161) bodyguard; (Li and Coblin 1987: 375) bodyguard of the king; (Dotson 2007a: 134) royal guard regiment; (Uebach and Zeisler 2008: 318) resp[ective] body + to guard; ‘the Guards of the [*bcan po*’s] body’, ‘the Guards’; fn. 18: they constitute a military unit (*stoñ bu čhuñ*) of about half the size of a thousand-district; in the later historiographic literature, the spelling of the term is *-s-less* throughout; (Dotson 2009b: 105) royal guards; (Walter and Beckwith 2010: 297) *sku sruñs* (literally, ‘*sku*-protector’), which was an office rather than simply a descriptor for a group, was one set from which members of the *bcanpo*’s comitatus were drawn; (Dotson 2012: 189) royal guards.

The formation is attested once in the OTA:

²⁵ (Uray 1953a: 55) related *sgral* ‘to cut into small pieces, viz. the picture of an enemy whom one wishes to destroy’ (J: 120a) to *ygrel* but it is rather cognate with *ral* (see (Bialek 2018c: 18)).

²⁶ Thomas read *ldam śid* and *lharu* (Thomas 1957: 15) translating the latter as ‘to the gods’ (ibid., p. 27).

(1)

dbyar (167) *γdun mkhr̄s pha tañ du blon čhen po khri gzigs gyis bsduste / sku sruñs gyī khram dmar pho brc̄is* / (ITJ 750)

The summer council, grand councillor [Dbays] Khri-gzigs [Žañ-ñen] convened at Mkhri-pha-tañ, counted up red tallies of the *sku sruñs*.

In ITJ 750 we also find other determinative phrases with *khram* as the head NP:

<i>rcañ čhen phayī</i>	<i>khram dmar po</i>	(l. 106)
<i>mñan gyī khab soe</i>	<i>khram</i>	(l. 161)
<i>ru gsum gyī</i>	<i>khram dmar pho</i>	(l. 187)
<i>dags poe</i>	<i>khram dmar pho</i>	(l. 208)
<i>dmag myī</i>	<i>khram skya</i>	(l. 297)

The determinating terms can be grouped according to their meanings as denoting either human beings (*rcañ chen pha*, *khab so*, *dags po*, *dmag myī*) or administrative units (*ru gsum*). The following passage from the Žol inscription helps us specify the meaning of *sku sruñs*:

(2)

sku sruñs *γphan yul payī* (42) *stoñ dpon du gžan su yañ myi gžug par* (43) *blon stag sgra klu khoñ gī myes po gsas slebs* / (44) *gyi bu cha rgyud peld las gañ rño thog pay* / (45) *dmañs ydrañ ba gčig / sku sruñs* *γpan* (46) *yul payī stoñ dpon g.yuñ druñ du scald* (47) *par gnañ ño /// ñan lam gsas slebs* (48) *gyi bu cha rgyud γpheld / nam žar gyañ sde sku* (49) *sruñs su gnañ ba las / sde čha gudu myī spoj myi* (50) *bsgyur bar gnañ rño ///* (Žol N)

[It] is granted that from the descendants of Gsas-slebs (the grandfather of councillor Stag-sgra Klu-khoñ) the capable one who leads the community is given in perpetuity [the office of] the head of the thousand-district of the *sku sruñs* [that consists of] the inhabitants of the Xphan land, so that nobody else is appointed as the head of the thousand-district of the *sku sruñs* [that consists of] the inhabitants of the Xphan land. [It] is granted that not [even] a part of the district shall be separated or turned aside from the district that was granted also for ever to the descendants of Ñan-lam Gsas-slebs as the *sku sruñs*.

This passage confirms that *sku sruñs* was a collective term, denoting human beings. ITJ 753 attests to another similar term: *mjod sruñs* ‘treasury guards’, and in ITJ 1247 we find *bcon sruñs* ‘prison guards’ (*apud* TLTD.2: 404). In both cases, the referents are human beings.

Since the semantics of v4-stems (cf. v1 *sruñ*, v2 *bsruñs*, v3 *bsruñ*, v4 *sruñs*) does not allow to form active, agent-oriented nouns, I consider the underlying structure of the compound to have been *[*sku sruñ pa*]+s, lit. ‘those guarding the body’, with the collective suffix -s.²⁷ *sku* is not a honorific classifier but an equal constituent of the compound.

skun kar (#718) ‘town’

[V] *skun mkhar* (Lčañ E 6; Or.15000/329: r1; Or.15000/312: r2; ITN 504 A: 1)
skur mkhar (PT 1287: 324)

²⁷ Cf. (Bialek 2018a.1: 228).

BTC: 118b: *sku mkhar*: rgyal po sdod saḡi mkhar; p. 127a: *skun khar*: skun mkhar dañ ḡdra; *skun mkhar*: (rñiñ) sku mkhar; BYD: 28b: *sku mkhar*: skun mkhar. rgyal po sdod saḡi mkhar; p. 30a: *skun kar*: sku mkhar dañ ḡdrayo; *skun khar*: sku mkhar dañ ḡdrayo; *skun mkhar*: sku mkhar dañ ḡdrayo; Gs: 55c: *sku mkhar*: h[onorific] of *mkhar*; WtS.5: 276a: *sku mkhar*: alttib. auch *skun kar*, *skun khar*, *skun mkhar*, *skur mkhar*, resp. Festung.

DTH: 191: *skun kar* = *sku mkhar*; TLTD.3: 114b: *sku mkhar* = *skun khar* fort, castle; (Tucci 1950: 79, fn. 44) old spelling for *sku mkhar*; (Stein 1972: 205) shrine; (Richardson 1985: 161) *skun* = *sku*; castle; (Li and Coblin 1987: 315) resp. for *mkhar* 'fortress, castle'; a sandhi variant of *sku mkhar*; p. 375: resp. form of *mkhar* castle; (Hazod 2003: 33) personal castle; (Uray 2007 [1979]: 127) citadel; (Dotson 2009b: 121, fn. 304) [possibly] *sku mkhar*.

The compound *skun kar* with its variant *skun mkhar* are attested in the following phrases:

- skun kar rma che* (ITJ 750: 280)
- śa čuyī skun kar* (ITJ 1459: 2)
- phyiñ bayī skun mkhar* (Lčañ E 6)
- skur mkhar pyiñ ba* (PT 1287: 324)
- skun kar ḡu then* (ITN 1643: A1)
- nob čhu* (2) *ñuyi skun mkhar* (ITN 504 A)
- skun mkhar nob čhuñu* (Or.15000/329: r1)
- skun kar gyi slad rol žiñ tog du* (ITN 893: A1)
- skun mkha[-]* (Or.15000/312: r2)

The change *skun* > *skur* in PT 1287 might have been triggered by the final *-r* in *mkhar* but more probably by the preceding verb *bskur*. The use of *skun kar* and *skun mkhar* to denote a kind of settlement suggests the identity of the terms. On other occasions *Phyiñ-ba* is also referred to as *mkhar* (PT 1287: 51, 118, 160) and *Nob-čhu-ñu* as *khrom* (Or.15000/530: r1). All the above examples contain the syllable *skun-*; the form *sku mkhar* (commonly identified with *skun* (m)k(h)ar) does not seem to be attested in OLT. The phrase *skun kar gyi slad rol žiñ tog du* (ITN 893: A1) 'to the field-harvest outside the *skun kar*' suggests that *skun kar* denoted not only a fort as a centre of a settlement but the whole settlement outside of which fields were located. This interpretation is supported by the comparison of two parallel clauses from the OTA:

- skun kar rma che slar thob* (ITJ 750: 280)
- mkar lčags rce slar thob* / (ITJ 750: 287)

The name of the stronghold *Lčags-rce* contains the syllable *-rce* like the name of the famous *Phyiñ-ba-stag-rce* that can be juxtaposed with the *skun mkhar* *Phyiñ-ba*.

It follows that *skun mkhar* denoted an inhabited area surrounding a stronghold or a castle (*mkhar*). There is no reason to assume that the compound should be reconstructed as **sku mkhar*. The latter resulted from folk etymology after *skun-* faded into oblivion.²⁸ The syllable *skun* is sparsely attested in lexicographical sources and thus only in the derived formation *skun bu*: 'koñ bu' (J: 23a), 'bžoñ bu' (CDSN, *apud* (Mimaki 1992a: 492)), 'kleiner Trug, Faß, Opferschale, Körbchen' (WtS.5: 288b). If *skun bu* meant 'bowl' then *skun* might have denoted

²⁸ *skun mkhar* cannot be explained as an assimilated form of **sku mkhar*; one would rather expect **skum mkhar*. Apart from that, there is nothing in OLT documents that could suggest a meaningful usage of *sku-* in this formation.

*‘basin’. However, for the lack of further evidence I refrain from analysing *skun-* and propose translating *skun mkhar* as ‘town’ meaning a settlement surrounding a castle (*mkhar*; cf. Eng. *city ~ citadel*).

skya sa (#415) ‘land with ripe (sunburnt) crops’

skyin ba (#719) ‘replacement’

bskos (#416) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘¹to appoint (to [GO]_{TERM}); ²to select’

The attested argument structure of the verb is:

OFFICIAL _{ABS}	NUM _{TERM}	
<i>mñan čhen po</i>	<i>drug du</i>	ITJ 750: 111–2
OFFICIAL _{ABS}		
<i>lña brgya čhen po</i>		ITJ 750: 114
<i>lña brgya</i>		ITJ 750: 189
<i>khrald pa</i>		ITJ 750: 241
<i>stoñ dpon</i>		Or.8212/187: 12
LANDSCAPE _{ABS}		
<i>γbrog</i>		ITJ 750: 115

None of the passages in the OTA-I contains the full argument structure of the verb that would also include the subject, but compare:

(1)

yab kyis / nu bo khyod bskos payī steñ du // (ITJ 737–1: 86, *apud* (de Jong 1989: 106))

Not only did [our] father appoint you, the younger brother [...].

The ergative marking on the subject is confirmed in modern dialects, for which *sko* (v2 *bskos*) is glossed unanimously with the argument structure cEDA (cf. CDTD.V: 35).

We may ascribe two main meanings to the verb: ‘¹to appoint (object = HUMAN); ²to select (object ≠ HUMAN)’. The argument structure for the first meaning can be reconstructed as [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ([GO]_{TERM}).

kh

kha gan (#723)

Lw. from OTurk. *xağan*. Like *ga tun* and *khoñ čö*, *kha gan* is used in the OTA-I as part of the proper name:

- Ton ya-bgo *kha gan* (ITJ 750: 117, 130–1, 133)
- Dur-gyis *kha gan* (ITJ 750: 268–9)

kha bstand (#744) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to regard’

The verb *bstand* ($\sqrt{\text{stan}}$) is regularly glossed as cE(D)A (CDTD.V: 535) and this argument structure is confirmed for OLT as well:

(1)

mas kyañ gdod bstan te / (PT 1287: 31)

The mother explained [him] the beginnings.

In (Bialek 2018a: 1.307–8, fn. 4) I argued that *kha bstand* in ITJ 750: 189 is an incorporate verb with the meaning ‘to regard’. This is suggested by the fact that in the OTA the verb acquired yet another object: [*sño sa skya sa*]_{ABS} *kha bstand* ‘regarded lands with unripe and sunburnt crops’. Since in OLT incorporate verbs inherit the argument structure of the underlying verb, I assume that the argument structure of *kha bstand* was the same as of *bstand*.

khab so (#417) ‘chamberlain’

khud pa (#768) ‘an office (?) of unknown duties and function’

(Lalou 1955: 204) trésorier; (Chang 1959: 310) *khud pa čhen po* great treasurer; (Uray 1960b: 46n26) Great Treasurer (?) (for *khud pa čhen po* – JB); (Iwao 2009: 103, fn. 27) rule; (Hill 2011b: 8) wealth; CM: 32a: *gžan nas thob paḡi rgyu dños dañ nor phyugs*.

The term is a *dis legomenon* known only from the OTA, where it is found as a part of the phrase *khud pa čhen po*. Its relation to CT *khud pa* ‘pocket, pouch’ (J: 41b) remains uncertain.

kho na (#774) 3SG M ‘he’

khor pha (#793) ‘male attendant’

BTC: 245a: (rñiñ) *khyim mi*; DSM: 61a-b: *mi gsod mkhan lag dmar baḡi miñ ste*; CM: 34a: *lag dmar*; WtS.9: 147a: *alttib[etisch] auch khor pha* Gefolge, Begleitung, Versammlung, Anhang (s.v. ²*ḡkhor*).

DTH: 63: *courtier*; BDN: 118: *khyim miḡam bzay mi dañ lag dmar gyi don yin par bkral ruñ/ ḡkhor pa ste bran gyi don yin pa ḡdra*; BNY: 118: *mi gsod mkhan (lag dmar)*; STK: 267: *ḡkhor pa ste bran gyi don yin par bkral yañ/ ḡdir* (Or.8212/187: 12 – JB) *yab bkroñs mkhan te lag dmar žes paḡi don yin pa ma yiḡ gi nañ don du gsal*; (Dotson 2009b: 128) *entourage*.

khor pha in this form is a *hapax legomenon*. I understand *khor pa* as ‘male (*pha*) attendant’, but this reading is only conjectural. None of the Tibetan works quoted above provides the source for the meaning ‘killer’ which seems to be purely contextual. The passage itself is difficult to interpret for its beginning is not preserved. Moreover, the reversed order of arguments, *yab gyi khor pha dag* in absolutive followed by *dmag myis* in ergative, suggests that the former should be understood as co-referential with the subject of the next clause which is barely possible due to the clause contents. The use of a common word for ‘attendant’ in connection with a *bcan po* seems very unusual but we find it also with the honorific *yum* in the *Li yul čhos kyi lo rgyus* (*apud* WtS.9: 149a, s.v. ²*γkhor*). Despite legitimate doubts, I tentatively understand *khor pha* as denoting a person from the retinue, lit. ‘male (*pha*) affiliated to the retinue (*khor*)’.

khyi (#585) ‘(calendric) dog’

khyim rcis (#418) ‘inventory of households’

khram (#424) ‘an account kept by means of a tally stick, tally’

[C] *bkral*

Cs: 14b: a cut or mark on wood, incision; Sch: 54b: ein Einschnitt od[er] Zeichnen in Holz; Desg: 714a: *ybel gzi sbu gu* = *khram śiñ*; BYD: 59a: rcis byed paḡi khram śiñ; WtS.8: 102b: Kerbe, Kreuz, auch Kerbholz, Holztafelchen.

DTH: 37: le registre; fn. 4: pourrait avoir le sens d'une division numérique, territoriale ou administrative. M. Thomas voit avec raison une forme de *kra ma* [*khra ma* – JB], registre, index. Ce sens s'accorde avec la mention d'une couleur, manière très usitée chez les Tibétains pour distinguer les ouvrages de même titre général; TLTD.2: 91: going back to *khra ma* ‘register’, etc.?; TLTD.3: 118a: wooden tablet for accounts; (Lalou 1952: 357) inventaire; (Lalou 1955: 198) crans dans des planchettes des bois servant de moyen de computation; (Róna-Tas 1956: 166) originally denoted records in red on material other than paper, drawn up from time to time for the accounting of taxes, which, upon the order of Khri lde gcug brcan, were exchanged for ‘yellow’ paper in 744; these sticks were mostly of tamarisk wood; p. 167: the tip of some of the sticks – sometimes as much as half of them – was cut off, evidently given to the taxpayer or to the debtor on receipt of the goods delivered; in the Old Tibetan language, the primary meaning of the *khram* had been ‘tally’ or ‘tally-stick’ used for registering taxes, debts or other data; Later, when the meaning of *khram* was extended to records written on paper, it may have been necessary to discriminate between the tally-stick and the records written on paper by designating the former by the term *khram śiñ*, that is: the wooden *khram*; Tibeto-Mongolian dictionaries give the meaning of *khram śiñ* as simply a tally-stick; p. 168: it appears that the original meaning of *khram śiñ* was identical with the Old-Tibetan *khram*; in some of the images of lHa mo even the notches on the stick are discernible; lHa mo repeatedly plays the part of a goddess of death, being at the same time the wife of the Lord of Death, Yama; the *khram śiñ* tucked in her belt means a ‘score of sins’ in her iconography; p. 170: As early as 744 the tally-stick was no longer employed for the recording of debts or taxes; Historic records of the Five Dynasties likewise mention that before the art of writing was known in Tibet, they used incised wooden tablets for the recording of deals (after Hamilton, J.R., 1955, *Les Ouighours à l'époque des Cinq Dynasties d'après les documents chinois*, p. 21); while in the 8th century the tally-sticks were mostly used for the recording of taxes and debts, in the 6th and 7th century their use became more wide-spread; (Chang 1959: 153, fn. 25) wooden tablet accounts, register, inventory, ticket, tally; was used for assesmant and revenue, and also in connection with levies, assignments, and orders upon the storehouses; p. 136: *khram dmar po*: presumably a kind of wooden tablet for recording purposes; (Haarh 1969: 322) one of the *mdos* ceremonies is called *γdre khram bsgyur ba* ‘to turn away the notched stick of the *γdre*’; (Bellezza 2008: 460) cross; (Uebach 2008: 57) tally; Ger.: Kerbholz; Fr.: taille; in early Tibetan state organisation and administration the *khram* ‘tally’, lit. ‘notch’, ‘incision’, or ‘indentation’ in wood had been widespread; it served as a fundamental means of effectuate administrative measures, civil and military; the tally had developed from an original type with two identical matching pieces into a new type with two pieces of different size with the *khram bu* serving for both, identification and receipt; certainly a short form of *khra ma*; (Dotson 2009b: 50) tally; pp. 52–3: tally, the implement for the tally – the tally stick, the

notch or incision on the tally stick; (Dotson 2011a: 90f.) tally or tally stick, implements used for record-keeping during the imperial period; (van Schaik 2011b: 55, fn. 34) notches cut into wooden documents.

In (Bialek 2018a: 1.370) I distinguished between two meanings of OLT *khram*: 1. 'an account kept by means of a tally stick'; and 2. 'tally stick'. Of these only the first meaning is attested in the OTA-I. A *khram* was a means of the administrative system devised to help recording various accounts, usually related to amounts of goods or people. OLT *khram* resulted from clipping of the original *khra mo* *'criss-cross' > CT 'two-coloured' (Bialek 2018a: 1.371).

khram skya (#423) 'pale tally'

khral (#531) 'tax'

[C] *bkral*

khral thud (#421) 'a tax [paid in] dairy products'

khrald pa (#542) 'tax collector'

BTC: 276b: sa rten la brten nas khral yu lag rgyug mkhan; Gs: 142b: taxpayer serf/subject, name of a category of serf who held taxable land; WtS.8: 104b: Steuerbauer, -zahler.

(Lalou 1955: 198) contribution; (Stein 1972: 128) tax-payers; (Cüppers 2004a: 34) Grundbauern/Steuerbauern; (Thargyal 2007: 50) taxpayers; (Dotson 2009b: 51) taxpayers; p. 257: tax official, taxpayer, tax; (Hill 2011b: 34) taxpayer.

In OLT *khral(d) pa* is a *dis legomenon*. The previously proposed renderings of *khral(d) pa* as 'taxpayer' definitively diverge from the OLT meaning of the lexeme; *khral(d) pas* could be appointed, for which activity the verb *bskos* is used (ITJ 750: 241). This verb denoted an action of assigning a particular official role or position to a person²⁹ and so the only plausible translation of *khral(d) pa* can be 'tax collector', lit. 'one affiliated (=pa) to taxes'.³⁰

khrim (#801) 'law'

[V] *khrim* (Or.8212/187: 91)

khrom (#728) 'colonial province'

(Thomas 1936: 285) town; DTH: 51, fn.4: marché; une assemblée passagère; (Lalou 1955: 180) la ville; (Thomas 1957: 3*) market town; (Uray 1960b: 39, fn. 15) town; (Uray 1980: 310) designated territorial units of considerable size; the *khrom* of the 7th – 9th centuries cannot be treated as equivalents to the so-called prefectures, the 州 *zhou*, of the contemporary China; p. 312: the analysis of the Tibetan and Chinese sources under discussion has demonstrated that the *khrom* were large units which comprised several earlier Chinese prefectures, *zhou*. In Tibetan, their leaders bore the title *dmag (d)pon* 'Military Head', and in Chinese *jie du shi* 'Military Governor' or, in vacancy of the post, *li hou shi*. This bears witness to the basically military character of the *khrom*, and I therefore consider 'military government', the adequate translation of the term *khrom*. As sub-divisions of the *khrom* one can only prove the existence of the small districts governed by the *rce rje*, i.e. the 'town prefects'; p. 314: military

²⁹ Other direct objects that the verb took in the OTA are listed s.v. *bskos*.

³⁰ On the functions of =pa in OLT, see (Bialek 2021f: 256ff.)

governments established in the borderlands, or at least in the eastern, northern and far-western frontier zones, which were of the greatest military importance for the Tibetan Empire; (Denwood 1990: 76) some sort of assembly; (Coblin 1991c: 90) large area administered by military government; (Takeuchi 1995: 25) the military district government; p. 141: military and administrative units established in the borderlands or frontier zones of the 8th–9th century Tibetan Empire. [...] Each *khrom* consists of several towns. [...] The assembly of each *khrom* was held twice a year: namely, in summer and in winter; (Richardson 1998b: 187) military and administrative headquarters; (Uebach 2003: 25) military provinces eight in total, are known to have been established at the borders of Tibet starting from Bru ʒa (Gilgit) in the south west along the southern part of the Tarim Basin up to the north east to Kwa ʒhu and Mkhar can; (Takeuchi 2004b: 50a) military district government; p. 56a: seems to have contained around four *ston sde*; [...] the head of a *khrom* may be considered to have been equal in rank to the *ru dpon* in Tibet proper, and both had the military rank of *dmag pon*; (Iwao 2007: 211) the military administrative unit in directly ruled areas; p. 212: consisted of several towns; was controlled by a *ru dpon*, or a *dmag dpon*; each town under the *khrom* was controlled by a *rce rje* or *jjeer*, a town prefect, who was always a Tibetan official; (Dotson 2009b: 41) colonial military government, served to legislate newly conquered areas through direct military rule; *khrom* belonged to a *khams*, a principality, which was controlled by several officials; (Zeisler 2010: 419, fn. 56) the designation *Khrom* for Rome [...] was applied to mere ‘market places’ on the Rome route; (Hill 2011b: 27) the regional military government; (Iwao 2012a: 67) military government; (Takeuchi 2012a: 9) military district; (Dotson 2013b: 72) the jurisdiction of the regional military government, or the confines of the market city.

khrom was the major territorial and administrative unit established in Tibetan colonies in Central Asia, comprising several earlier Ch. prefectures (*zhōu* 州). It corresponded to *ru* of the Tibet proper and comprised territories administratively not incorporated into the *ru bži*. It was governed by a military (*dmag dpon*, Or.8212/187: 13–4) and a civil official (*ru dpon*; (Takeuchi 2004b: 55–6)). Its subdivisions were governed by town prefects (*rce rje*). From east to west the known *khroms* of the Tibetan Empire were: Rma-grom, Dbyar-mo-thañ-khrom-čhen-po, Khar-Can-khrom-čhen po, Kwa-čhu-khrom-čhen-po, Chal-byi (i.e. Lop Nor region), Khotan (Tib. name unknown), Bru-śaḡi-yul-gyi-khrom (not known in OT sources).³¹

In (Bialek 2020a: 302) I proposed relating *khrom* to the verb *ɣgrem*s ‘to spread’ suggesting the following etymology: v4 *khroms* ‘is spread out’ > N *khroms* *‘what is spread’³² > *khrom* *‘a cloth spread over a sales booth’ or *‘goods spread on the ground’ > ‘bazaar’ > ‘town with a bazaar’. Therefore *khroms* were originally trading centres chosen as capitals for the newly established administrative units. By metonymy the name was transferred from the main town of the unit (‘colonial town’) to the unit itself (‘colonial province’).³³

mkhar (#406) ¹‘castle; ²‘stronghold’

Apart from its independent occurrence as *mkhar* or *mkar*, the lexeme frequently forms part of proper names, being attached at the end of a name. In the latter case its morphology might be reduced. The following forms are attested: *-mkhar*, *-mkar*, *khar*, or *kar*. The latter form is

³¹ (Uray 1980: 313–4). The translation ‘military government’, proposed for *khrom* in Uray (1980), is in so far inaccurate as the Eng. term *government* does not designate a territorial unit.

³² Reflexes of the original form *khroms* are preserved in the North-western dialects: Chiktan [khšoms] ‘festival place’, Leh [tšoms] ‘festival ground’ (CDTD: 963).

³³ Compare in this connection the popular use of the English word *bazaar* in modern Nepalese toponyms. Might Pol. *kram* ‘sales booth’ (OPol. *krom* ‘merchandise’; from 13th c. onwards) and Ger. *Kram* (OHG *krām* ‘Kaufmannsbude, Zelt’) be reflexes (perhaps via Turkic languages) of the OT *khrom*? Or did *khrom* assimilate from *khroms* to a Turkic word of a comparable meaning? Be that as it may, the phonetics and semantics of the words highly coincide.

homonymous with *kar* < *dkar* 'white' and caution must be kept when proposing etymologies of the respective toponyms.

In the OTA *mkhar* is used in two different meanings: 1. 'castle' when referring to a residence of a local lord in Central Tibet; and 2. 'stronghold' when speaking of military conquests of foreign regions.

(Wolfenden 1929: 28) proposed relating *mkhar* to the following lexemes: *dgar* 'to separate, confine, fold up, pen up' (< *'to shut up in an enclosure'); *ɣkhar* 'to be penned up, to be confined';³⁴ *skar* 'to fold a pen, separate' (Cs: 305a). In addition, Jäschke noticed the forms *bkar* and *ɣgar*, which he identified with *dgar* (J: 14a & 93a). To these we may add: *gar* 'to be separated' (CDTD.V: 160); *ɣgar* 'to recover (from an illness)' (CDTD.V: 219; < *'to get separated (from an illness)'); *sgar* 'camp, encampment' (J: 114a). The forms *ɣgar*, *bkar*, *dgar* suggest an old transitive conjugation **ɣgar/bkar/dgar/khor*.³⁵ On this basis we can reconstruct the original pair: INTR \sqrt{gar} ~ TR \sqrt{kar} . With the secondary derivations of the causative *skar* (< **s*+ \sqrt{kar}) and autocausative *ɣkhar* (< **ɣ*+ \sqrt{kar}) the voiceless stem has lost its transitive character. The etymological meaning of *mkhar* would be *'a confined place' or *'a place that one can close'; compare Ger. *Schloss* < *schließen*, Pol. *zamek* < *zamykać*.

mkhar pho če (#795) 'fortress'

(Beckwith 1993: 129, fn. 124) great fortified city; (Dotson 2009b: 126) great fortified city.

mkhar pho če is a *hapax legomenon*, with no attestations in OLT or later lexicographical works. It is formed in accordance with the well-known but barely understood pattern N+*pho/mo+če* (cf. OLT *khañ mo če*, *sdiñ po če*, *phal pho če* etc.) My translation is contextual (lit. 'great stronghold' > 'fortress') and its etymological explanation must await a more comprehensive study encompassing all analogous formations.

mkho śam (#389) 'administrative arrangement'

mkhos (#390) 'administration'

In (Bialek 2018a: 1.385) I proposed analysing *mkhos* (CT variant *ɣkhos*) as derived from *mkho* 'to be necessary, needed' by means of the deverbal suffix -s. Its etymological meaning would have been *'[things or actions] needed', i.e. 'needs, necessities'.³⁶ In the context of the state administration it denoted means necessary for the state maintenance and organisation. Therefore the term can be translated as 'administration'.

³⁴ Jäschke remarked that in Western Tibetan *ɣkhar* is an intransitive equivalent of *dgar* (J: 55b, s.v. *ɣkhar ba*²). CDTD glosses *ɣkhar* as 'to get stuck' (Kargil, Tshangra, Shigatse, Lhasa) and 'to be kept in a place, to be trapped' (Tabo; CDTD.V:107).

³⁵ Already Conrady proposed reconstructing the conjugation as **ɣgar*, *bkar*, *dgar* (Conrady 1896: 15). He did not reconstruct a v4-stem.

³⁶ Thomas seems to have been the first scholar who related *mkhos* to *mkho ba* and *ɣkhos* (cf. DTH: 67 & TLTD.3: 21).

In the OTA it invariably occurs in a collocation with the light verb *bgyid*: *mk(h)os* (*čhen po*) *bgyis* ‘administered’, lit. ‘did the (great) administration’. The OTA report on the following *mkhos*:

Phrase	Year	Text line
<i>žañ zuñ gyi mk(h)os</i>	662/3; 675/6 S; 724/5 S	PT 1288: 41–2; ITJ 750: 64; ITJ 750: 234
<i>ya žaḡi mkhos</i>	696/7 S; 714/5 S; 742/3	ITJ 750: 124; ITJ 750: 195; ITJ 750: 291
<i>sum ruḡi mkos čhen po</i>	702/3 W	ITJ 750: 141
<i>g.yo ruḡi ḡbrog gyi mkhos</i>	709/10 S	ITJ 750: 172
<i>mdo smad gyi mkhos čhen po</i>	715/6 W	ITJ 750: 201
<i>mtoñ sod gyi mkhos</i>	730/1 W	ITJ 750: 258
<i>khrom gyi mkos</i>	741/2 S	ITJ 750: 286
<i>dmag myi mkhos čhen po</i>	744/5 W	ITJ 750: 299
<i>ru bži mkhos</i>	744/5 W	Or.8212/187: 2
<i>ru bžiḡi ḡbrog sog gi mkhos</i>	746/7 W; 746/7 W	ITJ 750: 304–5; Or.8212/187: 8

It appears that not only people (*žañ zuñ*, *ya ža*, *dmag myi*) could be administered, but also landscapes (*ḡbrog*, *ḡbrog sog*) and administrative units (Sum-ru, Mdo-smad, Mtoñ-sod, *khrom*, Four Horns). In the majority of cases, the means concerned regions outside of the Four Horns. Only the last three measures were undertaken within the core part of the Tibetan Empire. The administration was carried out by an official (councillor, grand councillor, king of the Dags-po, *žañ*) or by a council.

mkhyud (#426) INTR [THEM]_{ABS} ‘HON to be enclosed’

[V] *mkhyid* (ITJ 750: 69 & 71)

On the grounds of their shared textual contexts I have identified *mkhyid* and *mkhyud* as variant forms of one verb. The verb *mkhyud* (PT 1288: 17) has acquired various interpretations from Western scholars. I list them in a chronological order of the publications:

<i>mkhyud čhiñ bžugste</i>	“étant conservé”	DTH: 30
<i>mkhyud čhiñ bžugste</i>	“wurde konserviert”	(Hoffmann 1950a: 12)
<i>mkhyud čhiñ bžugste</i>	“was placed”	(Haarh 1969: 358)
<i>mkhyud čhiñ bžugste</i>	“was preserved”	(Uebach 1980: 301)
<i>mkhyud</i>	“concealed”	(Dotson 2009b: 83)
<i>mkhyud</i>	“examining”	(Walter 2009: 283, fn. 54)
<i>riñ mkhyud</i>	“was interred”	(Hill 2011b: 18)
<i>mkhyud čhiñ bžugste</i>	“were keeping”	(Beckwith and Walter 2015: 63)

The first occurrence of the verb (PT 1288: 17) concerns a clause, the syntactic structure of which is distorted (see (Bialek 2018a: 2.529, fn. 1)). This fact, not realised by previous authors, influenced their interpretations.

It is apparent that the subject of the verb *mkhyud* is also the subject of the verb *bžugs* (HON); in both cases its referent is the body of *bcan po* Khri Sroñ-rcan. Following (Dotson 2009b: 83), in (Bialek 2018a: 2.529, fn. 1) I proposed relating *mkhyud/mkhyid* to the LT *mkhyud* glossed as ‘sbas’ (BDSN, *apud* (Mimaki 1992a: 482a)) ‘to keep, hold, embrace’ (Cs: 136a), ‘halten, fassen, umarmen’ (Sch: 59a), ‘v[erb] a[ctive] to keep sth. secret’ (Gs: 156c). What seems to be a later variant of the verb, *ḡkhyud*, can be likewise found in dictionaries with the meanings ‘to include, comprise’ (Cs: 13a), ‘¹umarmen, umfassen, umschlingen’ (WtS.9: 159b), ‘¹to embrace; to encompass by spanning’ (J: 60a); Nangchen [ntɕ^hɛiʔ], [tɕ^hɛiʔ], imp[erative] n[ot] r[ecorded]

'to embrace' (CDTD.V: 133). The structures of the above clauses suggest that in OLT *mkhyud/mkhyid* was an intransitive verb with the subject argument in absolutive. However, all the lexicographical sources agree that the verb was transitive. In (Bialek 2018a: 2.529, fn. 1) I reconstructed the meaning of *mkhyud* as *'to be embraced/encompassed', i.e. hidden like an object held in clasped hands. In OLT it seems to have denoted a state. *mkhyud* might have evolved towards a transitive cEA verb in consequence of a reinterpretation of the clause structure: 1) 'X_{ABS} Y_{ERG} *mkhyud*' 'X is embraced by Y' > 2) 'Y_{ERG} X_{ABS} *mkhyud*' 'Y embraces X'. A clause similar to 1) is indeed attested in OLT:

(1)

phu gsum ni gañs gyis bsgor (read: *bskor*) / (5v10) *mday gsum ni mthiñ gyis mkhyud* / (ITJ 739; *apud* OTDO)

Three upper parts of the valley are surrounded with glaciers. Three lower parts of the valley are embraced by streams.³⁷

BDSN has the compound *pus mkhyud* (CDSN: *bus mkhyud*) explained as 'sgom thag' (*apud* (Mimaki 1992a: 486b)), i.e. 'a meditation cord'. Such a cord is wrapped around the legs (*pus mo* 'knee') during meditation. The compound *pus mkhyud* can be reconstructed as **pus mo mkhyud pa*, lit. 'one embracing the knees'. Moreover, in WtS one finds the following seemingly cognate lexemes: *mkhyid* 'auch *γkhyid*, *mkhyud* ein Längenmaß' (9: 135b); *mkhyud mo* '2Ring, Rand' (9: 135b); and *γkhyud* '3eine Maßeinheit' (9: 159b–60a). This allows us to include a few other CT lexemes in this word-family as well: *dkyu* '4to run a race' (J: 11b); *dkyus* '4length' (J: 11b), '2lang, Länge' (WtS.3: 181b); *dkyus mo* 'Lauf' (WtS.3: 182a); *khyud mo* 'rim of a vessel' (J: 47b),³⁸ 'Klafter' (WtS.8: 91a); *γkhyu* 'to run' (J: 60a); *γgyu* 'to move quickly' (J: 96b).³⁹ The common semantic denominator would have been a concept of a string or line that extends in space by spanning. Similar to the Eng. *span*, Tibetan *mkhyud/γkhyud* also developed the sense of embracing by means of a cord-like object.⁴⁰

In the funeral context of the OTA, the verb could be interpreted as relating to the well-known Tibetan custom of wrapping corpses in a fetus position in a cloth which is then bound with a rope. The use of the verb *mkhyud* in ITJ 739 with reference to rivers, that embrace valleys, confirms that this meaning was still valid in OLT. However, since the OTA does not speak of other procedures concerning funeral ceremonies in much detail, I assume that the verb, having undergone metaphorisation, was used as an honorific with a more general meaning 'to be enclosed'; enfolding of a body of a *bcan po* was not knowable to everybody.

³⁷ As against my previous interpretation (Bialek 2018a: 2.529, fn. 1), *mthiñ* stands here metrically for **mthiñ bran* 'stream' (cf. (Bialek 2018a: s.v. *mthiñ bran*)).

³⁸ Already Wolfenden connected *mkhyud/γkhyud* with *khyud mo* (Wolfenden 1929: 35).

³⁹ I leave open the question whether *khyu* 'flock, herd' (J: 47b) should be included in this word-family as well.

⁴⁰ The word-family evolved around two etymons: TR *√kyu* 'to cause to move (through)' and INTR *√gyu* 'to move in a particular direction, to pass (through)'. They might have cognates in other TH languages, see s.v. STEDT #5410: *m-kyit MOVE.

γkhus (#764) INTR [AGT]_{ABS} ¹to turn away ([SEP]_{DEL} from); ²to revolt'

J: 55b: to offend, insult (s.v. *γkhu*); DSM: 70a: *ño ldog paγam ño rgol byas paγi don la γjug ste*; WtS.9:140b: ¹wetteifern, rivalisieren; ²hassen, beleidigen (s.v. *γkhu*); p. 142b: verabscheuen, sich abwenden, schädigen (s.v. *γkhus*).

(Denwood 1991: 131) in PT 1287: 299–302 *log* seems to be used as a stylistic alternative to *γkhu*, and *dku ba* as a nominalised form of it; p. 136: perfect: *γkhus*; to oppose, rebel; (Richardson 1998a [1965]: 11) implying disaffection and treachery, regularly followed by the death of the victim; to turn treacherous; (Xbyuñ-gnas 2001: 117, fn. 1) *spro lañs paγam khoñ khro skyes paγi don no. γdi nas* (PT 1287: 299 – JB) *ño log ziñ γkhrug la goγo*; (Dotson 2009b: 258) to be treacherous.

For a detailed lexical analysis of *γkhus* in OLT, see (Bialek 2016: 150ff.)

γkhord (#412) INTR/C [AGT]_{ABS} 'to turn round'

[C] *γgord*

The verb takes the form *γkhord* or *γkhor*. In the latter case the attached gerundial allomorph *te* clarifies that the underlying form of the verb is likewise **γkhord*. The recurring sentence structure is: 'HUMAN_{ABS} *slar γkhord*', lit. 'HUMAN turned back'. In addition, some clauses include an adjunct in relative that specifies the source (*γa źa yul nas, dru gu yul nas*). From the clauses it appears that the verb was intransitive and denoted an action by which the subject was directly affected. The meaning of the verb seems to have been narrowed down by the adverb *slar* 'back': *γkhord* 'turned round' > *slar γkhord* 'turned back'.⁴¹

⁴¹ For the etymology and word-family of *γkhord*, see s.v. *γgord*.

g

ga tun (#407)

ga tun is a borrowing from a Turkic *qatun*, OTurk. *xa:tun* 'lady' (cf. (Clauson 1972: 602b)). Tibetans rendered the initial voiceless fricative velar [x] with letter *g* which originally represented a voiced velar stop. This indicates that by the year 708/9 the Tibetan plain voiced consonants in word-initial position have already become devoiced. Since the entry in the OTA, from which the word comes, demonstrates some laxness in the structure, we can speculate that it was not edited later. Worth noticing is also the difference between the Tibetan transcriptions *qatun* and *qagan* (OTurk. *xağan* 'an independent ruler of a tribe or people', (Clauson 1972: 611a)). The latter is always transcribed as *kha gan* (see s.v.) in OLT even though both words had the same initial in Turkic languages. A plausible explanation can be put forward: *kha gan* was borrowed earlier, at the time when letter *g* still represented a voiced sound in Tibetan and did not match the pronunciation of the Turkic [x]. Later on, after the devoicing of plain stops in initial position has set in, one obviously considered letter *g* to better match the sound of the Turkic voiceless fricative velar and transcribed OTurk. *xa:tun* as *ga tun*.⁴²

I refrain from translating the term. Its position in the phrase, following the native Tibetan title *bcan mo*, suggests that *ga tun* was used as a proper name; compare in this context *bcan mo khoñ čo* (ITJ 750: 176) for *bcan mo Kim-śaṅ khoñ čo*, in which *khoñ čo* is a loanword from Ch. *gōngzhǔ* 公主 (see LS-O).

Concerning the identity of *ga tun* three hypotheses have been put forward:

- the daughter of the eastern Turk khagan Qutlug alias Eltäris (Uray 1978: 552, fn. 37)
- a Western Turkic princess (Beckwith 2003 [1983]: 280f., fn. 14)
- a daughter of the *Ḫa-ža kha gan* (Uebach 1997a: 59, fn. 12)

gud (#778) 'someplace'

Owing to the terminative allomorph =*du*, it is apparent that *gu* in ITJ 750: 305 should be read **gud*, identical with CT *gud* 'separation, solitude, seclusion' (J: 69b), 'Seite, abseits Gelegenes' (WtS.10: 209a). Compare also the clipped form *gudu* in Žol N 49. Common use of *gud* in OLT with case clitics such as inessive =*na*, terminative =*du*, genitive =*gyi*, relative =*nas*, and delative =*las* (see OTDO) confirms that it was a noun.

gum (#661) INTR [PAT]_{ABS} 'to die'

[C] *bkum*

⁴² For a more detailed discussion of the respective sound change in OT, see (Bialek 2018c: 29f.)

gor śa (#427) 'infected meat'

glañ (#532) '(calendric) ox'

Related to PTH *glañ OX/BULLOCK/ELEPHANT (STEDT #3318). Sapir suggested that the original meaning of *glañ* might have been 'beast of burden' or 'riding animal' and considered Tocharian A *klañk*, B *klenke* 'Reittier' borrowings from Tibetic (Sapir 1936: 265). This link is not mentioned in (Adams 2013: 238 & 245).

†**gleyu thogs** (#802) 'fallow rotation (?)'

The clause *stoñ sdeyī gleyu thogsła / khral pa gu du spags /* (ITJ 750: 305) has been variously understood and translated in previous works:

"[U]ne contribution supplémentaire fut imposée au lieu de prestation sur les districts improductifs." (DTH: 52)

"[Le *bcan po*] fit lever [une contribution] *khral*, imposée sur les rentes (*thog*) des [parcelles] *stoñ sde*." (Bogoslavskij 1972: 85)

"[D]opo (?) il raccolto dei campi no irrigui delle chiliarchie, le tasse furono trasportate altrove." (Petech 1988a: 298)

"They removed the salaries (?) of the thousand-districts, and transferred [this] to separate taxpayers." (Dotson 2009b: 124)

"[T]hey removed the salaries of the chiliarchy, and transferred [this] to separate taxpayers." (Hill 2011b: 34)

"[S]ie nahmen die kleinen, unbebauten Flächen der Tausendschaften und übertrugen sie gesondert den Steuerpflichtigen." (WtS.29: 156, s.v. *thogs*³)

The difficulties are of two kinds:

- Grammatical: How to divide *thogsła*? (i) V *thogs+la*_{ALL} (converbial clause); (ii) N *thogs+la*_{ALL}; or (iii) compound *thogs+sla*
- Lexical: What are meanings of (iv) *gleyu* and (v) *thogs*?

The grammatical interpretation of the second part of the passage does not pose any problems for *gu du*, others than assumed by Dotson and Hill, cannot be an attribute of *khral pa*. In OLT, *gu(d)* is only attested as a noun (see s.v.) Thus, we have two arguments: *khral pa* in absolutive and *gu du* in terminative, which accords with the prototypical argument structure of *spags*: $X_{\text{ABS}} Y_{\text{TERM}} \textit{spags}$ 'to move X to Y'.⁴³

The problem with the interpretation of *gleyu* as 'wages' is twofold. Firstly, the word is not attested in this meaning; OLT works quoted by (Dotson 2009b: 125, fn. 321) clearly read *gla*

⁴³ This also contradicts Hill's analysis of the terminative as marking a recipient argument (Hill 2011b: 34).

(see Or.15000/202: r2; Kh.206: r1; Or.15000/387: 5). Secondly, the phrase reads *stoñ sdeyi gleyu*, indicating that *gleyu* was in possession of administrative units (*stoñ sde*) and not humans. But what should ‘salaries of thousand districts’ mean? If anything, the phrase would have to be read metonymically ‘salaries of the officials working for thousand districts’. Such a figurative language is otherwise not employed in the OTA. Thousand-districts were the basic administrative units below the level of the Horns. During the winter council of 746/7, grand councillor *Ǫbro Čuñ-bzañ Ǫor-mañ* and councillor *Ǫbal Skyes-bzañ Ldoñ-cab* administered summer pastures and straw-lands of the Four Horns, and then sent tax collectors elsewhere to continue on the level of thousand-districts. In this interpretation, *gleyu* can be well equated with *gle* ‘a small uncultivated island’ (J: 81a), ‘dry ground amidst water’ (Gs: 211a).⁴⁴ This reading is supported by the mention of *gleyu* in one context with *Ǫbrog sog* ‘summer pasture and straw land’, and by its occurrence in two other OLT passages: *nag śod gi gleyu žiñ dor gñis* (ITN 759: A3; trslr. *apud* TLTD.1: 126) ‘two *dor* units of *gleyu* fields of Nag-śod’ and *gleyu žiñ dor* (ITJ 300: B2; trslr. *apud* TLTD.1: 350) ‘*dor* unit of *gleyu* fields’. *dor* was a measure unit of land⁴⁵ and is frequently encountered in OLT postposed to *žiñ*. The latter can also be modified as in *rkya/skya žiñ dor* (PT 1078bis: 16; PT 1115: 1; trslr. *apud* OTDO), confirming that *gleyu žiñ* is a compound and denotes some kind of crop field; cf. ‘rough land’ (TLTD.3: 121a). Being a compound, *gleyu žiñ* also supports the reading of *gleyu* in ITJ 750: 350 as a part of a complex word.

Regarding *thogsla*, we can certainly exclude the reading **thogs sla* for it would bring second argument in absolutive into the clause, which is not foreseen by the argument structure of *spags*. Thus, *la* has to be interpreted as allative clitic. Depending on how we interpret *thogs*, two clause readings are possible:

I. V *thogs*: [Grand councillor *Ǫbro Čuñ-bzañ Ǫor-mañ* and councillor *Ǫbal Skyes-bzañ Ldoñ-cab*] *thogs* rough fields of thousand-districts and moved tax collectors elsewhere.

II. N *thogs*: [Grand councillor *Ǫbro Čuñ-bzañ Ǫor-mañ* and councillor *Ǫbal Skyes-bzañ Ldoñ-cab*] moved tax collectors elsewhere for *gleyu thogs* of thousand-districts.

Re. I: Here *gleyu* is the direct object of verb *thogs* that can only be v2 of TR *Ǫthogs* ‘to take, to seize, to take up; to carry’.⁴⁶ The first problem is that this verb denotes actions in which a physical object is directly taken, usually in hands. This is obviously not possible with *gleyu* meaning ‘rough field’. Yet another problem consists in the fact that allative *la* otherwise does not coordinate two affirmative clauses in the OTA. We find it in this function in other, mainly narrative compositions. On the other hand, the punctuation with a *śad* after *la* could support *thogs la* as a converb.

⁴⁴ Also reconstructed as the second member of the compound [t^hōlē] ‘island’ in Dingri (CDD: 1417). The CT form *gle* is most probably a back formation from *gleyu*; the basic form underlying *gleyu* remains unknown, maybe *glo* ‘side’? In the latter case, the etymological meaning of *gleyu* would have been **a* ‘small side-land’.

⁴⁵ On *dor*, see (Bialek 2018a.2: 177f.)

⁴⁶ Cf. v2-stem *spags*.

Re. II: Another reading would see *gleyu thogs* as a nominal compound. *thogs* is attested as a second member in a number of compounds but the etymology of many of them is barely understood. I propose reconstructing the etymological meaning of *gleyu thogs* as *'shift of fallow lands'.⁴⁷ The noun *thogs* would be a derivation by conversion from the v4-stem of *ydeg*s; cf. *gzi ydeg*s 'to shift, to change, lodgings, to remove' (J: 345a, s.v. *ythegs pa*).⁴⁸ Here *gleyu thogs* would have been a technical term for 'fallow rotation' in the three-field system. There is a great confusion in lexicographical sources concerning the conjugations of verbs with roots $\sqrt{\text{deg}}$ and $\sqrt{\text{teg}}$, and a separate philological study would be necessary to establish their forms.⁴⁹ For now, I tentatively assume that *thogs* was the original v4 in the following conjugation: v1 *ydeg*s, v2 *bteg*, v3 *gdeg*, v4 **thog*(s). Vowel -o- in v4-stem is confirmed dialectally (see CDTD.V: 637). Presuming that *gleyu thogs la* form one NP, the allative must express purpose: 'for the sake of'.

glo ba (#534) 'breast'

In (Bialek 2018b: 408, fn. 34), I proposed interpreting *glo ba* as denoting a metaphorical seat of emotions, therefore the translation 'breast' (< 'lungs'). Concerning the etymology of *glo ba*, it could be related to *lo* (*ma*) 'leaf' for which compare the etymologies of Ger. *Lungen* and Eng. *lungs* (< PIE **l̥ngu̯h-/*lenguh-* 'leicht in Bewegung und Gewicht', <https://www.dwds.de/wb/Lunge#et-1>; 31.10.2017) or Pol. *ptuca* (< PIE **pleu-* 'to swim', Boryś 2005:447a⁵⁰) – both allude to the lightness of the organs and their ability to float in the water.

glo ba ñe (#746) INTR [THEM]_{ABS} 'to be loyal'

glo ba ñe is an incorporate verb, consisting of the noun *glo ba* 'breast' and the verb *ñe* 'to be near'. Its etymological meaning might have been similar to Eng. *abreast*.

glo ba riñs (#747) INTR [THEM]_{ABS} 'to be disloyal'

⁴⁷ Its underlying structure can be reconstructed as **gleyuyi thogs* or rather **gleyu žin gi thogs*. The latter is more probable since *gleyu* is known only from the compound *gleyu žin*.

⁴⁸ For derivation from v4-stems, see (Bialek 2020a: 302f.), (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming)).

⁴⁹ This is an interesting verb-family with primary verbs existing side by side with secondary or derived ones. For the distinction between 'primary verb-families' and 'secondary verb-families', see (Bialek 2020a: 266f. & 282).

⁵⁰ From the same PIE root Gr. *pleúmōn* and Lat. *pulmō* were derived.

dgu khol (#435) 'bondsman'

dguñ (#535) 'HON sky'

(Bialek 2018a: 1.413) put forward the hypothesis that *dguñ*, orig. *'the vast one', was derived from *guñ* 'the middle (i.e. vast space)', itself derived from *gu* 'extension, extent, room, space' (J: 68b; orig. *'broad space in-between') by means of the locative suffix *-ñ* ((Bialek 2018a: 1.388), (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))). In the OTA, *dguñ* occurs in the idiomatic expression *dguñ du gśegs* 'to pass away' (lit. 'to depart to the sky') and as an honorific classifier in *dguñ lo*.

dguñ lo (#533) 'HON year'

dgun (#536) 'winter'

The noun *dgun* 'winter' could be etymologically related to *gud*, *gun* CT 'loss, damage' (J: 69b; cf. also *god* 'loss, damage', J: 72b), denoting the season of the year when all plants wither and decrease. Further cognates could include: *ygud/gud* TR 'to ruin' (J: 94a), *rgud* INTR 'to decline, to sink, to get weak, frail' (J: 104a). The lexeme might have been derived by means of the circumfix *d-n* from the hypothetical root \sqrt{gu} *'to go down'.⁵¹

dgun stod (#537) 'the onset of winter'

dgun ydun (#609) 'winter council'

dgun smad (#538) 'the end of winter'

dgra bżer (#436) 'fortified encampment'

bgyis (#392) (v2 *bgyis*, v3 *bgyi*) TR/C ¹[AGT]_{ERG} [PAT]_{ABS} to prepare, to make; ²[AGT]_{ERG} [FUN]_{ABS} to function, act as; ³[AGT]_{ERG} [QUOT]_{RSFNL} to say'

The verb is attested in the OTA with three different meanings: 1. 'to prepare, to make'; 2. 'to function' and 3. 'to say'. The latter two meanings occur only once each. The first meaning is applied in various collocations:

<i>phyiñ ril bgyis</i>	'to make sheaves'
<i>mkho śam bgyi</i>	'to undertake administrative arrangements'
<i>rcis bgyis</i>	'to make an account'
<i>nol thabs bgyis</i>	'to make a fight; to fight'
<i>mkhos bgyis</i>	'to make administration'

⁵¹ (Zemp 2016: 112, fn. 60) reconstructed the etymological meaning of *dgun* as 'when plants shrink' < **d+goñ+d*, possibly (this is not stated explicitly) relating the latter to CT *ygōñ* 'to despond', NW (Kargil, Tshangra, Chiktan) & C (Kyirong, Yolmo) nCA 'to shrink' (CDTD.V: 236). The vowel alternation *u ~ o* remains unaccounted for in Zemp's etymology.

<i>rkañ ton bgyis</i>	'to make <i>rkañ</i> -conscription'
* <i>sog ma bgyis</i>	'to prepare straw'
<i>pha los bgyis</i>	'to make census'

Apart from **sog ma bgyis*, in the remaining phrases *bgyis* appears to be a light verb with little semantic content. Its main function is to form a predicate with the preceding noun. In all these instances the noun directly precedes the verb with no other elements in-between.

In OLT, the verb belongs to the normal register and not to the humble register as is the case in CT.

In the OTA, two stems of the verb are attested: *v2 bgyis* and *v3 bgyi*, whereas the OLT knows: *v1 bgyid*, *v2 bgyis*, *v3 bgyi*, *v4 gyis*; *v4 !bgyis* was blocked (and replaced by *gyis*) due to its homonymy with *v2 bgyis* (Bialek 2020a: 274f.)

bgrañs (#428) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} 'to count'

The complete argument structure of the verb does not seem to be attested in OLT but in modern dialects the verb is unanimously cEA (cf. CDTD.V: 208).

ygord (#362) 'hunting'; *ygord mjad* 'to hunt'

[C] *γkhord*

The phrase *ygord mjad* (PT 1288: 41) suggests that *ygord* was a noun combined here with the light verb *mjad*. However, we also find plain *γgor(d)* as a verb in OLT:

(1)

bchun po žig byañ γbrog snam stod du (11) *g.yag śor γbroñ γgor du gśegsna* (PT 1136)

A noble man went to Snam-stod, to the northern pastures, to chase yaks, to *γgor* wild yaks.

(2)

re śig re śig na thañ ba g.yu thañ byañ γbrog snam stod du / śa śor γbroñ γgor bžud / (PT 1285: r31)

One day, Thañ-ba G.yu-thañ departed to Snam-stod, to the northern pastures, to chase harts, to *γgor* wild yaks.

(3)

[-] bu / (r200) myi smon bu žig / yul γbrog dbye ldañ sum du śa γčhor du gśegs g.yag γgor du (ITJ 734, *apud* OTDO)

Myi-smon-bu, a son [of -], went to Dbye-ldañ-sum, the country's wilderness, to chase harts; [he] went to *γgor* yaks.

As already observed by (Bellezza 2008: 520, fn. 553), the repeated co-occurrence of *γgor* with the verb *γčhor/śor* indicates that the former must have denoted a similar action. This is also suggested in the clause *bya rgod γgor žiñ ydiñ bayi no* // (PT 1047: 352) 'The sign of *γgor* and spreading vultures'. Thomas translated *γgor* in ITJ 734 as 'to round up', apparently equating it with *γkhor* (Thomas 1957: 99, n. to l. 174). Since in OLT *γkhor* never co-occurs with *γčhor/śor*, I take the two to be distinct verbs. From the above quotations it occurs that *γgor* was a

transitive verb and so it might not have been related to *γkhor*. On the other hand, a hunting context is suggested for the dialectal *gor ba*: Western Drokpas ‘grössere Gruppe, Gesellschaft (zumeist Jagdgesellschaft); fairly large group (often hunting party)’ (CDTD: 1201). Owing to the fact that the form *γgor* is used with both v1 *γčhor* and v2 *śor*, the verb seems to have had only one stem. I deem *γgord* in the OTA to be a deverbal derived from the v2-stem. For the lack of more specific data I propose translating it as a nomen actionis ‘hunting’; for *γgord mjad* compare *rol mo mjad* in ITJ 750: 232. The proposed interpretation is also suggested by the place at which *γgord mjad* took place: G.yug. According to PT 1288: 23–4, in G.yug Mgar Stoñ-rcañ Yul-zuñ organised a yak-hunt in 653/4.

I assume that *γgor* belongs to one word-family with *γkhor* INTR ‘to turn round’ (see s.v.); *skor* ‘¹circle’ (J: 24b); *skor* TR ‘¹to surround, encircle, enclose; ²to go, move, ride round a thing’ (J: 24b); *gor ma* (OT *gor*) ‘a general name for stone’ (J: 73a); *gor mo* ‘¹round, circular’ (J: 73a); *sgor* ‘to turn on a lathe’ (J: 117b), ‘cEA to make round’ (CDTD.V: 294); *sgor mo* ‘¹round; ²a circle; ³a disc, a globe’ (J: 117b).

rgal (#662) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to cross’

[C] *brgal*

rgod g.yuñ (#663) ‘¹braves and weaklings; ²bondservants’

rgya rje (#371) ‘lord of the Chinese’

rgyal po (#368) ‘king’

(Lalou 1952: 358) feudataire; (Karmay 1998-2005: 447) in the pre-tenth century period this word did not have the connotation of the kind of spirits, but later it came to be associated with a particular type of spirits mostly connected with Pe-har who is considered as the chief of the *rgyal po* class in the scheme of the eight spirit categories; (Walter 2009: 281, fn. 50) several times we find the phrase *myiyi rgyal po* in the inscriptions, but not *myiyi bcan po*: The principle function of the *bcan po* was as war leader and maintainer of a comitatus, while that of *rgyal po* was as a day-to-day ruler; as we near the end of the Imperium, we can see *rgyal-po* begin to surpass *bcan po*. This would have been a function of one or both factors: The growing influence of Buddhism at court, or the need for a ruler who was more an administrator and leader of an empire than a warrior/military leader; (Beckwith and Walter 2010: 538f.) ‘king’ in Imperial period texts is used more or less exclusively for neutral or positive reference to the ‘rulers of the four directions’, who were nevertheless still viewed as subordinate to the *bcan po*.

King, a ruler of a country/people that came under Tib. control. In the OTA, used for rulers of the Bal-po, Se-rib, Bru-ža, and Dags-po (see s.v. *da rgyal*).

rgyal sa (#665) ‘throne’

sgrog (#666) ‘fetters’

brgal (#429) INTR [AGT]_{ERG} ‘¹to fight; ²to fight against [MAL]_{ALL}’

[C] *rgal*

The context of conquest suggests the identity of *brgal* in the OTA-I and OTA-II. However, the verbs attest to two different argument structures, a situation confirmed by the OTC:

[AGT]_{ERG} *brgal*

(1)

de γī nañ du lo ñam gyis brgal to / (PT 1287: 17)

In its middle Lo-ñam fought.

[AGT]_{ERG} [MAL]_{ALL} *brgal*

(2)

γuñ nas myi čhen gyis // dags po lha de la brgal te // dags po yoñs su bkug ste // (PT 1287: 214)

Thereafter, Myi-čhen, having fought against Lha-de [of] the Dags-po, completely subdued the Dags-po.

(3)

yu bus li{g} (431) myi rhya la rgol phod na ni g.yu thogs śig / (PT 1287)

If we dare to fight against Lig-myi-rhya, [we] shall bind the turquoises!

The last two quotations confirm that *rgol* and *brgal* belonged to one paradigm that can be identified with the CT *rgol/brgal/brgal* ‘to dispute, combat, fight’ (J: 104a), also attested in Balti as cED ‘to fight’ (CDTD.V: 271). The first citation, on the other hand, agrees with ITJ 750: 286–7 in that *brgal* took only one argument – the agent in ERG. I interpret *brgal* ‘to fight’ as a prototypical intransitive verb with one agent argument.

I propose relating *rgol/brgal/brgal* to: TR *rgal* ‘to cross (over)’ (see s.v. *rgal*); INTR *γgal* ‘to be in opposition or contradiction to; to counteract, to act in opposition to, to transgress, violate, infringe, break’ (J: 93a); TR *sgral/bsgral/bsgral* ‘to lead, transport, carry, to cross’ (J: 122b–3a).⁵² The sense of ‘to go beyond’ could be put forward as their common semantic denominator. The derivation process can be reconstructed as follows:

⁵² In (Bialek 2018a: 1.452, fn. 1), I added to these *rgyal* ‘to be victorious’, which I now consider as belonging to a distinct etymon. Wolfenden also included in the same word-family: *mgal* ‘jaw, jawbone’ (lit. ‘(the parts) in opposition’); *rgol* ‘to dispute, to combat’; *rkal* (?) ‘to quarrel, to accuse’; *gal* ‘to force or press something upon a person’; *gal* ‘constraint, compulsion’; and maybe also *gal te* ‘if’ (lit. ‘standing opposed’) (Wolfenden 1929: 27 & fn. 1).

⁵³ PTB etymon *g-ral ~ *g-ran ENEMY/FIGHT/QUARREL/STRIFE/SWORD/WAR (STEDT #2596) subsumes, in my opinion, two word-families not-necessarily related in Tibetic: 1. √gal; and 2. √gra {*dgra* (OT *gra* in compounds); *γgran*; *γgras*; *sgran*}.

brgyad (#664) 'eight'

brgyus (#430) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} 'to string'

In (Bialek 2018a: 1.397f.), I argued for the existence of two verbs with the v1 *rgyud*:

1. *rgyud/brgyus/brgyu/rgyus* 'to pass through, to string sth. on sth.'
2. *rgyud* 'to pass through; to traverse'

The argument structure of the first verb can be reconstructed on the basis of the OLT data. Namely, in ITJ 731 (v12–5) we find repeatedly the phrase 'X_{ABS} Y_{ALL} *brgyus*' '[one] string X on Y'. Another passage attests to the ergative marking on the agent argument:

(1)

[*bya gśen yjon mo yis*]_{ERG} *ygeg lug nag po dan ygeg ra rgya* (read: *skya*) *bo zig rgyusu brgyus* (56)
nas / (PT 1136)

The *bya gśen* Xjon-mo fastened a black *ygeg*-sheep and a pale *ygeg*-goat to a *rgyus*.

Since the third element here is in terminative and in ITJ 731 in allative, I assume that the verb had only two obligatory arguments and was prototypical transitive.

Both verbs *rgyud* are related to: *rgyu* 'to go, to walk, move, wander, range' (J: 111a); *rgyu ma* 'entrails, intestines, bowels; sausage' (J: 111a); *rgyud* 'string, cord' (J: 111b); *rgyun* 'stream', *rgyus* 'notice, intelligence, knowledge' (J: 113a); *rgyus pa* 'the fine threads or fibres of which animal muscle, plants etc. are composed' (J: 113a); and *brgyud* 'gehen, durchwandeln; überliefern, weitergeben' (WtS.14: 509a–b).⁵⁴

I tentatively reconstruct the EOT root as \sqrt{rju} , which is in fact attested as *ryu* [rju] in PT 1047 (see OTDO) side by side with *rgyu*. The text contains many archaic features but *ryu* might be confirmed by the Bathang [z̥y] 'to go by, to pass' for LT *rgyud* (CDTD: 278). Bathang has also [z̥] in the reflex of LT *g.yug* (CDTD: 1171). Thus, *rju might have been derived from *ju by means of the prefix *r-*. Whether this word family is cognate with PTH *rey ~ s-rwi(y) OBSCURE INTERNAL CHANNEL/CORD/STRING/CREEPER/CANE (STEDT #533) remains to be examined.

⁵⁴ For the first description of this word-family, see (Simon 1980: 133f.) (Beyer 1993: 85, fn. 16) related *rgyud* to different lexemes that are nowadays being connected with the PTH root *kr̥w THREAD/STRING/PLAIT (STEDT #5555).

ñ

mñan (#546)[C] *mñay*

SR.1: 525: mthu; DSM: 135b: ¹mthuḡi miñ ste; ²skyon gyi miñ steḡ ³dkon gñer ram mjod gñer gyi miñ ste; BYD: 123a: mthuḡam skyon dañ. nor srid las khuñs. rjoñ. gñer ba laḡañ; BTC: 682a: (rñiñ) skyon; WtS.15: 51a: eine Amtsbezeichnung, Verwalter.

STK: 137, fn. 19: skyon dañ ñan paḡi don. ḡdir blon poḡi gras kyi nor dañ khral la bdag byed paḡi mñan blon te khral dpon žes paḡo; BTK: 35, fn. 3: <brda gсар rñiñ gi rnam gžag li šiḡi gur khañ> las mñan ni mthuḡo. ḡdi nas (Lčañ 44 - JB) nor gñer paḡi miñ yin pa ḡdrayḡo; p. 106, fn. 3: mñan dpon te gñer paḡam phyag mjod laḡo. <brda gсар rñiñ> las. mñan ni mthuḡo; BDN: 30, fn. 15: rñan te nor gyi don. ḡdir mñan dpon te khral dpon lta buḡi go gnas laḡo.

(Francke 1914b: 56) sorcerer; DTH: 31: gouvernement; p. 36: district; p. 134: jurisdiction; (Richardson 1949: 63, fn. 4) appears to have been another monastic official, perhaps one concerned with magic, because Tibetan dictionaries treat *mñan* as the equivalent of *mthu* meaning 'inherent power' generally used with reference to magic; (Tucci 1950: 79, fn. 43) perhaps a lay official, in old times a government official, because the temples were the property of the kings; (Lalou 1955: 202) gouverneur; (Chang 1959: 130) a governor (?); p. 152, fn. 15: generally interpreted as 'government', but in four instances it seems, rather, to mean 'governmental division'; (Uray 1962b: 358) officers invested wholly or partially with fiscal competence; (Uray 1968: 293) economic officials; (Richardson 1978: 158) appear to have been senior administrative officials of the several divisions of the Tibetan kingdom and to have been concerned with revenue; (Richardson 1985: 93) seems to have been a civil district administrator; p. 101: chief administrative officer of a district (?); (Li and Coblin 1987: 123) officials in charge of fiscal affairs and revenue; p. 314: custodians, were official in charge of fiscal affairs and revenue; maintained records and documentation regarding property rights, economic activities; (Richardson 1992: 106, fn. 2) The *mñan* were important fiscal and revenue officials. The *mñan čhen* the great *mñan*, is seen here (PT 997 - JB) to be responsible for the *lha ris* of Kwa-ču district as a whole while the *sgo mñan*, the special *mñan* was in charge of the affairs of Yu-lim *gcug lag khañ*; (Takeuchi 1995: 510a) an official in charge of fiscal affairs and revenue; (Takeuchi 1998: 2.50) finance official; (Takeuchi 2004b: 53b) official of treasury; (Dotson 2007b: 9) governor; (Uebach 2008: 58, fn. 4) fiscal governor; (Dotson 2009b: 52, fn. 73) fiscal governor; pp. 57-8: a high ranking post, p. 58: regional governor in charge of matters extending beyond taxation; (Hill 2011b: 31) governor.

mñan denoted an official concerned with fiscal affairs. The prerogatives of the official changed as the administrative needs of expanding empire grew. For a more detailed description of the office and other related positions in the state administration, see (Bialek 2018a: 1.535ff.)

mñan is derived from *mñay* 'to own' by means of the -n suffix (Bialek 2018a: 1.498f.)

mñan čhen (#547) 'great *mñan*'**mñay** (#687) COP [BEN]_{ALL} [THEM]_{ABS} 'HON to own'[C] *mñan*

For a detailed analysis of the argument structure of OLT *mñay*, see (Bialek 2018b: 403f.) The etymology of the verb is discussed in (Bialek 2018a: 1.497f.) Prefix *m-* is probably the assimilated prefix *b-* in its verbalising function (see (Bialek 2020a: 272, fn. 19), (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))).

lña brgya (#548) 'a head of a five-hundred unit'

sña (#667) 'before'

sño sa (#431) 'land with unripe crops'

č

gčal (#432) (*gčald) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} 'to pay (?)'

The events from *bcan po* Khri Sroñ-rcan's reign narrated in the *Preamble* of the OTA-I are likewise recorded in the OTC:

(1)

(6) [---] / *bcan po khri sroñ rcan gyīs / śuld byañ lam du pyuñ ste / ya źa dañ rgya lay* (7) [---]ñ
ya źa gñīs gyis dpyay gčalto / (PT 1288)

bcan po Khri Sroñ-rcan, having left [his] traces on the northern road, [---] against the Xa-źa and the Chinese. Both [the Chinese] and the Xa-źa paid tribute.

(2)

yuñ gī yog du bcan po źabs kyis bcugs ste // (306) byañ lam du ma byuñ ma drañs par // rgya dañ ya źas dpyay gcal lo // (PT 1287)

Thereafter, the Chinese and Xa-źa were paying tribute even though the *bcan po*, having walked, neither occurred nor marched on the northern road.⁵⁵

The verb is not known in CT lexicographical sources but might be etymologically related to OLT *yjal/bčal/gźal/čhol* '1to weigh; 2to measure; 3to appraise, to tax; 4to pay, pay back, repay' (J: 175a) although it was certainly a distinct verb.⁵⁶ The latter conjugation points to two verb roots: TR $\sqrt{t\check{c}al}$ and INTR $\sqrt{z\check{c}al}$.⁵⁷ The verb *gčal* must have been derived from the former but its original meaning is unknown. The form *gčalto* (cf. PT 1288: 7) indicates the underlying v2 *gčald. Therefore the conjugation can be tentatively reconstructed as: v1 *gčal* (PT 1287: 306), v2 *gčal*d* (PT 1288: 7), v3 *gčal, v4 *gčold* (PT 1072: 45). *gčal* seems to have been a secondary derivative from $\sqrt{t\check{c}al}$. I translate *gčal* in the OTA contextually as 'to pay'.

gčuñ (#397) 'HON younger brother'

[C] *ču ñu, sčuñs, ñuñ, sñuñ*

The kinship term *gčuñ* is used in the OTA only with reference to the younger brother of *bcan po* Khri Sroñ-rcan (PT 1288: 8, 9) who is called *gčen* 'elder brother' in this context (ibid., l. 8). The honorific register of *gčuñ* can be inferred from the following phrases:

(1)

yab sras gčen gčuñ yum sras (Žwa W 7) 'fathers and [their] children, elder and younger brothers, mothers and [their] children'

(2)

⁵⁵ The message of the sentence seems to be: the Chinese and the Xa-źa were paying tribute when the *bcan po* only moved his feet without even going on a military campaign.

⁵⁶ Thomas (TLTD.3: 128b) and WtS (17: 152b) falsely assumed the identity of the OLT *gčal* and v2 *bčal*.

⁵⁷ On Schiefner's law and its consequences for PT, see (Hill 2014a); (Jacques 2021a); (Bialek 2021a: xiiif.)

gčuñ slon kol dañ / yum stoñ cun gñis (PT 1287: 179) ‘the younger brother Slon-kol and the mother Stoñ-cun’

Other kinterms occurring in the passages are all honorific. Likewise CT *gčuñ po* is glossed as honorific (J: 144b).

The lexeme is derived from the adjective *čuñ [tɕuŋ] ‘small’ by means of the nominalising prefix *g-*.

gčen (#399) ‘HON elder brother’

[C] *čhen po*

The kinterm *gčen* is used in the OTA with reference to *bcan po* Khri Sroñ-rcan as the elder brother of Bcan-sroñ (PT 1288: 8) and with a certain Lha-bal-pho (ITJ 750: 152). The latter is called *bcan po gčen*.⁵⁸ *gčen* belongs to the honorific register (see s.v. *gčuñ*) as is confirmed by CT *gčen (po)* (J: 144b).

The lexeme is derived from the adjective *čen [tɕen] ‘big’ by means of the nominalising prefix *g-*.

bčad (#433) (v1 *gčod*) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to decide’

[C] *čhad ka, rabs čhad, lhag čad, man čhad, yan čad*

The use of the postpositional phrase *bcan poe bkas* in ITJ 750: 121 indicates that the agent of the verb required the ergative marker. Otherwise no complete argument structure is attested in the OTA, but the verb is unanimously glossed as cEA for modern dialects (cf. CDTD.V: 348).

bčug (#437) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ¹[DIR]_{TERM} to put in; ²[FUN]_{TERM} to install’

The verb *bčug* is attested with two meanings in the OTA: 1) ‘to put in’; and its metaphorical extension 2) ‘to install (i.e. to put sb. in a position)’. In the second meaning the verb is used to denote the action of installing a person in an official position which could be that of *mñan*, equerry, *bruñ pa*, councillor, grand councillor, or even a foreign ruler (PT 1288: 12, Or.8212/187: 49–50, 54). The complete argument structure is not attested in the OTA, but can be complemented from modern dialects. Namely, in the meaning ‘to put into’ the verb is glossed as cEDA (cf. CDTD.V: 415). The OLT quotations confirm that *bčug* was an extended transitive verb and required a goal argument for its indirect object (see (Bialek 2023b)). This argument receives the terminative marker.

bčos (#461) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [PAT]_{ABS} ¹to change; ²to reduce’

A complete argument structure of *bčos* does not seem to be attested in OLT but all modern dialects confirm that the verb was cEA (cf. CDTD.V: 402). In the OTA the verb takes optional

⁵⁸ For a new interpretation of the respective passage see (Bialek 2021c: 13).

arguments depending on the meaning: 1. [AGT]_{ERG} [PAT]_{ABS} [RES]_{TERM} 'to change sth. to'; and 2. [AGT]_{ERG} [PAT]_{ABS} [ORIG]_{DEL} [RES]_{TERM} 'to reduce sth. from to'. The second meaning is attested only with numeral arguments.

lčam (#668) 'HON sister'

(Benedict 1942: 329) resp[ective] sister (man speaking); p. 330: connected with *lčam* 'lath, pole, rafter, spar of a roof', often written *phyam* or even *khyam*; p. 331: the metaphor involved here is perhaps that of a series of siblings arranged in proper order; (Uebach 1997a: 63) a consort of the emperor, who assumedly ranks lower than *bcam mo*, 'empress'; (Dotson 2009b: 32) sister (?); fn. 41: sister, wife; (Dotson 2013c: 212, fn. 17) sister.

The juxtaposition of *lčam (mo)* with *sriñ (mo)* in some OLT texts allows us to identify the meaning of the former as 'sister'; cf.:

(1)

myiñ po dral po skyi pyugi yjon pa dañ / sriñ mo (63) lčham mo skyi nam ñag čig ma gñis (PT 1068)

both the brother Pyugi-yjon-pa [of] Skyi and the sister Nam-ñag-čig-ma [of] Skyi

The term apparently denoted a female member of a royal or elite family and therefore can be deemed an honorific.

(Gong 1977: 218), followed by (Jacques 2004 (unpublished): 6), related LT *lčam* to the verb *ltam*. This hypothesis requires further examination.

sčuñs (#434) *TR/*C* *[AGT]_{ERG} [PAT]_{ABS} 'to reduce'

[C] *gčuñ, čhu nu, ñuñ, sñuñ*

sčuñs is a *hapax legomenon*. In (Bialek 2018a: 1.313) I argued that *sčuñs* is a palatalised form of the original *skyuñ* 'to diminish'.⁵⁹ The latter verb is likewise attested in OLT:

(1)

(21) *zla goñ gī bu cha rgyud gyis // bcan poe* (22) *ža sñar // glo ba ma riñs na / noñs* (23) *myig gžan čī byuñ yañ ruñ / srog* (24) *srid la myī dbab par // bkaγ gyod gyī* (25) *chigs čī la bab pa las // bkaγ gyod* (26) *na gčīg gis smad čīñ bskyuñ bar* (27) *gnañ ño // (Žol N)*

Should the line of the descendants of Zla-goñ not become disloyal towards the *bcan po*, whatever other offence attempts may have appeared, [it is] allowed that, in order not to threaten (lit. cast upon) [their] life or sway, the accusation, while being each time (lit. with one time, *na gčīg gis*) diminished, shall be **reduced** upon the words of accusation have appeared on whatever [issue].

(2)

yo byad sbyard (8) *paγ yañ de las myi dbri myi* (9) *bskyuñ bar bgyiyo* / (Bsam)

The equipment prepared [for the temple] shall be neither diminished nor **reduced** from that [assigned here].

⁵⁹ This meaning of *skyuñ* was put forward in (Simon 1974: 444, fn. 13), based on the gloss in Mvy: *alpašubda* 'sgra (b)skyuñ ba' (Mvy.l: 8475). In Mvy *alpa* is rendered with 'čuñ ba' (Mvy.l: 2702).

(3)

γbañs mgo nag po yañ mtho dman ni (449) *bsñams* / *dpyay sgyu ni bskyuñs* / *dal du ni mčhis* / (PT 1287)

[They] treated even black-headed subjects, high and low ones, uniformly, **diminished** tax frauds, [and] proceeded leisurely.

The verbs closely resemble each other in their semantics. However, I think a process different than palatalisation might have taken place instead. It is widely acknowledged now that the EOT dental affricate *c-* [tʃ-] could take the prefix *s-*. The complex onset *sc-* was subsequently simplified to *s-*, cf.:

OLT	CT
<i>scañ</i> [stsaŋ]	<i>bsañ</i> [bsaŋ]
<i>scan</i> [stsaŋ]	<i>gsan</i> [gsaŋ]
<i>scogs</i> [stsoɡs]	<i>sogs</i> [soɡs]
<i>scon</i> [stsoŋ]	<i>gson</i> [gsoŋ]
<i>scol</i> [stsoʎ]	<i>gsol</i> [gsoʎ]

I assume that the same derivational process of adding the causative prefix *s-* was possible with the alveolo-palatal affricate *č-* [tʃ-]: *čuñ* ‘(to be) small’ > *s+√tʃuŋ*, lit. ‘to make small’. The onset *sč-* then underwent simplification parallel to *sc-* > *s-*:

sc- [stʃ-] > *s-* [s-]
sč- [stʃ-] > *[tʃ-] ⁶⁰ > *ś-* [ʃ-] ⁶¹

Therefore one should expect some reflexes of this process in the alternations *č-* ~ *ś-* which are actually found in:

<i>č-</i> [tʃ-]	<i>ś-</i> [ʃ-]
<i>√tʃag</i> ‘to break’	<i>gśog</i> ‘to break open’ (< * <i>g+s+√tʃag</i>)
<i>√tʃad</i> ‘to cut’	<i>śad</i> ‘punctuation mark’ (< * <i>s+√tʃad</i> *‘the cutter’) ⁶²
<i>s+√tʃuŋ</i> ‘to diminish’	<i>gśuñ</i> ‘to rebuke’ (< * <i>g+s+√tʃuŋ</i> ‘to belittle’) ⁶³

⁶⁰ A similar regressive assimilation of prefix *s-* when added to an alveolo-palatal affricate occurs in Polish, cf.: *ciągnąc* [tʃ-] > *ściągnąć* [ʃtʃ-] but *toczyć* [t-] > *stoczyć* [st-].

⁶¹ These two sound laws have already been described in (Li 1933: 140–1).

⁶² Without explaining his decision, Conrady likewise included *śad* in one word-family with *gčod* and its cognates (Conrady 1896: 62).

⁶³ In lexicographical sources *gśuñ* is paraphrased with *γkhañ pa* (BDSN, *apud* (Mimaki 1992a: 491a)), *śub bur smad* (J: 565b, s.v. *gśuñ ba*), *śub bur dmod pa byed pa dañ skyon brjod pa* (D: 1250a, s.v. *gśuñ ba*), *rañ dañ gźan gyi skyon dños su brjod pa* and *γkhañ ba dañ dmaγ γbebs byas pa* (DSM: 950a). In addition, Das also glosses *gśuñs pa* as ‘= *smod pa*, a curse, rebuke, censure’ (D: 1250a, s.v. *gśuñs*). In these glosses we notice the repeated occurrence of lexemes derived from *ma* ‘low’: *smad*, *dmod*, *dmaγ*, and *smod*. There is an important common vector in the semantic development of *čuñ* > *gśuñ* and *ma* > *smad* etc. The causative verbs denoting actions of humiliation and downgrading were derived from two adjectives denoting the negative counterpart in their pairs (small–big, low–high). Other cognates of *čuñ* and *gśuñ* include: *ñuñ* ‘little; to be little’ (J: 189a); *sñuñ* ^{d.1} ‘to make less, to reduce, to diminish; ² resp[ective] to be ill, sick, indisposed; ^{ll.1} ‘the state of being ill, illness, indisposition’ (J: 199b):

1. **tʃuŋ*

Therefore I conclude that *sčuńs* resulted from a regular causative formation.

sčuńs is attested in an entry from 746/7 and the OTA (but also the Central Tibetan inscriptions) consequently keep writing *sc-* and not *s-*. Does it mean that the change occurred first in Middle Tibetan? If not, at least the WAT and AT dialects should attest to earlier complex onsets, but they usually don't. The only exception I was able to trace down is Rmastod [tsar] ~ [tsal] for the conservative LT *scol*. The WAT reflexes of this verb show unanimously *s-* (cf. CDTD.V: 998). In his meticulous study of Chinese transcriptions of Tibetan proper names from the ST Treaty inscription, Preiswerk established that prefix *s-* was consequently transcribed into Chinese and therefore most probably still pronounced at the beginning of the 9th century (Preiswerk 2014: 53). Unfortunately, the complex onset *sc-* does not surface in the surveyed material. Preiswerk's results are in harmony with modern dialectal data which show that prefix *s-* has been preserved in WAT and AT in those instances in which LT has *s-*. Two hypotheses can be put forward:

- I. The complex onsets *sc-* and *sč-* were simplified in the 7th century and the simplified variants were inherited by all dialects, but the productive *s-*-prefixation was bringing new lexemes also later. LT *scol*, reflected in Rmastod [tsar] ~ [tsal], might have been formed later (the earliest attestation comes from the entry 699/700) or preserved locally in Rmastod due to the fact that the lexeme belonged to the official register.⁶⁴ The latter was certainly the reason why the LT orthography has preserved the complex onset *sc-* in this one case.
- II. The *s-*-prefixation was still productive in the middle of the 8th century and the prefix was pronounced even in complex onsets with affricates (*sc-*, *sč-*). Its later simplification in all dialects (apart from one lexeme in Rmastod) occurred either independently in various dialect groups or spread from more prestigious dialects.

I deem the first hypothesis more convincing. Both hypotheses presume that the prefix remained productive and this might have been mirrored in the OLT standard orthography even though all vernaculars had already simplified *sc-* and *sč-*.

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2. Derivation by means of the *m-* prefix: *m+ṭuŋ*
 3. Assimilation: *ṛṭuŋ*
 4. Simplification: *ṛuŋ*
 5. Causative derivation: *s+ṛuŋ*

The semantic proximity of *skyuń* and *sčuńs* has been noticed above. Simon included the former in the above word-family of *čhuń* (Simon 1975a: 613). However, no known derivational processes can account for the inclusion of *skyuń* together with the other listed lexemes.

Apart from the pair *śad* ~ *čhad* Li also quotes: (g)*śam* 'the lower part of a thing' ~ *čham la ybebs pa* 'to throw down'; *śas* 'part' ~ *čha* 'part, portion'; *śom/bśams/bśam/śoms* 'to prepare' ~ *čhom* 'to be finished' (Li 1933: 141). Although these pairs might well include cognates, more philological research is needed to account for morphological differences between the members of a pair.

The above analysis contradicts Conrady's statement that *r-*, when added to a palatal root consonant, is an allomorph of *s-* (Conrady 1896: 53).

⁶⁴ It is likewise possible that the complex onset had been preserved independently in other dialects as well but was later superseded by forms with the simplified onset.

Still another problem connected with *sčuṅs* is the lack of prefix *b-*. We notice that even though complex onsets *bsc-* and *gsc-* are attested in OLT (see OTDO), neither occurs in the OTA. The former is most frequently encountered in verbs *bscald* and *bscogs*, both attested in the OTA as *scald* and *scogs* respectively. *gsc-* is less popular but occurs even in the Žol and Žwa W inscriptions. In general, this onset is attested in three words only: *gscal* (= CT *gsal*), *gscan* (= CT *gsaṅ*), *gscan(d)* (= CT *gsan*).⁶⁵ In all three cases *g-* is a derivational and not inflectional prefix. The fact that no official document attests to the onset *bsc-* indicates that it was not authorised by the rules of the standard orthography, at least not in the period from which our documents stem. Why then does it occur at all? Two factors can be made responsible for the phenomenon: 1. hypercorrection generalising the inflectional prefix *b-* to contexts in which it was not allowed by rules; and 2. urge to archaïse the language. Each factor might have played a decisive role under different circumstances. The first factor might have preponderated among non-native Tibetan scribes of the Central Asian oases, whereas the second might have gained in importance after the fall of the Empire. Because *b-* is allowed before the complex onset *sC-* (C = stop or nasal) and, on the other hand, *brc-* is a regular onset even in CT, we may assume that prefixing *b-* to *sc-* was for some reason blocked. I assume that it was blocked because it would have facilitated the simplification *sc-* > *s-* (and *sč-* > *ś-*) despite the continuing productivity of the prefix *s-*. Accordingly, I interpret *sčuṅs* (< **b+s+√tṣuṅ+s*) as a regular *v2* of **sčuṅ* < *s+√tṣuṅ*.⁶⁶

⁶⁵ *gscug* in PT 1283: 67 is a scribal error for *gcug*.

⁶⁶ For a more detailed discussion of *bsc-* in *bscogs*, see (Bialek 2022e).

čh

čhags (#438) TR/NC [EXP]_{ABS} [GO]_{ALL} 'to indulge in'

S.v. *bkay gyod* I have demonstrated that in the phrase *bkay gyod la čhags*, *čhags* is a near-synonym of *thogs*. Accordingly, I translate *čhags* here as 'to indulge in', meaning 'to become involved in (sth. undesirable)'.

čhad ka (#626) 'sales tax'

[C] *bčad, man čhad, yan čad*

BTC: 783b: *čhad dañ don gčig*; DSM:169b: *čas kačam rgyu nor gyi miñ ste*; BYD: 146b: *čhad dañ ydrayo*.

(Bsod-nams-skyid 1992: 78, n. 101) (*čas ka*) *rgyu dños*; BDN: 244, n. 7: *čhad pa ste khirms kyi čhad pa sogs la yjug pa ydra. čhas ka ste spyi rjas su yjug pači ygreł yañ ybyuñ*; BTK: 342, fn. 3: *dus btab nas bsam bžin du žes pa lačo*; STK: 80, n. (*čas ka*) *spyi rjas dañ don gčig*; p. 325, n. 7: *čas ka ste phyugs zog gso byed kyi ybru rigs e yin nam sñam*.

(Bogoslovskij 1972: 88) *une taxe irrégulère et épisodique dont le taux était arrêté par le roi en fonction des circonstances*; (Richardson 1985: 164) *fine*; (Li and Coblin 1987: 313) *fine*; (Dotson 2009b: 51) *extraordinary taxes*; p. 121, fn. 303: *this was probably not a tax taken at regular intervals of time*; p. 258: *extraordinary tax, punishment, fine*.

čhad ka occurs altogether four times in the OTA:

(1)

čhad ka bčad / (ITJ 750: 279)

[They] decided sales taxes.

(2)

dgun (280) *yđun sgreğs gyi bya cal dañ ču bgoe rteyu mkar du yđuste / čad ka brtsis* / (ITJ 750)

The winter council, having convened at Bya-cal of Sgreğs and in Rteyu-mkar of Ču-bgo, calculated the sales taxes.

Both these quotations stem from the annual entry for the summer and winter 738/9 respectively and so one is justified to state that both activities related to *čhad ka* formed parts of one administrative means; first *čhad ka* was decided and then counted. In the second case, counting *čhad ka* was apparently the responsibility of the council.

(3)

mđo smad gyi dbyar yđun žaň stoň (31) *rcan gyis dbu šiň ñag du bsduste yul yul du čhad ka bgraňs* / (Or.8212/187)

The summer council of Mđo-smad, *žaň Stoň-rcan* convened at *Dbu-šiň-ňag*, counted sales taxes in every region.

(4)

mđo smad gyi dgun yđun gce nam yor du bsduste čhad kači rcis bgyis (Or.8212/187: 32)

The winter council of Mđo-smad, [they] convened at *Gce-nam-yor*, made an account of the sales taxes.

The latter two quotations come again from the year 758/9. Likewise here counting and making account of *čhad ka* fell in the jurisdiction of a council. Furthermore, this time it was the council of Mdo-smad and so we can infer that *čhad ka* of the region under the jurisdiction of this council was calculated separately.

In (Bialek 2018a: 1.369) I juxtaposed various administrative means recorded in the OTA that were completed with an account. I distinguished between two kinds of phrase used in the document to inform about the means:

1. A verbal phrase with *brcis* with the following arguments of the verb:

<i>nor</i> 'wealth'	<i>mjug</i> 'rest' ⁶⁷
<i>lhag čad</i> 'deficiency'	<i>snon god</i> 'balance'
<i>žugs loñ</i> 'beacon station'	<i>khram</i> 'tally'
<i>khram skya</i> 'pale tally'	

2. A determinative phrase with the head *rcis*:

<i>phyiñ rild</i> 'sheaves'	<i>sog ma</i> 'straw'
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Apart from *mjug*, we have here two distinct groups of lexemes: countable nouns with a concrete meaning (beacon station, sheaves, straw) and abstract nouns from the semantic field of economy (wealth, deficiency, balance, tally). It follows that *čhad ka* that is attested in both phrases must have belonged to one of those. Moreover, we observe that one of the economic terms, *lhag čad*, shares with *č(h)ad ka* the syllable *čad*. In order to specify the meaning of *č(h)ad ka* I shall quote another OLT passage:

(5)

lha rīs kyī ybañs dañ / dkor (29) la / khral myī dbab pa dañ / khwa dañ / čhad ka (30) myi bžes pa las scogs pa yañ // lha rīs (31) čhen poyi thañ du // bkaγs gnañ ño // (Lčañ)

It is granted by an order as the right (? *thañ*) of the great monastic estate that neither taxes will be imposed on subjects and movable property of the monastic estate nor land and sales taxes will be taken [from it].

In addition, one finds also the phrase *čhad kaγi rin* (Or.15000/401: v2) 'the value of *čhad ka*'.⁶⁸ The coordination with *khwa* in the Lčañ-bu inscription and the fact that *čhad ka* could have value unanimously locate the lexeme in the group of economic terms. Regarding the semantic contents of the term, only a very general description can be provided on the grounds of the textual evidence. *čhad ka* must have had some common traits with *khwa* and both could be taken or received by authorities – *bžes* was an HON verb used in inscriptions to denote an action on behalf of superiors to appropriate property of their subjects. When negated with

⁶⁷ The phrase *mjug brcis* is most probably an error for *mjug bčad*.

⁶⁸ *čhad ka* is also attested in the clause *čhad kar yphañs re žes*, repeatedly occurring in PT 1071 and PT 1072 (see OTDO). However, in this case I think we should read *čhed kar* 'on purpose' (cf. CT *čhed du* 'designedly, purposely, expressly', J: 160b, s.v. *čhed*). The latter is indeed attested in the same contexts in PT 1071. The proposed interpretation is confirmed by the definition delivered by BTK (see above the lexicographic section).

myi (as in Lčaṅ), the verb was meant to express the fact that the given objects but also rights (like jurisdiction and authority over certain territory or people) were conceived of as the legacy of their owner(s) who shall not be deprived of it. Therefore using the negated verb *bžes* equalled the acknowledgement that the respective entities were the legitimate possession of the party. With respect to the Lčaṅ-bu inscription, this would mean that the monastic estate was the legitimate owner of *khwa* and *čhad ka* which should not be requested by higher authorities.

Concerning the term *khwa*,⁶⁹ in accordance with my hypothesis on the origin of -w- (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))), I reconstruct its primary form as **kha ba* < *kha* 'part'. From PT 1111 we can infer that *khwa* was a tax paid in grain from arable land (*rkyā*).⁷⁰ It was then based on crop yield. In the context of Lčaṅ, it means that the monastic estate was entitled to collect *khwa*-tax from fields cultivated by its subjects and this tax could not be claimed by any higher authorities. On these grounds, I render *khwa* as 'land tax'.

From Lčaṅ it occurs that *čhad ka* (and *khwa*) had a positive value; the term denoted entities that could, at least theoretically, be taken away from their owner and this would be conceived of as unjust. It follows that *čhad-* should not be related to the meanings 'shortage, deficit' or 'fine, punishment'. Instead, I propose deriving *čhad-* from *γčhad* with the literal meaning 'what is decided'. I assume the lexeme is historically identical with CT *čhad* 'promise, engagement, agreement' (J: 154b) but as a part of economic vocabulary it may be rather rendered as 'bargain; deal'⁷¹ for which compare CT *čhad yig* 'contract, bargain' (J: 509a, s.v. *yi ge*), i.e. a written contract. Consequently I interpret *čhad ka* as a determinative compound with the underlying structure **čhad kyī kha*, lit. 'a part of a deal', assuming that it was an economic term used to denote a tax imposed on profit from concluded agreements. Thus, I propose rendering the term as 'sales tax' with the reservation that the tax possibly concerned any kind of transaction that yielded profit, not only sale but also borrowing etc.⁷²

čhab srid (#751) ¹realm; ²sovereignty; ³policy; *čhab srid la gšegs* ^ato go in support of foreign policy; ^bto go for a political campaign; ^cto go for a military campaign; ^ddiplomatic relations'

For a thorough discussion of the compound, see (Bialek 2022c).

⁶⁹ On OLT *khwa* cf.: "may have been the same as the *khwa ba*" (Li and Coblin 1987: 313), 'fine' (Dotson 2007b: 51), 'agricultural tax levied on units of arable land (*rkyā* and *dor*)' (Dotson 2009b: 50–1), 'tax, usually of grain' (ibid., p. 257), "a small tax connected to a particular field. In Chinese manuscripts from Dunhuang under Tibetan rule it was known as *dizi* 地子" (Taenzer 2013: 27, fn. 9). CT *khwa ba* is glossed as '= *dpya ba* rent or tax in kind' (D: 137a).

⁷⁰ The document states, for instance, that two *khal* of *khwa* were to be paid from each *rkyā* in Śa-ču (i.e. Dunhuang; l. 15). In addition the compound *khwa scaṅ*, lit. '*khwa* that is grain', is used in l. 3.

⁷¹ I add the meaning 'deal' understood as 'an agreement entered into by two or more parties for their mutual benefit' (OED: 368a) because of its similar etymology. To wit, Eng. *deal* goes back to OE *dælan* 'divide, participate' (ibid.) and is cognate with *dole* and Ger. *Teil* and *teilen*.

⁷² The positive economic connotation of *čhad* and *γčhad* has left its traces in modern Bathang, Themchen, Arik, and Bayan, in which *γčhad* is glossed as 'to owe (money)' (CTD.V: 384).

čas (#766) 'tack'

(Denwood 1986: 98) usually it implies a complete set or outfit of 'things', particularly tools, implements or equipment for some specific occupation.

čas < *ča* 'thing' + collective suffix -s (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))).

čhibs (#767) 'riding-horse'

As suggested by modern data from dialects and argued for in (Bialek 2018a: 1.312 & fn. 2), *čhibs* originally denoted a special kind of horse, a riding-horse.⁷³

čhibs sde (#669) 'cavalry regiment'

čhibs pon (#439) 'equerry'

ču ňu (#670) 'small'

[C] *gčuŋ, sčuŋs, ňuŋ, sŋuŋ*

če čhuŋ (#745) 'great and small'

čhen po (#671) '1large; 2great; 3grand'

In the OTA adjective *čhen po* is used attributively with nouns from the following semantic fields:

1. Material objects 'large':

gser zaŋs čhen po 'large golden pot'

2. Titles 'grand':

blon čhen po 'grand councillor'

mŋan čhen po 'grand *mŋan*'

lŋa brgya čhen po 'grand heads of the five-hundred units'

dmag pon čhen po 'grand general'

zaŋ lon čhen po 'grand aristocrat'

khud pa čhen po 'grand *khud pa*'

3. Place names 'great':

rcaŋ čen po 'Great Rcaŋ'

coŋ ka čhen po 'Great Coŋ-ka'

4. Official documents 'great':

bkay taŋ čhen po 'great decree'

thaŋ khram čhen po 'great tally of jurisdiction'

⁷³ See (Bialek 2023c).

bkay so čen pho 'great code of law'

5. Others 'great':

gnag nad čen p(h)o 'great cattle disease'

mkho sam čen pho 'great administrative arrangements'

ša liñs čen pho 'great game hunt'

ybrog mkhos čen po 'great administration of summer pastures'

ston mo čen po 'great feast'

mk(h)os čen po 'great administration'

pha los čen po 'great gathering'

bkay nan čen pho 'great instruction'

čhog śes (#777) 'contentment, satisfaction'; *čhog śesu* 'condentedly, in satisfaction'

mčhid (#759) 'speech'

mčhid śags (#672) 'pleadings'; *mčhid śags ychal* 'to plead'

DSM: 186a: ¹žal čeyam gyod bśad pa ste; ²rcod gleñ gi miñ ste.

TLTD.2: 150: pleading; 3.28: a formal statement of a case; 3.132a: statement (honorific?); TLTD.3: 21: *mčhid śags ychal* perhaps 'requested a discussion'; (Chang 1959: 142) letter of complaint or protest; (Dotson 2009b: 94, fn. 181) to put forth one's case in a legal dispute; p. 258: complaint in a legal case; (Dotson 2015b: 285) charge; (Iwao 2015: 318) counterclaim; p. 319: literally means 'the refute (*śags*) report'.

Apart from its occurrence in the OTA (ITJ 750: 87), the compound is also known from other OLT documents:

(1)

mčhid (21) *śags ychol čhig* (PT 1084; *apud* OTDO)⁷⁴

"Plead!"

(2)

ho to to gñayi myiñ rus la / čañ lha spyin (22) *dañ / ho ju ju dañ / ho ču ži la scogs pas gñaste / mčhid śags ychal baḡi dus /* (23) *ni lan ydiḡi ston sla ra ba ches bdun la / žal čhe paḡi grar mčhid śags ychal* (24) *žiñ mčhi bar bgyis /* (PT 1084; *apud* OTDO)

As for the personal and family names (*myiñ rus*) of Ho-to-to's witnesses, Čaň-lha-spyin, Ho-ju-ju, and Ho-ču-ža, among others, witnessed; at the time of pleading, on the seventh day of the last autumn month of this year, [they] caused (lit. made) that, pleading at the judge's court,⁷⁵ [they] spoke.

(3)

⁷⁴ In the passage immediately preceding the clause some letters are missing and it is not clear where the clause in fact begins.

⁷⁵ For the identification of the OLT *gra* with CT *grwa* see (Bialek 2018a: 2.408).

rta bdag hiñ ce mčhid śags rnam čhig la / bdag gi rta chugs (r19) khor na dguñ gsum mčhis pa / sluñs gyi rta gžan gčhig kyañ ma mčhis la / rta ŷdi chugs phon gyis myi mthoñ (r20) du yañ myi ruñ na / rku[s] su yañ glo ba čhuñ na / khoñ ta gar mčhis žes rmar gsol žes mčhi // (PT 1096)

As for the pleadings [of] the horse owner Hiñ-ce, [he] was saying: “Once, my horse was three nights long in the pen; there was no other horse of the stage station. If the head of the encampment must have seen this horse, [I] request [you] to ask: ‘If [he] is despondent about [the horse] being stolen, where is he?’”⁷⁶

(4)

chugs phon yañ gñay (r28) scol la / qab sab ñañ dañ / žan ŷdo khug la // dgun sla ra ba ña la mčhid śags ŷchol čhig (r29) par bčade // (PT 1096)

[One] decided that the head of the encampment must provide guarantors, summon Qab-sab-ñañ and Žañ-ŷdo, and plead on the full moon day of the first winter month.”

(5)

[---] (13) *la ŷphral du mčhid śags ŷchol te / (PT 1297.2; apud OTDO)*⁷⁷

Having immediately pleaded [...]

(6)

khoñ ta rna[ms] (16) // kyī gñayī myiñ rus la / ŷgreñ ro klu brtan / khra stag čhuñ dañ / (17) so nam legs / [rum mcho brcan / ŷbrīñ ŷbrug spe / dru gu lha legs rnams (18) kyī gña rgya dañ riñ lugs dañ dpañ čen dañ khon taŷ rnams kyi sug rgyas btab paŷ]_{app} (19) gra dus ni dbyar sla ŷbrīñ poŷi ño la mčhid śags⁷⁸ ŷchal par bgyis // (Or.15000/489)

As for their personal and family names, ŷgreñ-ro Klu-brtan, Khra-stag-čhuñ, and So-nam-legs, confirmed with the seals of the witnesses of Rum-mcho-brcan, ŷbrīñ-sbrug-spe, [and] the Turk Lha-legs, and the private seals of a representative, *dpañ čen*, and themselves. Concerning the court-time, [one] has caused [them] to plead at the beginning (? ño) of the middle summer month.

(7)

[---] (30) *gi mčhid śags las khar ca čin sar pa glo ba riñs paŷi dpon sna dañ // (Vol. 56, fol. 72; apud TLTD.2: 24)*

From the pleadings of [...], the heads of those citizens of New Khar-ca-čin who became disloyal [...]

(8)

dños gyi mčhid śags las ŷbyuñ bas [---] (Vol. 56, fol. 72; apud TLTD.2: 24)

what appears from the pleadings concerning (lit. of) the issue

(9)

⁷⁶ On PT 1096, see (Bialek 2021b).

⁷⁷ Unfortunately the preceding and the following passage are both missing due to the paper damage.

⁷⁸ What Thomas and Takeuchi have transliterated as *u* in *śagsu* (TLTD.2: 149, (Takeuchi 1998: 2.206, text 606)) seems to be rather discolouration of the paper.

(44) *thir bul khye dpal gi mčhid śags las // bdag čhagi myes po led koñ blar glo ba ñe [---]* (Vol. 56, fol. 72; *apud* TLTD.2: 24)

[It occurs] from the pleadings of Thir-bul Khye-dpal, our grandfather Led-koñ was loyal to the authorities [...].

(10)

bkas sbyañ žiñ mñan gyi mčhid śags myi brcan bar čhad (B14) *myi scal pa cham tu thugs rje čhir gzigs //* (Vol. 56, foll. 73–4; *apud* TLTD.2: 75)

Would [you] look with kindness that the pleadings of the *mñan* are not forcibly established nor accepted (lit. given)?⁷⁹

In OLT, *mčhid śags* occurs in the following collocations:

<i>mčhid śags</i>	<i>γchal/γchol čhig</i>
<i>mčhid śags la_{FOC}</i>	<i>mčhi</i>
<i>mčhid śags las</i>	<i>γbyuñ</i>
<i>mčhid śags</i>	<i>myi čhad myi scal</i>

Three points are relevant for the lexicological analysis: 1. *mčhid śags* occurs most frequently as object of the verb *γchal* and its causative equivalent *scal*; 2. it co-occurs with the verb of speaking *mčhi*; and 3. it functions as a delative complement of *γbyuñ*. Scholars who have previously dealt with *mčhid śags*, a technical term related to the judicial system of the Tibetan Empire, tacitly assumed that *śags* is the semantic head of the compound. This is apparent if one compares their renderings of *mčhid śags* (see above) with the CT meanings of *śags*: ‘²cause of a contention, object of a dispute or a quarrel, matter in dispute; quarrel, dispute, contention’ (J: 556a–b), ‘²kha mčhu rgyag paḡi rcod gtam’ (BTC: 2832a); *śags γgyed* ‘rcod pa rgyag pa’ (DSM: 931a); *śags rgyag* ‘¹va. to debate in court’ (Gs: 1093a); *śags γdebs* ‘id. śags rgyag’ (Gs:1093a); *śags gdab* ‘ñes pa drañs paḡam skyon brjod pa’ (DSM: 931a). However, as a cursory view at OLT databases reveals, it is *mčhid* that occurs frequently together with the verb *γchal* (or its cognates *scal* and *gsol*). In OLT and in CT, *śags* is used with verbs *byed*, *γgyed*, or *γdebs*. From this it follows that *mčhid* is actually the syntactic head of the compound.

Ex. (3) suggests that *mčhid śags* denoted an oral utterance. The utterance called *mčhid śags* ends with *gsol*. It seems to be a part of interrogation or dispute during a lawsuit, in which both the suspect and the plaintiff participated. In this passage, it is the plaintiff, the horse owner, who utters the *mčhid śags*. On the other hand, in two instances *mčhid śags* is used in imperative clauses as the object of *γchol čhig*, which means that one could be urged by authorities to present his *mčhid śags*. In ex. (4), the chief of the station (*chugs phon*) is urged to present his *mčhid śags* on a given day. From the document, one learns that the chief of the horse station was likewise accused of being involved in stealing the horse.⁸⁰ Therefore, both litigants of a lawsuit could present their *mčhid śags*.

⁷⁹ The translation is only tentative. Thomas’ rendering: “Will you have the kindness not to send orders invalidating the instructions of the authorities?” (TLTD.2: 78).

⁸⁰ For a concise description of the content of PT 1096, see (Dotson 2015b: 285). A detailed study can be found in (Bialek 2021b).

Regarding the phrase *mčhid śags las ybyuñ*, in (Bialek 2018a: 1.438f.) I argued that phrases of the structure ‘X las ybyuñ’, in which X denotes some kind of official document, introduce an authority on which an ensuing action rests. It follows that *mčhid śags* was an official form of an oral statement made within a lawsuit on which further proceedings depended.

According to OTDO, *mčhid śags* is the only attested compound with the first constituent *mčhid*. Therefore, we can dismiss its interpretation as an honorific equivalent of *śags*; apparently, at this stage of the language, *mčhid* was not used as an honorific classifier, otherwise we would have other similar formations.⁸¹ If, as argued above, *mčhid* is the head of the compound, *śags* has to be interpreted as its modifier. *śags* is scarcely attested in lexicographical sources on CT, but if, it is only known to be a noun. Regarding *śags* in OLT, we find, for instance, the compound *ma śags* in ITJ 730: 49, in what seems to be a title of the document: *sum pa ma śags čhen po rjogs s.ho* ‘Great *ma śags* of Sum-pas is finished.’ The same text is found in PT 992, where the title is stated at the beginning and repeated at the end as *sum pa ma śags čhed po* (14v1 & 21v8). Thomas interpreted *ma* as ‘mother’, “for, on the one hand, there is in the sayings a feminine and domestic note, [...] and on the other hand, the Sum-pa people is appropriately represented in literature by the work of a woman, since the Sum-pa country was known to the Chinese as the country of the Eastern Women” (Thomas 1957: 103). Whether one agrees with Thomas on this issue or not, there can be no doubt that the text uses the term *śags* self-referentially. On this basis, I define it as denoting aphorisms or short folk sayings that contain some general truth about life.⁸²

I conclude that *mčhid śags* was an appositional compound with the literal meaning ‘a speech that is a concise statement including the most crucial points’. Since the lexeme was a technical term used only in judicial context, I propose rendering it as ‘pleadings’ understood as a formal statement of a litigant that was delivered during a lawsuit. Because of the frequent usage of the collocation *mčhid śags ychal*, lit. ‘to request pleadings’, in official situations I deem it reasonable to assume that the phrase was highly lexicalised and therefore propose translating it as ‘to plead’, i.e. ‘to present one’s position in court’. The argument structure of *ychal* in ITJ 750: 87 confirms that the verb was transitive but nevertheless needed subject in ABS (for details, see s.v. *ycald*). *mčhid śags* was, formally speaking, its object.

mčhis¹ (#489) INTR/C [AGT]_{ABS} [DIR]_{TERM} ‘to go’

[C] *mčhis*²

⁸¹ LT *kha śags* ‘crosstalk’ was apparently coined after *mčhid* had been re-interpreted as an honorific classifier.

⁸² According to Richardson, “The tradition survived in a contest in which people of neighbouring villages might meet at their common boundary and exchange wise maxims or jesting verses in challenge and response, known as *śags ygyed pa*; similar exchanges might serve as entertainment at a party” (Richardson 1990b: 54). In this context, we can remark that Eng. *punchline* defined as the “the culmination of a joke or story, providing the humour or climax” (OED: 1164b) encompasses both meanings provided for CT *śags*: ¹‘joke, jest, fun’ and ²‘matter in dispute’ (J: 556a–b).

The basic argument structure of *mčhis* is 'HUMAN_{ABS} PLACE_{TERM} *mčhis*', lit. 'HUMAN went to PLACE'. The crucial element for the proper interpretation of the clauses is the terminative of the locative adjunct that indicates that the action denoted by the verb was a dynamic one.

***mčhis*² (#490)** INTR [THEM]_{ABS} [LOC]_{INESS} 'to stay'

[C] *mčhis*¹

The argument structure of *mčhis* is 'HUMAN_{ABS} PLACE_{INESS} *mčhis*', lit. 'HUMAN stayed at PLACE'. I assume that *mčhis* is a lexicalised inflected form of *mčhi* 'to go' derived by means of the resultative suffix -s, lit. 'to have gone': *mčhi* 'to go' > *mčhi* + -s 'to have been gone' > *mčhis* 'to be there' (Bialek 2020a: 269). In the OTA *mčhis* belongs to the normal register and is used to refer to actions undertaken by councillors. It is an equivalent of the honorific *bžugs*.

ĵ

ĵe ba (#720)

(Uebach 1997a: 55) *hapax legomenon* of hitherto unknown meaning; p. 61: was related to *bcan po*. With regard to the daughters addressed *bcan mo*, it may be assumed that *ĵe ba* indicates a lower rank. Perhaps by *ĵe ba* daughters of the *bcan po* and a co-wife are addressed; fn. 21: Perhaps the word is connected with *ĉhe ba* = elder daughter, elder sister'; (Dotson 2009b: 37, fn. 49) One possibility is that it refers to sisters of the Bcan-po's wives, in which case they are not in fact of the royal clan; p. 258: princess, lady, royal lady.

In the OTA, the difference between the titles *ĵe ba* and *bcan mo* seems to have concerned their social status; they were given in marriage to different categories of rulers:

<i>ĵe ba</i>	<i>bcan mo</i>
<i>kha gan</i> of Dur-gyis (734/5)	Sña-śur Spuñs-rye-rgyug, ruler of the Žaň-žuň (671/2)
lord of Bru-ža (740/1)	ruler of the Dags-po (688/9)
	ruler of the Ŷa-ža (689/90)

The first were independent or semi-independent rulers, whereas the latter were subjugated by the Tibetans and their polities incorporated into the Tibetan Empire. This most probably determined the social group, from which their wives were chosen. Social status of *bcan mos* seems to have been higher for their activities are always referred to with honorific verbs, which is not the case with *ĵe bas*; cf. *ĵe ba* [...] *bag mar btañ* but *bcan mo* [...] *bag mar gśegs* or *ĉhab srid la gśegs*. The term must have denoted a young woman of aristocratic descent.⁸³

ĵo mo (#722)

J: 173a: ¹mistress, a female head of a household, a woman that governs as mistress of her servants; ²lady, esp. a cloistress, nun; ³goddess.

(Thomas 1936: 285) lady; (Richardson 1985: 165) lady, queen; (Li and Coblin 1987: 398) queen; (Dotson 2007b: 16) princess; (Dotson 2009b: 32) junior wife; p. 258: junior queen, lady, royal lady.

Khri-bcun is the only *ĵo mo* mentioned in the OTA (ITJ 750: 302). Because her name does not recur in any other OLT document nothing is known about the person and her social status. Nevertheless, her high social position is evidenced by the fact that the OTA register her burial using the phrase *mdad btañ*, which otherwise refers to burials of a *bcan po* (PT 1288: 20; ITJ

⁸³ Uebach's suggestion to relate the term *ĵe ba* to LT *ĉhe ba* is problematic on linguistic grounds. Moreover, the proposed meaning of the latter term, 'elder sister, elder daughter' (Uebach 1997a: 62, fn. 21) does not seem to be attested in lexicographical sources; LT knows only *qa ĉhe* '¹an elder sister of a female person; ²wife, mistress, madam' (J: 603a). Dialectally attested voiced forms, Dzongkha *āzi* and Nangchen *ḷaze* (CDTD: 9327) resulted from voicing between vowels. The etymology of *ĵe ba* remains therefore unknown. We may only point to its unusual morphology and the use of the nominal =*ba* in a title that referred to women. In the OTA, six distinct forms of address are used with reference to women: 1. kinterms (*yum, phyi, lčam*); 2. titles (*bcan mo, ĵo mo*); and 3. *ĵe ba* (see also (Uebach 1997a)). The kinterms are simple nouns, the titles consist of two syllables, the second of which is the feminine marker =*mo*, whereas *ĵe ba* has a yet distinct word-formation. The term is used twice within the reign of Khri Lde-gcug-rcan (704–54), which fact disqualifies the proposed meaning 'elder daughter', since if both *ĵe bas* were daughters then only one of them could have been 'elder'. Neither could they be 'elder sisters' because that would mean that they were sent as brides being more than 30 and 36 years old respectively.

750: 74, 159), *bcan mo* (ITJ 750: 85, 170, 288), grandmother of a *bcan po* (ITJ 750: 162, 191, 229), and his sister (ITJ 750: 264). This fact might indicate Khri-bcun's royal descent.

The title *jo mo* is also known from other historical documents. In Bsam a certain *jo mo* Rgyal-mo-brcan is referred to as mother (*yum*) of the heir to the throne (ll. 1–2). This seems to be the only instance where a mother of the heir is given a title in a historical document. The Khra inscription attributes the donation of the bell to *jo mo* Byañ-čhub (ll. 10–1). (Richardson 1985: 82) and (Li and Coblin 1987: 346) assume that it was the same person as *jo mo* Rgyal-mo-brcan for, according to later historiographical sources, Xbro-bzay Khri Rgyal-mo-bcan became a nun, after her son (a *bcan po*-apparent) had died young, and she took the ordained name Byañ-čhub-rje.⁸⁴ In both Žwa inscriptions, *jo mo* occurs in *jo mo mched* (W 48, E 35–6). In Žwa W the order of persons enumerated is: elder brother Mu-rug-brcan – *jo mo mched* – petty kings (*rgyal phran*) – councillors of the realm (ll. 48–9). The position of *jo mo mched* between the elder brother of the *bcan po*⁸⁵ and petty kings proves that *jo mo mched* must have referred to important persons from the royal family. Analogously to *jo mo mched*, *mched* following a title is also attested in: *bcan po mched gñis* (PT 1287: 201) ‘*bcan po* [Slon-mchan and his] brother’ and *rgyal po mched gñis* (ITJ 737.1: 165, 166; *apud* OTDO) ‘king [and his] brother’. From these we can infer that *jo mo mched* was not an appositional but coordinative phrase: ‘*jo mo* and *mched*’.⁸⁶ From Bsam and Khra we have learnt that *jo mo* was applied to a woman, evidently the first wife of a *bcan po*, who gave birth to the heir to the throne, but also to the same person after she had lost her child – the heir. On the other hand, *jo mo* Khri-bcun from the OTA-I is not overtly called *yum* but nevertheless deserves a royal funeral. I assume she was the mother of Lhas-bon, who died in 739/40 (compare the similar usage of the title *jo mo* with reference to Byañ-čhub in Khra).⁸⁷ This resembles much the life history of *jo mo* Rgyal-mo-brcan alias Byañ-čhub.

In terms of its morphology, it is apparent that *jo mo* is a feminine equivalent of *jo bo*.⁸⁸ The etymology of *jo-* is unclear and the plain initial *j-* highly unusual. *je ba*, *jo bo* and *jo mo* are in fact the only meaningful lexemes with this onset in OLT.⁸⁹ We may perhaps connect *jo* to the verb ~ *yjo* (< * $\sqrt{\text{dzo}}$) ‘to milk’.⁹⁰ The original meaning of *jo mo* would have been *‘a nursing she’

⁸⁴ For a more detailed discussion, see (Bialek 2021c: 24).

⁸⁵ In (Bialek 2023a), I argued that Mu-rug-brcan was primarily the heir to the throne but due to some unknown circumstances his younger brother Khri Lde-sroñ-brcan was favoured by their father Khri Sroñ-lde-brcan.

⁸⁶ Compare, for instance, *bcan po yab sras* ‘the *bcan po*, the father and the son’.

⁸⁷ This assumption is confirmed by later historiographers who addressed Khri-bcun as *ljañ mo* (Sørensen 1994: 351) and attributed the son (*ljañ cha*) Lha-dbon to her (Sørensen 1994: 354).

⁸⁸ Cf. their co-occurrence in *jo bo jo mo* (PT 1047: 54; *apud* OTDO).

⁸⁹ Words that begin with *j-* in OLT belong to one of the following groups: 1. onomatopoeia; 2. loanwords; and 3. interrogative *ji* and emphatic *je*.

⁹⁰ On the basis of the compound *khu ljo* I have demonstrated that the verb also had the meaning ‘to suckle, to nurse’ in OLT (see (Bialek 2018a: 1.337) and (Bialek 2021a: xvi)).

from which first ‘a married woman’ and then ‘queen’ (with a shift in register) developed.⁹¹ In connection with the above observations on the historical usage of the term, I assume that *jo mo* was an official title bestowed on the first consort of a *bcan po* after she had given birth to an heir to the throne.⁹² It follows that *jo bo* would have been a secondary derivative based on *jo mo*. Its primary meaning might have been *‘a married man’ but it does not seem to have paralleled the semantic development of *jo mo* to become a title. One reason for the varying histories of the terms might be that social and political hierarchy was controlled by men and accordingly their titulature was much more diverse and developing more dynamically than that of women. Consequently more titles were available for male members of the society and there was no need to include *jo bo* as well.⁹³

mjal (#673) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to meet’

mjug (#612) ¹rest; ²end’

rje žiñ (#440) ‘lord’s field’

rje žiñ gliñs (#441) ‘lord’s fields and fallows’

rjes (#674) ‘the hind part’; in POSTP GEN+rjes *la* ‘after’

rjes is a relator noun, forming the postpositional phrase *rjes la* ‘after’ in the OTA. The latter expresses the temporal posteriority of the action with reference to the preceding action; ‘GEN+rjes *la*’ can therefore be labelled a temporal postpositional phrase.

The vast majority of Tibetan postpositions and postpositional phrases are constructed around a lexeme that was historically a noun with spatial reference.⁹⁴ Although *rjes* is usually glossed

⁹¹ For an analogous shift in the word-family of PTH *s-nəw BREAST/MILK/SUCK (STEDT #253) see (Schuessler 2007: 446), s.v. *rū*₃.

⁹² In modern dialects the term is unanimously glossed as ‘(Buddhists) nun’ (CDTD: 2778). One can speculate that this semantic shift resulted from the fact that the respective woman was called by the title after the child had died because she could not be called *yum* anymore. We know that at least in the case of Rgyal-mo-brcan she became a nun after the loss of her child. It might be that this custom was more popular and triggered the semantic change. Further semantic shift is attested in local cults of Eastern Himalayas. Namely, Huber reported that “in many communities along the Mon-yul Corridor Jumu/Jomo (= OLT *jo mo* – JB) is a female deity who is especially worshipped to benefit young children” (Huber 2020: 581, fn. 108) and further “[a]t most sites where Qa-ma Jo-mo retains a non-Buddhist character, [...] her functions frequently relate to fertility, birth and life-maintainance” (ibid., p. 581, fn. 109). Thus, the connection of *jo mo* to young children and birth continues even in modern times.

⁹³ I hypothesise that *jo bo* have been replaced by *rjo bo*, with which it alternates in PT 1287, and then by *rje*. (Hill 2014a: 171, fn. 7) argued that *rjo bo* is the original form from which both *jo bo* and *rje* developed. However, he leaves aside the problem of the motivation for the change *rj-* > *j-* and does not consider the parallel lexeme *jo mo*.

⁹⁴ For a list of most frequently used relator nouns in CT, see (Hahn 1996: 182ff.); (Schwieger 2006: 329ff.).

as an abstract noun ‘trace’,⁹⁵ in one OLT compound *rjes* has been shown to have had a concrete meaning of ‘the hind part; rear’:⁹⁶ *rjes mčhil* ‘sole’ has been reconstructed as *‘the bottom of the hinder part’ (Bialek 2018a: 2.77f.) The literal rendering of ‘GEN+*rjes la*’ would then be ‘on the rear of’ that was transferred from the spatial to temporal domain to acquire the meaning ‘after’.

⁹⁵ In (Bialek 2018a: 1.479f.) I listed the following meanings of *rjes*: 1. ‘a physical trace transferred onto a surface through direct contact’; 2. ‘lasting physical trace’; 3. ‘a track’; 4. ‘what remains after a part has been used or consumed; remnants’; and 5. *fig.* ‘what remains as a spiritual heritage, an outcome of an action, deed’.

⁹⁶ The meaning ‘der Hintertheil’ was ascribed to *rjes* already by Schmidt (Sch: 185a), although Jäschke questioned this gloss (J: 181a). Schmidt seems to have extracted the meaning on the grounds of postpositional phrases with *rjes*. Simon’s reconstruction of *rjes* as **rje* so ‘leaving-behind-place’ is as problematic as its presumed cognates *rje* ‘to barter’ and *rjed* ‘to forget’ (Simon 1941: 388 and fn. 76).

ñ

ñe (#660) **INTR** [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to be near’

gñard (#359) **TR** [AGT]_{ERG} (?) [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to tend’; *śa gñard* ‘to revenge’

In the OTA-I *gñard* is undoubtedly a verbal stem:

(1)

mdo smadu kam khri (26) *bzañ bye ydaṅ thoñ myis bkum ste śa gñard phar lo gchīg* / (PT 1288)
In Mdo-smad, a murderer killed Kam Khri-bzañ Bye-ydaṅ; [they] revenged [him].

In the following, I only cite those clauses from OLT, in which the syntactic features of the verb can be unanimously settled.

(2)

(8r316) *yul skyi ro ljañ sñon na / rje skyi rje rmañ po žig / srin skyi srin ca luñ žaṅi mchid nas* {*srin yul*} / (8r317) *mye myi dgu čhu myi rlañ gyi yul du bkri žes mchiy / skyi gśen rgyan nar žig gñar* {*te?*} / *srin* / (8r318) *ṅog du ni glud bor / lha ṅog du ni gdaṅ* (read: *gtaṅ?*) *spags* / (ITJ 734; *apud* OTDO)

In the land Skyi-ro-ljañ-sñon, *srin* Ca-luñ-ža, the *srin* of Skyi, said to lord Rmañ-po, the lord of Skyi: “[You] will be led to the land of *srin*, [to] the land where fire does not rise [and] water does not evaporate.” Rgyan-nar, the *gśen* of Skyi, was **tended**; [one] threw a ransom beneath *srins*; [one] brought forward a pledge beneath deities.

(3)

bu ni lha ṅi / buṅ ca ni / srin gyi chay {*ste*} *bon gśin/ gśen drag / čhig yod na / (88) de gñar teṅ / mgon chun phywaṅ dañ gñis gyis / gto bgyis / dphyad bgyiste / myi / śi / ba* (89) *ni / gsor myi sos / gor gam ba ni / myi ṅbyor gyis / mdad śid čher gtañ čha gar čher brsig* (PT 1134; *apud* OTDO)

As for the son – the son and grandson of deities – being the grandson of a *srin*: if there was a good *bon*-specialist, an effective (lit. forceful) *gśen*-specialist, he was **tended**. Both together with Mgon-chun-phywaṅ made a *gto*-rite, made a *dphyad*-rite. Since a dead man is not cured as a cured one, since a *gam ba* (broken?) stone does not unite, funeral ceremonies were greatly offered, *čha gar* was greatly built.

Due to the highly ritualised language of these (and other) passages and their primarily rhythmic character resulting from the metrical sentence structure, it is difficult to determine the verb valency of *gñar*. In both passages, *gñar* acquires only one argument, and thus in absolutive. The same concerns the clause from PT 1288. The absolutive arguments have very distinct semantics: human being (*skyi gśen rgyan nar žig*), body part (*śa*), and a demonstrative pronoun (*de*, for a human being: *bon gśin gśen drag*). Following Thomas,⁹⁷ I accept the

⁹⁷ (Thomas 1957: 100): “Aorist of *gñer*, ‘employed’, ‘be in charge’”. DTH translated *śa gñard* as ‘se vengèrent’ (p. 31) and was followed by Chinese and Tibetan scholars. The same interpretation was also adopted in (Yamaguchi 1975: 26), (Dotson 2009b: 85), and (Hill 2011b: 28).

identification of OLT *gñar(d)* with CT *gñer* ‘to take pains with, to take care of, to provide for, to try to get; to procure, to acquire’ (J: 194a). According to CDTD, two verbs of similar morphology and semantics are attested in modern dialects:

LT *ñar* Nurla [ɲara ~ ɲara tʃo] cEA ‘to keep’; Western Drokpas [ɲar] ~ [ɲa:] cEA ‘aufbewahren, behalten; to keep’; Nangchen [ɲa:] cEA ‘sorgen für; to look after’ (CDTD.V: 437)

LT *gñer* Tabo [ɲēr] cEA ‘to hold, to take care of’; Yolmo [ɲèr] ‘to pester, to bother so.’ (CDTD.V: 453)

Except for Yolmo, for which the respective data is missing, the remaining dialects attest to both lexemes as controllable transitive verbs.

The identification of our *gñard* with CT *gñer* is also supported by the following OLT passage, in which the phrase *śa gñer* occurs:

(4)

nu na re mkhon byuñ na / śa gñer (281) *taṃ myi gñer // phu na re // śa khrims gyis gñer pas čhogo //* (PT 1283; *apud* OTDO)

The younger brother continued: “When dissension occurred, does [they] tend the flesh or not?” The elder brother answered: “It is allowed to tend according to the flesh-law.”

In PT 1288 *śa gñard* occurs after information on a murder and in PT 1283 *śa gñer* is an action allowed in consequence of a dissension or a conflict (*mkhon*).

OLT phrase *śa gñard* can be juxtaposed with *sku mchal gñer* from a later source:

(5)

khyod kyis // ña yi yab kyi go bgyis rgyal sar bton // sras kyi go bgyis yab kyi sku mchal gñer // (KhG 163; *trslr. apud* (Dotson 2013a: 170, fn. 116))

You, having taken place of my father, raised [me] to the throne; having taken place of the son, [you] tended the blood of [my] father.

By analogy with the *b*-verb *bton* from the first clause, we can interpret *gñer* in (5) as a *v2*-stem. Its direct object *sku mchal* ‘blood’ comes from the same semantic field of BODY PARTS as *śa* ‘flesh’. In the given context, the metaphorical phrase *sku mchal gñer* seems to express the biological relationship between a father and his son who is obliged to take care of his father’s blood (metaphorically) and not to spoil it.⁹⁸

The etymological meaning of *śa gñard* is better understood if we include the following passage that contains the lexeme *śa* in a very particular meaning related to death:

(6)

⁹⁸ Matrilineal and patrilineal descents are related to in Tibetic by means of the terms *śa* ‘flesh’ and *rus* ‘bone’. However, in the phrases *śa gñard* and *sku mchal gñer* ‘flesh’ is juxtaposed with ‘blood’, and it appears from the KhG that blood was a metaphor for patrilineal descent. The same pair of concepts is encountered in Sog-ru village, in the Reb-goñ area of A-mdo. There “[i]t is said that each of the four *cho ba* is composed of people who have had ‘flesh and blood relationship’ (*śa khrag ybrel ba*)” (Buffetrille 2008: 16). The latter author also noticed the departure from the common flesh and bone system (*ibid.*)

spyan / bltas / na mčič / bas sño śa / bltas gyis (81) dar / bas dkar (PT 1134; *apud* OTDO)

When [they] examined [his] eyes, [they] were bluer than the sky. When [they] examined [his] flesh, [it] was whiter than silk.

The passage concerns examination of a corpse. Here, *śa* seems to denote ‘surface of the body’ (J: 554b, s.v. *śa*), in particular of a dead body.

I assume that the primary meaning of *śa gñard* was ‘to tend a dead body’ understood as taking care of deceased’s earthly remains. This reading is indirectly supported by CT *sku mchal gñer*, lit. ‘to tend the blood’. However, the latter phrase is already attested in OLT in a derived meaning:

(7)

(50) *gčuñ ña khyī nī yab kyī mdad gtoñ ño / gčen śa khyī ni yab kyī sku mchal gñer du gśegso /* (PT 1287)

The younger brother Ña-khyi was performing the funeral ceremony for (lit. of) the father. The elder brother Śa-khyi was going to take revenge for [his] father (lit. to tend the father’s blood).

The story further narrates that Ña-khyi was Rkoñ-dkar-po (ll. 50–1), i.e. the ruler of Rkoñ. The story continues without an overt subject switch, which makes the impression that it is still Ña-khyi who sets out with an army of 3300 soldiers to take revenge. This would contradict the events related in the story. First of all, it is said (see ex. (7)) that it was Śa-khyi who took revenge. Secondly, the person who kills people from the Lo-ñam clan (ll. 54-55) returns to Pyiñ-ba-stag-rce after the succesful revenge (l. 58). Now, if Ña-khyi was Rkoñ-dkar-po, he could not have resided in Pyiñ-ba-stag-rce at the same time. Therefore, *sku mchal gñer* announced in l. 50 can be identified with actions undertaken by not overtly addressed Śa-khyi and aimed at eliminating the clan of Lo-ñam.⁹⁹

In conclusion, the following semantic development can be proposed for both phrases:

<i>śa gñard</i>	‘to tend the (dead) body’	> ‘to take revenge’
<i>sku mchal gñer</i>	‘to tend the blood’	> ‘to take revenge’

The quoted passages provide us with the following forms of what seems to be one and the same verb: CT/OLT *gñer*, OLT **gñerd*, OLT *gñard*, OLT *gñar*. There are good reasons to concern *gñer* and **gñerd* as distinct forms. On the one hand, we have the clause *śa gñer taṃ myi gñer* (see ex. (4)), in which the question clitic *taṃ* attests to the underlying **gñerd*. On the other hand, in (7) we find *sku mchal gñer du gśegso*. The expected form of the terminative marker after an underlying *da drag* would be *tu*. (Garrett, Hill, and Zadoks 2013) established that in subordinate constructions such as the one discussed here *gśegs* can take either v1 or v3-stems. Therefore we have:

gñard = v2

⁹⁹ For a detailed grammatical analysis of the passage, see (Zeisler 2011a: 170f.) Her analysis is correct but overlooks the fact that the grammar of the first chapter of the OTC is much distorted and cannot be analysed at face value without previous restoration. For some examples of the said distortions, see (Bialek 2018a: s.v. *rje dbyal*).

gñer = v1/v3

**gñerd* = ?

The phrases *śa gñard* (1) and *śa gñer* (4) confirm that *gñard* and **gñer* belong to one conjugation. Since in modern dialects only reflexes of *ñar* (v4 *ñor*) and *gñer* are attested, a plausible solution would be to assume that OLT *gñar(d)* was derived from *ñar*. Accordingly, I tentatively reconstruct the following derivation: $\sqrt{\text{ñar}}$ 'to keep'¹⁰⁰ > *d-/g-* + $\sqrt{\text{ñar}}$ 'to tend' (on the agentive prefix *d-/g-*, see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))). The alternation *gñer* ~ **gñerd* requires further study; both forms seem to represent v1-stem of the verb.

gñis (#659) '1two; 2both'

gñe bo (#675) 'personal assistant'

J: 193a: *gñe ba*; also *gñe bo*, *smye bo*, a wooer, courter; WtS.23: 522b: Gefolgsman, Bote.

(Bellezza 2008: 528, fn. 610) the groom's receiving party; mod[ern] = *gñen po*; (Dotson 2009b: 258) groomsman.

From ITJ 750: 176–7 it appears that the function of *gñe bo* was to assist Kim-śaṅ *khon* čo on her arrival in Tibet.

bsñeṅs (#442) TR [STIM]_{ERG} [EXP]_{ABS} (?) 'HON to frighten'

The morphology of the verb, with the causative prefix *s-*, suggests that it was a transitive verb and accordingly we would expect its actual meaning to have been *'to terrify, to frighten'. In support of this hypothesis, the verb is attested in at least two out of four forms available for TR verbs: *bsñeṅs* and *sñeṅs*:

(1)

rgyal pos ma sñeṅs śig (*Mjaṅs blun*, *apud* J: 200a, s.v. *sñeṅ ba*)

Don't be afraid of the king!

On the other hand, its argument structure recalls the argument structure of typical verbs of fear, like *dkrog*, *skrag*, *yjigs*, *γchabs*, for which the object of fear is marked with ergative in CT and usually by allative in modern spoken varieties.¹⁰¹

The verb is a *hapax legomenon* in OLT and one of the arguments is omitted so that its marking remains unknown. A few more occurrences of *bsñeṅs* in the meaning 'to stretch' are attested in a single document – Or.15000/266 (see (Takeuchi 1998: 2.120, text 367)). Curiously enough, none of the modern digital versions of *Mjaṅs blun* knows the clause quoted in (1) (cf. rKTs, BCRD, BDRC). Instead, in canonical literature we find two types of clause with final imperative clitic:

HUM_{ABS} *ma bsñeṅs śig* 'HUM, don't be afraid!'

¹⁰⁰ Cf. dialectal meanings cited above.

¹⁰¹ BDSN glosses *bsñeṅs pa* as 'yjigs pa' (*apud* (Takeuchi 1998: 484)). In *Śiṣyalekha* (115a) *mi bsñeṅs* renders Skt. *abhaya* 'unfearful, not dangerous, secure' (MW: 60c). The data quoted from *Śiṣyalekha* is based on an unpublished index that I prepared for the late Prof. Hahn.

X_{ERG} *ma bsñeñs śig* 'Don't be afraid of X!'

On this scarce evidence, I propose the following semantic development:

'to let sth. stretch' > idiomatic usage *'to let one's hair stretch' > (metaphorisation) 'HON to scare up; to terrify' > 'to be terrified, afraid'

In this context we can quote Eng. idioms *hair-raising* and *make sb's hair stand on end*. The same connotations between fear and hair-raising were apparently present in OLT as the following verse attests:

(2)

bsrogs kyañ ni spu (468) *myi lañs* // (PT 1287)

Although [they] frightened [the tiger], the hair [of its fur] was not able to stand on end.

The change from the once transitive to intransitive verb can be explained as resulting from re-analysis of the argument structure:

X_{ERG} Y_{ABS} *bsñeñs* 'X terrified Y' > ' X_{ERG} *bsñeñs*' 'id.' > '[Y] was terrified by X' > '[Y] was afraid of X'

The latter change might have occurred under the influence of other INTR verbs of fear that mark the object of fear with ergative.

t

gteyu (#444) ‘hostage’

Apart from its occurrence in the OTA-I, *gteyu* is also attested in the following passage:

(1)

gteyu [-] (4) *gčig dañ sña gčig bsruñ ba žag lña sa ti puñ bgyis* (ITJ 1247; trslr. *apud* TLTD.2: 404)

Five days long, Sa-ti-puñ guarded one [-] hostage and one witness (?).¹⁰²

Although the right edge of the document is torn off and we can't know how much of the text is missing at the end of each line,¹⁰³ the comparison with other sentences allows us to assume that the phrase *gteyu* [-] *gčig* (maybe even originally restricted to these two words) denoted a human being that in a way was related to a judicial system of the Empire. The text also mentions: *bcon sruñs* ‘prison guards’, *sña bran* ‘serf of a witness’, *sgo g.yog* ‘private servant’, *sña* ‘witness’. Thomas translated *gteyu* with ‘guarantor’ (TLTD.2:404), whereas DSM explains the term as ‘ñes čan gco boyam rcod gži mkhan’ (245a). In the OTA, the action expressed with *gteyu bsdus* seems to be related to the preceding event, in which many *ᠬᠠ-ᠵᠠ* paid homage to the Tibetan *bcan po*. This is suggested by the gerundial =te. On the other hand, in canonical literature the most frequently occurring phrase with *gteyu* is *gteyu bzuñ*, which follows a subjugation of a region (cf. BCRD). With this scanty information in mind, I propose reconstructing the OLT meaning of *gteyu* as ‘hostage’ (cf. J: 208, s.v. *gte bo*).

gteyu is derived from *gtay*, CT ‘pawn, pledge’ (J: 206b), by means of the imitative diminutive -*bu* (cf. (Bialek 2021f: 261)). Csoma glosses *mi gtay* as ‘a bailman, an hostage’ (27b).¹⁰⁴ The phrase ‘gathering hostages’ might have referred to a common practice of taking members of ruling or aristocratic families (frequently also the heir to the throne) hostage in order to secure political obedience of the subjugated ruler. In the case of his disobedience, the hostages were to be killed. From Chinese sources, we know that also other society members were taken hostage and worked for, e.g., the Tibetan administration: “First of all, whenever they get Chinese, those without any ability serve as local servants and their faces are branded. Those roughly familiar with arts and letters have their arms tattooed and are made to wait upon the orders of the emperor. When they obtain Chinese whom they use as supplementary government servants they call them retainers.” (Zhào lín 趙璘, *Yin huà lù* 因話錄; *apud* (Sperling 1979: 23)). Chinese sources also describe detention of envoys by the Tibetans (*ibid.*, 26f.) Therefore, it is no wonder that in the OTA taking hostages apparently took place in

¹⁰² Thomas (TLTD.2: 404) suggests to equate *sña*, attested a few times in this document, with the CT *gñay bo* ‘witness’ (J: 192a). I follow Thomas’ interpretation. The literal translation of [...] *bsruñ ba* [...] *bgyis* would be ‘did guarding of [...]’.

¹⁰³ This description follows Thomas (TLTD.2: 403). A scanned image of ITJ 1247 is not yet available on IDP.

¹⁰⁴ DTH: 33, followed by (Dotson 2009b: 88), read *gteyu* as a toponym. This interpretation does not seem plausible – there is no parallel case of omission of a terminative clitic after a toponym in the OTA and *bsdus* is not known to take a toponym as direct object.

connection with a foreign embassy to the Tibetan court. The preceding clause mentions numerous *Xa-ža* (*ya ža mañ po*) people that paid homage to the *bcan po*. I assume that those are exactly the people that were taken hostages.

gtogs (#804) INTR [EXP]_{ABS} [STIM]_{ALL} ‘to participate in’

btañ (#447) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘¹to send (to [DIR]_{TERM})’; *bag mar btañ* ‘sent as a bride ([FUN]_{TERM}) for sb. ([BEN]_{ALL})’; ‘²to let have, to give’; *mdad btañ* ‘organised a funeral’

Apart from its single occurrence as an independent verb, in the OTA *btañ* is used first of all in collocations *mdad btañ* ‘organised a funeral’ and *bag mar btañ* ‘sent as a bride’. The latter rests on the basic meaning ‘to send’ attested in ITJ 750: 133. If we paraphrase the verb *to send* as *to let have*, we can interpret *mdad btañ* as ‘let have a funeral (of sb.)’, i.e. ‘organised a funeral’. The complete argument structure of the verb is not attested in the OTA but can be adduced from another OT text:

(1)

spad mchan bdun gyīs gtañ rag čhed po btañ ño // (PT 1287: 273)

The seven kinsmen (? *spad mchan*) sent great thanks.

btab (#550) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘¹to cast; ²(LV) to prepare’

In the OTA, *btab* is used only as a light verb:

khram btab (ITJ 750: 106, 112, 208) ‘to issue a tally’

thañ khram btab (ITJ 750: 222, 251, 290–1; Or.8212/187: 9) ‘to issue a tally of jurisdiction’

gnag liñs btab (Pt 1288: 24) ‘to organise a yak-hunt’

pho brañ btab (ITJ 750: 296; Or.8212/187: 2, 38–9) ‘to settle the court; to encamp’

phyiñ rild btab (ITJ 750: 96, 98, 107, 213–4) ‘to prepare sheaves’

śa liñs btab (Pt 1288: 31–2) ‘to organise a game hunt’

The meaning underlying all the above phrases seems to have been ‘to prepare; to make ready’. The argument structure [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} of the verb is demonstrated in:

(1)

mgar ybrīñ rcan / rcañ (107) *rton dañ / pa cab rgyal can thom po gñīs gyis / g.yo ruḃī žiñ gyi phyiñ ril btab* (ITJ 750)

Both *Mgar Ybriñ-rcañ Rcañ-rton* and *Pa-cab Rgyal-can Thom-po* prepared sheaves from the fields of Left Horn.

btuñs (#445) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [PAT]_{ABS} ‘to slaughter’¹⁰⁵

DSM: 247b–8a: *bsad payi miñ layañ yjug ste*.

¹⁰⁵ This verb was briefly discussed in (Hill 2008: 77ff.)

BDN: 106, fn. 9: *bduñs te brduñs dañ don gčig čin ɣdir* (i.e. PT 1287: 379 – JB) *bsad paɣi don* (s.v. *bthuñs* – JB); STK: 215, fn. 7: *brduñs dañ don gčig la ɣdir* (i.e. PT 1287: 379 – JB) *bsad paɣi don ston paɣo* (s.v. *bthuñs* – JB); BTK: 124, fn. 4: *bthuñs. bduñs pa ste btuñs pa dañ gčig go. bsad paɣi don no* (s.v. *bthuñs* – JB); BNY: 166, fn. 27: *brduñs pa*.

DTH: 33: *tuer*; (Chang 1959: 135) to be killed or massacred; (Li and Coblin 1987: 168) appears to be the perfect form of some other verb, perhaps cognate to *rduñ ba*; (Hill 2008: 77) to massacre; (Dotson 2009b: 89) to massacre; fn. 155: seems to apply most often to a large numbers of people.

Verb *btuñs* of the OTA can be juxtaposed with:

(1)

dbaɣs skyes bzañ stag snañ gis // (379) rgya ɣi dmag pon hon je sañs dañ / ɣguɣ log sgañ du g.yul sprad nas / rgya mañ po bthuñs ste / (380) ɣguɣ log rgya dur du btagsɣo // (PT 1287)

At *ɣguɣ-log-sgañ* (lit. hill of *ɣguɣ-log*), *Dbagys Skyes-bzañ Stag-snañ* committed a battle against (lit. with) *Hon-je-sañs*, the general of the Chinese. Then, having slaughtered many Chinese, [he] named *ɣguɣ-log* ‘Chinese grave’.

(2)

go bar du g.yul sprad de // rgya mañ po bthuñs nas / rgya ɣi ro gčhig gnam du ɣgreñ ba ya{ñ} (523) {*myi?*} *ɣb[u]m bsad pa ɣi mchan ma zes bya ɣo / (PT 1287)*

Having committed a battle in the middle [between the two armies], [one] slaughtered many Chinese. Therefore, [it] is called ‘a body of a Chinese upright to the sky [is] a token for one hundred thousand people killed’.

(3)

bod kyis g.yul (61) bzlog nas // rgya mañ po btuñs pas // rgya rje kwañ (62) peñ ɣwañ yañ / keñ śiɣi mkhar nas byuñ stey / (63) ssem čiyur bros nas / (Žol S)

Because Tibetans slaughtered many Chinese after [they] had won the battle, even the Chinese ruler *Kwañ-peñ-ɣwañ*, having left the stronghold of *Keñ-śi*, fled to *Ssem-čiyu*.

In PT 1285 we find the following analogously formed verses:

(4)

*bdud čhab ni gžur la / ɣthuñs /
bdud (v14) zag nī / thems la bsad /*

The couplet is not intelligible to me but it seems to be based on a parallel between the following (synonymous?) terms:

<i>bdud čhab</i> ‘water of a <i>bdud</i> ’	~ <i>bdud zag</i> ‘a drop of a <i>bdud</i> ’ ¹⁰⁶
<i>gžur</i> ‘?’	~ <i>thems</i> ‘?’
<i>ɣthuñs</i> ‘?’	~ <i>bsad</i> ‘killed’

This as well as the morphology of the OLT variant *bthuñs* (see above) suggest that the verb *btuñs* could be cognate with: *rtuñ* ‘to make shorter, to shorten, to contract’ (J: 213a); MT *stuñ* ‘to shorten’ (CDTD.V: 528); and *thuñ ba* ‘short’ (J: 233b); Yolmo [thūŋ] ‘to be shortened, to become too short’ (CDTD.V: 528). Moreover, *btuñs* is explained as: ‘*bsad pa*’ (CDSN, *apud*

¹⁰⁶ I understand *zag* as cognate with the verb *ɣag* ‘to drop, drip, trickle’ (J: 463b). For a nominal formation compare MT *gzag thigs* ‘drop’ (CDTD: 7455).

(Mimaki 1992a: 495b)) and 'kuṭṭita; = *bsad pa* killed' (D: 529b). The Skt. participle *kuṭṭita*, 'bruised; pounded, flattened; unskillful opening of a vein (the latter being cut to pieces by repeated application of the knife)' (MW: 289a), is derived from the root √*kuṭṭ* 'to crush, bruise; to grind or pound, paw (the ground); to strike slightly; to multiply; to censure, abuse; to fill' (MW: 288c). The following derivatives from the same verb root can be of interest for the understanding of the semantics of *btuñs*:

kuṭṭaka 'cutting, breaking, bruising, grinding' (MW: 288c)

kuṭṭana 'cutting, pounding, grinding, beating, threshing' (MW: 288c)

In addition, Lokesh Chandra provides *kuṭṭā* with Tibetan equivalents *gčod gtogs* and *gčod rtogs* (Chandra 2007: 173c). The same source, on the other hand, glosses *kuṭṭayati* as 'γthub pa, (b)rduñ ba' (ibid.). Since neither *γthub* nor any of its potential forms seems to be attested in OLT in meanings glossed in CT lexicographical sources, we may assume that in the latter definition it has replaced the earlier **γthuñs*. The presented data suggest that the original meaning of **γthuñs* was 'to make short(er) by cutting down'.¹⁰⁷ From this the figurative meanings 'to crush, smash; to slay' derived. According to Jäschke (269b), CT *rduñ* 'to beat, to strike; to cudgel, to drub; to beat with a hammer, to hammer; to knock; to break to pieces, to smash; to beat out, to thrash; to pound, to bray' (J:285b) has a variant *bduñ*. It is possible that the original meaning of *rduñ/bduñ* has changed towards 'to beat, to strike' under the influence of *rdug* 'to strike against, to stumble at' (J: 285b). As another cognate we could consider Themchen [tun] *ncA* 'to disperse (fog)' (CDTD.V: 593), glossed (mistakenly?) s.v. *duñ* 'to desire'. *btuñs* was a near-synonym of *bkum*¹⁰⁸ and *bsad* but seems to have been used with plural objects and thus in a context of a battle or other military actions only. While *bkum* and *bsad* could also have denoted an intentional action against a concrete person, *btuñs* was lacking this kind of individuation. In order to differentiate between *bkum* and *bsad*, on the one hand, and *btuñs* on the other hand, I propose rendering the latter as 'slaughtered' understood as killing large groups of people in a violent way.

The above discussion is based on semantic proximity of a set of verbs. The exact derivational processes (e.g., affixing) and the alternation between voiced and voiceless consonants in onsets of the verbs remain to be clarified.

¹⁰⁷ The forms *γthuñs* and *btuñs* indicate that the final -s belonged to the stem. It might come from the original agentive suffix *-d, deriving verbs from non-verbs (cf. (Bialek 2020a: 318, fn. 136) and (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))).

¹⁰⁸ Cf., for instance:

blon čhe khri γbriñ (122) *γa ža yul du mčīs śiñ / stag la rgya dur du rgyayī dmag pon γwañ žañ śo dañ g.yul sprade rgya mañ po bkum* (ITJ 750)

Grand councillor [Mgar] *Khri-γbriñ* [Bcan-brod], while having gone to the *Ya-ža* land, fought a battle with the Chinese general *Xwañ žañ śo* at *Stag-la-rgya-dur* [and] killed many Chinese.

bton (#452) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} 'to expel'

None of the OLT passages provides clues as to the verb's complete argument structure. For modern dialects the verb is unanimously glossed as cEA (cf. CDTD.V: 646). The absolutive object argument is confirmed in the following passage:

(1)

dbays bcan bžer mdo (382) *lod la scogs pas / mkhar chan yan čhad du drañste / mkhar ču pa brgyad phab nas / dor po bton te /* (383) *γbañs su bžes so //* (PT 1287)

Dbays Bcan-bžer Mdo-lod, among others, having marched up to Mkhar-chan, captured eight [forts] of the Mkhar-chan prefecture.¹⁰⁹ Thereafter, having expelled the resistant ones, [he] took [them] as subjects.

btol (#351) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} (?) [THEM]_{ABS} 'to expose, reveal, uncover; to make visible/open'¹¹⁰

Itab mar (#676) 'again'

Cs: 277b: fold, crease, plait; WtS.26: 119a: Schlinge [des Dünndarms].

DTH: 39: ITab ma (interpreted as a place name -JB); (Dotson 2009b: 101) intercalary month; fn. 213: read *ldab*.

There can be no doubt that *Itab mar* in ITJ 750: 136 is an adverb. I propose relating it to the verb family TR √*Itab* (v1 *ldab*, v2 *bldabs*, v3 *bldab*, v4 *ldob*) 'to double' ~ INTR √*ldab* (v1 *ldab*) 'to do sth. again/repeatedly'.¹¹¹ *Itab ma* was a noun derived from the verb root by means of the matrix =*ma*.¹¹² The entry for the year 701/2 mentions twice a military action against Zon-č(h)u and Theyu-č(h)u. With the second mention the adverb *Itab mar* is used. Thus, I reconstruct its meaning as *'again, repeatedly'.

rta (#551) '(calendric) horse'

[C] *tha* in: *tha skar* (Li 1933: 150)

***Itaṅ** (#798) 'bale'

Following (Dotson 2009b: 94, fn. 182), I propose emending *Itoṅ* in ITJ 750: 88 with **Itaṅ*, ¹a bale of goods, carried on one side of a beast of burden, half a load' (J: 217b), 'Ledersack, Tierlast' (WtS.26: 117b). For a detailed analysis of the phrase **Itaṅ brgyus*, see (Bialek 2018a.1: 397ff.)

¹⁰⁹ I understand *mkhar ču pa* as a mixed formation of the underlying structure *[*mkhar chan ču*]+*pa*, lit 'those (*pa*) related to Mkhar-chan-ču'. The syllable -ču might be a loanword from Chinese *zhou* 州 'prefecture' and so Mkhar-ču would be the prefecture of the Mkhar-chan region. For Mkhar-chan, see LS-O, s.v. Khar-can.

¹¹⁰ For this verb, see (Bialek 2021e).

¹¹¹ This word-family can be extended by √*slab* (v1 *slob*) 'to learn (by repeating)'. The stem alternations of the verbs allow to reconstruct two roots: TR √*lab* and INTR √*lab*.

¹¹² On the matrix function of -*ma*, see (Bialek 2021f: 272f.)

Itaṅ yo (#797) ‘?’

Itaṅ yo is a hapax legomenon known only from the clause *dru gu yul du Itaṅ yor mčhis* (ITJ 750: 64), that has been variously translated in previous studies: “fut à Ltaṅ-yo dans le pays Dru-gu” (DTH: 34); “[Minister Bcan-sña] went to Itaṅ-yor in the Dru-gu country” (Chang 1959: 148); “was gone to Ltaṅ-yo in Dru-gu-yul” (Uray 2007 [1979]: 120); “went to Turkistan for plunder” (Beckwith 1993: 42, fn. 24); “[He] went to [Western] Turkestan (Dru-gu-yul) for plunder” (Dotson 2009b: 91); “went to Ltaṅ-yo in the land of the Dru-gu” or “went to the land of the Drugu for a (forced) ?trade agreement (*Itaṅ yo*)” (Zeisler 2010: 392); “[He] went to Turkestan for plunder” (Hill 2011b: 33).¹¹³

As correctly observed by (Beckwith 1993: 42, fn. 24): “The grammatical construction of this sentence does not allow the last word (i.e. *Itaṅ yo* – JB) to be taken as a place name.” *mčhis* as a verb of motion allows only one argument in terminative that expresses the direction towards which the movement proceeds. The interpretations proposed by Bacot, Chang, and Uray would have required the determinative phrase **dru gu yul gyi Itaṅ yor*, lit. ‘to Ltaṅ-yo of the Dru-gu-land’.

According to the OTA, in the winter 676/7 councillor Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu drew (*draṅs*) to the Dru-gu land. The verb *draṅs* is generally used to refer to troop movements. Thus, in 675/6 the councillor first went (*mčhis*) to the Dru-gu land (with, as for now, unknown intentions) and then, one year later, led a military campaign there. From Chinese sources we know that the military campaign was carried out in cooperation with A-shi-na (Beckwith 1993: 42: *Aršila) Du-zhi, the qaghan of the Western Turcs, who, although appointed by the Chinese emperor, created an alliance with Tibetans and attacked together Kucha (Chavannes 1903: 73f.) Therefore, if the verb *draṅs* expressed the joint military activities of Tibetans and Turcs in the Dru-gu land, the preceding (non-military) ‘visit’ of councillor Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu could have been connected to the formation of the alliance with the Turcs. It is important to emphasise the dependence of A-shi-na Du-zhi on the Chinese at that time, to whom he owed the appointment to the General over one of the Turkic tribes in 671 (Chavannes 1903: 73); (Beckwith 1993: 37f.) Thus, the mission of Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu seems to have aimed at persuading A-shi-na Du-zhi to change his allies.

Now, there are two possibilities for interpreting *Itaṅ yor* (whatever its internal structure might have been) in the clause: (i) *Itaṅ yor* stands in absolutive; (ii) *Itaṅ yor* stands in terminative and its base-form is *Itaṅ yo*. If *Itaṅ yor* stands in absolutive, then it must denote an agent (in the given context, a human being) of the verb *mčhis*. We know that the subject of *mčhis* is councillor Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu. If, on the other hand, *Itaṅ yor* stands in terminative, the

¹¹³ The interpretation put forward by Beckwith (‘he went to Turkistan for plunder’, (Beckwith 1993: 42, fn. 24) and accepted by (Dotson 2009b: 91) and (Hill 2011b: 33) has to be rejected because the semantic role of purpose was expressed by allative in OLT: *žaṅ rgyal zig [bod yul du]_{TERM} [mol čen la]_{ALL} / mčhis* (Or.8212/187: 55) ‘žaṅ [Mčhims] Rgyal-zigs [Šu-theṅ] went to the Bod land for a great conferral.’ In addition, we can remark that Beckwith’s interpretation of the formation as consisting of *Itaṅ* ‘a bale of goods’ and *yo byad* ‘necessities for life, provisions, supplies’ (ibid.) does not address the problem of negative connotations of ‘plunder’ that, for obvious reasons, cannot stem from the constituents.

clause has two elements in terminative: *dru gu yul du* and *ltañ yor*. I have found a few clauses in OLT with the verb *mčhi(s)* and two elements in terminative. I group them according to the thematic role of the non-locative terminative:

1. Directional adjunct

(1)

jeɣu hiñ yir [slar] [chugsu]_{TERM} mčhis te (PT 1096: r15–6)

Jeɣu-hiñ-yir came again to the encampment.

(2)

[zu ce gan du]_{TERM} [mkhar khri bomsu]_{TERM} mčhis nas (ITJ 1375: v6)

[He] went **to** (lit. in the vicinity [of]) Zu-ce, to [his] stronghold Khri-boms.

(3)

blon čhe snañ bžer [bod yul du]_{TERM} [slar]_{TERM} mčhis (Or.8212/187: 30)

Grand councillor [Dbays] Snañ-bžer [Zla-brcan] came back to the Bod land.

(4)

žañ rgyal zigs [slar]_{TERM} [bod yul / du]_{TERM} / mčhis (Or.8212/187: 52–3)

žañ [Mčhims] Rgyal-zigs [Śu-theñ] went back to the Bod land.

2. Temporal adjunct

(5)

lo ñam rta rjī yañ / [mkhar myañ ro śam por]_{TERM} [sñar]_{TERM} mčhīs so (PT 1287: 13)

Lo-ñam Rta-rjī went **first** to the castle Myañ-ro-śam-po.

3. Function adjunct

(6)

[ju čhañ yan čhad dañ / lug luñ man čad du]_{TERM} [gñer du]_{TERM} mčhi (PT 1096: r21)

[I] am coming from Ju-čhañ to Lug-luñ **as** helper/to help.¹¹⁴

(7)

legs sgra zla brcan [śa čur]_{TERM} [pho ñar]_{TERM} mčhi (PT 2204c: 15)

Legs-sgra Zla-brcan goes to Śa-cu **as** emissary.

4. Verbal complement

(8)

khug ron rmañ dar (r71) rkyañ ron rñog bkra gñis [yul byañ ka snañ brgyad du]_{TERM} [phu rlag nu yis chol du]_{TERM} mčhi mčhi na / (r72) phu yid kyi gdañ pyam gyi bšos kyi žal dañ dañ ni ma mjal / (ITJ 731; trslr. *apud* OTDO)

When both Khug-ron Rmañ-dar [and] Rkyañ-ron Rñog-bkra were going to the land Byañ-ka-snañ-brgyad **to** look for the lost elder brother by the younger brothers, [they] did not encounter the *žal dañ* of the living elder brother Yid-kyi Gdañ-pyam.

¹¹⁴ On problems with the interpretation of this passage, see (Bialek 2021b: 698).

In all these examples, one of the elements in terminative expresses the direction towards which the subject is proceeding; the semantics of the other terminative varies. Now, knowing the historical context and the possible interpretations of the semantics of a second terminative in a clause, the following readings of the phrase *Itaṅ yor mčhis* can be put forward:

Re. 1: Directional adjunct: ‘across’ (?); *Itaṅ* = CT ‘also *Iteṅ*, W[estern Tibet]: through, quite through’ (J: 217b),¹¹⁵ *yo* = CT ‘oblique, sloping, slanting, awry, crooked; obliquity, slope, slant’ (J: 514b). In this interpretation, *Itaṅ yor* would denote the way councillor Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu went from the Žaṅ-žuṅ land (where we carried out the administration, ITJ 750: 64) directly to the Dru-gu land omitting Central Tibet.

Re. 2: Temporal adjunct. I am not able to propose any analysis of *Itaṅ yo* that could yield a temporal reading.

Re. 3: Function adjunct: ‘[Councillor Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu] went to the Dru-gu land as a *Itaṅ yo*.’ In this case *Itaṅ yo* would denote an office or a function that the councillor would have represented. The reading of *Itaṅ yor* as adjunct of function would require a human referent, for which I am currently unable to suggest any plausible underlying structure.¹¹⁶

Re. 4. Verbal complement: *Itaṅ yor mčhis* = ‘went in order to do *yo* to *Itaṅ*’. In this interpretation *Itaṅ* has to be the direct object of a transitive verb *yo*. Since *yo* is only known as an intransitive verb (cf. CDTD.V: 1159) we would need to somehow emend the phrase. One possibility is to assume a loss of a velar prefix after the velar final of the preceding word: **Itaṅ g.yo* > *Itaṅ yo* (*g*- > Ø / -*n*_#_C). The phrase **Itaṅ g.yo* could be interpreted as ‘to incite (lit. move) *Itaṅ*’ (for *g.yo*, see CDTD.V: 1179). However, loss of a prefix in a free morpheme is rather infrequent and the meaning of *Itaṅ* in this phrase remains unknown. We can only speculate that by the time the text has been copied the phrase had already become obsolete and the scribe understood it as one word, inadvertently leaving the prefix out.

Admittedly, none of the proposed interpretations is really plausible, especially as I am unable to propose a convincing underlying structure for any of them. Modern lexicographical sources provide several compounds in *-yor* but they are either nouns or adjectives. Thus, the only thing we can be certain is that the form of the lexeme is *Itaṅ yo* (most probably a noun) and that *-r* is to be identified with the terminative clitic but the semantics and etymology remain unexplained for now.

stag (#552) ‘(calendric) tiger’

J: 220a: tiger.

(BUSHELL 1880: 521) When alive they [Tibetan nobles who had gained fame in battle – JB] wore the tiger-skin, and it is a sign of their valour when dead; (Stein 1972: 201) a red roof built beside the tomb carried the painting of a white tiger, symbol of warlike valour; (Stein 1984: 258) En Chine, depuis l’antiquité (*Tcheou-li*), on appelait ‘tigres’

¹¹⁵ Cf. also *Itaṅ* ‘through, all the way through (?)’ (Coblin 1991c: 95); *Itaṅs spyad pa* ‘yag ñes žib dpyod byed payi don te’ (DSM: 257b), where *Itaṅs* can be translated as ‘thoroughly’.

¹¹⁶ The gloss *Itaṅ ba* ‘utthānam’ (Sakaki 1965: 9325) is based on a false reading of the Tibetan text and should be emended as *Idaṅ ba* (see (Ishihama and Fukuda 1989: 9260).

les soldat braves (*hou-p'en*). Au Tibet, l'image est attestée par les Annales chinoises; (Stein 1985: 105) tigre, soldat brave; (Richardson 1998d: 272) It is known from Chinese records that the Tibetans were highly skilled in fine metalwork and also that they decorated the tombs of their warriors by painting white tigers on them; (Beckwith 2008b: 179) regular loan reflex of 虎 Old Chinese *stâγ ~ *steγ 'tiger'; (Dotson 2009b: 147, fn. 426) Tiger skins were employed during the period of the Tibetan Empire to distinguish and decorate soldiers.¹¹⁷

stañs dbyal (#446) 'HON husband and wife'

stoñ (#557) 'thousand'

stoñ sde (#559) 'thousand-district'

WtS.27: 155b: Tausendschaft, Tausendschaftsdistrikt.

DTH: 52: dictrict improductif; (Tucci 1949: 738) chiliarchy; (TUCCI 1956B: 81, FN. 1) chiliarchy, thousand-district, a territorial division; each territory was obliged to contribute in case of war a regiment of one thousand men; (Chang 1959: 139) chiliarchy; (Uray 1960b: 31) thousand-district; (Stein 1963: 328) groupes de mille; (Stein 1972: 53) group of thousand; (Stein 1984: 264) groupes de mille; (Uebach 1985b: 23) Tausendschaftsdistrikt; (Li and Coblin 1987: 181) thousand-district, a fundamental unit into which the early Tibetan empire was divided; (Coblin 1991c: 95) a Thousand-district, a military/administrative unit; (Richardson 1992: 107, fn. 16) thousand district; (Takeuchi 1994b: 848) the basic military and administrative units of the Tibetan Empire; p. 859, fn. 18: the Tibetan military and administrative system, including *stoñ sde* and *chan*, finds its origin in the Central Eurasian nomadic system; p. 861, fn. 36: the numeral in the term *stoñ sde* 'thousand-district' refers to the number of member households and not the number of soldiers to be raised; (Uebach 1997b: 997) thousand-district, the fundamental military and civil administrative unit of Tibet proper, i.e. the Four Horns; (Takeuchi 2004b: 53b) Each *ru* comprised in principle eighth *stoñ sde* or chiliarchies, which served as the basic unit for supplying soldiers to the government; (Iwao 2007: 219) the operative military unit in the Old Tibetan Empire; if a soldier on duty became sick, he had to be replaced by someone in the same *stoñ sde*; (DOTSON 2007A: 30) thousand district; (Dotson 2007b: 58) thousand-districts were not concerned only with military matters, and cannot be regarded as brigades. They levied provisions, processed them and sent them along; (Dotson 2009b: 39) thousand-district, each comprised of one thousand households; each thousand-district supplied one thousand soldiers; (DOTSON 2015B: 287) thousand-district.

< **stoñ gi sde*, lit. 'a district of thousand'; a military and administrative unit of territorial division within the Four Horns and in the colonies; presumably consisted of approximately one thousand households obliged to various duties, including supplying soldiers.

stoñ dpon (#560) 'thousand-district head, head of a thousand-district'

J: 222b: a commander over a thousand.

(Francke 1914b: 44) master of thousand, colonel; (Francke 1924a: 17) Herr über tausend; (Thomas 1933: 382) head of Thousand-district; (Lalou 1955: 180) chef de mille; (Chang 1959: 130) officer of a *stoñ sde*; p. 139: commander; (Uray 1961: 227, fn. 6) chief of thousand(-district); (Uray 1982: 546) head of a thousand(-district); (Li and Coblin 1987: 181) a commander of a *stoñ sde*; (Orofino 1990: 174) commander of a thousand men; (Coblin 1991c: 95) commander of a Thousand-district; (Richardson 1992: 107, fn. 16) *stoñ pon (dpon)*; (Dotson 2009b: 58) a head of thousand district.

< **stoñ sdeyi dpon*, lit. 'head of a thousand-district'.

¹¹⁷ These ornaments given for bravery seem to have been called *stag gi thog bu* (cf. PT 1287: 386).

stoň bu rje (#735) ‘chief of a little thousand-district’

(Uray 1982: 546) master of a little thousand(-district), head of the *stoň bu čhuň*; (Uebach 1997b: 1000) Lord (or master) of little thousand[-districts]; (Dotson 2009b: 58) a head of little thousand-district; p. 105, fn. 231: The existence of a *stoň bu rje*, who is presumably the head of a *stoň bu čhuň* or ‘sub-thousand district’ is a good indication of the probable existence of thousand-districts (*stoň sde*) and heads of thousand districts (*stoň dpon*) at this time; (Hill 2011b: 33) heads of little chilliarchies.

< **stoň buyi rje*. The comparison with two other OT offices suggests that *stoň bu rje* was a chief of **stoň bu* and not of **stoň bu čhuň*, as maintained in earlier works.¹¹⁸

Head of an office	Little-head of an office
<i>stoň dpon</i>	<i>stoň čhuň</i> ¹¹⁹
<i>stoň bu rje</i>	<i>*stoň bu čhuň</i>

To these we can also add:

<i>ru dpon</i>	<i>ru ybriň</i>	<i>ru čuň</i> ¹²⁰
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The proper title (*dpon* or *rje*) could be replaced if the resulting term was unambiguous. *stoň čhuň* cannot be interpreted as ‘little thousand-district’ because there is another technical term for the latter: *stoň bu*. However, the fact is that neither of the terms, **stoň bu* or **stoň bu čhuň*, is attested in OLT. KhG is the most authoritative source that mentions *stoň bu čhuň* as a territorial unit (cf. (Tucci 1956b: 75–7, 81–6); (Uray 1960b: 31)). I suspect that post-imperial authors misinterpreted the term *stoň bu čhuň*, ascribing to it the meaning of *stoň bu*, i.e. ‘little thousand-district’; they identified *stoň bu čhuň* with *stoň bu*.¹²¹

stod smad (#677) ‘upper and lower’

ston (#558) ‘autumn’

ston mo (#448) ‘feast’

I propose a tentative etymology of *ston mo* that relates the noun to another noun: *ston* ‘autumn’. Originally *ston mo* would have referred to a festival that marked the end of the harvest season and the beginning of the autumn; cf. Pol. *dożynki*, Ger. *Erntefest*, Eng. *harvest home*. In the OTA, the lexeme is used in a more general meaning ‘feast’; it was prepared in the spring 675/6 by *bcan mo* Khri-mo-lan for *bcan po* Khri Maň-slon Maň-rcan (ITJ 750: 62–3).

¹¹⁸ Cf. (Uray 1982: 546), (Dotson 2009b: 58), and (Bialek 2018a: 1.374).

¹¹⁹ For the identification of *stoň čhuň* as an office, see (Uray 1982: 546).

¹²⁰ (Uray 1961: 226–7 & fn. 6).

¹²¹ Otherwise it would be difficult to explain the morphology of **stoň bu čhuň* for the DIM *-bu* already informs that its referent is a smaller version of the original, i.e. *stoň sde*, and so *-čhuň* is superfluous.

stord (#520) INTR/NC [THEM]_{ABS} 'to get lost'

bltam (#521) TR [AGT]_{ERG} (?) [THEM]_{ABS} 'HON to cause to be born, to give birth'

In the OTA *bltam* is used in the meaning 'to be born' and thus only with respect to the heirs to the throne. Its passive v3-stem (with the prefix *b-* but without the suffix *-s*) indicates that the verb was transitive.¹²² In OLT the verb is almost exclusively attested in the form *bltam* and the only occurrence of the form *bltams* (PT 1084: 18) suggests that it was used in a different meaning. CT dictionaries gloss the verb as *ltam(s)/bltams/bltam/ltams* (or *ltoms*) '1to be full, also *gtams pa*; 2resp[ectful] to be born' (J: 218a). Neither of the meanings conforms to the transitive character of the verb but the verb is also explained as 'to cause to be born; to give birth to; to fill' (Kharto: 116f.) The latter meaning is confirmed in Sertha (CDTD: 522) and allows us to relate the verb to the following potentially cognate formations: *gtam(s) pa* 'full' (J: 206b); *Item pa* 'the state of being full; full, overflowing' (J: 219a); *tham pa* 'complete, full' (J: 230a); *thams čad* 'whole, all' (J: 230a); *lhams kyis* 'at once, all, every thing' (J: 601b; < *'fully').¹²³

These, however, suggest two underlying roots:

√ <i>l</i> am	√ <i>t</i> am
<i>ltam(s)</i>	<i>gtam(s) pa</i>
<i>Item pa</i>	<i>tham pa</i>
<i>lhams kyis</i>	<i>thams čad</i>

The verb root √*l*am can be derived by the prefixation of *γ-*: *γ*+√*l*am > **γ*+D+√*l*am (D-epenthesis) > **γ*tlam (devoicing) > **t*lam (loss of *γ-*) > √*l*am (metathesis). *lhams* seems to have been a noun from which an adverb was derived by means of the ergative clitic *kyis*. The vowel *-e-* in *Item* can only be explained if we assume that it was the original v1 of the verb: v1 *Item* (< **ltam+d*; cf. (Bialek 2020a)), v2 *bltams*, v3 *bltam*, v4 **lhoms* (?). Whether these lexemes can be connected to the root √*t*am remains uncertain.¹²⁴

Given the semantics of the word-family, the original meaning of the verb **Item/bltams/bltam/*lhoms* must have been 'to fill' < **ltam* 'to be full'. The etymological meaning underwent metaphorisation and the verb started to be used as an honorific: 'to fill' > *'to cause to become full (of a baby)' > 'to cause to be born'. Although the verb is abundantly attested in canonical literature I have not found any complete clause that would attest to the expected argument structure *[AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS}. This is not a surprise as giving birth to a child

¹²² Because the root of the verb was √*l*am, it could only form v2 with *b-s* and v3 with *b-*; cf. (Bialek 2020a).

¹²³ The relation of *lhem* 'now, at present, directly, instantly; all' (J: 602a) to the discussed word-family, although suggested by Jäschke, is less probable due to its diverging semantics.

¹²⁴ Neither a derivation by means of a prefix *l-* nor the loss of preconsonantal *l-* are known in Tibetan languages. Therefore, if the roots √*l*am and √*t*am were historically related their divergence must have started at an earlier period. (Gong 1977: 218) proposed deriving *lčam* *'children of the same parents, brothers and sisters' from *ltam* *'1to be full; 2to be born' by means of a presumably honorific infix *-y-*: **lt+y-* > **lty-* > *lč-*. Since the existence of such a prefix has not been proved (for a distinct hypothesis on the origin of honorifics, see (Bialek 2023c)) and there is no indication that *lčam* might have originally denoted children, Gong's reconstruction has to be rejected.

can hardly be conceived of as a controllable action. One can even assume that the meaning 'to cause to be born' was used only with the passive v3 *bltam*. First after the collapse of the original verb inflection the meaning 'to be born' (< *bltam* 'be caused to be born') spread to the other forms of the verb as well.

bstod (#679) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} 'to advance'

The argument structure (MT: cEA, CDTD.V: 534) is confirmed in the following OT passage:

(1)

khyo ḡdaḡ / (207) bcan po ḡi snam pyī par bkay scal nas // lo du ma žig lon na // ḡjañs rño thog go žes // [myī čhig gīs]_{ERG} / (208) bstod pa kho bos ma thos na // (PT 1287)

"In many years that have passed since you, Sir, were ordered [to act] as an attendant of the *bcan po*, I have not heard a single man praise [you saying] '[He] is wise [and] capable'."

√*stod* was derived from the noun *thod* 'crown' by means of the causative prefix *s-*; *stod* *'to make the crown; to raise to the crown' > 'to advance' > 'to praise'.

In the OTA the verb seems to be attested in its primary meaning 'to advance', which we also see in:

(2)

zla goñ gi bu cha rgyud (18) ḡpeld la rje blas gyī rño thog paḡī (19) rñams jī cam du rño thog par bkas (20) bkur žiñ bstod par gñañ ño/ (Žol N)

[One] grants to the descendants of Zla-goñ that, as far as [they are] competent [persons] for (lit. of) an official duty, [they] will be honoured by [*bcan po*'s] words as capable ones and advanced.

th

thañ (#776) ‘¹level; *thañ du* to the level (of); ²jurisdiction’

For a detailed semantic analysis of *thañ* in OLT, see (Bialek 2018a: 1.499f.) For *thañ du* ‘to the level of’, see (Coblin 1991c: 96).

thañ khram (#425) ‘tally of jurisdiction’

thams čad (#678) ‘all’

(Francke and Simon 1929: 113) The first syllable of *thams čad* is related to the word *γtham pa*, to seize, grasp. The same stem is also found in the word *tham pa*, used after decimal numerals; (Zimmermann 1979: 118) ich sehe in *thams* eine erstarrte Form von *γtham* ‘pack-’, (um)faß-’, ‘verein-’; (Hahn 2003b: 81) *thams čad* ist nämlich nicht, wie die Wörterbücher uns glauben machen möchten, ein Adjektiv, sondern ein Adverb, etwa ‘allesamt’. Damit erklärt sich [...] dass dieses Wort auch nach einer Pluralpartikel stehen kann.

thugs ñen (#449) ‘supply’

[C] *rdugs*

thoñ myi (#529) ‘murderer’

thoñ myig (#578) ‘suicide attempt (?)’

thob (#579) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to get possession of, to obtain’

In CDTD.V: 583 the verb is unanimously glossed as ncDA. A different argument structure is attested in the OTC:

(1)

γbañs (343) *mgo nag pos kyañ / rgya dar bzañ po khyab par thob bo //* (PT 1287)

Black-headed subjects also acquired fine Chinese silk as coverings (lit. to cover [themselves] with).

Likewise in WtS.29, s.v. *thob*, we find single attestations of the verb with the argument structure [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} in CT texts. From this we can infer that the subject of the verb could acquire the agent role if its referent was volitionally striving for obtaining the object, which is evidently the case in the OTA. In these instances it may be preferable to translate the verb as ‘to get possession of’ or ‘to procure (with effort)’. In the OTA, *thob* is used with the adverb *slar* ‘back’ and so *slar thob* can be translated as ‘to retake’.

mthay (#580) ‘border’

The lexeme is attested only once in the OTA and thus at the beginning of the manuscript (PT 1288: 2) where the paper is badly damaged. Therefore its identification must remain tentative.

mtha bži (#724) 'all'

DTH: 63: all round; p. 66: generally; (Dotson 2009b: 128–9) four directions; p. 134: four frontiers (for so *mtha bži*).

Orig. a possessive attribute *'having four ends'. Since it was originally an attribute of the horizon and the sky it came to denote vastness and inclusiveness of the respective objects.

d

da (#581) 'now'

da rgyal (#586) 'king of the Dags-po'

(Chang 1959: 130) an official title; (Uray 1960a: 206) eine Würde ähnlich wie *dbon ya za rje*, *Rkoñ kar po* und *Myañ bcun*; eine Variante des Titels *Da rgyal/Dar rgyal*; 'König von Dags'. Dieser *Da rgyal/Dags rgyal* regierte die Landschaft *Dags/Dags śul/Dags yul/Dags po*, welche die Tradition für eines der zwölf, bzw. dreizehn vorgeschichtlichen Länder, d.h. Stammesgebilden des Schneelandes hielt. Diese Landschaft lag östlich von *Yol-kha* und *Yar-luñ* am nördlichen oder an den beiden Ufern des *Gcañ-po* und ist im wesentlichen mit dem heutigen *Dwags-po* identisch; (Richardson 1967: 19, fn. 8) seems to be a princely title; (Uray 1972b: 30) a title, namely that of the king of the vassal state *Dags-po*.

Basing his analysis on the "Katalog der Fürstentümer" (= PT 1286?) and "Türkiskatalog eines mythologischen Textes" (= PT 1285?), Uray maintained that the OLT title *da rgyal* should be read as a variant of *dags rgyal* 'König von Dags', i.e. 'king of Dags' (Uray 1960a: 206). Unfortunately, Uray did not present any arguments that led him to the identification of *da rgyal* with *dags rgyal*. The following list provides all the mentions of the title *da rgyal* in the OTA-I:

	<i>da rgyal</i>	Mañ-po-rje	653/4	PT 1288: 24
	<i>da rgyal</i>	Mañ-po-rje	659/60	PT 1288: 37
<i>γbon</i>	<i>da rgyal</i>	Khri-zuñ	675/6	ITJ 750: 63
<i>γbon</i>	<i>da rgyal</i>	Khri-zuñ	687/8	ITJ 750: 98
<i>dbon</i>	<i>da rgyal</i>	Khri-zuñ	688/9	ITJ 750: 100–1
<i>dbon</i>	<i>da rgyal</i>		690/1	ITJ 750: 105
<i>γbon</i>	<i>da rgyal</i>		694/5	ITJ 750: 118
<i>γbon</i>	<i>da rgyal</i>	Bcan-zuñ	706/7	ITJ 750: 157
<i>γbon</i>	<i>da rgyal</i>		707/8	ITJ 750: 160–1
<i>γbon</i>	<i>da rgyal</i>	Bcan-zuñ	711/2	ITJ 750: 179–80
<i>γbon</i>	<i>da rgyal</i>	Bcan-zuñ	711/2	ITJ 750: 181
<i>γbon</i>	<i>da rgyal</i>		712/3	ITJ 750: 184
<i>γbon</i>	<i>da rgyal</i>		712/3	ITJ 750: 186
<i>γbon</i>	<i>da rgyal</i>		713/4	ITJ 750: 188
<i>γbon</i>	<i>da rgyal</i>		714/5	ITJ 750: 194
<i>γbon</i>	<i>da rgyal</i>		714/5	ITJ 750: 196

In other OLT documents we encounter the title *dags rgyal*:

	<i>dags rgyal</i>	Sprogs-zin	<i>dags śul</i> ¹²⁵	PT 1285: r23
	<i>dags rgyal</i>	Spro-zin	<i>dags śul</i>	PT 1285: r91
<i>rje</i>	<i>dags rgyal</i>	Sprog-zin	<i>yul dags</i>	PT 1286: 18–9

to these we shall add

<i>rje</i>	<i>dar rgyal</i>	Sprog-zin	<i>dags yul</i>	ITJ 734: 8r335 ¹²⁶
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¹²⁵ *śul* is an assimilated form of *yul*; for details, see (Bialek 2018a: 216).

The fourth column gives the assumed land, over which the respective ruler was reigning. Not only the land, but also the title and the proper name of the ruler indicate that one and the same person is addressed in the last four cases.

Not being a historical document, PT 1286 includes a list of petty kings (*rgyal pran*) that seem to have ruled at one time. The only historically attested person is Lig Sña-śur, a ruler of Žaň-žuň (l. 7). The same person occurs in the OTA-I likewise as ruler of the Žaň-žuň. There we are told that Lig Sña-śur was defeated by *bcan po* Khri Sroň-rcan and his land subjected in 644/5 (ll. 13–4). We can speculate that Sprog-zin was a contemporary of Lig Sña-śur and so ruled Dags-yul in the 630/640s.

The last OLT passage that mentions a *da rgyal* reads:

(1)

da rgyal kyi g.yu rma lčhags Turquoise of the *da rgyal* – Rma-lčhags;

rkoň rgyal kyi g.yu (r126) thi[n s]nar Turquoise of the *rkoň rgyal* – Thiň-snar.

(ITJ 734r; *apud* OTDO)

da rgyal and *rkoň rgyal* are preceded by *spu rgyal* in the same fragment. All three apparently denoted local rulers of polities in some vicinity to each other. In other documents the land of *Dags* is mentioned in the company of:

Smra – **Rkoň** – Myaň – Žoň – Mčhims – **Dags** – Rñegs – Xol-phu – Dbye-mo – Yar-luň – Skyi-ro – G.yu-ro (PT 1285: r19–29)

Rñegs – **Dags** – Mčhims – Žoň – **Rkoň** (PT 1285: r90–4)

Rcaň-ro – Skyi-ro – Yar-luň – Dbye-mo – Xol-phu – Rñegs – **Dags** – Mčhims – Žon – **Rkoň**
(PT 1285: 171–83)¹²⁷

Žaň-žuň – Myaň-ro – Gnubs – Śam-po – Skyi-ro – Ńas-po – Dbye-mo – Xol – Rñegs – Klum-ro – Slibs – **Rkoň** – Myaň – **Dags** – Mčhims – Sum – Xbrog (PT 1286: 7–22)

By mentioning only *da rgyal* and *rkoň rgyal* the passage from ITJ 734 ascribes them a special position among the so-called petty kings (*rgyal phran*).

According to the OTA-I, *da rgyals* were involved in the administration of the Four Horns in: preparing sheaves of fields (l. 24), organising great exchange of fields (l. 25), appointing a *mñan* of the Žaň-žuň (l. 25), fighting with Chinese (l. 37), convening councils (ll. 98–9, 100–1, 105–6, 118, 157, 160–1, 179–80, 181–2, 184–5, 186–7, 188–9), appointing heads of five hundred units (l. 189), preparing administration of the Xa-ža (ll. 194–5), and leading an army (ll. 196–7). As for their rank, *da rgyals* occur preceding Gnubs Maň-ñen Bži-brcan and Mgar Sta-gu Ri-zuň (l. 98), grand councillor Mgar Khri-ybriň Bcan-brod (ll. 105–6), Gnubs Maň-ñen Bži-brcan (l. 118), grand councillor Dbays Khri-gzigs Žaň-ñen (ll. 157, 160–1, 179–80, 181–2,

¹²⁶ In PT 1043: 95 we find *da ryal* that should be read *da rgyal* but it forms part of a mythical name of a *smān* – Da-ryal-bcun-mo, lit. ‘the lady of a *da rgyal*’. *dar rgyal* of ITJ 844: 5 does not belong here. It is part of the name Dar Rgyal-ma (cf. (Takeuchi 1995: 259)).

¹²⁷ The localities mentioned in PT 1285 are projected on a map in (Dotson 2008: 54).

184–5, 186–7, 188–9, 196–7), and *żań* Bcan-to-re Lhas-byin (ll. 194–5). Most informative is their mention before grand councillors.

As rightly observed by (Uray 1960a: 206), out of three *da rgyals* mentioned in the OTA-I, only the last two were additionally called *γbon/dbon*: Khri-zuñ and Bcan-zuñ. According to the latter author, the kinterm indicates that they were descendants of a Tibetan royal princess, ‘Königstochter’ (ibid.).¹²⁸ This, however, does not have to be the case; in fact, two options are at hand:

- I. Khri-zuñ was a son of a *bcan po*’s sister who had been married to Khri-zuñ’s father, a *da rgyal*. This should have been *da rgyal* Mañ-po-rje and the Tibetan princess would have been a sister of either Khri Mañ-slön Mañ-rcan or his father Guñ-sroñ Guñ-rcan (cf. PT 1286: 63–4). However, none of the preserved OLT documents speaks of marrying a *da rgyal*. On the contrary, a marriage with a ruler of the Dags-po is first mentioned in 688/9:

(2)

dgun (Čhos-γphel) *dbon da rgyal* (101) *khri zuñ gyis / žogs gyi chur luñ du bsdus / bcan po khri mo steñs dags yul du čhab srīd la gśegs* (ITJ 750)

In the winter *dbon* Khri-zuñ, the king of the Dags-po, convened [the council] at Chur-luñ of Žogs. *bcan mo* Khri-mo-steñs went to the Dags-po land in support of foreign policy.

Although this one entry mentions both a *da rgyal* and the Dags-po land, no connection is drawn between the two.

- II. Title *γbon/dbon* was used as a political metaphor like, for instance, in ST Treaty where *bcan po* Khri Gcug-lde-brcan is called *dbon* and the Chinese emperor – *żań* (Treaty W 1–4). According to PT 1286: 68–9, the mother of Khri Gcug-lde-brcan was Lha-rgyal Mañ-mo-rje, a lady from the Xbro family (*γbro za*), and there is no indication in any OLT source that it might have been a Chinese princess instead.¹²⁹

Apart from *dbon/γbon da rgyal*, in the OTA-I only *γa ža rje* is addressed with the kinterm *dbon/γbon*. This once more confirms a higher position of the *da rgyals* against other Tibetan functionaries, including grand councillors.

Concluding, in no document does *da rgyal* occur in connection with either *dags yul* ‘the land of the Dags-po’ or *dags po* ‘Dags-po people’. On the contrary, the ruler of *dags yul/śul* is called *dags rgyal* in PT 1285 & PT 1286. Was Uray wrong with his identification of *da rgyal* with *dags rgyal*? Not necessarily. Two arguments speak actually for Uray’s hypothesis: 1. if we were to reject his identification, the title *da rgyal* would stand alone and could not be related to any

¹²⁸ Cf. also (Dotson 2009b: 84, fn. 136): “Da-rgyal was the epithet of the vassal king of Dags-po, who later became related to the Tibetan emperor by marriage after which he enjoyed the epithet *dbon*, meaning nephew, son-in-law, and bride-receiver.”

¹²⁹ On the classificatory function of kinterms in OLT, see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming)).

other known polity;¹³⁰ and 2. *dar rgyal* of ITJ 734 is related to *dags yul*, on the one hand, and, on the other hand, is given the proper name Sprog-zin. The proper name is identical with the name of the *dags rgyal* from PT 1285 and PT 1286, but the title is *dar rgyal* instead of *dags rgyal*. The form *dar rgyal* can be easily explained away as resulting from dittography: *-r* of *dar* is repeated from *r-* in *rgyal* due to quick and thus inaccurate pronunciation. Therefore, *dar rgyal* shall be reconstructed as **da rgyal* and this yields us the only thus far identified evidence of the historical relationship between the *da rgyal* title and the *dags yul*. Since the earliest mention of *da rgyal* comes from the year 653/4 and the demonym *dags po* is attested in the OTA-I as late as in 718/9, it would be unwise to state that *da-* is a reduced form of *dags-*. Whatever the origin of the syllable *dags-*,¹³¹ its identity with *da* of *da rgyal* can now be considered established and the underlying structure of the compound *da rgyal* may be reconstructed as **dags poḡi rgyal po*, lit. ‘the king of the Dags-po people’.

dug ma (#588) ‘malefactor’

DSM: 323a: dug gtoñ mkhan gyi miñ ste.

DTH: 36: poison; (Dotson 2009b: 95) poisoner.

The assumed connection between *dug ma* and *dug* ‘poison’ is confirmed in the following clause:

(1)

dug ma źig gīs dug sbyos te ñi ma la dug physis bźag pha ño /// (PT 1047: 204; *apud* OTDO)

The sign [of] a poisoner who, having showed¹³² the poison, put the poison-cloth in the sun.

Here, as well as in the OTA (ITJ 750: 93), *dug ma* obviously denoted human beings. But the function of *-ma* still needs an explanation. I tentatively propose interpreting *-ma* as a morpheme forming adjectives from nouns; thus, *dug* ‘poison’ > *dug ma* ‘poisonous’ (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))). The latter word subsequently underwent semantic broadening: ‘poisonous’ > ‘venomous’ > ‘vicious’, and could be applied to humans with bad character, malicious.¹³³ Thus, *dug ma* did not have to denote poisoners *per se*, but in general persons who committed or intended to commit a crime.¹³⁴ Accordingly, I propose the translation ‘malefactor’ in the OTA and the literal ‘poisoner’ in PT 1047, where *dug ma* is directly related to *dug* ‘poison’. The OTA speak of ‘many *dug mas*’ that were caught. The vision of many

¹³⁰ This in itself is not a serious obstacle, since we have other titles attested that likewise cannot be connected with any known polity; compare, for instance, *ra sañ rje*.

¹³¹ It could, for example, go back to a clipping of **da+Xags*. Alternatively, *da* could be part of an endonym for which Tibetans used the form *dags*.

¹³² CDSN glosses *sbyos pa* as ‘bsdigs pa’ (*apud* (Mimaki 1992a: 499)); *sdig(s)* ¹‘to show, to point out; ²‘to aim; ³‘to menace, to threaten’ (J: 293b).

¹³³ Metaphorical extension is also attested for *dug*, cf. ‘poison; *dug gsum* in a moral sense, *γdod chags*, *gti mug*, *že sdañ*; sometimes *dug lña*, five moral poisons, are mentioned’ (J: 252b).

¹³⁴ For the proposed derivation, compare: *bla* ‘the space over, above a thing’ (J:382) > *bla ma* ‘superior’ > ‘a lama’. This function of *-ma* is described in (Hahn 1996: 35, § 5.6h) and (Bialek 2022a: 101).

poisoners undertaking action against the *bcan po* is less appealing than the one of many malefactors plotting in order to impede the enthronement of an adolescent ruler.

de (#590) DIST.DEM ‘that’

dra čen (#680) ‘great [advance] force’

For a detailed discussion of the lexeme, see (Bialek 2018a: 2.178ff.)

dra ma (#760) ‘advance force’

DTH: 136: la noblesse; (Chang 1959: 135) attack; (Uray 1962a: 223) army or troop sent on an enterprise or campaign, expeditionary army; p. 224: not only does the word *dmag/mag* occur more frequently than *dra ma* but it has a wider meaning since it is used also in compounds denoting offices of permanent, organisational and not occasional character whereas *dra ma* occurs only in connexion with military expeditions against foreign territories or with the termination of the former. Accordingly, we must ascribe to *dra ma* a meaning which is related to the meaning ‘army, host, troops, soldiers’ of the word *dmag* but somewhat narrower yet comprising the connotation ‘military expedition’; (Coblin 1991a: 319) expeditionary force; BDN: 30, fn. 18: *dmag dpuñ gi don*; BTK: 108, fn. 5: *dmag dpuñ ñam dmag mi la*ϣo. *bzañ po*ϣi *don la*ϣañ *ϣjug go. yul sul kha skad du mi bzañ po la mi dra ma zes ybod srol yod*; STK: 137, fn. 21: *dmag sdeyam dmag dpuñ gi don*; (Dotson 2009b: 259) military campaign; (Zeisler 2010: 393, fn. 25) elite expedition corps.

For a detailed discussion of the lexeme, see (Bialek 2018a: 2.181ff. & 524ff.)

drags (#803) ‘to be much’

drañs (#5) ¹TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} (*ϣdrañ/drañs/drañ/droñs*) ‘to lead, to draw’; ²INTR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [DIR]_{TERM} (*drañ/drañs*) ‘to draw, to march to’

In the OTA-I, *drañ(s)* as a simple verb occurs with the following argument structures:

I.	HUM _{ERG}	PLACE _{TERM}	<i>dra ma</i> _{ABS}	<i>drañste</i>	(ITJ 750: 196–7)
			<i>dmag</i> _{ABS}	<i>drañs pha</i>	(ITJ 750: 255)
II.	HUM _{ERG}	PLACE _{TERM}		<i>drañste</i>	(ITJ 750: 67–8, 97, 127)
	HUM _{ERG}	PLACE _{TERM}		<i>drañs</i>	(ITJ 750: 97, 274–5, 276–7)
		PLACE _{TERM}		<i>drañs</i>	(ITJ 750: 133)
		PLACE _{TERM}		<i>drañste</i>	(ITJ 750: 135, 136–7)
	HUM _{ERG}	PLACE _{TERM}		<i>drañ</i>	(ITJ 750: 94)

Arguments structures of both groups attest to an agentive subject of the verb (marked with ergative on the human argument). The difference between the groups concerns the transitivity of *drañs*: the verb is transitive in group I, but intransitive in group II. This has been confirmed by my survey of PT 1042 (see (Bialek In Preparation)), showing that two meanings of *drañs* bound to distinct argument structures should be distinguished: ¹TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} (v2 *drañs*, v3 *drañ*) to lead; to fetch; ²INTR/C [AGT]_{ERG} (v2 *drañs*) to lead’ (see also (Bialek 2020a: 281)). PT 1042 depicts a funerary ritual and *drañs* with one argument in

ergative cannot be interpreted as representing the phrase *dra ma drañs*. The latter interpretation of *drañs* when occurring without an object argument in the OTA was put forward by (Uray 1962a: 224) and more recently accepted by (Zeisler 2010: 393, fn. 25).¹³⁵ In fact, we have two distinct albeit cognate verbs (sharing at least one form – *drañs*). Apart from the already discussed forms *drañs* and *drañ*, OLT also knows *ɣdrañ*, *droñs*, and the presumably belonging to the same conjugation *ɣdren*. In the following, I shall look more closely at these forms by quoting passages that can shed more light on the morphology and semantics of this verb family.¹³⁶

drañ

(1)

blon khri ɣbriñ gyīs / dru gu yul du drañ zes (95) bgyī ba las / phyī dalte / (ITJ 750)

Upon [it] was being said “[Grand] councillor [Mgar] Khri-ɣbriñ [Bcan-brod] marches to the Dru-gu land,” [the action] delayed.

(2)

bod rgya gñis // [...] de las phan chun dgrar myī (32) ɣthab // [dmag]_{ABS} myī drañ // yul myī (33) mnam // (ST Treaty)

Both Tibetans and Chinese [...] from that [moment on] shall not fight one another as enemies; armies shall not be led; land shall not be seized.

It is apparent that in *myī ɣthab*, *myī drañ*, and *myī mnam* all the verbs display the same grammatical categories. The form *mnam* unanimously points to a v3-stem (a v2-stem would be **mnam/brnam*). Therefore also *drañ* has to be interpreted as a v3-stem.

¹³⁵ Also Dotson seems to have followed the same interpretation although not stating it explicitly. For instance, he read ‘led a military campaign’ for *drañs* in ITJ 750: 67–8 (Dotson 2009b: 91).

¹³⁶ Since the orthography of *drañste* is ambiguous and the word can be interpreted as either *drañ ste* or *drañs te*, I will likewise scrutinise the latter forms in contexts that leave no doubt concerning the argument structure and the identity of *drañ* and *drañs*.

I relate *ɣdrañs* not to the verb-family under consideration but to *rañ* ‘to rejoice’ and its cognates and consequently exclude from the following discussion; cf.:

[śa ba ɣam glañ / (254) / bu ɣam mjo čhig]_{ABS} [snor gyīs]_{ERG} ɣdrañs phayī ño // (PT 1047; apud OTDO)
a sign that a deer, a bullock, or a *mjo* are satisfied with a good meadow

DSM paraphrases *snor thog tu btañ ba* as ‘spañ thog tu btañ ba’ (429b). In addition, the dictionary glosses *snor ma* as ‘rcwa bzañ bayi spañ thog dañ rcwa bzañ po’ (ibid.)

Simon examined cognates of *rañ* (Simon 1969) but he was apparently not aware of the OLT form *ɣdrañs* which on the basis of the parallel phrases OLT *lto ɣdrañs* (PT 1052: r139; ITJ 740: 83; apud OTDO) ~ CT *lto ɣgrañs* (see BCRD & BDRC) can be identified as the original form of the CT *ɣgrañs*. *ɣdrañs* was derived from *rañ* by means of the prefix *ɣ*-; *-d-* being an excrescent consonant. This derivational process with the issuing addition of a dental stop has been labelled ‘Conrady’s law’ by Hill (Hill 2012b: 5). I assume that *ɣdrañs* was replaced by *ɣgrañs* after the merger of the reflexes of *ɣdr-* and *ɣgr-* had taken place in the spoken language. For a discussion of an analogous merger **sdr-* > *sgr-* see (Bialek 2018c). The proposed reconstruction is confirmed by dialectal data from WAT: Balti, Tshangra [drañs], KarMZ [dañs] ~ [drañs] ‘to be satisfied, to be satiated’ (CTD.V: 248). WAT dialects are the only ones that still attest to the original dental and so suggest that the change *ɣdr-* > *ɣgr-* most probably took place during MOT.

(3)

(56) *keñ śir drañ baḡī dmag dpon čhen phor // (57) źaň mčhims rgyal rgyal zīgs śu theñ daň // (58) blon stag sgra klu khoň gñīs / bkaḡ scald te / (59) keñ śir draň nas // (Žol S)*

Having appointed both *źaň* Mčhims-rgyal Rgyal-zigs Śu-theñ and councillor Stag-sgra Klu-khoň as great army commanders, who march to Keň-śi, [they] marched to Keň-śi.

In (3), both *draň* and *draňs* belong to the intransitive verb ‘to march (towards)’.

draňs

(4)

rgyaḡī srid gyī ñam (26) drod rtog čiň / khar can phyogs su (27) thog ma draňs paḡī / dmag dpon (28) du / bkaḡ scald gyis kyaň / (Žol S)

Since [the *bcan po*] ordered [Ñan-lam Stag-sgra Klu-khoň] as an army commander who led the head (lit. beginning¹³⁷) to Khar-can while examining initiatives of the Chinese realm [...].

(5)

(56) *keñ śir draň baḡī dmag dpon čhen phor // (57) źaň mčhims rgyal rgyal zīgs śu theñ daň // (58) blon stag sgra klu khoň gñīs / bkaḡ scald te / (59) keñ śir draň nas // (Žol S)*

Having appointed both *źaň* Mčhims-rgyal Rgyal-zigs Śu-theñ and councillor Stag-sgra Klu-khoň as great army commanders, who march to Keň-śi, [they] marched to Keň-śi.

(4) and (5) are very instructive because of the determinative phrases *draňs paḡī dmag dpon* and *draň baḡī dmag dpon*. In the first case, *draňs* receives an object – *thog ma*, whereas *draň* has no object. However *draňs* in (5) likewise lacks an object. This confirms the earlier observation that *draň* and *draňs* were forms of two verbs: a transitive and an intransitive one.

γdraň

(6)

blon stag sgra klu khoň gī myes po gsas slebs / (44) gyi bu cha rgyud peld las gaň rño thog paḡ / (45) [dmaňs]_{ABS} γdraň ba gčīg / sku sruňs γpan (46) yul paḡī stoň dpon g.yuň druň du scald (47) par gnaň ño // (Žol N)

[It] is granted that from the descendants of Gsas-slebs, the grandfather of councillor Stag-sgra-klu-khoň, the capable one who leads the community is given in perpetuity [the office of] the head of the thousand-district of the life guards who are inhabitants of the Xphan country.

(7)

gcīgs kyi mkhar bu γdī / nam źig (59) dbye dgos na yaň // sras dbon čhab sřid kyi mñay gaň mjad pas rñň lugs (60) thugs čhes pa [gcīgs bdag]_{ABS} γdraň ba gsum yan čad (61) bsko ste / (Žwa W)

Should it ever be necessary for this chest [containing] the edict to be opened, children and grandchildren, who execute whatever power over (lit. of) the realm, having appointed up to three trustworthy representatives who would lead the custodian of the edict [...].

¹³⁷ Cf. *sna draňs* abundantly attested in OT documents.

γdrañ in (6) and (7) can be classified as a transitive verb.

droñs

(8)

mtho la rkal (read: *rgal*) *gyañ myi phyugs / mñam / du / skyibs lu(128)g mar bas / droñs śig /*
(PT 1134; *apud* OTDO)

Crossing the heights, let the man together with cattle be led by the red sheep mount!

Apart from *droñs śig* we find also *droñ śig* in which the final -s has been elided before another sibilant (ś-) as a result of haplography. The clause structure leaves no doubt that *myi* is the theme argument. Parallel clauses are repeated in PT 1134: 129, 148, and 149. They all attest to ergative on *skyibs lug mar ba*.

γdren

Pairs such as

(9) <i>sna γdren</i> (PT 239: r15.4; <i>apud</i> OTDO)	<i>sna drañs</i> (passim)
<i>myig γdren</i> (PT 1283: 226; <i>apud</i> OTDO)	<i>myig drañ</i> (PT 1283: 219; <i>apud</i> OTDO)
<i>spyan γdren</i> (PT 1287: 182)	<i>spyan drañs</i> (PT 1042: 40; PT 1288: 11; ITJ 739: 2v3–4; <i>apud</i> OTDO)

suggest that at some point the form *γdren* was incorporated into the transitive conjugation. I agree with Bielmeier (Bielmeier 2004b: 405f.) that the CT conjugation of *γdren* (v1 *γdren*, v2 *drañs*, v3 *drañ*, v4 *droñs*) is suppletive. In OLT, *γdren* and *γdrañ* never occur in the same text; they have complementary distribution.¹³⁸ The phrases in (9) are all idiomatic, but if we look closer at other occurrences of *γdren*, we find out that the original meaning of the verb was much more concrete and presumed physical contact between the agent and the theme. In (Bialek In Preparation), I have proposed the meaning ‘to fetch’ for this sense. Primarily *γdren* might have had the concrete meaning of ‘to drag, to pull’. Its semantic proximity to the original ‘to draw, to lead’ of *γdrañ* enabled its incorporation and the inception of the suppletive conjugation.¹³⁹

Beside its use as a simple verb, *drañs* also occurs in the honorific form *spyan drañs* in the OTA-I:

(10)

{b}can mo mun čhañ koñ čo / mgar stoñ rcan yul zuñ gyīs spyan drañste bod yul (12) du gśegso / (PT 1288)

[b]can mo Mun-čhañ koñ čo, led by Mgar Stoñ-rcan Yul-zuñ, came to the Bod land.

In (Bialek 2018a: 1.556, fn. 1), I proposed relating *spyan* (orig. ‘an inspecting one’) to *dpyod* ‘to try, to examine’.¹⁴⁰ *myig γdrañ* (see ex. (9)) might have been a later formation coined by

¹³⁸ In PT 1283 we find *γdren* and *γdrañs*, but the latter, as established above, is a distinct verb.

¹³⁹ This is additionally supported by the phrase *spyan γdren no* (PT 1287: 182). Would have *γdren* be an assimilated form of **γdrañd*, one would expect *γdren to* instead.

¹⁴⁰ For the origin of the honorific *spyan* ‘eye’, see (Bialek 2023c).

analogy with *spyān ydrañ*. If we consider the historical context of (10), it becomes obvious that *spyān drañs* could not mean ‘to invite’ for it was not Mgar Stoñ-rcañ Yul-zuñ who invited Mun-čhañ koñ čö; he was only accompanying her from the Chinese court to the Tibetan border (Uray 1978: 561–3). The phrase could be reconstructed as *‘to draw [sb.’s] eyes’, meaning that the agent was leading the person who was looking after him; cf. Eng. *to follow with the eye*. Therefore, the phrase seems to have originally been a mere honorific equivalent of *drañs* ‘led’.

In conclusion, the above quotations provide a sound basis for the reconstruction of two verb conjugations:

TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} *ydrañ drañs drañ droñs*¹⁴¹
 INTR/C [AGT]_{ERG} *drañ drañs*

The homonymy of *drañ* and *drañs*, forms occurring in both conjugations, resulted from regular sound changes. To wit, *drañs* and *drañ* of the transitive conjugation are secondary; their underlying forms can be reconstructed as **b-drañs* and **b-drañ*, respectively (Bialek 2020a: 281).¹⁴²

drug (#553) ‘six’

gdan (#750) ‘bolster, mat’

In the OTA, *gdan* occurs only in the incorporate verb *gdan chom* ‘to celebrate’ (see s.v.) (Tournadre and Suzuki 2023: 255) proposed relating it to the verb *gday* ‘to sit’.

gdan chom (#592) INTR [AGT]_{ABS} ‘to celebrate’

(Dotson 2009b: 36, fn. 48) The phrase *gdan chom* may simply be an expression for an intimate meeting such as a summit, but it is also similar to a phrase used in matrimonial context: the ‘spreading of the carpet’ (*gdan btiñ*) is one of the phrases of a Tibetan marriage ceremony where a carpet is spread out for the bride.’; p. 259: ‘to arrange the carpet’.

The incorporation *gdan chom* (or sometimes *gdan ychoms*) is attested a few times in other OLT documents as well. Unfortunately, its occurrences are restricted to highly enigmatic divination

¹⁴¹ Later *droñs* has given rise to the separate verb *ydroñs*, orig. *‘to be drawn’.

¹⁴² As against the ubiquitous presence of the ergative marker on the agent argument we also find:

[*rgyaγī dmag dpon ybaγ cañ kun*]_{ABS} / [*kog yul gyi rgya{γ}ī* (5) *byim po*]_{ABS} *drañste* / *dbon γa za rje dañ blon mañ pho rje gñis gyis mkhar jid par la brgalde* / [*rgyaγī ram yday*]_{ABS} *jīd par du* / *phud* (6) *gon mkhar pho čer drañste* (read: *drañ ste*) / *rgya phal čer bkum* / (Or.8212/187)

The Chinese general *Ybaγ cañ kun* led Chinese military troops of the Kog land. Both *dbon*, the lord of the *Ya-za*, and councillor *Mañ-pho-rje* fought against the stronghold *Jid-par*; [they] drew support forces of the Chinese to *Jid-par*, to the fortress *Phud-gon*; [they] killed Chinese in great numbers.

Here, the first *drañs* has two arguments in absolutive, whereas the second one, only one, but likewise in absolutive. The text of the OTA-II attests to several serious orthographical and grammatical errors (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))). Moreover, the absolutive marking on the agent argument (in *rgyaγī dmag dpon ybaγ cañ kun*) is exceptional and not found elsewhere in OLT.

texts where the phrase occurs without any context that could facilitate its interpretation. As the only exception I can quote:

(1)

(11) *rgyal pho rgyal mo thugs dgyes śiñ gdan com baḡi / ño //* (PT 1047; *apud* OTDO)

The sign of the king [and] the queen, [who], being happy, celebrated.

The argument structure attested in ITJ 750 is confirmed in:

(2)

phywa dañ lī sa rya dañ rgyal pu wer mu sman gyi rgyal mo gdan chom baḡi źal / (PT 1047: 16; *apud* OTDO)

the effigy of a queen of the king Pu-wer who celebrated with *phywa* and *li sa rya*

As the only dictionary, Goldstein includes the phrase *gdan ḡjoms* explained as ‘v[erb] i[n]active] to meet, to gather’ (Gs: 557c). This would be synonymic with the simple CT verb *ḡjom(s)* ‘to come together, to meet’ (J: 467a). On the other hand, *gdan* forms a few idiomatic expressions: W[estern Tibet] [dan kyal če] (LT *gdan skyel byed* – JB) ‘to accompany’ (J: 265b); *gdan ḡdegs* ‘v[erb] a[ctive] to move/change residence to a different place’ (Gs: 557c); *gdan ḡdren* ‘to invite; to appoint, nominate’ (J: 265b); W[estern Tibet] [dan p̄eb pa] (LT *gdan p̄heb pa* – JB) ‘to arrive’ (J: 265b); *gdan źu byed* ‘to invite’ (Gs: 557c). The connotation of *gdan* with celebrations and banquets is confirmed in the OLT idiom *gdan la gśeḡs* ‘to go for a (ceremonial) repast’, for which see (Bialek In Preparation). It seems therefore plausible that *ḡchoms* and *chom* are cognates of *ḡjom(s)*.¹⁴³ The latter is unanimously glossed as a cA verb in modern dialects (cf. CDTD.V: 1065). The same argument structure is attested for *gdan ḡjom* in:

(3)

bcan poḡi spyān śnar bande čhen po dpal gyi yon tan dañ / bande čhen po tiñ ñe ḡjin la sogs pa yañ ḡchogs te / rje blon gdan ḡjom pa la źus nas (*Sgra sbyor*, trslr. *apud* (Ishikawa 1990: 2))

Great *bande* Dpal-gyi-yon-tan and great *bande* Tiñ-ñe-ḡjin, among others, having gathered in front of the *bcan po*, spoke to the assembled lords and councillors.

In the Tabo version of the *Sgra sbyor*, the phrase *rje blon gdan ḡjom* is rendered as *rje blon mol ba* (ka r1, cf. (Panglung 1994: 162)) ‘lords and councillors, who were conferring’. The equivalence of *gdan ḡjom* and *mol ba* indicates the highly lexicalised character of the former.

I assume that OLT *gdan chom* was an incorporation going back to the verbal phrase *‘for bolsters to meet’ formed with an intransitive verb that has not been attested independently thus far. From general observations on verb incorporation in OLT follows that, since the phrase *gdan chom* is intransitive, the original verb *chom* must have also been intransitive (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))). Apparently, *gdan* was used metonymically to denote people who were to sit on the seats during the celebration. As its subject (*gdan*) was incorporated, the argument structure of the complex verb changed so that it could take another argument (beside *gdan*) and thus in absolutive.

¹⁴³ CT *chom pa/po* ‘bundle, bunch’ (J: 453b) and possibly also *choms* ‘court-yard’ (J: 453b; < *‘assembly-place’) can be deemed further cognates.

The complex verb might have denoted a situation of assembling and bringing together bolsters for a greater festivity organised on the occasion of a formal meeting – in all above quotations members of the ruling class are involved: *bcan po*, the lord of the *ᠬᠠ-ᠵᠠ*, a king, a queen. Ex. (1), in which *gdan com* follows *dgyes* ‘to rejoice’ suggests indeed that the phrase was already lexicalised. I propose the following semantic development of **gdan ychoms*: **‘for bolsters to meet’ > ‘to celebrate’*.

bden (#761) ‘truth’

mdad (#611) ‘funeral ceremony’

DTH: 30, fn. 2: tombeau; (Hoffmann 1950a: 5) Totenfeier (although he read *mdaṅ* – JB); (Tucci 1950: 76, fn. 23) = *Idem*: tumulus, mound; (Haarh 1969: 361) derives from *γday*, to die or to be dead, based on the idea of transition, *γdas*; *mdad btaṅ* [...] means in its narrowest sense the presentation of the funeral-meal, the final act of the burial, while *mdad-btaṅ* or simply *mdad*, signifies in a wider and generalized sense the funeral itself and the funeral feast in all its various aspects; (Eimer 1979: 1.108) Die Vermutung liegt nahe, daß *γdad* eine graphische Abbeviatur von *γdas mčhod* (Fn. 4: In der Form *γda(s mčho)d*) ist, die dann als eigenes Wort in die Sprache aufgenommen wurde; (Chu 1991: 119-20, fn. 37) *mdad* refers to bury; etymological, *mdad* is related to *γdas*; (Dotson 2009b: 83) funeral; (Zeisler 2011a: 108) funeral repast.

According to the OTA, a *mdad* was prepared mainly in the winter. The document records *mdads* for: *bcan pos*, *bcan mo* *Mun-čaṅ koṅ čo*, *bcan po*’s mother *Maṅ-paṅs*, *bcan mo ga tun*, *bcan po*’s grandmother *Khri-ma-lod*, *bcan po*’s mother *Bcan-ma-thog*, *bcan po*’s sister *Lha-spaṅs*, *bcan po*’s son *Lhas-bon*, *bcan mo khoṅ čo*, and queen (*jo mo*) *Khri-bcun*.¹⁴⁴

As argued by (Hoffmann 1950a: 5), *mdad* was derived from the verb *√da* (v1 *γday*, v2 *γdas*) ‘to pass (away)’ by means of the deverbal suffix *-d* (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))) and the prefix *m-*. Its derivational character is still clear in the orthography of its first attestation in the OTA: *mdayd*. In the OTA, *mdad* occurs only in the VP *mdad btaṅ* that is used to signal a ‘closing event of long-lasting (1 to 3 years) funeral ceremonies’ (Bialek 2018a: 2.194). The use of this particular verb might suggest that the original meaning of *mdayd* was ‘funeral repast’, i.e. something that could be offered (*btaṅ*) to the deceased. The etymological meaning of *mdayd* could therefore have been **‘repast for the deceased (γday)’*.

ydun ma (#450) ‘council’

[C] *γdus*, *bsdus*

The OTA-I mention a few kinds of council:

γdun ma ‘council’

dgun γdun ‘winter council’

dbyar γdun ‘summer council’

mdo smad gyi γdun ma ‘council of Mdo-smad’

mdo smad gyi dgun γdun ‘winter council of Mdo-smad’

bod yul gyi dgun γdun ‘winter council of the Bod land’

¹⁴⁴ A detailed analysis of *mdad* in OT sources is provided in (Bialek 2018a: 2.191ff.)

In addition, the OTA-II reports

mdo smad gyi dbyar ydun 'summer council of Mdo-smad'

Jurisdiction of the Central Tibetan councils can be inferred from those clauses, in which council is the subject of the verb *ydus*. It can be that in clauses with the verb *bsdus* some of the described activities were the duties of those who convened such a council and did not fall directly in the jurisdiction of the council. The following juxtaposition summarises the duties that are reported in connection with a council:

		<i>ydun ma ydus</i>	<i>ydun ma bsdus</i>
1. <i>brcis</i>	<i>žugs loñ dmar pho</i>	W 674/5; W 709/10	
	<i>čad ka</i>	W 738/9	
	<i>khram dmar pho</i>		S 708/9, W 712/3
	<i>lhag čad brcis</i>		W 722/3
<i>rcis bgyis</i>	<i>phyiñ rild dañ rabs čad</i>	S 691/2	S 720/1
	<i>blon [...] phyuñ ste [...]</i>	W 730/1	
	<i>bčug pa</i>		
	<i>bruñ pa [...] phyuñ ste</i>	W 745/6	W 731/2
	<i>[...] bčug pa</i>		
	<i>khud pa phul ba</i>		W 723/4
<i>phyuñ [...] bčhug</i>	<i>mñan</i>		S 723/4
	<i>bruñ pa</i>		S 714/5
	<i>čhibs pon</i>		W 717/8
<i>bčug</i>	<i>bruñ pa</i>		S 715/6
<i>bgyis</i>	<i>rkañ ton</i>	W 691/2	W 673/4
	<i>pha los</i>		W 734/5
	<i>ybrog mkhos</i>		S 673/4
	<i>dmag myi</i>		W 744/5
<i>phab</i>	<i>bkyon</i>		S 706/7
	<i>čas</i>		W 720/1
<i>btab</i>	<i>phyiñ rild</i>	W 686/7	
	<i>khram dmar po</i>	[W 692/3]	W 690/1, S 718/9
	<i>thañ khram</i>		W 721/2, W 728/9
<i>bčos</i>	<i>mñan</i>	W 684/5	
	<i>lña brgya</i>		W 707/8
<i>bskos</i>	<i>mñan</i>	S 692/3	
	<i>ybrog</i>	W 693/4	
<i>bkug</i>	<i>pha los</i>		W 673/4, [W 711/2], W 719/20
	<i>myi</i>		W 696/7
<i>spos</i>	<i>khram</i>		S 707/8
	<i>khram dmar po</i>		W 744/5
<i>bkral</i>	<i>yo byad</i>	S 710/11	
<i>btañ</i>	<i>mdad</i>	W 745/6	W 732/3
<i>bor</i>	<i>bkay tañ</i>		W 702/3
<i>phul</i>	<i>ybañs</i>		W 713/4
2. <i>bskos</i>	<i>lña brgya</i>	S 693/4	S 713/4
3. <i>bgyis</i>	<i>rgod g.yuñ [...]</i>	<i>mkho</i>	[S 654/5]
	<i>šam [...]</i>	<i>rcis mgo</i>	

	<i>žaṅ zuṅ gyi mkos</i>	[S 724/5]
<i>brcis</i>	<i>nor</i>	[S 680/1]
<i>bcud</i>	<i>log pho daṅ pho</i>	[W 687/8]
<i>sbyard</i>	<i>mṅan gyi thaṅ</i>	[Sp 726/7]
<i>bskos</i>	<i>khrald pa</i>	[Sp 726/7]
4. <i>gsold</i>	<i>mchan</i>	W 685/6
<i>kha bstand</i>	<i>śho sa skya sa</i>	S 713/4
<i>bgyis</i>	<i>γbrog sog gī mkos</i>	W 746/7
<i>brcis</i>	<i>snon god</i>	W 729/30
<i>bor</i>	<i>byaṅ bu</i>	S 743/4
<i>spags</i>	<i>khral pa</i>	W 746/7
<i>brcis</i>	<i>rabs čhad</i>	W 733/4

A council had jurisdiction over the administration of the Empire, including Central Tibet and the conquered territories of the *Žaṅ-zuṅ*, *Sum-pa*, and *Ya-ža*. Duties that occur either only with the verb *γdus* or with both verbs *γdus* and *bsdus* were certainly under the jurisdiction of a council. With regard to the remaining activities listed for the verb *bsdus*, the syntax of the respective clause is decisive. In group 1. of the table, the council was responsible for carrying out the respective activity. For activities of group 4. human individuals were responsible. Clause structures of group 3. had to be reconstructed (therefore the entries are bracketed) and so the activities have to be left out from the discussion. Duties of group 2. are ambivalent for they are once ascribed to a council (< + > sign), once to individual persons (< - > sign). The discrepancy seen with respect to *mkos bgyis* is superficial. This activity is ascribed to the council in W 744/5 but to individuals in W 746/7. The first case concerns the administration of soldiers (*dmag myī mkhos čhen po*), whereas the second one the administration of summer pastures and straw-lands of the Four Horns (*ru bžiγi γbrog sog gi mkhos*). In fact, these are two distinct activities.

Although the complete phrase *γdun ma bsdus* is mentioned for the first time in S 673/4, there is a good reason to assume that the institution existed already earlier. To wit, in 654/5 one reads:

(1)

blon čhe stoṅ rcan gyis / [γdun ma] moṅ pu sral γjoṅ duy bsduste / (PT 1288: 27–8)

Grand councillor [Mgar] Stoṅ-rcaṅ [Yul-zuṅ] convened [the council] at Moṅ-pu-sral-γjoṅ.

This is a typical clause introducing a council even though the word for council is missing from the text and has to be reconstructed. Also in later entries the word for council is sometimes omitted. We can assume that the institution of council existed from the very beginning of the Empire, but had at first less political significance because the major decisions were made by families, first of all the powerful Mgar family. I count the entry for 654/5 as the first official mention of a council.¹⁴⁵

¹⁴⁵ As against, for instance Uebach, who states that councils start to be mentioned in the OTA beginning with year 673/4 (Uebach 1988: 503).

Regarding the morphology of *γdun ma*, the first syllable of the lexeme is a deverbal derivative from INTR *γdu* ‘to gather, convene’ (see s.v. *γdus*) by means of the nominal suffix *-n*. The exact function of the particle *-ma* has yet to be determined.

γdus (#681) INTR/C [AGT]_{ABS} ‘*to come together; ¹to convene (at [LOC]_{TERM})’

[C] *γdun ma, bsdus*

γdus is the only form of the verb attested in the OTA. The verb is used with the same subject (*γdun ma, dgun γdun, dbyar γdun*) throughout the text. The verb always acquires a locative adjunct in terminative that specifies the place of the event. The terminative case clarifies that the action denoted by the verb was conceived of as dynamic.

γdus is cognate with *sdud*, attested in the OTA only in the form *bsdus*. Their etymon has been reconstructed as \sqrt{du} (Bialek 2020a: 282).

rdugs (#684) INTR/NC [PAT]_{ABS} [RES]_{ALL} ‘to be reduced to’

(Chang 1959: 135) to be killed or massacred; (Hill 2011b: 14) to reduce.

In OLT *rdugs* seems to be a *dis legomenon*:

(1)

da rgyal mañ po rjes / mcho nag stoñ rur / rgya seyu den pañ dañ / nol thabs bgyište / da rgyal gyañ gum žiñ (38) *brgyad khri stoñ la rdugs phar lo gčig* / (PT 1288)

Mañ-po-rje, the king of the Dags-po, fought against the Chinese [general] Seyu Den-pañ at Mcho-nag-stoñ-ru. While the king of the Dags-po [himself] died, eighty thousand were reduced to [one] thousand.

Previous translations rendered *rdugs* in (1) once as an active, once as a passive verb:

“ils furent réduits”	(DTH: 32)
“to be killed or massacred”	(Chang 1959: 135)
“were defeated (and reduced)”	(Uray 1972b: 30)
“he reduced”	(Hill 2008: 74)
“he reduced”	(Dotson 2009b: 86)
“he reduced”	(Hill 2011b: 14)

Although it is hardly possible that one person, the king of the Dags-po, could have killed 79,000 people, one could argue that the expression is to be read figuratively and the king of the Dags-po is a metonymy for the Tibetan army. However, it is conspicuous that the form *rdugs*, and not for instance *!brdugs*, is used here as well as in the second occurrence of the verb in OLT:

(2)

ra sa ni mo la (v9) *rdugs ni g.yu ru γphrul* / (PT 1052)

Ra-sa is reduced to a lot. [...] is transformed into a turquoise.¹⁴⁶

In (2) the argument structure of *rdugs* is the same as in the OTA: ‘S_{ABS} Q_{ALL} *rdugs*’, lit. ‘S *rdugs* on Q’. Lexicographical sources provide the following meanings for *rdugs*: ‘¹vi. to be worn out; ²vi. to be boring; ³immoral, unethical’ (G: 585b), ‘(tha mi dad pa) ¹zad pa dañ. thug payam thogs pa; ²mcher ba. yjigs pa. sun pa; ¹ma rabs’ (BTC: 1432a–b), ‘reduziert werden, eingeschränkt sein, versagen’ (WtS.38: 476b), Kyirong [tʰ:] ncAD ‘to strike against sth., to collide with so.’ (CDTD.V: 668). Yet another sense can be detected in the following verse from Sa-skya Paṇḍita:

(3)
*mkhas pa ji ltar thabs rdugs*¹⁴⁷ *kyañ//*
blun po yjug payi lam mi ygro//
 Even if any means are dispelled from a wise man,
 [he] will not go the way that fools enter.¹⁴⁸

I understand the first verse as **mkhas pa ni ji ltar thabs rdugs kyañ*, lit. ‘As for a wise man, in whatever manner [his] means might be dispelled [...]’.

Beside *rdugs*, some dictionaries also cite the verb *rdug/brdugs/brdug/rdugs*:¹⁴⁹ ‘¹to conquer, to vanquish (?); hence prob[ably] to annihilate, destroy, undo; ²to strike against, to stumble at’ (J: 285b), ‘¹to conquer, to worst; ²to devastate, wreck, undo’ (D: 700a), ‘to conquer, to defeat’ (Kharto: 136–7). WtS provides two entries for *brdugs*: ‘^{1.1}reduziert werden, eng sein; ²besiegen’ and ‘¹aufsteigen’ (39: 564a). The example quoted for the latter meaning is doubtful and *brdugs* could possibly be an error for *rdugs*. Presuming that there were indeed two verbs 1. **rdug/rdugs* and 2. *rdug/brdugs/brdug/rdugs*, the latter involving a subject in ergative, it seems that *brdugs* was sometimes falsely written instead of *rdugs*.

Already Jäschke suggested that *rdug* might be related to *thug* (J: 285b, s.v. *rdug*²): ‘^{1.1}to reach, arrive at, come to; ²to meet, to light upon; ³to touch, to hit or strike against’ (J: 232b). In (Bialek 2018a: 2.604) I proposed including in one word-family the following lexemes:

gtug ‘¹to reach, to touch; to overtake, to reach; to meet with, to join; ²to bring an action against a person, to sue’ (J: 207b)

¹⁴⁶ The second part of the clause is distorted; each verse is expected to have the structure ‘σ σ ni σ σ σ’. This structure is kept in *ra sa ni mo la rdugs* but not in *ni g.yu ru yphrul*. The latter verse lacks the first two syllables that should precede *ni*. Unfortunately due to the paper damage, the context of this passage remains unclear.

¹⁴⁷ (Hahn 1996: 236) and (Kun-dgay-rgyal-mchan 2014: 80) decided for the form *brdugs* even though *rdugs* is attested in the *Sde dge* and *Mañ yul guñ thañ* editions (cf. (Kun-dgay-rgyal-mchan 2014)). I assume that the reading *rdugs* is the correct one; *thabs*, the subject of the clause, stands in absolutive, and with *brdugs* one would expect *mkhas pa* in ERG instead.

¹⁴⁸ Hahn’s translation: “Wie sehr der Kluge auch aller Mittel ermangeln mag – nie wird es den Weg betreten, auf dem Toren wandeln” (Hahn 2003e: 36).

¹⁴⁹ The last form is quoted only in (Kharto: 136).

thug ¹to reach, arrive at, come to; ²to meet, to light upon; ³to touch, to hit or strike against' (J: 232b)¹⁵⁰
rdug ²to strike against, to stumble at' (J: 285b)

To these I shall also add CT:

thug 'until, to' (J: 232a)
thug pa 'soup, broth' (J: 232b)
mthug/γthug 'thick; dense' (J: 244b)
stug po 'dicht, massiv' (WtS.27: 143a)
stug(s) pa 'thickness, density, thick; sound, heavy' (J: 221a)

Their common semantic denominator could be the concept of reaching, coming closer (i.e. becoming condensed), also running into sth. The original verb roots can be reconstructed as TR √*tug* and INTR √*dug*. The morphology of *rdugs* can be explained as:

r- = directional/applicative 'onto'
 √*dug* = 'to reach, to come closer'
-s = resultative

I tentatively interpret **rdug/rdugs* as an intransitive verb with the original meaning **to run onto (from above)* that evolved along the lines: 'to run down' > 'to become reduced; to become dispelled'. It seems that the CT verb *rdug/brdugs/brdug/rdugs* was an innovation based on *rdugs* and elaborated by analogy with the well-known paradigms of transitive verbs.

ldeg ren pa (#453) 'instigator'

bsdus (#683) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} **to bring together; ¹to gather (humans); ²to collect (taxes); ³to convene (a group of humans; γdun ma 'council') (at [LOC]_{TERM})'*

[C] *γdun ma, γdus*

In the OTA-I, *bsdus* is used most frequently in the collocation *γdun ma bsdus* 'to convene a council'¹⁵¹ but the sentence structure may vary, mainly due to the distorted discourse (see (Bialek 2023b)):

1.	HUMAN _{ERG}	PLACE _{TERM}	<i>bsdus</i>	PT 1288: 27-8, ITJ 750: 75, 76, 84-5, 98-9, 105-6, 184-5, 236, 239, 266-7
2.	HUMAN _{ERG} γdun ma _{ABS}	PLACE _{TERM}	<i>bsdus</i>	ITJ 750: 81-2, 86-7, 116-7, 188-9, 200-1, 205-6, 234-5, 235, 254, 293-4, 303-4
3.	HUMAN _{ERG} TIME _{ABS}	PLACE _{TERM}	<i>bsdus</i>	ITJ 750: 92
4.	γdun ma _{ABS}	PLACE _{TERM}	<i>bsdus</i>	ITJ 750: 58-9, 79-80, 142, 144, 218, 251
5.	γdun ma _{ABS} PLACE _{TERM} HUMAN _{ERG}		<i>bsdus</i>	ITJ 750: 57, 76-7, 118, 137-8, 140-1, 149, 157, 158, 160-1, 163-4, 166-7, 168-9, 178,

¹⁵⁰ For this verb, see also *thugs ñen*.

¹⁵¹ S.v. *γdun ma* I have listed all administrative means that underlaid the Central Tibetan council according to the OTA-I. In the following analysis, I take *γdun ma* as representing all terms that could refer to a council, including councils of Mdo-smad. For their list, see s.v. *γdun ma*.

					179-80, 182-3, 186-7, 191, 193-4, 196, 198-9, 200, 204-5, 207-8, 212-3, 215-6, 217, 221, 222-3, 224, 225, 226, 227, 229-30, 231, 233, 246, 247, 250, 260, 263-4, 298
6.	γ dun ma _{ABS}	HUMAN _{ERG}		PLACE _{TERM}	<i>bsdus</i> ITJ 750: 203-4, 209, 214, 241-2
7.	PLACE _{TERM}	HUMAN _{ERG}			<i>bsdus</i> ITJ 750: 181-2, 233-4
8.	TIME _{ABS}	HUMAN _{ERG}	γ dun ma _{ABS}	PLACE _{TERM}	<i>bsdus</i> ITJ 750: 78-9, 82
9.	TIME _{ABS}	HUMAN _{ERG}		PLACE _{TERM}	<i>bsdus</i> ITJ 750: 100-1, 241
10.	TIME _{ABS}	PLACE _{TERM}	HUMAN _{ERG}		<i>bsdus</i> ITJ 750: 124

Table 1. Sentence structure of *bsdus* in the OTA.

Some of the sentence structures are considered distorted, e.g., 3, 7 9, 10.

I assume that in all the attested cases the underlying form of the verb is *bsdus*. Theoretically *bsduste* could also be read as **bsduste*, but three arguments speak against such an interpretation: 1. *bsdus* is not attested independently in the OTA-I; 2. v3-stems are only scarcely used in the OTA-I; and 3. every sentence structure that is attested with *bsduste* is independently attested with *bsdus*, e.g., 'SO *bsduste* > OV' has its equivalent in 'SO *bsdus nas* > OV'.

It is apparent that transitive *bsdus* is a cognate of intransitive γ dus. The verbs are derived from the root $\sqrt{\text{du}}$ by means of the causative prefix *s-* and autocausative prefix γ - respectively. *bsdus* is a v2-stem of the conjugation *sdud/bsdus/bsdus/sdus* with all inflected forms attested in OLT (see OTDO). The root $\sqrt{\text{du}}$ was originally the voiced and so intransitive counterpart of the voiceless and transitive $\sqrt{\text{tu}}$ (Bialek 2020a: 282).

n

nag po (#554) ‘¹black; ²met. black’

In two NPs the attribute *nag po* is used not to describe the colour, but to categorise a group of people: *mywa nag po* ‘Black Mywa’ and *ban yġag nag po* ‘Black Ban-yġag’ (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))). In the former case, the attribute *nag po* serves to disambiguate two groups of the Xjañ people: *mywa dkar po* ‘White Mywa’ (PT 1287: 335, 343, 393) and *mywa nag po* ‘Black Mywa’. No information on **ban yġag dkar po* has been preserved in the sources. The use of the adjective in the exocentric NP *mgo nag po* ‘black-headed’ (ITJ 750: 306) can be considered a borderline case; it refers to the colour of the hair as black but at the same time categorises a group of people as of lower social status; members of higher social strata were entitled to wear various head coverings, by which they distinguished themselves from those without head coverings, i.e. ‘black-headed’.

nañ (#685) ‘the inside’

nad (#555) ‘illness’

nan thur (#787) ‘punishment’

DSM: 395b: ¹khirms kyi čhad pa gčod paŷi don la yġug ste. ²sdigs chig gi miñ ste (s.v. *nan tur*); p. 396a: čhad las kyi miñ ste (s.v. *nan stur*); nan tan gyi miñ ste (s.v. *nan thur*); WtS.41: 66b: ¹ernsthaft, betont; ²auch ~ *du bya ba* eine Strafe im Vinaya, eine Zurechtweisung durch den Saṃgha, die Bestrafung erfolgt je nach Schwere des Vergehens; CM: 220a: ¹khirms lugs sam drag poŷi thabs kyis ma rabs kyi las byed paŷi bya spyod yġog pa; ²nan mo. bzlog med.

Two OLT passages clarify the meaning of *nan thur*:

(1)

yoñ ni// ya rabs ni/ drin gyis bkold/ ma rabs ni// (217) *nan thur gyis bkol žes bya mod gyi// yġeñs ñan kun la yañ/ drin dañ nan thur myed du* (218) *myi ruño//* (PT 1283; *apud* OTDO)

Even though it is indeed said concerning all [the people]: “Upper classes are subjected with favours, lower classes are subjected with *nan thur*,” it is not correct not to have favours and *nan thur* for all the prominent (?)¹⁵² and bad ones.

(2)

ñes byed na// nan thur skyed čhig// (PT 1283: 222; *apud* OTDO)

If [they] commit an offence, increase the ***nan thur!***

These confirm the meaning ‘punishment’ provided by lexicographical sources. The morphology of the compound is not transparent anymore (although *nan* is certainly to be related to *non* ‘to press’).

¹⁵² I tentatively read *yġeñs* but its meaning is also uncertain.

noñs (#686) **INTR/NC [PAT]_{ABS}** 'to pass away'

nor (#627) 'wealth'

(Thargyal 2007: 75) animal wealth, wealth on animals; referred exclusively to the pastoralists' yak and *ybri*.

In OLT, *nor* seems to have already possessed an abstract meaning denoting either wealth or valuables in their collectivity. However, the lexeme might originally have had a rather concrete meaning; WtS glosses *nor* as 'Tier, Vieh, Kuh, Yak' (41: 126b), quoting numerous passages from CT, and these meanings are confirmed in modern dialects (cf. CDTD: 4600).¹⁵³

nol thabs (#549) 'battle'

nold (#556) **INTR/C [AGT]_{ABS}** 'to fight'

[C] *snol*

(Richardson 1998a [1965]: 11) to be in contention; (Dotson 2009b: 81) to fight.

The verb *nol* is a *dis legomenon* in OLT. Apart from its occurrence in the *Preamble* of the OTA-I, we also find it in a divinatory text:

(1)

čhuñ mas phyi phyin te lha kun phañ/ nolte mo ñan to// (PT 1046B: 20; *apud* OTDO)

The wife came late; all *phañ* deities fought; the lot is bad.

The verb is not attested in later lexicographical sources of LT. Instead, we find *snol* 'to wrestle, scuffle, fight; to contend with, fight against, subdue' (J: 320b). For modern dialects the verb is sometimes glossed as an intransitive, sometimes as a transitive verb, but it is always controllable (cf. CDTD.V: 754). There can be no doubt that *snol* was derived from *nol* by means of the causative prefix *s-*. Since in the clause from the OTA-I the *bcan po* and his brother are the subject of the verb, I consider the verb to have been intransitive with one agent argument. The form *nold* is apparently a *v2*-stem.

gnag nad (#454) 'cattle disease'

gnag liñs (#455) 'yak hunt'

snon god (#456) 'balance (econ.)'

snom bu pa (#457) 'investigator'

DSM: 429b: *gsañ myul paçam rtog žib paçi miñ ste*.

DTH: 36, fn. 6: le drapier; (Hill 2008: 76) warden; (Dotson 2009b: 59) investigator; p. 95. 'sniffer'; p. 259: royal taster who checks for poison, investigator.

¹⁵³ Cf. Kurtöp *nor* 'cow' (Hyslop 2017: 142).

The word-formation of *snom bu pa* suggests that it denoted humans (-*pa*) affiliated to *snom bu*. DSM glosses the lexeme as ‘gsaṅ myul paṅam rtog źib paṅi miṅ ste’ (p. 429b) although it is clearly a contextual definition. In the present work, *snom bu* is assumed to have been derived from the verbal stem *snom* by means of the DIM -*bu* (not a frequent word-formation) that expresses decreased (iterative) agency (see (Bialek 2021f: 260, 274)). Semantically we can juxtapose **snom bu* with Ger. *Riecher* ‘¹Nase; ²Ahnung, Spürsinn’ (DWDS). Thus, I subscribe to Dotson’s rendering ‘investigator’ for *snom bu pa*, lit. ‘sb. having a (good) smell’ (cf. Ger. *einen guten Riecher für etw. haben*), with the reservation that the term does not seem to have denoted a ‘taster’ but a person investigating furtively in an attempt to find out something, especially information held secret.

p

pyir (#748) ‘again’

dpur (#566) ‘**HON** dead body’

In the OTA *dpur/spur* is reserved for the corpse of a *bcan po* and therefore must have belonged to the honorific register. The lexeme could be related to CT *γphur* ²‘to wrap up, envelop, muffle up; ³= *mñed pa* to rub with the hand’ (J: 356b). *dpur* might have been the original form derived from the verb root $\sqrt{\text{pur}}$ by means of the nominalising prefix *g-* (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))).¹⁵⁴ The custom of shrouding the body of the deceased is alluded to in the verb *mkhyud/mkhyid* (see s.v.), as well as in the funeral descriptions of PT 1042 (cf. (Bialek 2021e) and (Bialek In Preparation)). The honorific register resulted from the metaphorical use of the term in connection with royal corpses: *‘shrouded one’ > ‘dead body’.¹⁵⁵

dpya dar (#458) ‘silk tribute’

dpyaṅ (#689) ‘tribute’

[C] *phya*

The passage from PT 1288: 7 can be juxtaposed with the following one:

(1)

rḡya dan ḡa žas dpyaṅ gčal lo // (PT 1287: 306)

The Chinese and ḡa-ža paid tribute.

The passages concern the same events: the conquest of the ḡa-ža and Chinese in the 630s (see also s.v. *gčal*). The events preceded the ultimate subjugation of the ḡa-ža thirty years later. Thus, we can translate *dpyaṅ* as ‘tribute’, i.e. a compulsory payment made by one state to another one.

I consider *dpyaṅ* a derivative of *phya* ‘share’.

¹⁵⁴ Whether CT *sbur ma/sbun pa* ‘chaff, husks’ (J: 404b) should be included in the same word-family remains to be clarified.

¹⁵⁵ The variant *spur* might have been an early folk etymology influenced by the verb *spur* ‘to scare up’ (J: 331a). Or, alternatively, *dpur* and *spur* were independent derivations *‘shrouded one’ and *‘a shroud’ (lit. ‘a shrouder’), respectively, that came to be confused with the sound change of the pre-consonantal *d-* to *s-*. The latter change is still attested in the WAT (see CDTD). The original *dpur* of the text was replaced by *spur* in the course of later redaction.

Bunan has the verb *pur* ‘to kill’ (Widmer 2017: 624). It does not seem to be related to the Tibetan lexemes, but a dedicated study would be necessary to clarify the issue.

dpyid (#563) ‘spring’

spags (#567) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to move, to relocate’

I identify *spags* with CT *spog/spags/spag/spogs*: ‘to carry, bring forward by turns’ (Cs: 336a), ‘to remove and to bring near by turns’ (J: 331b).¹⁵⁶ Dialectally it is attested as a cEA verb with the meanings ‘to change, to shift sth. (in several turns, with stops in between), to move’ (CDTD.V: 769).¹⁵⁷ On these grounds, I interpret *spags* in the OTA as denoting the action of relocating tax collectors to other places of the Empire in order for them to continue their work.

spo bleg (#459) ‘promotion-slate’

& spos (#690) TR [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘¹to change; ²to move to ([DIR]_{TERM}); ³to transfer to ([GO]_{ALL})’

[C] *γphos*

In ITJ 750: 161 and 299 *spos* is undoubtedly a TR verb with the direct object in ABS. Problematic is the following occurrence of *spos* in the OTA-I:

(1)

(56) *bya gagī lo lay bcan po dbyar stod pho dam mdo na bźugs śīñ / dbyar smad [pho brañ] sum čhu bor sposte / (ITJ 750)*

In the hen year, while in the onset of summer the *bcan po* was abiding in Pho-dam-mdo, [he] moved [the court] to Sum-ču-bo at the end of summer.

Sum-ču-bo was also the summer residence of the *bcan po* one year earlier, in 672/3 (l.54). It seems therefore that the clause is formed correctly, even though it apparently lacks a direct object. I juxtapose the above clause with:

(2)

(219) § / *bya gagī lo la / bcan po dbyard duñs gyī stag cal na bźugs pa las / rnañ po dur myīg du γphos śīñ / (ITJ 750)*

In the hen year, in the summer, while the *bcan po*, upon abiding in Stag-cal of Duñs, moved to Rnañ-po-ñur-myig, [...].

In terms of the argument structure, the two clauses are identical. If we dismiss the possibility that *sposte* in l. 56 is an error for **γphoste*, we are in need for another plausible explanation. Bielmeier put forward the hypothesis that the prefix *s-* was originally a directive marker, introducing movement (Bielmeier 1988b: 18–9, 25–6). He also used this hypothesis to explain the existence of the *s-* prefix in INTR verbs (ibid., p. 24, fn. 14). However, the counterpart of *spos*, *γphos*, has been shown to be likewise a verb of motion (see s.v.) and so no true difference can be established in this regard between the verbs. In modern dialects *spo* is

¹⁵⁶ The noun *spogs* ‘gain, profit’ was derived by conversion from v4 *spogs*. For its meaning, compare Ger. *das Ankommen*.

¹⁵⁷ *spags* occurs several times in OLT records but its complete argument structure is not documented; the agent argument is missing in all cases.

preponderantly a cEA verb ‘to move, to change, to replace’, but a few exceptions are recorded:¹⁵⁸

Western Drokpas	cA	‘usu[ally] with <i>kompā</i> to step’
Dingri	cA	‘with <i>kānpā</i> to step on’
Nangchen	cA	‘with <i>kō^hmpa</i> to step’
Themchen	cAD	‘to step on’ ¹⁵⁹

These data demonstrate that *spos* can be used as an intransitive verb only in complex phrases in which another word (WT *gom pa* or *rkañ pa*) is incorporated into its argument structure. Since in all the other OLT occurrences *spos* is unanimously a transitive verb, I deem the passage in ITJ 750: 56 as distorted and suggest reconstructing its direct object as *pho brañ* ‘court’.

spyan (#610) ‘HON eye’

There can be no doubt that *spyan* is an honorific in the OTA; it is used in connection with a *bcan po* (ITJ 750: 272 & 286) and a Chinese princess (PT1288: 11). It occurs only in phrases:

- PP *spyan śna* ‘in front of’, lit. ‘in front of the eyes of’¹⁶⁰
- VP *spyan drañs* ‘HON to lead’ (see s.v. *drañs*)

In (Bialek 2018a: 1.555, fn. 1), I suggested relating *spyan* (< *s+√dpⁱad+n) to the verb √dpⁱad (v1 *dpyod*, v2 *dpyad*) ‘to examine’ with the etymological meaning ‘an inspecting/examining one’.¹⁶¹ The reconstructed prefix *s-* is assumed to be identical with the causative *s-*, also encountered in other terms for body parts: *sna* ‘nose’, *sñan* ‘ear’. Suffix *-n* derives adjectives from verbs (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))).

spyan śna (#789) ‘HON presence (?)’; in POSTP GEN+*spyan śna*+TERM ‘in front of’

spyan drañs (#790) TR [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘HON to lead’

spyugs (#691) TR [AGT]_{ERG} (?) [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to banish (to [DIR]_{TERM})’

The complete argument structure is not attested in OLT.

¹⁵⁸ Data after CDTD.V: 768.

¹⁵⁹ The same argument structure can be presumed for Bayan where the verb is glossed as ‘to step on, to tread, to trample’.

¹⁶⁰ See (Bialek 2018b: 396f.) for other analogously formed PPs.

¹⁶¹ Compare hereto OLT *spyan* ‘inspector’ (Or.15000/497: v4, PT 1067: 13, Or.15000/265: v7); *spyan čhen po* ‘great inspector’ (PT 1287: 394–5); *gscañ spyan* ‘grain inspector’ (PT 2204c: 2). For the translation ‘inspector’, see (Uray 1975: 160) and (Richardson 1992: 106, fn. 9); *spyan pa pa* is explained as *bya ra ba* in BDSN (*apud* (Mimaki 1992a: 486)).

sprod (#642) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ¹to let meet; ²to deliver; *g.yul* to fight, to commit (a battle)

In OLT, the verb occurs with three different argument structures:

1. X_{ERG} Y_{COM} *g.yul*_{ABS} *sprod* 'X let the army meet with Y' (ITJ 750: 122)
2. X_{ERG} Y_{TERM} *g.yul* *sprod* 'X commits a battle at Y' (ITJ 750: 253)
3. X_{ERG} Y_{ALL} Z_{TERM} *g.yul* *sprod* 'X commits a battle against Y at Z' (PT 1287: 355–6)

We can explain the differences between them only if we assume a semantic shift from the original 'to let sb./sth. meet' to 'to deliver'. I assume that the shift occurred in the collocation *g.yul sprod* from 'to let the army meet' to 'to fight/commit a battle'.

spreyu (#565) '(calendric) monkey'

There can be no doubt that in OLT *spreyu* also denoted an animal. Moreover, the phrase *spre yu yphags par che ba zig* (PT 983: v2.2; *apud* OTDO) 'an exceedingly great monkey' proves that the term referred to an adult animal. This usage is attested in the Tibetan version of the Indian *Rāmāyaṇa* story but also in a passage from PT 1287: 18 where Lo-ñam is said to have pulled out a monkey from the armhole (? *mčhan*) of *bcan po* Dri-gum. On the other hand, *spreyu* frequently occurs as a term for a calendric unit: *spreyu yi lo*, lit. 'the year of the monkey'.

In terms of its etymology, *spreyu* seems to have been derived from *spra* 'large monkey; ape' by means of the DIM *-bu*.¹⁶² To the best of my knowledge, the latter term is attested only once as an independent lexeme in OLT: in *sprayi* (Or.8212/187: 2), most probably erroneously for *spreyu*. Apart from that, the syllable is found in the formation *spra bo che* (ITJ 737.1: 182; *apud* OTDO) translated by de Jong as 'big monkey' (de Jong 1989: 28). The text speaks of *spra bo che gsum* which is paraphrased as *spre yu gsum* two clauses later (ITJ 737.1: 183; *apud* OTDO).¹⁶³ Concerning its morphology, *spra bo che* can be juxtaposed with OLT *phal pho che* 'bulk' (see s.v.).

In OLT, *spreyu* does not seem to have denoted young of a monkey. Monkeys are found on the southern slopes of the Himalayas or in the forests of the Eastern Himalayas. The apparently derived character of the syllable *spra* (< s+√pra ?) suggests that the term does not belong to the inherited vocabulary of Tibetan. This is supported by the fact that thus far no cognates could be traced in other Trans-Himalayan languages (cf. STEDT #5566). I put forward the hypothesis that *spra* was derived from the verb *yphra/yphras*, CT 'schlagen, mit den Füßen ausschlagen' (Sch: 360a), 'to kick, to jerk, to strike with the foot' (J: 359a), attested dialectally in Leh as 'to kick (out), to flail (of animals)' (CDTD.V: 824); cf. also *yphras* 'stroke, blow, kick' (J: 360a). Schmidt quotes also the compound *yčhi yphras* 'der Todeskrampf, die Agonie' (Sch: 361a). The causative prefix *s-* would have turned the verb into an active one allowing the

¹⁶² This etymology was proposed in (Uray 1952: 206), explaining "a species is denoted by the diminutive form, while the basis itself has assumed a specific meaning". Below I express my doubts about its correctness.

¹⁶³ The oldest Tibetan dictionary, *Mahāvīyutpatti*, knows only *spreyu* which is glossed as 'vānaraḥ, markāṭaḥ, kapiḥ' (Mvy.l: 4829–31).

literal rendering of *spra* as *‘the striking one’. An analogous etymology can be proposed for Skt. *jhampāka/jhampāru/jhampin* ‘Affe’ (Böht.2: 281a) < √*jhamp* ‘to jump suddenly’ (cf. NWS s.v.). *jhampāka/jhampāru/jhampin* are all marked as attested only in lexicographical sources and neither is known to Sanskrit-Tibetan dictionaries. Therefore, it is problematic to assume that *spra* was based on one of these. Nevertheless, we can remark that Skt. *jhampāka* ‘monkey’ is formed from *jhampā* ‘a jump’ (NWS) by means of the suffix *-ka* that frequently forms diminutives. This morphology could be a faint indication that *spra* was indeed based on √*jhamp* and *spreṅyu* on *jhampāka*. (Uray 1952: 210, fn. 24) identified another Tibetan ‘diminutive’ coined by analogy with a Sanskrit word in *-ka*: *gzugs bu ‘rūpaka* simile, metaphor’ (D: 1106a); *rūpa* = *gzugs*, *-ka* ≈ *-bu*.

Should *spreṅyu* have been modelled on Skt. *jhampāka* or a similar formation, the question arises: why was a Sanskrit and not a Chinese model chosen if the duodenary calendar was borrowed from the Chinese? Tibetan duodenary calendar was modelled on the Chinese one and the animals were taken over from the latter. Despite this historical fact Chinese does not offer any motivation for OLT *spreṅyu*.

Concluding the discussion, I put forward the following tentative etymology of *spreṅyu*: *spreṅyu* ‘monkey’, lit. ‘the striking one’ < √*spra* tr ‘to strike’; cf. *snom bu* Ger. ‘Richer’ < *snom* ‘to smell’ (see s.v. *snom bu pa*; cf. also (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))). Since I can’t demonstrate that *spreṅyu* primarily denoted a young of a monkey or a smaller monkey, the derivation *spra* > *spreṅyu* seems less probable. The scarcely attested (and almost unknown in OLT) *spra* ‘(large) monkey’ could in fact be a back formation from *spreṅyu* after *-ṅyu* had been reanalysed as a diminutive clitic marking a small animal.

ph

pha los (#460) ‘¹suitable commoners; populace; ²gathering; ³census’

phag (#561) ‘(calendric) swine’

Regarding coffins excavated from a Tibetan grave in the Dulan region, Heller wrote: “the lateral panels have paintings of the twelve animals of the Tibetan calendar cycle, six on each side. It is to be noted that a black boar is substituted for the pig” (Heller 2016: 152). As against the identification of the animal as a ‘boar’, one can remark that Tibetan swine is generally black in colour (cf. (Pérez-Enciso, Burgos-Paz, and Ramos-Onsins 2015) & (Ren et al. 2011: 862)).

phab (#694) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘¹to throw down; ²to depose (from [SOUR]_{EL}); ³to impose; ⁴to bring/put down (?); [AGT]_{ERG} [PAT]_{ABS} ‘⁵to defeat; ⁶to capture’

[C] *bab*

phal če (#694) ‘abundance’

phal pho če (#695) ‘bulk’

sum ru pal po če in Or.8212/187: 35 is the only OLT example in which *phal pho če* is postposed to a head noun which does not denote human beings.

phul (#419) v1 *γbul*; DITR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} [BEN/REC]_{ALL} ‘to give’

(1) allows us to establish the complete argument structure of the verb as: [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} [BEN/REC]_{ALL}:

(1)

γdun ma moñ kar du (230) *blon khrī sum rjes bsduste / khud pa čhen pho blon khrī sum rjes / žañ khrī mñes smon zuñ la phul bayī rcis bgyīs* / (ITJ 750)

The council, [grand] councillor [Dbays] Khri-sum-rje [Rcañ-bžer] convened at Moñ-kar, made an account concerning (lit. of) [the fact that grand] councillor [Dbays] Khri-sum-rje [Rcañ-bžer] had given [the office of] grand *khud pa* to *žañ* Khri-mñes Smon-zuñ.

I have not found a clause with this verb and the indirect object in allative but preceding the direct object in absolutive. It appears that the argument in allative had to immediately be followed by the verb. The only exception concerns two metrical passages:

(2)

la la ni bcas phul / myi la ni yon phul nas / (PT 126: 131)

To the mountain passes [we] offered wages. To men [we] offered presents.

(3)

lha la ni yon phul / myi la ni phyag ychal // (ITJ 747: v12; *apud* OTDO)

To the deities [they] offered presents. To men [they] paid homage.

In (2) and (3), the position of the indirect object is fixed by the metrics of the five-syllable verses.

It is difficult to establish the speech register of *phul* as used in the OTA-I due to the uncertainty of the relative social positions of the persons involved in the actions. In most of the modern dialects the verb belongs to the honorific register but there are numerous exceptions (cf. CDTD.V: 882). Ex. (1) speaks rather against an honorific interpretation of the verb for there the grand councillor Dbays Khri-sum-rje Rcañ-bzer, i.e. the second highest political official in the state (after *bcan po*), gave an office to *žañ* Khri-mñes Smon-zuñ. Whatever the exact function of the *khud pa* office might have been, it was certainly ranked below that of a grand councillor. Moreover, in the OTA the only persons for whom the honorific register is used are members of the royal family. Thus, I conclude that at this stage of the language *phul* belonged to the part of the lexicon unmarked for speech register.

pho (#569) 'a male person, a man'

pho ña (#696) 'emissary'

Cs: 85b: an envoi, ambassador; Schr: 190a: an express sent for any particular purpose, a messenger; Sch: 345b: ein Gesandter, Bote, Botschafter; J: 345b: ¹messenger; ²ambassador, envoy; Desg: 632a: messenger, légat; D: 828a: a messenger, deputy, envoy; R.6: 52a: *dūta*, *dūtikā*, *avacāraka*, *kiñkara*; *посыльный*, *вестник*; *посланник*, *посол*; *духовный* (небесный) *вестник*, *ангел*; messenger; envoy; spiritual messenger, angel; Gs: 684c: messenger; WtS.49f.: ¹Bote, Abgesandter; ²eine Gruppe von Gottheiten; ³n[omen] pr[oprium] ein Ort in Khotan.

Mvy: 3809: *dūṭaḥ*; Tsh: 107r2: *abcaraka*, *kingkaraḥ*; YeŚes: 345b: *do hi ya*, 'el chi; GC: 525b: *bañ chen nam 'phrin yig slyel ba po*; Negi.8: 3523a: ¹*dūtaḥ*; ²*dautyam*; ³*preṣaṇam*; LCh: 512c: *dūta*; BTC: 1724a: *bañ chen*.

(Waddell 1911: 396, fn. 1) literally 'man + woman', with reference, as I believe, to the envoy being often a eunuch; p. 416: adopted by missionaries in translating the 'angel' of the Bible; fn. 2: Professor Parker: Eunuchs as envoys were sent to the Huns, but never to the Tibetans or Turks, only as messengers; (Francke 1914b: 50) One document which speaks of a *pho ña*, or 'messenger', is impressed with a seal showing a rider galloping; DTH:38: un messenger; (Lalou 1955: 182) messenger; (Dotson 2009b: 99) emissary; (Hill 2011b: 29) emissary; (Hill 2021a: 93) envoy.

The OTA document visits of emissaries from the following regions or peoples: Če-dog-pan, Rgya 'Chinese', Xbug-čor, Stod-phyogs, Dur-gyis, and Black Mywa.

pho brañ (#462) 'court'

phyag (#697) 'HON hand'

(Simon 1941: 388) *phyogs* (~logs) ~ *phyog* (~log) < *phyag* (~lag); (Kitamura 1975: 73) hon[orific] for *lag pa*; forms compounds with the ordinary forms whose meanings are related to <part of the hand, functions of the hand, and the like>; (Lyovin 1992: 54, fn. 8) Zhang (1975: 11) suggests that *phyag* < **ph-lag*, i.e. it is derived from the plain form *lag* by the prefixation of *ph-*. Zhang points out that although Classical Tibetan has initial cluster *bl-*, there are no clusters like *phl-* probably because *l*>*y* after voiceless aspirated stop initials.

p(h)yag occurs in the OTA predominantly in the idiom *pyag γc(h)al* (for a thorough analysis, see s.v. *γchald*). The latter always follows a clause in which a *bcan po* is mentioned. In the OTA, *p(h)yag* as an honorific term can only refer to the hands of the *bcan po*. The phrase *phyag du bžes* (Or.8212/187: 17) confirms that the noun *phyag* belongs to the honorific register.

phyi (#562) ‘HON grandmother’

(Benedict 1942: 315) < TB *p'i ‘grandmother’.

As I argued in (Bialek 2021c), all kinterms used in the OTA have the currently ruling *bcan po* as their reference point. This necessitates the use of honorific forms throughout the text, also for the grandmother of the *bcan po*. The honorific register of *phyi* is confirmed by its use as subject with honorific verbs *bžugs* and *noñs*.

phyi dal (#375) INTR [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to delay’

(Thomas 1957: 38) late-dallying; p. 156: dilatoriness (for *phyi dal čhe* – JB); (Nishida 2011: 324) ‘serious hindrance’ (for *phyi dal čhed* – JB).

dal is not attested as a verb in lexicographical sources on CT but we find it in modern dialects with the following meanings: Kargil nCA ‘to be free (from work), to be still’; Nurla nCA ‘to be free (from work, etc.)’, Leh nCA ‘to be free (from work), to have leisure’, Zanskar nCA ‘to relax’, Bathang ‘to die out (fire)’, Themchen nCA ‘to be extinguished (lamp)’, Bayan ‘to die out (fire)’ (CDTD.V:590). *dal* is clearly an intransitive verb. The entry for the year 687/8 informs us that councillor Mgar Khri-γbriñ Bcan-brod indeed drew to the Dru-gu-gu-zan land (l. 97). Thus, I assume that *phyi dalte* means something like ‘to be postponed for later’.

I propose understanding *phyi dal* as a coordinate compound with the underlying structure **phyi la dal*, lit. ‘(to be) late and slow’, i.e. ‘(to be) dilatory’. It was lexicalised first to the intransitive verb ‘to delay’ and then converted to the noun ‘delay’.

phyi sbon (#572) ‘HON grandmother and grandson’

phyiñ rild (#465) ‘sheaf (of corn)’

phyuñ (#699) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘¹to bring to light, cause to occur; ²to remove’

[C] *byuñ*

phyogs (#692) ‘direction’

(Simon 1941: 388) **‘hand-place’; ~ *phyog* (log) < *phyag* (lag).

γphos (#573) INTR/C [AGT]_{ABS} ‘to move’

γphos is the intransitive counterpart of transitive *spos* (see s.v.), requiring the subject in absolutive: ‘HUMAN_{ABS} *γphos*’, lit. ‘HUMAN moved’. Worth noticing is that the verb does not

require a complement that would express the goal of the movement (see ITJ 750: 163). In this case Ger. *sich (fort)bewegen* or Pol. *przemieszczać się* might be more appropriate translations than the Eng. *to move*.

b

bag ma (#387) 'bride'

DTH: 33, fn. 5: fiancée, jeune mariée; (Dotson 2009b: 259) bride, almost always in a virilocal marriage.

The word *bag ma* occurs in the OTA four times in two distinct VPs, cf.:

I. *bag mar gśegs*, lit. 'to go as *bag ma*'

(1)

bcan mo sña mo s[t]eñs s[ñ]a śur spuñs rye rgyug la bag mar gśegs (PT 1288: 53)

bcan mo Sña-mo-steñs went as bride for Sña-śur Spuñs-rye-rgyug.

(2)

bcan mo khri bañs / ya źa rje la bag mar (103) *gśegs* / (ITJ 750)

bcan mo Khri-bañs went as bride for the lord of the Ya-źa.

II. *bag mar btañ*, lit. 'to send as *bag ma*'

(3)

je ba ydron ma lod dur (269) *gyis kha gan la bag mar btañ* / (ITJ 750)

[They] gave *je ba* Ydron-ma-lod in marriage to Dur-gyis *kha gan*.

(4)

(283) § / *ybrugī lo la / bcan poe po brañ / dbyard mchar bu snaγī ñañ mo gliñ na bźugste / je ba khri ma lod bru źa rje la bag* (284) *mar btañ* / (ITJ 750)

In the dragon year, in the summer, the *bcan po*'s court, having abode in Ñañ-mo-gliñ of Mchar-bu-sna, gave *je ba* Khri-ma-lod in marriage to the lord of the Bru-źa.¹⁶⁴

bag ma clearly concerns a female member of the royal family who is sent to marry a foreign ruler. Neither **bag pa* nor **bag po* is attested in OLT as a masculine equivalent of *bag ma*, even though the marker =*ma* suggests that the lexeme has been derived in order to mark the feminine gender. CT knows, however, *bag po* 'bridegroom'. Would both have been derived from **bag*, one would rather expect *bag po* and ¹*bag mo* (cf. the OLT pairs *bcan po* ~ *bcan mo* and *jo bo* ~ *jo mo*). A similar asymmetry is seen in: *bod pa* 'Tibetan (man)' ~ *bod mo* 'Tibetan woman'. Here, however, *bod pa* is the matrix lexeme and can apply to any person disregarding his/her gender. Thus, *bod mo* is a secondary formation derived from *bod pa*.¹⁶⁵

Morpheme *bag* as denoting a male person can be traced in the following Central Asiatic records:

(5)

bag mdo stoñ (ITN 656: 1)

¹⁶⁴ To these we can add *bag ma ydor* from a fragmentarily preserved document ITN 1739: 3. Thomas suggested reading *bag med* instead of the attested *bag ma* (TLTD.2: 447).

¹⁶⁵ According to Beyer, in CT "there appears to be some tendency for native Tibetan words to select -*mo* and for borrowed expressions and neologisms to select -*ma*." (Beyer 1993: 125). This would accord with the proposed etymology of *bag* as a loanword (see below).

bag Mdo-stoñ¹⁶⁶

(6)

§ /:/ *bag ra bźaγi mčhid gsol pa* (ITN 862r)

a request of *bag* Ra-bźa

(7)

mthoñ khyab gyi s[d]e bag ra khri (ITN 1090r)

Mthoñ-khyab district, *bag* Ra-khri¹⁶⁷

(8)

[-] [*kh*]yab gyi sde yug pa mo *bag za mñen mo* [-] (ITN 501: 1; reconstr. after TLTD.2: 345)

[-]-khyab¹⁶⁸ district, a widow Mñen-mo-[-], a lady of a *bag*

(9)

[-] *gom paγi sde pu*¹⁶⁹ *bag mu ne stañ* / (ITN 1745)

Gom-pa district, *pu bag* Mu-ne-stañ

(10)

rlañ gi sde / pu bag ñuñ [-]¹⁷⁰ (ITN 2171: r1)

Rlañ district, *pu bag* Ñuñ-[-]

(11)

§ // *yar skyañ gī sde / pu bag yul mthoñ* (ITN 1361)

Yar-skyañ district, *pu bag* Yul-mthoñ

I put forward the hypothesis that *bag ma* is derived from a foreign word that denoted a male person. A perfect candidate seems to be the originally Iranian word *bag* that was borrowed into diverse languages of Central Asia:

The appellative *baga-* ‘god’ came to be applied to the Great King of Kings of the Persians initially. Later it suffered a social decline, which was most marked in Sogdiane. The local king adopted it, then the kinglet, then the owner of a castle, finally any gentleman laid claim to it. Yet at the same time Sogd[ian] βγ- continued as designation of the ancient divinities, and the representatives of monotheistic religions, as the Christian missionaries, used it of ‘God’ with a capital letter. [...] in the Mugh documents [...] βγ- almost exclusively is used of men of some social standing. (Henning 1965: 249)

¹⁶⁶ In addition, Thomas suggested reading *bag* instead of the attested *rag* in ITN 1824:v1 (TLTD.3:181a, s.v. *rag*).

¹⁶⁷ In (6) and (7), Thomas read ‘*bag ra Bźa*’ and ‘*bag ra Khri*’ (TLTD.2: 446), but it is rather improbable that a proper name would consist of one syllable only; cf. ex. (5).

¹⁶⁸ Most probably Mthoñ-khyab should be reconstructed.

¹⁶⁹ TLTD.2: 458: *phu bag*. According to Thomas (ibid.), *pu/phu bag* could have been ‘an official (or local) designation’.

¹⁷⁰ TLTD.2: 210: *pu bag ñuñ k[uγ]*.

According to Henning, this $\beta\gamma$ - occurs in differing versions of a Sogdian compound, the contextual analysis of which suggests the meaning ‘wedding, marriage’ (Henning 1965: 243f.):

While $\beta\gamma$ - ordinarily was an appellative, it did, however, also exist as the individual name of a divinity, then corresponding with the Indian god *Bhaga* (= Iran[ian] *Baga*). The hypothesis I wish to put forward is this, that in the Sogdian compound $\beta\gamma'n\gamma$ - means not simply ‘divine’, but ‘referring to, associated with the god *Baga*’. (ibid., p. 247)

He proposes reconstructing the meaning of the said compound, which was a term for ‘marriage’, as ‘Baga-union’ (ibid.).

Henning’s interpretation of the compound was rejected by Dietz who proposed understanding the Sogdian expression $\beta\gamma'n\gamma\check{s}$ *kt'kw* as ‘the making of a son of a divine (being)’, i.e. ‘the making of an emperor’ (Dietz 1978: 113). Dietz based his interpretation on a marriage custom common among Central Asiatic societies, in which a bridegroom is called *šāh*, ‘king’ (*rāja* among the Rajputs in Northern India), during the wedding ceremony and the ensuing festivities. In his view, ‘the compound $\beta\gamma'n\gamma\check{s}$ may have come to denote husband in Sogdian, at least in a figurative sense’ (ibid.).

In the light of the OLT evidence, I put forward the hypothesis that **bag* was borrowed from an as for now unidentified Middle Iranian language in which it denoted a gentleman¹⁷¹ and was used in the context of marriage ceremonies.¹⁷² In OLT **bag* might have originally denoted a foreign nobleman (cf. Eng. *count*) and for this reason *bag ma* was primarily applied to Tibetan princesses that were married to foreign rulers.¹⁷³

¹⁷¹ Consider that in the OTA *bag ma* is used only with reference to royal princesses, called then *bcan mo* or *je ba*. This suggests a higher social status of a person denoted by the term.

¹⁷² An alternative hypothesis would be to consider **bag* as a loan from Old Turkish *be:g* ‘originally ‘the head of a clan, or tribe, a subordinate chief’, and the like. [...] almost certainly a [loan]-w[ord] from Chinese *po* ‘head of a hundred men’” (Clauson 1972: 322b). Maciuszak, following a remark of Sims-Williams (s.v. *baga* in: *Encyclopaedia Iranica*, <http://www.iranicaonline.org/articles/baga-an-old-iranian-term-for-god-sometimes-designating-a-specific-god>; 19.10.2017), suggests relating Turkish *be:g* (her: *bäg*) to the Iranian honorific title *bag*, *bay*, *bay* ‘lord, prince’ (Maciuszak 2010) – words historically related to the above mentioned Sogdian $\beta\gamma$ -. In her opinion, the Turkish term could have been borrowed from Eastern Iranian languages of Sogdiana and Turfan. However, the vowel of the Turkish word speaks against Maciuszak’s hypothesis. The Chinese *bó* 伯 (Clauson: *po*) ‘older brother; father’s elder brother; senior male ‘sire’; feudal rank ‘count’” (MDBG) has been reconstructed as: LH *pak*, ONW *pək*, OCM **prāk* (Schuessler 2007: 169); MC *paek*, OC **pʰrak* (Baxter and Sagart 2014). Thus, it seems more probable that the Turkish term was indeed borrowed from Chinese. Since the Chinese *bó* does not seem to have had any connotations with marriage customs, the hypothesis connecting OLT *bag ma* to the Iranian stem *bag* (Sogdian $\beta\gamma$ -) is preferred.

¹⁷³ A similar case is represented by the OTurk. *xa:tun* ‘lady’ which, according to (Clauson 1972: 602b), was borrowed from Sogdian *xwt'yn* [xwatēn] ‘the wife of the lord, ruler’ – a female equivalent of *xwt'y* ‘lord, ruler’.

Hill analysed *bag ma* as a word inherited from the PTH stock. In Hill’s book the following correspondences for the LT plain *b*- in onset are found (MC and OC after (Baxter and Sagart 2014), LH and OCM after (Schuessler 2007)):

LT	PY	MC	OC	LH	OCM
<i>bag ma</i>	<i>fù</i>	<i>bjuwX</i>	<i>*mə.bəʔ</i>	<i>bu^B</i> < <i>buə^B</i>	<i>*bəʔ</i>

(Hill 2019b: 41)

bab (#701) **INTR** [THEM]_{ABS} ‘¹to fall; ²to happen’

[C] *phab*

bond (#753) **TR/C** [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘(HUM) to give’

The following passage confirms that the verb requires agentive subject in ergative:

(1)

yuñ nas myañ dbays mnon dañ gsum gyis / (158) ches poñ nag señ las prin kyīs // spu rgyal stag bu yī sñan du bon nas // (PT 1287)

Thereafter, the three, Myañ, Dbays, and Mnon, informed (lit. gave to the ear of) *spu rgyal Stag-bu* [Sñā-gzigs] with a message from Ches-poñ Nag-señ.

Phrases like *mchan bon* (Or. 8212/187: 17; cf. *mchan gsold* in ITJ 750: 93, 185–6), *sñan du bon* (PT 1287: 158), *bcan po pyag du bon* (PT 1287: 184), *dug bon te bkroñs so* (PT 1287: 301) prove that the verb belongs to the humble register.

bor (#700) **TR/C** [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to issue’

Reconstructed conjugation: v1 *dor*, v2 *bor*, v3 **bor* (?), v4 *yor***d*.

bya gag (#463) ‘(calendric) hen’

According to Heller, the bird of the Tibetan calendar cycle that is seen on Tibetan coffin panels from the grave in Dulan can be identified as hen (Heller 2013b: 119). She described the bird as follows: “the bird has very long tail feathers, but does not have the comb on the top of the head, nor waddles” (ibid., p. 120). The origin of the second constituent of the compound remains uncertain. It might have been a clipping from **ga ga* imitating sound made by a specific bird species; cf. the Eng. *cackle* or *gaggle*, Ger. *gackern* or *gakeln*, and Fr. *caqueter* – all of onomatopoeic origins and with two velar stops.

The Tibetan compound *bya gag* can be classified as a special case of appositional compound of the subsumptive type ‘generic term+hypernym’ as first defined by Marchand (Marchand 1969: 62f.); lit. ‘a bird which is a hen’. This is a very seldom type of compounds in OLT and

<i>bañ ba</i>	<i>fáng</i>	<i>bjang</i>	*[Cə-N-]paŋ	<i>buaŋ</i>	*baŋ	(Hill 2019b: 263)
<i>bar</i>	<i>bàn</i>	<i>panH</i>	*p ^ç an-s	<i>pan^c</i>	*pâns	(Hill 2019b: 263)
<i>buñ ba</i>	<i>fēng</i>	<i>phjowng</i>	*p ^h (r)oŋ	<i>p^huoŋ</i>	*phoŋ	(Hill 2019b: 36)

These data provide three different correspondences for LT *b*-:

LT	MC	OC	LH	OCM
<i>b</i> -	<i>bj</i> -	*mə.b-	<i>b</i> -	*b-
		*[Cə-N-]p-	<i>b</i> -	*b-
	<i>p</i> -	*p ^ç -	<i>p</i> -	*p-
	<i>phj</i> -	*p ^h (r)-	<i>p^h</i> -	*ph-

The obvious differences are not addressed to by Hill and so we have to remain sceptical about the correctness of the equivalents. On the other hand, we cannot exclude the possibility that the Iranian stem *bag* was independently and at different times borrowed into Tibetan and Chinese.

could either be based on a foreign pattern or represent a PT word-formation not productive in OT any longer. This pattern reminds us of the rule set up in the *Sgra sbyor bam po gr̄is pa* for names that cannot be plausibly translated: one is advised to add a hypernym (e.g., *yul, me tog*) before such a word.¹⁷⁴

bya sga (#734) 'reward'

YeŚes: 373a: śaṅ, haṅi ra, yaṅi śaṅ, yug le ge (s.v. *bya dgay*); Tshe: 115r3: bharmanra (s.v. *bya dgay*); GC: 566b: gsol ras (s.v. *bya dgay*); Negi.9: 3773a: ¹dhanam; ²bhṛtiḥ; ³sammānaḥ (s.v. *bya dgay*); LCh: 542c: prasāda (s.v. *bya dgay*); BTC: 1856a: gzeṅs bstod kyi ster čhayam rñan pa (s.v. *bya dgay*); DSM: 545a: gzeṅs bstod kyi ster čhayam rñan pa; BYD: 354a: brñam paṅam gsol ras (s.v. *bya dgay*); p. 354b: bya dgay. gsol ras.

Cs: 94b: a reward, a gift, a present (s.v. *bya dgay*); Sch: 372a: ein Geschenk, eine Gabe, Belohnung (s.v. *bya dgay*); J: 372b: gift, present, esp. as a reward (s.v. *bya dgay*); D: 883a: favour, boon, royal favour, recognition of services with rewards and presents (s.v. *bya dgay*); Desg: 677a: récompense, don (s.v. *bya dgay*).

(Thomas 1936: 283) reward (s.v. *bya dgay*); DTH: 39: présent; fn. 6: pour *bya dgay* 'don, récompense'; (Lalou 1955: 184) sinécure (s.v. *bya dgay*); (Yamaguchi 1970a: 60, fn. 9) reward, given by a superior person to a man in lower position; (Uray 1975: 159) récompense (s.v. *bya dgay*); (Coblin 1991c: 100) gift, reward (s.v. *bya dgay*); (Dotson 2009b: 100) gift; p. 260: present, reward, gift in recompense.

OLT records attest to five different spellings of the lexeme. The second syllable *sga* is only known from the OTA and seems to be *lectio difficilior*. Accordingly, the etymological meaning of the compound must have included the word 'saddle'. I may recall here the lexicalisation of *žo śa* from 'milk and meat' to '¹payment; ²contribution' (Bialek 2018a: 2.475). Similar generalisation is assumed to have occurred with *bya sga*: from denoting concrete object(s) to an abstract idea of reward or gift (the latter meanings are secured for OLT and CT). The necessary condition for the semantic shift is that the objects must have been connected to prestige in the society; in the OTA *bya sga* is bestowed by the *bcan po*.

Regarding the first syllable, the sources are also uncertain as to its spelling. The form *byad* resulted most probably from dittography; the first consonant of the following syllable has been repeated as the final of the first syllable: Ø > -d / _+d-. However, the compound *bya sga* cannot be etymologised in a plausible way: < **bya baṅi sga* 'a saddle for what has been done/deeds' (?). Therefore I propose reconstructing its original form as **byes sga*, lit. 'journey saddle'. The latter is preserved in Tshangra as [bezga] 'saddle (for loads)' (CDTD: 5713). The attested *bya sga/dgay* resulted partly from regular changes, partly from folk etymologisation: **byes sga*¹⁷⁵ > **byas sga* (regressive vowel assimilation)¹⁷⁶ > *bya sga* (haplography and/or folk etymologisation) > *bya dgay* (folk etymologisation). The replacement of *-sga* by *-dgay* took place after the lexicalisation to 'reward' had been completed and the connotation with saddle fade into oblivion.

¹⁷⁴ For a translation of the rule, see §18 in (Simonsson 1957: 253–4).

¹⁷⁵ (Thomas 1957: 18) noticed the formation *čes sga* in ITJ 738: 3v10, which he reconstructed as **čhibs sga* (?). The manuscript has not been digitised yet so that it is impossible to either confirm or correct Thomas' reading. The question is: could *čes* be a local transcription of OLT *byes*?

¹⁷⁶ For vowel assimilation in OLT compounds, see (Bialek 2018a: 1.217ff.)

Originally **byes sga* (< **byes kyi sga* 'saddle for a journey')¹⁷⁷ denoted a saddle prepared for long journeys; that is, equipped with additional bags (cf. Tshangra 'saddle (for loads)'). In nomadic or pastoralist society saddle was a highly valued object. One may speculate that when presented as a gift, bags of such a saddle might have been additionally filled with precious objects. The semantic shift must have occurred not later than by 762¹⁷⁸ but most probably prior to 699/700 for in ITJ 750: 130 *bya sga* is coordinated with *yig gcañ* 'insignia'. Tshangra [bezga] indicates that the primary meaning was still in use in EOT.

byañ bu (#658) 'wooden tablet'

J: 375a: ¹inscription, direction, label; ²the tablet on which an inscription is written.

(Thomas 1933: 391) ~ *byañ* wooden tablet; (Uray 1972b: 27) tablet; (Kværne 1985: 12) drawing of the deceased; (LaRocca 2006a: 51a) a general term for a small label, card, or flat object of rectangular shape; (Bellezza 2008: 235) ritual tablets of variable function; (Dotson 2009b: 123) wooden slips; (Dotson 2011a: 91, fn. 21) wooden slips; (van Schaik 2011b: 55) an inscribed rectangular wooden tablet; (Dotson 2013a: 54) wooden slip.

byañ rold (#706) 'northern side'

byañ lam (#705) 'northern road'

byi ba (#577) '(calendric) rat'

Possibly derived by the nominal =*pa* from an onomastic root **bji*.

byim po (#708) 'military troops'

DTH: 67-8, fn. 5: *gyim po*: possibly means 'man of the Gyim śan region'; the name Gyim po (Byim po) is evidenced in N.E. Tibet as tribal; (Beckwith 1987: 128, fn. 124) probably from Chinese, *ping pu*, 'Board of War'; p. 133, fn. 148: army; (Dotson 2009b: 126, fn. 326) a Chinese expeditory army for driving the Tibetans out of Wakhan; probably from the Chinese, *ping pu* 'Board of War'; p. 260: Chinese border troops.

Beckwith suggested linking OLT *byim po* to Ch. 兵部 *bīngbù* 'Ministry of War' (Beckwith 1993: 128, fn. 124). For the Ch. terms the following reconstructions have been proposed:

<i>bīng</i>	LH <i>pi̯aŋ</i> , OCM <i>*praŋ</i> (Schuessler 2007: 168) MC <i>pjaeng</i> , OC <i>*pran</i> 'weapon' (Baxter and Sagart 2014)
<i>bù</i>	LH <i>bo^B</i> , OCM <i>*buʔ</i> (Schuessler 2007: 168: 244) MC <i>buwX</i> , OC <i>*[b]ʃ(r)oʔ</i> 'lead, govern' (Baxter and Sagart 2014)

Therefore, Beckwith's hypothesis seems plausible, but we have to reconstruct the sound change *-ñ > -m* to OT which might have resulted from the assimilation to the labial initial of the following syllable: *-ŋ > -m / _+p-*.

¹⁷⁷ For the etymology of *byes*, see (Bialek 2018a: 2.323, fn. 1).

¹⁷⁸ Cf. *rgyaŋi dpya dar / dañ sa ris* (49) *las / scogs pa / [...]* *bya sgar scald* /// (Or.8212/187) '[The *bcan po*] bestowed silk tribute and territories of the Chinese as a reward (!as a journey saddle)'].

In OLT sources, *byim po* is a *dis legomenon* each time determined by the word *rgya* ‘Chinese’. In Or.8212/187: 4–5, it occurs as direct object of the verb *drañs* that is commonly used in OLT with *dmag* ‘army’ and *dra ma* ‘expeditionary army’. In addition, *byim po* was led by a general (*dmag dpon*). Its second occurrence announces the loss of Bru-śa and the Gog people, we may assume, to the Chinese. Whatever its original meaning in Ch. might have been, *byim po* denoted military forces in OLT. Accordingly, I propose translating the term as ‘military troops’ to distinguish between *byim po* and *dmag*.

byuñ (#698) INTR [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to occur’

[C] *phyuñ*

bran (#702) ‘serf; a labourer in the feudal system of the Tibetan Empire bound to working on his lord’s estate’

TLTD.3: 160b: servant, slave; (Róna-Tas 1955: 261) a category of law rank in a dependant position; in Old Tibetan texts [...] are often mentioned together with the land; [...] dependent on his lord; p. 262: at the time of the consolidation of the central power, under Gnam-ri Sroñ-bcan, it was still possible to rise from the *bran* status; p. 263: in the period between the 7th and the 10th century, the *bran*-s were a strata of serfs. During that period, their social position underwent substantial change; (Stein 1972: 112) liegeman, serf; (Beckwith 1977a: 207) dependent subject; (Richardson 1985: 171) bondsman; (Li and Coblin 1987: 432) servant, liegeman; serf; (Uebach 1985b: 31) Leibeigene; (Coblin 1991c: 100) servant, liegeman, serf; (Richardson 1992: 108, fn. 22) The *bran* though bound to the estate on which they served seem to be of a higher status than the other subjects (*ybañs*); (Takeuchi 1995: 25) bondservant; p. 142: was able to act as both seller and guarantor; (Richardson 1998b: 187) male and female bondservants attached to an estate who could be employed as cultivators, servants or craftsmen. They could be transferred together with the estate to another owner or lent individually. [...] In certain circumstances it seems possible that *bran* could be given possession of land; (Richardson 1998h: 162, fn. 10) bondsmen; (Dotson 2009b: 67) bondservant; p. 68: parallels in many ways the pre-modern *mi ser*; p. 81: subject.

brims (#601) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to parade’

J: 401a: pf. *brim(s)*; ¹to distribute, deal out, hand round; ²Ld. to throw away, what is worthless; BTC: 1997: *γgyed pa dañ. γdren pa dañ. stob pa*; DSM: 602b: *γbrims pa ni γgyed par byed pa. źes gsuñs pa ltar to*.

DTH: 50: *furent réparties*; (Coblin 1991a: 311) to inspect; p. 312: to examine; (Coblin 1991b: 531a) to distribute, spread out; (Dotson 2009b: 120) paraded; fn. 297 read *γgrimste*; (Hill 2011b: 30) paraded; (Dotson 2013b: 66) hunt (for *γdrim* – JB).

Beside the occurrence in the OTA, *brims* is also attested in:

(1)

thañ ba g.yu thañ dañ / smra gol skyi ma gñis śig / śa bśor śa ma / khums / dgo brims dgo ma (r33) khums / (PT 1285)

Both *Thañ-ba-g.yu-thañ* and *Smra-gol-skyi-ma* chased deer, the deer were not killed. [They] scattered antelopes, the antelopes were not killed.

In analogous passages, we find the form *γdrim*:

(2)

śa śor (41) dgo γdrim du gśegs gis / (PT 1040; apud OTDO)

[I] go to chase deer, to scatter antelopes.

(3)

myiñ po dral po ni byañ ka snam bži ru ša bšor dgo ydrim du bžud (PT 1068: 67; *apud* OTDO)
Regarding the brother, the sister's brother, [he] went to Byañ-ka-snam-bži to chase deer, to scatter antelopes.

(4)

rje dañ dañ dañs gyī rje gyañ ka snam brgyad du / (v2-03) ša šor du gšegs / dgo ydrim du gšegs / (PT 1289; *apud* OTDO)

The lord Dañ-dañ, the lord of Dañs, went to Gyañ-ka-snam-brgyad to chase deer. [He] went to scatter antelopes.

In all these fragments *ydrim/brims* is juxtaposed with *šor/bšor*. There is no doubt that both verbs described an activity typical for or constituting part of a hunt. The CT *ybrim/brims* is glossed as ¹'to distribute, deal out, hand round; ²'to throw away' (J: 401a). In the hunting context, the verb might have denoted the action of chasing the game so that it is scattered around, leaving weaker individuals separated from the herd and therefore more vulnerable to hunters. Accordingly, I reconstruct the verb as TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} *'to scatter'.

On the other hand, the verb is used in military contexts (cf. PT 986), where army divisions are presented in front of (*spyan śna*) a high ranking person. Since in ITJ 750 *brims* is used with reference to a military unit, I translate the verb as 'paraded', i.e. spread for display or in order to examine.¹⁷⁹

Certainly *ydrim* and *brims* belonged to one conjugation, which on this basis can be reconstructed as **ydrim/brims/brim/rims*. *rims* 'epidemy, plague' (J: 530a; lit. 'what is scattered'), derived from the v4 by means of conversion, confirms the proposed reconstruction of the verb semantics.

bris (#593) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [PAT]_{ABS} 'to write'

bris is an inflected form of the root √ri with the etymological meaning *'to cut (letters in wood)'.¹⁸⁰ From the same root two word-families were derived in OLT:

- I. 'to diminish': *rid pa* 'mager, verkrümmert; rar, selten' (Sch: 546b), 'meager, emaciated' (J: 529a); *ris* 'part, section, division, region' (Cs: 235a; < *'a portion, by taking away of which sth. is diminished'); *ybri* 'to lessen, decrease, diminish' (J: 400b); *yphri* 'to lessen, diminish; take away from' (J: 360a); *ybrid* ²'minus (in math.), ³'to cut, take away, deduct a small portion or amount' (Gs: 770c)

¹⁷⁹ Cf. Eng. *to parade* ^{1b}*transitive*. To march through (a place) in procession or with great display; to walk up and down, promenade along (a street, etc.) or through (a place), esp. in order to be seen; ³*transitive*. To assemble (troops, etc.) for inspection or review; to cause to go on parade' (OED online).

¹⁸⁰ Compare hereto the etymology of Eng. *write* 'Old English wriþan 'score, form (letters) by carving, write', of Germanic origin; related to German reissen 'sketch, drag' (OED online). Ger. *schreiben* (and related forms in other Germanic languages) is a borrowing from Lat. *scribō, -ere* 'mit einem Griffel graben, einzeichnen, schreiben' (Walde 1910: 689). All these words contain the elements *ri* or *re* that seem to have constituted the core of the various words with the original meaning 'to carve, to cut off'.

II. 'to write': ^lris 'figure, form' (J: 530b); *γbri* 'to draw, design, describe' (J: 400b)

It follows that the Tibetan script must have been invented before the introduction of paper in 630s or 640s (see (Bialek 2018c: 22f.)), and that the first texts were written by carving letters in wooden tablets. This is confirmed by the contemporary Chinese sources; *Jiù Tángshū* 舊唐書 relates: "[Ces gens] n'ont pas d'écriture; ils concluent leurs contrats au moyen de bois entaillés et de cordelettes nouées" (Pelliot 1961: 1) and in *Xīn Tángshū* 新唐書 we read: "Dans leurs raport officiels, ils n'ont pas d'écriture, mais concluent leurs contrats au moyen de cordes nouées et de bois encochés" (ibid., p. 80).

bru źa rje (#732) 'lord of Bru-źa'

bruñ pa (#604)

DSM: 564a: gnaṅ lugs dpon gyi go gnas śig gi miñ ste.

(Thomas 1936: 284) official; p. 286, fn. 35: = *druñ pa*; DTH: 43, fn. 5: fonctionnaire, secrétaire; (Chang 1959: 130) secretary; (Uray 1962b: 353) The *bruñ pa* offices, at least under this title, presumably existed only in the initial period of the Tibetan kingdom; p. 354: the *bruñ pa* offices were either abolished or re-named during the reorganization that took place under Khri Sroñ-lde-brcan; the *bruñ pas* appear in the first place to have had a fiscal function. According to a passage in the Law of Theft, the moveables of the thieves executed or exiled devolved, in the absence of legitimate claimants, upon the State and were turned over to the possession (care) of the *bruñ pas* or the fiscal officials called *khab so/khab so pa* 'palace guard'; p. 355: they belonged to the significant officials, since the death, dismissal and appointment of the *bruñ pas* are registered in the early 8th century reports of the Annals; p. 358: in the winter of 731 A.D. the number of the *bruñ pas*, and thereby also their territorial competence, changed; the fusion of the *bruñ pa* offices in the winter of 731 A.D. was a more or less significant step in uniting the Three Horn and Great Rcañ 'provinces' into a single Four Horn 'province' and in setting up the Dbus and Gcañ as 'sub-provinces' containing each two horns; (Hill 2008: 82) revenue officer; (Dotson 2009b: 58) commissioner, involved in the legal confiscation of wealth; (Hill 2011b: 25) revenue officer.

Apart from ITJ 750, only one OLT text mentions the term:

(1)

bruñ pa ṡam / khab so gañ gyi (v49) dkor stord paṡi ris su bźes so / (ITJ 753)

[The property of a thief who has been killed or banned] is taken to the domain of the one, *bruñ pa* or *khab so*, who lost his wealth [owing to thefts committed by the thief].

(2)

rkun po bkum pa dañ spyugs paṡi bañ za pyugs nor (v50) blar bźes pa dañ / rce rgod dañ mjod sruñs / nor gyi spu / myed du mñon ba la ño ño ste bzuñ (v51) ba la rkud phabste / rkud phruñ paṡam khab soṡi risu blar bźes pa / rlag paṡi / čhad bruñ pa ṡṡaṡ (v52) ṡis snon myi gdabo / (ITJ 753)

Having accused the commander and the treasury-guard, who were caught, of the theft,¹⁸¹ the fine (*čhad*) for (lit. of) the loss of stolen goods, that were taken to the superiors as a domain of *khab so* or *bruñ pa*, shall not be added with interests to the *bruñ pa*.

¹⁸¹ As against the previous proposals (cf.: (Thomas 1936: 282) 'to lay penalty'; (Uray 1962b: 355, fn. 2) 'to impose penalty'; (Dotson 2007b: 15) 'to levy a *rkud*'; to receive a *rkud*', p. 69: *rkud* = 'fine, penalty?'; (Dotson 2015b: 278) 'punishment for theft'), I interpret the phrase *rkud phab* by analogy with *bkyon ṡbebs*, lit. 'to throw a *bkyon* (upon one)', i.e. 'to accuse sb. of *bkyon*'.

(3)

myiyi čhaldu yoris payī rnam s / rkod (read: *rgod*) *mun mag myī žig na* (v53) *bruñ pa la myiñ snond / du gdabo thañ snon du myī snan do* / (ITJ 753)

If those who came as a compensation (? *čhald*) of men are border guards-braves (lit. braves who are border guards), [they] shall be added as a name-gain for the *bruñ pa*.

(4)

khab so ba žig / las / dkor (v54) *gyi čhaldu myī žig mčhīs bruñ pa len pa la myī snondu bsnado* (ITJ 753)

[If] a man has come from one *khab so ba* as a compensation (? *čhald*) for wealth, [one] added the man as an acquisition (*snon*) for the receiving *bruñ pa*.

The OTA-I distinguish between two positions of *bruñ pa*: *bruñ pa* and *bruñ pa* of Rcañ-čhen. In this context, *bruñ pa* of Rcañ-čhen is juxtaposed with the other *bruñ pa*, from which fact we may infer that the latter was an official with jurisdiction over the Three Horns. The positions were occupied by:

bruñ pa

Lho Xbrin-po-rgyal Sum-sregs	(?–682/3–?)		
Gnubs Kho-ma-re	(?–707/8 S)		
Rdo Xphan-koñ	(707/8 S–714/5 S)		
Ches-poñ Tre-goñ	(714/5 S–?)		
Ru-yoñ Phyi-señ	(?–719/20 S)		
Señ-go Mon-bu	(719/20 S–?)		
žañ Tre-goñ	(?–745/6 W)	Señ-go Xphan-la-skyes	(?–745/6 W)
Čog-ro Rma-goñ	(745/6 W–?)	Myañ Xdus-khoñ	(745/6 W–?)

bruñ pa of Rcañ-čhen

Lañ Sa-ceñ	(?–715/6 S)
žañ Khri-mñes Smon-zuñ	(715/6 S–723/4 W) ¹⁸²
Ža-sña Thañ-rcañ	(?–731/2 W)
Señ-go Mon-bu	(731/2 W–?)

The last mentioned appointment to *bruñ pa* of Rcañ-čhen was in 731/2. For the year 745/6 two offices of *bruñ pa* are attested. After the formation of the Four Horns the separate administration of Rcañ-čhen was apparently abandoned and the region was completely incorporated into the Horn-administration. It follows that the re-organisation of the administration took place after 731. In winter 733/4, the OTA-I mention the Four Horns for the first time (ITJ 750: 267). Two *bruñ pas* for the Four Horns means that each official had two Horns under his jurisdiction. Uray identified Ches-poñ Tre-goñ with *žañ* Tre-goñ and Señ-go Mon-bu with Señ-go Xphan-la-skyes (Uray 1962b: 356). This forced him to assume that there were two *bruñ pas* in the Three Horns. The second identification can be dismissed on

¹⁸² As remarked by Uray (Uray 1962b: 357, fn. 12), in winter 723/4 *žañ* Khri-mñes Smon-zuñ received the office of *khud pa* (ITJ 750: 231) and so, we may assume, he resigned from the office of *bruñ pa*.

the fact that *Señ-go Mon-bu* is mentioned twice in the text, first as a *bruñ pa* and then once again as a *bruñ pa* of *Rcañ-čhen*. Uray's argument that proper names consisted of two individual names at that time and so both *Mon-bu* and *ᠬphan-la-skyes* could be used with respect to one person (Uray 1962b: 357, fn. 10) is in so far misplaced as this pattern of usage is not confirmed in the OTA (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))). The case of *Ches-poñ Tre-goñ* and *žañ Tre-goñ* is less problematic and here indeed the names refers to one person. Uray assumed that *Ches-poñ Tre-goñ* alias *žañ Tre-goñ* held the position of *bruñ pa* from 714/5 to 745/6. It is, however, also possible that he was appointed to the office twice in his life. Since this was possible with respect to grand councillors (cf. *Mgar Stoñ-rcañ Yul-zuñ* in PT 1287: 102–4), it was most probably also admitted in cases of other positions. Although the office is reported several times in the OTA-I, it is mentioned rather at random; for the majority of *bruñ pas* only one date is given, either their appointment or dismissal. For *bruñ pa Lho ᠬbriñ-po-rgyal Sum-sregs* neither is provided. Thus the *Annals* do not provide comprehensive information on the office neither do we learn anything about the duties of the *bruñ pas*.

The fact that there were only two *bruñ pas* in the Four Horns suggests a high rank of the office. In (Bialek 2018a.1: 334), I drew attention to the fact that, according to ITJ 753, the officials were involved in certain legal cases that concerned theft in the area under their jurisdiction.¹⁸³

Regarding the etymology of the term, Uray dismissed Thomas' suggestion (expressed in (Thomas 1936: 286, fn. 35)) that *bruñ pa* could be related to CT *druñ pa*: "because, on the strength of its meaning 'secretary, waiting man, page in ordinary', it undoubtedly belongs to the family of the radical *druñ* 'near'" (Uray 1962b: 354). In (Bialek 2018a: 1.334, fn. 1), I have tentatively proposed relating *bruñ* to: *gruñ* 'wise, clever' (CDTD: 1308); *gruñ ba/po* '1wise, prudent; 2meek, mild, gentle' (J: 77b); *druñ po* '1prudent, sensible, judicious, wise; 2sincere, candid; 3diligent?' (J: 263b). Accordingly, *bruñ pa* might have been a public officer appointed to oversee legal cases in the territory under his jurisdiction. For the lack of a good English equivalent I refrain from translating the term.

bro (#595) 'oath'

bros (#596) INTR/C [AGT]_{ABS} 'to flee'

bla (#703) 'authority'

Desg: 692a: = *steñ* = *goñ*, *pars superior*, *quod est in alto supra*, la partie supérieure, en haut, sur; Sch: 380b: statt *steñ* od[er] *goñ* der Obertheil; oben; Jä: 387b: der Raum über etwas, meist in Composs.; J: 382b: the space over, above a thing; superior, better, preferable.

(Thomas 1936: 282) sovereign; (Simon 1941: 378) OT *lay* ~ *lañ* 'to rise' / *Idañ*; the old pronunciation was **dla* - **dlañ*; ~ *bla* 'above' < **dla*; p. 379: It may be that this secondary form is identical with *la* in the meaning 'pass' or 'mountain' which would then be 'the top (which can be passed)' ~ *ltag* (< **tlag*); p. 380: ~ *ltañ* 'bale, load' (= what is loaded upon) ~ *blag* *'to raise, prick one's ears'; *la* as a suffix 'above, upon, on top'; (Macdonald 1971: 217) chef;

¹⁸³ Cf. also (Bogoslovskij 1972: 140); (Dotson 2009b: 58).

(Stein 1983: 101) signifie 'supérieur, chef' (p. ex. PT 1038 = *rje*) et désigne souvent le roi ou son administration; (Richardson 1985: 171) above, uppermost; (Li and Coblin 1987: 433) over, above, superior; head, commander; (Coblin 1991c: 100) over above, superior; commander; (Dotson 2007b: 16) authority; (Walter 2009: 97) government; p. 152, fn. 2: its original meaning was clearly that of *governing power*.

blon (#602) 'councillor'

(Thomas 1933: 382) councillor; (Tucci 1950: 61) a general title of all officials, whether it is employed alone or with other determinatives; (Róna-Tas 1955: 268) the terms *dku rgyal*, *blon po* and *žaṅ lon* all denote the feudal aristocracy; the expression *dku rgyal* indicates belonging to the royal court, the *blon po* term denotes the real or titular ministerial rank, while *žaṅ lon* (*žaṅ blon*) marked the group of aristocrats built up on the avuncular system; (Uray 1960a: 206) Ratsherr; (Takeuchi 1994a: 578) Khot. *bulunä*; (Walter 2009: 280, fn. 48) *b-lon* 'one who has the function of, or acts as, minister'; [*l*] *lon* 'notice, message'; p. 281, fn 48: *Perhaps* the first and most important function of the *blon-pos* was to bring intelligence and messages back and forth among clans, local leaders, and the court; (Walter and Beckwith 2010: 539) by form an adjective based on the root *blon*, which seems likely to be derived from the Old Tibetan verb *lon-* 'to send', making *blonpo* originally an adjective meaning 'missive, one who is sent', or 'emissary [of the emperor]'.

The OLT monosyllabic lexeme *blon* 'councillor' corresponds to CT *blon po* 'officer (prop[erly] counsellor), any magisterial officer of higher rank; more particularly minister (of state)' (J: 385); compare, for instance, *ra saṅ rjeṅi blon rid stag rhya* (PT 1288: 24) 'Rid-stag-rhya, the councillor of the lord of the Ra-saṅ'. I assume that it is a cognate of the OLT verb *blod* 'to confer, discuss', cf.:

(1)

dmaḡ pon sus bya žes blod na // (205) seṅ go myi čhen gyis // kho bos rño thog čhes khas blaṅs so // (PT 1287)

When [they] were discussing who should be made general, Seṅ-go-myi-čhen claimed 'I am capable.'

(2)

gžan glo ba ydriṅ bar sems pa daṅ blod re / (PT 1287: 290)

[We] shall never confer with others who think of becoming disloyal.

(3)

rje blon blod blod de // lig myi rhya yī srid brlag go // (PT 1287)

Lords and councillors, having conferred, destroyed the dominion of Lig Myi-rhya.

I assume that both *blon* and *blod* were derived from the noun *blo*, CT '1understanding; 2mind, thought, memory; 3mind, sentiment, disposition' (J: 384b). The original meaning of *blo* could have been 'advice, counsel' as suggested by the synonymic compound *blo gros* and confirmed in the following passage:

(4)

de yī che blon po srid byed pa yī rnam s kyaṅ / (370) blo mthun gros gčhig ste // pyī yi dgraḡ byuṅ ba la / thabs daṅ ye myig čher byed / (PT 1287)

At that time, also councillors who were ruling, being unanimous [in their] advices [and] of one counsel, were greatly using [their] eagle eyes and means against external enemies who occurred.

Accordingly, the etymological meaning of *blon* would have been *'advising one'.

It seems possible that the lexeme *blo* itself was derived from *lo* 'information; report'¹⁸⁴ (see s.v.) by means of the nominal prefix *b-*:

According to the OTA-I, the following official activities can be unanimously ascribed to councillors:

- administration of the *Žaň-zuň* (ITJ 750: 64) and *Ya-ža* (ITJ 750: 291)
- marching to the *Dru-gu* land (ITJ 750: 67–8, 94, 97) and *Bru-ža* land (ITJ 750: 276–7)
- convening a council alone or with other officials (ITJ 750: 75, 76–7, 92, 116–7, 140–1, 196, 198–9, 200, 204–5, 207–8, 210–1, 212–3, 215–6, 217, 222–3, 226, 231, 233–4, 235, 247, 298, 303–4)
- fighting a battle (ITJ 750: 252–3)
- conquering *Khri-ša-čan* (ITJ 750: 270)

The relative position of a councillor in the social hierarchy can sometimes be established from his mentions together with another person:

- grand councillor *Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu* – councillor *Mgar Khri-ybriň Bcan-brod* (ITJ 750: 77)
- *Khu Maň-po-rje Lha-zuň* – councillor *Maň-rčan Ldoň-ži* (ITJ 750: 140–1)
- *žaň Bcan-to-re Lhas-byin* – councillor *Khri-sum-rje Rcaň-bzer* (ITJ 750: 207, 210, 212, 215, 217)
- grand councillor *Xbro Čuň-bzaň Xor-maň* – councillor *Xbal Skyes-bzaň Ldoň-cab* (ITJ 750: 298, 303–4)

Apparently, a councillor had a position lower than a grand councillor and a *žaň*. Interesting is the ordering of *Khu Maň-po-rje Lha-zuň* and councillor *Maň-rčan Ldoň-ži*. The former became a grand councillor in winter 705/6 but the events narrated here are from winter 702/3. A hierarchy similar in structure is repeated in Or.8212/187: grand councillor *Xbro Čuň-bzaň Xor-maň* – *Xbal Skye-zaň Ldoň-cab* – councillor *Maň-po-rje* – *žaň Xbriň-rčan* (ll. 10–1). According to PT 1287: 111–2, *Xbal Skye-zaň Ldoň-cab* succeeded *Xbro Čuň-bzaň Xor-maň* as grand councillor but he is never called grand councillor in the OTA. The fact that both *Khu Maň-po-rje Lha-zuň* and *Xbal Skye-zaň Ldoň-cab* are mentioned before a councillor might

¹⁸⁴ A parallel semantic shift is observed in Eng. *counsel* '1[*g*]uidance or recommendations offered with regard to prudent future action; ³*archaic* [*mass noun*] [i]nformation; news' (<https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/advice>; 17.08.2017).

¹⁸⁵ For this etymology compare the English word-family *counsel*, *council*, *counsellor*, *councillor*, *consult*. A different etymology deriving *blon* from *lon* was proposed in (Walter 2009: 280, fn. 48) and repeated in (Walter and Beckwith 2010: 539). However, both publications overlooked an apparent cognate of *blon*, i.e. *blod*. This word-family is cognate with *lo* 'to be able', *zlo* (< **s-√lo*) 'to answer' and *γdo* (< **γ-√lo*) 'to say'; all derived from *√lo* 'to speak'.

suggest that the succession to the position of grand councillor was determined some time before the actual appointment.

In one single case a councillor became later a grand councillor; Mgar Khri-γbriñ Bcan-brod is mentioned as a councillor between 680/1 and 686/7, although already in 685/6 (ITJ 750: 91–2) he was nominated a grand councillor.

Beside councillors who seem to have been officials of the Tibetan Empire, the OTA-I also mention three other councillors: Rid-stag-rhya of the lord of the Ra-sañ (PT 1288: 24), as well as Čhog-ro Sña Žiñ-koñ and Lañ-gro Khoñ-rcañ of Kim-šeñ koñ čo (ITJ 750: 257).

blon čhe (#603) ‘grand councillor’

DTH: 30: le premier ministre; fn. 3: grand ministre; (Richardson 1952b: 136) Chief Minister; (Chang 1959: 130) prime minister; (Uray 1960b: 33) Great Councillor; (Richardson 1990b: 52) Chief Minister; (Denwood 1999: 283) great minister; (Dotson 2009b: 84) Chief Minister.

In the OTA-I, the title is attested in two variants: *blon č(h)e* and *blon čhen p(h)o*. They seem to have a clear temporal distribution. *blon č(h)e* occurs regularly from 652 to 667, and additionally in 684 and 689–696, whereas from 680 to 746 *blon čhen p(h)o* dominates, with the exception of the few years at the end of the 7th century in which *blon čhe* recurs. We could conclude that *blon č(h)e* was an older version that has been replaced by *blon čhen p(h)o* by the end of the seventh century. However, *blon č(h)e* recurs in Or.8212/187 where it is used interchangeably with *blon čhen p(h)o*. *blon čhe* is the only form known to PT 1287 and PT 1072, whereas in PT 1071 we again find both. Maybe *blon čhe* remained in use after *blon čhen p(h)o* had been introduced, but was relegated to a less official or unofficial speech register.

According to the OTA-I, the activities of a grand councillor encompassed:

- Subjugation of Glo-bo and Rcañ-rhyaγ (PT 1288: 21)
- Organisation of hunts (PT 1288: 23–4, 31–2)
- Convening a council (PT 1288: 27; ITJ 750: 76, 77, 78–9, 81–2, 84–5, 86–7, 105–6, 157, 160–1, 164, 167, 168–9, 179–80, 181–2, 184–5, 186–7, 188, 191, 193–4, 200–1, 203–4, 205–6, 209, 214, 224, 225, 227, 230, 233, 234–5, 236, 239, 241, 250, 254, 260, 263–4, 266, 293–4, 298, 303–4)
- Writing of sovereign law (PT 1288: 29–30);
- Administration of the Žaň-žuň (PT 1288: 41–2), Xa-ža (ITJ 750: 123–4), and Mtoñ-sod (ITJ 750: 258)
- Marching to the Dru-gu land (ITJ 750: 97), Great and Small Coñ-ka (ITJ 750: 127), Xbu-šiñ-kun (ITJ 750: 196–7)
- Counting border guards (ITJ 750: 104)
- Bestowing the office of great *khud pa* (ITJ 750: 230)
- Swearing an oath to the *bcan po* (ITJ 750: 305–6)

The relative position of a councillor in the social hierarchy can be established from his mentions together with another person:

- *dbon*, the king of the Dags-po – grand councillor Dbays Khri-gzigs Žaň-ñen (ITJ 750: 160–1, 184–5, 186–7, 188, 196–7)

- *dbon* Bcan-zuñ, the king of the Dags-po – grand councillor Dbays Khri-gzigs Žaň-ñen (ITJ 750: 179–80)
- grand councillor Dbays Khri-gzigs Žaň-ñen – *žaň* Bcan-to-re Lhas-byin – *žaň* Khri-bzaň Stag-cab (ITJ 750: 220–1)
- grand councillor Xbro Čuň-bzaň Xor-mañ – councillor Xbal Skyes-bzaň Ldoň-cab (ITJ 750: 298, 303–4)

The hierarchy might be sketched as: *dbon*, the king of the Dags-po¹⁸⁶ – grand councillor – *žaň* – councillor.

From ITJ 750: 91–2, we learn that a councillor (Mgar Khri-ybriň Bcan-brod) could be promoted to a grand councillor. However, the most common promotions concern people who did not held a councillor position before:

- Khu Maň-po-rje Lha-zuň (ITJ 750: 154)
- Dbays Khri-gzigs Žaň-ñen (ITJ 750: 155)
- Dbays Khri-sum-rje Rcaň-bžer (ITJ 750: 223)
- Rñegs Maň-žam Stag-cab (ITJ 750: 237–8)
- Dbays Stag-sgra Khoň-lod (ITJ 750: 244)
- Xbro Čuň-bzaň Xor-mañ (ITJ 750: 249–50)

According to the OTA, the following persons held the position of a grand councillor in the period covered by the *Annals*:¹⁸⁷

Mgar Stoň-rcaň Yul-zuň	652/3 ? –667/8	PT 1288: 21–48
Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu	680/1 ?–685/6	ITJ 750: 76–91
Khu Maň-po-rje Lha-zuň	705/6	ITJ 750: 154
[Mgar] Khri-ybriň Bcan-brod	685/6–698/9 ?	ITJ 750: 92–127
Dbays Khri-gzigs Žaň-ñen	705/6–721/2	ITJ 750: 155–220
Dbays Khri-sum-rje Rcaň-bžer	721/2–725/6	(ITJ 750: 223–36
Rñegs Maň-žam Stag-cab	725/6–727/8	ITJ 750: 238–44
Dbays Stag-sgra Khoň-lod	727/8–728/9	ITJ 750: 245
Xbro Čuň-bzaň Xor-mañ	728/9–746/7 ?	ITJ 750: 250–303
Dbays Snaň-bžer Zla-brcaň	757/8–764/5 ?	Or.8212/187: 25–58 ¹⁸⁸
Mgos Khri-bzaň Yab-lag	764/5–?	Or.8212/187: 60

The OTA do not record any reason for a removal from the position of grand councillor other than one's death. But if we compare this list with the respective fragment of the list of councillors provided in the OTC, we find an interesting regularity:

OTA	OTC
1. Mgar Stoň-rcaň Yul-zuň	Mgar Stoň-rcaň Yul-zuň

¹⁸⁶ According to PT 1286: 18–9, kings of the Dags-po were so-called petty kings (*rgyal phran*).

¹⁸⁷ Years marked with the question mark concern the first or the last mention of the person as great councillor but no appointment or death are reported.

¹⁸⁸ According to Or.8212/187: 58–9, Dbays Snaň-bžer Zla-brcaň was appointed great councillor in 764/5 but the text refers to him by the title as early as in 757/8.

2. Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu	Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu
3. Khu Mañ-po-rje Lha-zuñ	Khu Mañ-po-rje Lha-zuñ
4. Mgar Khri-γbriñ Bcan-brod	Dbays Khri-gzigs Žaň-ñen
5. Dbays Khri-gzigs Žaň-ñen	Mgar Khri-γbriñ Bcan-brod
6. Dbays Khri-sum-rje Rcaň-bžer	Dbays Khri-sum-rje Rcaň-bžer
7. Rñegs Mañ-žam Stag-cab	Rñegs Mañ-žam Stag-chab
8. Dbays Stag-sgra Khoň-lod	Dbays Stag-sgra Khoň-lod
9. Xbro Čhuň-bzaň Xor-mañ	Xbro Čhuň-bzaň Xor-mañ
10. {Xbal Skyes-bzaň Ldoň-chab}	Xbal Skye-zaň Ldoň-chab
11. Dbays Snaň-bžer Zla-brcan	Dbays Snaň-bžer Zla-brcan
12. Mgos Khri-bzaň Yab-lag	Mgos Khri-bzaň Yab-lag

Apart from 4 and 5 whose order is reversed in the OTC, the lists agree but on one person: Xbal Skyes-bzaň Ldoň-chab. In 755/6, his servants were banished and wealth confiscated (Or.8212/187: 12–6). Therefore he must have been appointed grand councillor somewhere between 746/7 (in this year Xbro Čhuň-bzaň Xor-mañ was still a grand councillor) and 755/6. As I argue in (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming)), Xbal Skyes-bzaň Ldoň-chab might have been grand councillor already in 747/8.

With one exception (ITJ 750: 92), in the OTA-I grand councillors are appointed by the *bcan po* himself which fact is indicated by the verb: *bkaγ scald*. On the other hand, Or.8212/187 uses twice the verb *bčug* (ll. 59 & 60).

dbon (#600) ¹nephew; ²classificatory title'

[C] *sbon*

[V] *γbon*

J: 389a: ¹resp. for *cha bo*, grandson; nephew; ²Lama-servant; ³a certain sect of Lamas, clad in red, shorn, and married; ⁴a Lama skilled in astrology, who for instance, when a person has died, performs those ceremonies, that serve to avert harm from the survivors

(Benedict 1942: 329) resp. sibling's child, grandchild; p. 330: = *cha*; (Tucci 1950: 58) son in law; p. 63: nephew; (Uebach 1980: 304) in Old Tibetan texts there is no genealogical evidence for *dbon* meaning 'sister's son' or 'brother's son'. In Old Tibetan, *dbon* with this meaning is almost inseparable from the term *žaň* and the pair of terms *dbon-žaň* occurs repeatedly; it is from the Chinese text of the inscription (Sino-Treaty Inscription – JB) that the meaning *dbon* 'nephew on the mother's side' or 'sister's son' has been deduced; p. 305: in Old Tibetan generally there is no testimony to a distinction being made between *myes* 'grandfather and great grandfather' or 'ancestor', or between *dbon* 'grandchild and great grandchild'; the kinship term *dbon* 'grandchild' as well as 'sister's son, son-in-law and husband', the meaning of the latter being mainly based on the equation with the Chinese *cheng*, is used in Old Tibetan only for the kings and the Xa-ža. Concerning *dbon* 'grandchild' it remains reserved to the kings in later literature too, whereas *dbon* 'sister's son' in the later period is used as an honorific term for common *cha bo*, also for 'brother's son'; p. 306: the collateral relationship is expressed by the antecedent *dbon* in names; *dbon* 'sister's son' in Old Tibetan was reserved to the royal family. After the collapse of the Tibetan kingdom it was taken over to denote respectfully within the clergy famous 'nephews', father's sister's sons as well as father's brother's sons, of renowned uncles. Thus *dbon* even became part of the name of some religious men; p. 307: the *dbon rgyud* has survived to denote royal descendants; many prominent families of Tibet trace their origins back to the Tibetan kings; these distant relatives of the Tibetan kings used the term *dbon*, for in absence of a common dynastic name

what expression could better denote their royal descent that this term for grandchild and nephew, implying both direct and collateral royal descendants?; (Coblin 1991c: 100) nephew; (Yamaguchi 1992: 58) ‘grandchild’, rendered in Chinese as *sheng* 甥 (‘nephew/niece’, ‘son/daughter-in-law’, ‘grandchild’); (Uebach 1997a: 61) = *γbon*; (Dotson 2009a: 224) *dbon* designates not only son-in-law and bride-receiver, but can also extend to his descendants; p. 235, fn. 3: like its non-honorific equivalent *cha*, can indicate not only uterine nephews, but parallel cousins and cross-cousins, as well as grandsons; (Dotson 2009b: 59) bride-receiver; p. 260: bride-receiver in relation to bride-giver (*žan*); son-in-law; nephew

The OTA-I is the only OLT document in which *dbon* alternates with *γbon*. That these are mere variants is confirmed by doublets like: *γbon da rgyal khri zuñ* (ITJ 750: 63 & 98) ~ *dbon da rgyal khri zuñ* (ITJ 750: 100) and *γbon γa ža rje* (ITJ 750: 245) ~ *dbon γa ža rje* (Or.8212/187: 5). Since in the OTA-I at least three different kings of the Dags-po (*da rgyal*) are called *γbon/dbon* (see s.v. *da rgyal*), it is conspicuous that the lexeme had a classificatory value and was not used as a mere kinterm (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))). The variant *γbon* is known only from the OTA-I and seems to be secondary as suggested by the form *dbon* preserved in the compound *žan dbon* (ITJ 750: 245) ‘maternal uncle and nephew’. Nevertheless, the fact remains that in the OTA-I *γbon* is used much more frequently than *dbon* with ratio 13 : 2. The question is then: why should have *dbon* been written as *γbon*?

I think the solution might be sought in regular sound changes that must have occurred prior to the first usage of *γbon* in the OTA-I and have influenced the orthography. The hypothesis is that the onset *γb-* represents a step towards the labial [w] that some time later started to be written as a digraph *γw-* (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))). The process of labialisation can be sketched as: *db-* [db-] > *γb-* [γb-] > [γ^w-] > [w]. That this change must have occurred very early is attested by dialectal data. The modern reflexes of LT *db-* are:¹⁸⁹

WAT	[∅] / [w]
WIT	[ø]
CtrT	[ø] / [w̄] / [ɣ̄v] (Western Drokpas)
ST	[w̄]
HT	[ø]
KT	[ø] / [w̄] / [ɣw]
AT	[ɣ] / [γ] / [ɣw] / [γw] ¹⁹⁰

An interesting case is Balti [γbus] (LT *dbus*) ‘central pillar (of different materials in mosques, houses, etc.)’ (CDTD: 5849). Balti [γb-] and AT [γw-] confirm the proposed stages of the sound change. Moreover, Balti [γb-] supports the explanation of *γbon* put forward above and indicates that the sound change [db-] > [γb-] must have occurred in EOT. AT [γw] attests to the next shift in the chain, that apparently occurred in MOT and was inherited by AT dialects. *γbon* occurs in the OTA-I between years 675 and 727 with the exception of 688 and 690 in which reports *dbon* is used. Between 727 and ca. 764 not only orthographic standardisation

¹⁸⁹ The juxtaposition is based on a survey of nominal stems from CDTD: 5817–5854. Different reflexes are attested for *dba rlabs* ~ *rba rlabs* (CDTD: 5815), *dbag pa* (CDTD: 5816), *dbu ba* ~ *lbu ba* (CDTD: 5832), and partially also *dbug* (CDTD: 5840). Hence I have omitted the data which suggest distinct etymology.

¹⁹⁰ As demonstrated by (Hill 2006b), AT [ɣ] is an areal feature.

must have been carried out but also *dbon* fused with *sbon*.¹⁹¹ The latter point is evidenced by the compound *sras dbon* (Žol N 12) ‘son or grandson’ in which *dbon* has taken over the meaning ‘grandson’ previously reserved for *sbon* (see s.v.) as is also the case in *dbon sras* ‘descendants’ of PT 1287: 289. As I have pointed out above, the variant *dbon* is also attested in year 745 (Or.8212/187: 5) but the latter manuscript is not a reliable source for linguistic generalisations due to its multiple scribal errors. Concluding, this discussion has unanimously established the identity of *dbon* and *ȳbon*.¹⁹²

In (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming)), I speculate that *dbon* was derived from **bo* ‘?’ by means of the circumfix *d–n*. It is historically related to *sbon* (see sv.).

dbyañs (#353) TR [AGT]_{ERG} (?) [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to clarify’

dbyañs seems to have been a technical term frequently used in judicial texts in conjunction with *bčad* ‘decided’ or *žal če* ‘sentence’. On the other hand, in PT 1283 it co-occurs with the verb *bslab/bslabs* (v1 *slob* ‘to learn; to teach’) in two forms: *dbyañ* and *sbyañ(s)*. It takes the form *dbyañ* with the v3 *bslab*, indicating that *dbyañ* was a v3-stem either. The existence of v2 *dbyañs* and v3 *dbyañ* proves that the verb was transitive and that *d-* belonged to the stem. On these grounds I relate *dbyañs* to LT *sbyoñ* ‘to exercise, to practise; to study’. In (Bialek 2016: 150f.) and (Bialek 2020a: 317, fn. 135), I reconstructed the prefix *d-/g-* that seems to have derived control verbs from non-control verbs (see also (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))). In the case of $\sqrt{dbjañ}$ and $\sqrt{sbyañ}$ we have two verbs derived from $\sqrt{bjañ}$ by means of the ‘control’ prefix *d-* and the causative prefix *s-*, respectively.¹⁹³ Since the verb *dbyañs/dbyañ* (v1 **dbyoñ?*) is not attested in LT, I assume that it merged with *sbyoñ*. The use of *dbyañ(s)* in judicial contexts, always denoting an action that preceded the final decision, (*bčad*), and on the other hand its co-occurrence with *bslab*, suggest the meaning ‘to clarify; to study’.¹⁹⁴

dbyard (#605) ‘summer’

The form *dbyard* is used only as a simple lexeme. When forming part of a compound it is replaced by *dbyar*, with one exception: the erroneous *dbyard duñ* for **dbyar ȳdun* (ITJ 750: 114).

dbyar stod (#606) ‘the onset of summer’

< **dbyard kyi stod*, lit. ‘the upper part of summer’ (cf. also s.v. *-stod*).

¹⁹¹ The confusion continues in modern dictionaries which gloss only *dbon* but in two meanings: ‘grandson’ and ‘nephew’; see J: 389a and (Uebach 1980: 301).

¹⁹² As against Richardson’s assertion that “*ȳbon ȳa ža* (which must be distinguished from *bdon* (sic! for *dbon* – JB)) [...] seem to have been a tribe or section of the *ȳa-ža*” (Richardson 1967: 19, fn. 8).

¹⁹³ Since the onset cluster *!rby-* is not allowed in OLT, an issue to be clarified in future is whether *dby-* either has not merged with PT **rby-*, or does not represent the latter.

¹⁹⁴ The present analysis supersedes the reconstruction put forward in (Bialek 2018a: 439, fn.3).

dbyar ydun (#607) 'summer council'

< **dbyard kyi ydun ma*, lit. 'council of the summer'. The first summer council is reported in 686/7 (ITJ 750: 95).

dbyar smad (#608) 'the end of summer'

< **dbyard kyi smad*, lit. 'the lower part of summer'.

dbye (#704) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [PAT]_{ABS} 'to divide'

ybañs (#599) 'subjects'

(Lalou 1955: 194) les sujets; (Uray 1960b: 45, fn. 26) subjects (or the store-house?); (Haarh 1969: 447, fn. 2) *ybañs* seems to be Tibetans living in the old feudal state which was created around the Yar luñ Dynasty. It is relate to the word *dbañ*, *dbañ po*, and it means 'those under the power'; (Coblin 1991c: 100) ordinary subjects, the common people; (Takeuchi 1995: 63) commoners; p. 223: usually translated as '(free) subjects, commoners'. But, since the tax was imposed on each household, this 'bañs actually refers to a household or its head; householders; (Richardson 1998h: 162, fn. 10) subjects; (Dotson 2009b: 68) indicate anyone who is subject to the *bcan-po*; subject.

In (Bialek 2018a: 2.334ff.) I argued that *ybañs* was formed as a collective term by means of the collective -s from the reconstructed verb **ybañ* 'to have sth./sb. under one's feet', itself a denominal formation derived from *bañ* *¹foot, leg; ²basis, foundation'.

ybul skyems (#464) 'HON an offering drink, libation'

ybyuñ yjug (#466) 'replacing'

ybyor (#754) INTR [THEM]_{ABS} 'to agree (COM with)'

There is a confusion in the lexicographical sources on CT concerning the root vowel of the verb. Jäschke (399a) provides two forms: *ybyor* ($\sqrt{N}bjor$) and *ybyar* ($\sqrt{N}bjar$), but only the latter can be cognate with CT *sbyor* (\sqrt{sbjar}). A detailed textual survey would be necessary to disentangle not only the forms but also the original meanings of the two verbs.

ybrug (#594) '(calendric) dragon'

ybrum bu (#467) 'small-pox'

ybrum bu is derived from *ybrum*, CT ¹grain, minute particle; ²pustule, pock' (J: 401b), by means of the diminutive suffix -*bu*. The original meaning of *ybrum* seems to have been *'grain, corn' and the lexeme could be cognate with *ybru*, CT 'grain, corn, seed; ²a single grain, piece, letter; ³collectively, grain, corn' (J: 401a).¹⁹⁵ We can speculate that *ybrum* came into being by clipping

¹⁹⁵ For further cognates, see (Bialek 2018a: 2.301f.)

from **ybru ma*. However, the latter form does not seem to be attested in OLT although one finds it in CT (see BCRD) and in modern Jirel [d̥uma] ‘unhusked millet’ (CDTD: 5992).¹⁹⁶

ybrog (#597) ‘summer pastures’

ybrog mkhos (#471) ‘administration of summer pastures’

The underlying structure of the compound *ybrog gi mkhos*, lit. ‘necessaries of summer pastures’, is attested in the OTA (ITJ 750: 172).

ybrog sog (#468) ‘summer pastures and straw-lands’

sbon (#472) ‘HON grandson’

[C] *dbon*

In the OTA-I, three kinterms very similar in form are attested: *sbon*, *dbon*, and *ybon*. The last two are variants of one lexeme (see s.v. *dbon*) from which the first one should be distinguished. *sbon* as a kinterm is a *dis legomenon* known only from the OTA-I (see OTD). The first quotation (PT 1288: 18) comes from the annual entry of 650/1. There is no doubt that Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rcan, called here *sbon*, was the grandson of Khri Sroñ-rcan, called in this passage *myes*. The report from 707/8 (ITJ 750: 163) concerns the grandmother Khri-ma-lod and her grandson Rgyal-gcug-ru, the son of Khri Xdus-sroñ who died in 704/5. Again, *sbon* clearly denotes a male descendant of Khri-ma-lod in the second line. *sbon* is used here in reference to *phyi*. Thus, the proposed meaning ‘grandson’ is ascertained.

I tentatively reconstruct the term as *s+bo+n. For details, on the derivational processes and the root **bo*, see s.v. *dbon*.

sbyard (#707) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} (?) [THEM]_{ABS} ‘¹to arrange; ²to fix’

sbrul (#598) ‘(calendric) snake’

(Beckwith 2008b: 189) Old Tibetan *sbrul* ‘snake’ (reflecting non-oralised OChi *s-mrul ~ *s-mreul) and OBur *mrwiy* both reflect a Chinese *(s)mreul, so they were certainly borrowed from Old Chinese dialect forms of 虺 *huī* ‘viper’, not directly from 蛇 *shé* ‘snake’; p. 193: OTib *sbrul* and OBur *mrwiy* ‘snake’ [...] reflect two different Old Chinese dialect forms; they are loanwords that must have been independently borrowed from Old Chinese; (Jacques 2014a: 163) *smrul (Burm. *mrwe*¹) > *smbrul > *sbrul*.

In (Bialek 2018a: 2.558, fn.1) I related *sbrul* to the word-family of *sprul* and *yphrul*, among others, suggesting that its etymological meaning might have been *‘moulting one, moulter’; cf. Tabo [t̥yl] (LT *ybrul*) ‘to scale off (skin)’ (CDTD.V: 923).

¹⁹⁶ Cf. also ¹‘a single grain of barley or grain’ (Gs: 771c).

m

mañ po (#614) 'many'

man čhad (#709) 'RN 'what is down'; ^{||}POSTP 'downward'

mas (#619) **Adv** 'down'

J: 412a: the lower part, gen[erally] however with terminative meaning, downward, towards the lower parts; backward, last.

(Simon 1941: 387) < **ma+sa/so* 'below-place'; (Richardson 1985: 172) from below, the last; (Li and Coblin 1987: 289) (those) below; from below.

The phrase *bog la nas mas byuñ* (ITJ 750: 79) can literally be rendered as 'occurred (lit. came out) down from the Bog pass'. *mas* here is an adverb that qualifies the verb *byuñ*. An analogous adverbial usage of *yas* is attested in the Rkoñ-po inscription:

(1)

gčen kar po nī / thog ma yas gśegs paḡi che // mčhed gñīs kyī / sku bla gñan po gsol ba dañ / sku bla de mo dañ bśos pa (7) *ḡī lha bdag bgyīd* [...]

As regards the elder brother Kar-po, when [he] first came **up**, [he] propitiated the fierce tutelary deity of both brothers and became the master of gods living with the tutelary deity De-mo.

All previous studies read 'from above' for *yas* (cf. (Haarh 1969: 154), (Richardson 1985: 67), (Uebach 1985b: 27),¹⁹⁷ (Li and Coblin 1987: 205), (Walter 2009: 101), (Dotson 2013a: 114), (Hill 2013a: 172), (Hill 2015a: 53), (Bialek 2018a: 1.302)). However, if we consider the parallelism between the two passages, it appears self-evident that *mas* and *yas* were equivalents and both should be translated either as 'to-directive' or 'from-directive' (i.e. ablative) adverbs. Since the ablative meaning 'from' is clearly ruled out in ITJ 750, we are left with the interpretation of *mas* and *yas* as 'to-directive' adverbs: 'towards the lower place; down' and 'towards the upper place; up', respectively.¹⁹⁸ *mas* in ITJ 750: 79 denotes the point at which Gnubs Mañ-ñen Bži-brcan and Mgar Mañ-žam Stag-cab occurred having crossed the Bog pass; they came out in a place that was located below the pass, i.e. they occurred down the Bog pass.

mol čen (#620) 'great conferral'

(Chang 1959: 135) a great consultation (after a military campaign); (Uray 1962a: 225) a great conference; (Dotson 2009b: 260) great consultation; (Dotson 2013a: 107) great conferral.

¹⁹⁷ Ger. *von oben*.

¹⁹⁸ In this context we can recall the use of *mar* and *yar* as adverbs with verbs of motion in modern Central Tibetan (cf. (Samuels 2014b: 229)).

The compound *mol čen* (< **mol čhen po*) is a *dis legomenon* known only from the OTA-II.

mun mag (#473) 'border guards'

myi (#757) 'human'

myi rta (#755) 'man and horse'

Additively coordinated compound (see (Bialek 2018a: 1.181ff.))

myes (#618) 'HON grandfather'

In the entry 650/1, *myes* is contrasted with *sbon*. The former is used with reference to Khri Sroñ-rčan, whereas the latter to Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rčan. From other OLT sources (cf. PT 1286: 62–4), we know that Khri Sroñ-rčan (PT 1286: 62: Sroñ-lde-brčan) was the grandfather of Khri Mañ-slon Mañ-rčan (PT 1286: 64: Mañ-slon Mañ-rčan) – the son of Guñ-sroñ Guñ-rčan. The latter is not mentioned in the *Annals*.

dmag (#615) 'army'

dmag dpon (#616) 'general'

(Francke 1914b: 44) army officer; (Thomas 1933: 380) army-commander; DTH: 38: général; p. 62: army commander; (Tucci 1950: 62) military officers; (Lalou 1955: 180) le chef d'armée; (Tucci 1956b: 87) military officer; (Chang 1959: 130) military commander; (Uray 1960b: 31) army commander; (Uray 1980: 310) military head; (Uray 1990b: 429) = Ch. *jiedushi*; (Takeuchi 1995: 30) general; the general mentioned must have been the head of the Kwa ču *khrom* at that time; p. 230: the head of a *khrom* ('the military district government'); (Takeuchi 2004b: 55b) the highest-ranking military officer; (Iwao 2007: 212) general; (Dotson 2009b: 39) general.

< **dmag gi dpon* 'head of an army'; for *dpon* see (Bialek 2018a: 1.544).

dmag myi (#474) 'soldier'

< **dmag gi myi*, lit. 'person of the army'. The compound should be distinguished from *myi dmag* (ITJ 737-1: 286) 'army of men' which is juxtaposed with *spreyu dmag* 'army of monkeys' in the text.

dmар po (#617) 'red'

In the OTA, *dmар po* is used attributively with two nouns: *žugs loñ* 'beacon station' and *khram* 'tally'. The connotations of the attribute phrases are not certain but it seems that *dmар po* had a purely classificatory function here. It might have been used to point to a military denotation of the respective term (cf. (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))).

dmey (#711) 'family conflict'

DSM: 660a: mi gcañ ba bcog paḡi miñ ste.

DTH: 36, fn. 3: souillure, homicide; (Karmay 1998-2005: 383) *dme*, 'impurity', refers more particularly to the type of impurity incurred by murder, especially of a member belonging to the same family or clan. p. 384: homicide/fratricide; (Orosz 2003: 24) armed conflict between family members; (Bellezza 2008: 232) contamination caused by murder of relatives, incest; (Dotson 2009b: 95, fn. 183) generally applies to incest, but it also extends to another transgression between blood relatives, namely, fratricide; can also refer to impurity between members of religious fraternities; the term has a slightly different meaning in Rebkong where fratricide is called *nañ dme*. There the term *dme*, or rather *dme bo*, refers to an outsider who kills a member of one's family (personal communication, Dongzhi Dorje); p. 260: incest, fratricide, problems between confrères.

According to ITJ 750: 90–1, persons involved in the *dmey* were from the same family: Mgar. Therefore, we can assume that *dmey* denoted family affairs. The next event recorded in the OTA concerns the death of Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu, although he is said to have died (*gum*) and not to have been killed (*bkum*), so that it is not certain that his death was caused by the *dmey*. Chinese sources mention Mgar Bcan-sña Ldom-bu (Ch. Zànxīruò 贊悉若) but not Mgar Mañ-žam Stag-cab as son of Mgar Stoñ-rcan Yul-zuñ (Garatti 2015). It seems therefore that *dmey* denoted a violent conflict within a family, but was most probably not restricted to fratricide.

dme(y) is never palatalised in OLT as opposed to its cognate *sme* ~ *smye* (for details, see (Bialek 2018a: 1.327f.))

rmas (#756) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [ADDR]_{ABS} 'to enquire'

The arguments structure of the verb is confirmed in the following two passages:

(1)

rgyal pos rmas pa las // (ITJ 737-1: 179; *apud* OTDO)

The king enquired.

(2)

chugs phon rmas pa las // (PT 1096: r23)

[One] enquired the head of the encampment.

C

ce čī (#356)

Title of an official (?) in Se-ču (Or.8212/187: 22). Maybe from Ch. *cì-shǐ* 刺史 ‘provincial governor’ (MDBG):

	(Baxter and Sagart 2014)	(Schuessler 2007)
<i>cì</i> 刺	MC <i>tshjeH</i>	OC *[ts ^h]ek-s
<i>shǐ</i> 史	MC <i>sriX</i>	OC *s-rəʔ
		LH ts ^h ie ^C
		LH ʂə ^B
		OCM *tshekḥʂ
		OCM *srəʔ

(Bailey 1951: 24) identified Ch. *cì-shǐ* with Tib. *čhi śi*.

gcañ (#799) ‘dependent member of a household’

From its position in ITJ 750: 217, where *gcañ* forms one NP together with *żañ lon*, we can infer that it must have been either a noun or an adjective, eligible of modifying a noun (*żañ lon*) with a human referent. Similarly, in two OLT compounds *gcañ* is a noun and has a human referent:

gcañ č(h)en: ‘fonctionnaire supprimé à la suite de la suppression des districts’ (Lalou 1955: 195); ‘an official of lower rank than those who held letters of various degree’ (Richardson 1998e: 138, fn. 21); ‘an official title just behind the twelve ranks, which were provided in the regime of the ancient Tibetan Empire’ (Takata 2006: 165); ‘describes a rank, and not a post; rank just below that of ministerial aristocracy’ (Dotson 2007b: 9 & 70); ‘appears to describe a rank, and not a post; from the rank of *gcañ čhen* downwards, kin are not included in one’s legal status. Below the rank of a *gcañ čhen*, this is probably also a practicality, as we are no longer dealing with ennobled aristocracy; rank in the ministerial hierarchy just below ministerial aristocracy (*żañ lon*)’ (Dotson 2009b: 61, fn. 84, pp. 63 & 260); ‘the Tibetan title *gcañ čhen* is likely to have been modeled on the Chinese *qing ping guan* or *qing guan* and was specifically created to honour Non-Tibetans as ‘great integer officials [in the service of the *bcan po*]’ (Uebach 2012: 61).

gcañ dkar: ‘independent interrogating officers; I understand *gcañ bkar* (sic), “honest (independent) interrogators”. Similarly in the phrase *dkar kyis čhañs*, “proved by interrogation”. *čhañ, chañ, chañs* [...] are apparently scribal variations’ (Richardson 1998h: 150, 161, fn. 4); ‘jurors; [in PT 1071 – JB] [t]welve jurors swear an oath, and are joined by one other, either the complainant or the accused, making thirteen who swear the oath. By employing this numeric formula of 12+1=13, the “jurors” are marked off as an explicit microcosm of Tibetan society. In this case, it is the “jurors” who decide the case, award the requisite blood money, and who appear to have the power to accept or reject any denials of guilt’ (Dotson 2007a: 217); ‘juror; similar to *gcañ mi*’ (Dotson 2007b: 10 & 70).

This *gcañ* seems to be identical with *gcañ* in:

(1)

blon snañ bzañ (26) *γdus koñ gi bu cha γphel rgyud dmañs kyi rnam s kyañ gcañ* (27) [*da*]ñ *stoñ las scogs pa sgor bde bayī nams / żañ lon yī ge* (28) *čan gyi thañ du gnañ ba dañ /* (Ẓwa E)

The descendants of the councillor Snañ-bzañ Xdus-koñ, even those among commoners, are granted good *sgors* such as *gcañ* and *stoñ*, among others, in the rank of aristocrats possessing letters.

Unfortunately, the meanings of *stoñ* and *sgor* in this context are likewise unknown but it is clear that both were nouns. The available transliterations of the inscription all read *sgor*,¹⁹⁹ which is also clearly visible on Plate 8 in (Richardson 1985). Maybe a meaning similar to *‘suite; staff’ was intended?²⁰⁰ It is interesting that in (1) *gcañs* are supposed to have the same rank as aristocrats (*žañ lon*) while in the OTA *gcañ* is used in apposition to *žañ lon*, modifying the latter.

In terms of its history, we can be certain that in OLT *gcañ* was a distinct word than the proper name Rcañ used for a province of the Tibetan Empire but also for the river; in CT both are spelled as Gcañ. It seems also to have been a word etymologically distinct from *gcañ* ‘(to be clean)’. I propose relating the *gcañ* of concern here to *chañ* ‘¹nest; ²variously applied to human places of abode’ (J: 444a); for which compare also: ‘family, house; nest’ (Thargyal 2007: 35), Dingri [tʰāŋ] ‘nest, den, household’, Nangchen [tʰaŋ] ‘family’ (CDTD: 6743).²⁰¹ Noun *gcañ* was derived by the nominalising prefix *g-* to possibly denote members of a household, either dependent relative or maybe even non-relative. This may explain the collective character of *gcañ dkar* noticed by Dotson (see above); the latter term might have denoted members of a household appointed to a function related to judicial issues, whenever a member of the same extended household was called to a court. On this basis, I propose the tentative translation of *gcañ* as *‘dependent member of a household’ or *‘household resident’. This word seems to have been abandoned after the fall of the Tibetan Empire; we do not find its reflexes in later languages.

bcan po (#352)

(Bushell 1880: 440) They call a famous hero *tsan*, and man *p’u*, hence the title of the sovereign, *tsanp’u*; p. 538, fn. A: The title of the great *rgyal po*, *bcan po*, appears to be the equivalent of the Chinese *tsan-p’u*, which is explained to mean champion or hero, which agrees with the corresponding adjective defined as firm, strong; (Francke 1924a: 13) Ich halte es für durchaus möglich, daß die tibetischen Herrscher Zeit ihres Lebens *bcan po* (Majestät) genannt wurden, und daß erst nach ihrem Hinscheiden ihnen ein Name endgültig gegeben wurde, ähnlich, wie das bei den Chinesen geschah; (Thomas and Giles 1948: 754) the Chinese rendering *t’ien tzü* ‘Son of Heaven’; (Uray 1967a: 502) the Mighty One; (Richardson 1985: 173) the ruler of Tibet; (Li and Coblin 1987: 84) chin. translit.: *tsan-p’u*; [...] in this inscription the word mighty is consistently written as *brcan*, never as *bcan*, and the two are in fact scrupulously distinguished here. [...] it seems clear that *bcan* and *brcan* were distinct words in OT, though perhaps etymologically related. Wang (1982:44) suggests that *bcan po* is to be associated with *bcan*, a type of spirit or god in the indigenous religion, and this idea is worthy of further study; p. 442: title of the Tibetan king; (Walter and Beckwith 1997: 1041) The *bcan pos* of Tibet, both ‘mythological’ and historical, possessed numerous magical and martial accoutrements which display a steppe origin; (Dotson 2004: 76, fn. 2) a term reserved almost exclusively for the rulers of the Tibetan empire; it literally means something like ‘mighty one’, it is located hierarchically above other terms for rulers, such as king (*rgyal po*), ruler (*mñay bdag*) and so forth; (Walter 2009: 281, fn. 50) several times we find the phrase *myiyi rgyal po* in the inscriptions, but not *myiyi bcan po*: The principle function of the *bcan-*

¹⁹⁹ (Richardson 1985: 56); (Li and Coblin 1987: 271); (Iwao, Hill, and Takeuchi 2009: 21).

²⁰⁰ Cf. LT *skor ba*: Tabo [kōrpā] ‘person doing circumambulation’, Dingri [kōrā] ‘guardian’ (CDTD: 386).

²⁰¹ The word might be related to *ychañ* ‘to press into, to stuff’ (J: 457b).

po was as war leader and maintainer of a comitatus, while that of rgyal-po was as a day-to-day ruler; as we near the end of the Imperium, we can see rgyal-po begin to surpass bcan-po. This would have been a function of one or both factors: The growing influence of Buddhism at court, or the need for a ruler who was more an administrator and leader of an empire than a warrior/military leader; (Walter and Beckwith 2010: 537) emperor; p. 538: 'the one *legitimate* ruler over the entire world'; neither the title *bcanpo* in Tibetan nor the title 皇帝 *huangdi* in Chinese could be used for any other empire's ruler. The titles were unique and culturally specific; *bcanpo* is never, ever used in Tibetan, Chinese, or any other language for any other ruler except the Tibetan emperor; (Zeisler 2011a: 104) scion; p. 109: refers primarily to a group of siblings from the same mother.

A legal son of a Tibetan ruler; < $b+\sqrt{tsa+n_o}+po$, lit. 'born-he' (Bialek 2023a: 129f.)

bcan mo (#721)

DTH: 29: la princesse; (Uebach 1997a: 55) a) consort of the emperor, empress; b) daughter of the emperor, imperial princess; (Dotson 2009b: 32) grammatically the female equivalent of Bcan-po (Tibetan emperor), was used to refer to Tibetan princesses, that is, those ladies of the royal family who were eligible to contract dynastic marriages. Similarly, it was used to refer to foreign princesses who married in to the Tibetan royal line. [...] [P]rincess is a woman of the royal line who marries out, or a foreign bride who has married in.

In the OTA-I the term is used to refer to:

1. Foreign women married to the Tibetan *bcan po*:

bcan mo Mun-čan koñ čo, of Chinese origin, married to *bcan po* Khri Sroñ-rcan

bcan mo, the *ga tun*; apparently a woman of Turkic origin

bcan mo Kim-šan khoñ čo, of Chinese origin, married to *bcan po* Khri Lde-gcug-rcan

2. Tibetan women married to a foreign or dependent ruler:

bcan mo Sña-mo-steñs married to Sña-śur Spuñs-rye-rgyug, a ruler of the subjugated Žañ-zuñ

bcan mo Khri-mo-steñs sent to the Dags-po land, presumably to marry Khri-zuñ, the king of the Dags-po (*da rgyal*)

bcan mo Khri-bañs married to the ruler of the Xa-ža

3. Tibetan woman (most probably) married to a *bcan po*:

bcan mo Khri-mo-lan

bcan mo Mañ-mo-rje²⁰²

bcan mo Sña-mo-steñs was given in marriage to Sña-śur Spuñs-rye-rgyug in 671/2 and *bcan mo* Khri-bañs was married to the ruler of the Xa-ža in 689/90. Both marriages took place more than 20 years after the subjugation of the peoples. Therefore, they were not part of any marriage-alliance. None of the foreign *bcan mos* is known to have given birth to the heir to the throne (Bialek 2021c) but it has been argued that *bcan mo* Khri-bañs gave birth to the heir to the throne of the Xa-ža (see (Uray 1978) & (Uebach 1997a)). Thus, a Tibetan *bcan mo* could be sent to a dependent polity to bind it by kinship with the house of Tibetan *bcan pos*. On the other hand, foreign *bcan mos* did not have any impact on the Tibetan politics. The reason for that is that the Tibetan Empire was never subjugated or forced to acknowledge foreign political authority.

²⁰² Two distinct persons are called Mañ-mo-rje in the OTA-I (Bialek 2021c: 18. fn. 31). The first one bears the title *bcan mo* (ITJ 750: 124) and the second, *yum* (ITJ 750: 292).

The title itself is apparently formed by analogy with *bcan po*, as its feminine counterpart.²⁰³ It was given to an aristocratic woman (most probably of royal descent) who was to contract marriages with Tibetan or foreign rulers.²⁰⁴ An important difference between Tibetan *bcan mos* and *je bas* is that the former were married to lords of polities fully incorporated into the Tibetan Empire (Žaṅ-žuṅ, Dags-po, Ḥa-ža), whereas *je bas* were married to rulers of independent or semi-independent polities (Dur-gyis, Bru-ža; see s.v. *je ba*). I refrain from translating the title due to its native connotations that were distinct from those of the Eng. title *queen* or any other.

bcan yul (#23) ‘*bcan po*’s land’

bcugs (#621) TR [AGT]_{ERG} [PAT]_{ABS} ‘to establish’

The complete argument structure of the verb does not seem to be attested in OLT. In later lexicographical works the verb is unanimously glossed as TR/C EA (cf. CDTD.V: 1054, s.v. *yjugs*).

bcud (#622) TR [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to intern’

In modern Nangchen the verb is attested as cEA ‘to lock in; with *tson* to jail’ (CDTD.V: 1055), which is a specialised meaning of the more general ‘to put, to lay, into a box, into the grave’ (J: 466a). Since the OTA speaks of rebels (*log pho*), it is legitimate to assume that they were locked in for political reasons; thus the proposed rendering ‘interned’. The complete argument structure of the verb is not attested in OLT, but in later lexicographical works the verb is unanimously glossed as TR/C EA (cf. CDTD.V: 1055, s.v. *yjud*).

rcañ čhen pha (#475) ‘inhabitants of Great Rcañ’

The formation *rcañ čhen pa* (*[*rcañ čhen*]=*pa*, lit. ‘one affiliated to Rcañ-čhen (region)’) is a *hapax legomenon*. Red tallies, mentioned in the context of *rcañ čhen pa*, were issued on several occasions according to the OTA-I and were intended for the following target groups:

sku sruṅs gyi khram dmar pho (ITJ 750: 167) ‘red tally of life guards’

ru gsum gyi khram dmar pho (ITJ 750: 187) ‘red tally of the Three Horns’

dags poe khram dmar pho (ITJ 750: 208) ‘red tally of the Dags-po’

The first and the last examples agree that a red tally could be issued for a group of humans. The toponym Rcañ-čhen is attested independently in the OTA-I and there can be no doubt that *rcañ čhen pa* was derived from it to denote inhabitants of the region.

²⁰³ In (Bialek 2023a: 130) I reconstructed the etymological meaning of *bcan mo* as ‘a born-she’ (< **b+√cha+n+mo*).

²⁰⁴ I can’t see any indication that would support Uebach’s conclusion that *bcan mos* were ‘daughters of the emperor’ (Uebach 1997a: 60). In the OTC Sad-mar-kar, a sister of Khri Sroṅ-brcañ who married the Žaṅ-žuṅ ruler Lig Myi-rhya, is called *bcan mo* (PT 1287: 399). Here the pattern is confirmed: *bcan mo* was of royal descent and sent to marry a dependent ruler; but this is the only such case.

rcis (#623) 'account'

[C] *brcis*

In the OTA, *rcis* occurs in a fixed collocation with the light verb *bgyid*: *rcis bgyis* 'made an account'. I assume *rcis* was derived by conversion from the v4-stem of the verb *rci* 'to count' and its etymological meaning could be reconstructed as *'what is calculated'.

rcis mgo (#479) 'initial account'

< **rcis mgo nan*, lit. 'an account [which is] an incipit'. For a thorough analysis of the compound, see (Bialek 2018a: 2.409ff.)

scald (#712) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [REC/BEN]_{ABS} [THEM]_{ABS} 'HON to bestow'

[C] *ychal, gsold*

In the OTA-I, the verb *scald* is attested as a simple verb and in the collocations *bkaγ scald* and *bro scald*. The context of the clauses leaves no doubt that it was a *bcan po* acting as the agent of the verb. The clauses with the simple verb have the structure: 'HUM_{ABS} OBJECT_{ABS} *scald*', lit. '[one] bestowed HUMAN [with an] OBJECT'. The verb required two arguments in ABS: a human recipient and an inanimate theme (*bya sga* 'rewards', *yi ge* 'diploma'). The collocation *bro scald* differs in its argument structure in so far as it replaces the recipient with a beneficiary argument. Clauses with the collocation *bkaγ scald* all have the same structure: 'HUMAN_{ABS} *blon čhen p(h)or bkaγ scald*', lit. 'bestowed order [to] HUMAN as grand councillor' or, more freely, 'proclaimed HUMAN as grand councillor'. Also here does *scald* allow for two arguments in absolutive: HUMAN and *bkaγ* 'order'. The honorific *bkaγ* indicates that the subject of the verb was a *bcan po*.

Thus, *scald* is a di-transitive honorific verb. Its basic argument structure can be reconstructed as: S_{ERG} IO_{ABS} DO_{ABS} *scald*, lit. 'S bestowed DO on IO'. The arguments S and IO have human referents, in particular S has always a *bcan po* as its referent. The reconstructed argument structure (the subject argument is never overtly stated in the OTA) agrees with modern dialectal data; according to CDTD.V, LT *scol* is a cEDA verb in all surveyed dialects. Compare also the following OLT passages, in which, however, *scal* is a prototypical transitive verb with one object argument:

(1)

bcan po khri slon bcan gyīs / bkaγ stsal te / (PT 1287: 184)

bcan po Khri Slon-bcan issued an order.

(2)

(200) *γuñ nas / bcan po slon bcan gyīs // rcañ bod khyim ñi grī // zu ce glo ba ñe ba yi bya dgayr stsal to // (PT 1287)*

Thereafter, *bcan po* Slon-bcan gave twenty-thousand houses [of] Rcañ-Bod as a reward for (lit. of) the loyal Zu-ce.

Concerning its morphology, in OLT we find the following forms of the verb:

<i>scol</i>	<i>passim</i>
<i>scold</i>	<i>passim</i>
<i>scal</i>	<i>passim</i>
<i>scald</i>	<i>passim</i>
<i>bscal(d)</i>	PT 16: 29r2, 31v2; PT 1051: 26; ITJ 751: 40v1 ²⁰⁵

On this basis, the inflection of this OLT verb can be reconstructed as *scold*/**scald*/**scald*/*scold*, with the verb root $\sqrt{\text{stsald}}$.²⁰⁶ After a new pattern in *g-* had been introduced, v1 *scold* was replaced by *gsol* < *g-* + *scol*. The verb is cognate with *γchal* (see s.v.). In the light of the analysis presented s.v. *γchal*, the etymological meaning of *scald* can be reconstructed as *‘to let sb. beseech sth.’

scogs (#381) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘to cause to assemble’; *las scogs pa* ‘among others’

For a detailed textual analysis of the verb, its etymology, and the idiomatic phrase *las scogs pa* in OLT, see (Bialek 2022e).

brcigs (#624) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [PAT]_{ABS} ‘to build’

The verb *rcig/brcigs/brcig/rcigs* (all forms attested in OLT) is well-known in OLT and CT sources and there are no doubts concerning its general meaning which is given as ‘to build’ (J: 439a), i.e. to construct things (tomb structures, buildings, edifices) by putting construction elements together. In some modern dialects its meaning is more specific: ‘to build by laying bricks or stones’ (cf. CDTD.V: 991). In LT, it is a TR verb which fact is confirmed by modern dialects where *rcig* is unanimously glossed as a cEA verb. The argument structure is confirmed in the following OLT passage:

(1)

yul bkra śīs dbyar mo thañ de ga g.yul cal du // [blon čhen po žaṅ khri sum rje daṅ / žaṅ čhen po lha bzaṅ daṅ / bkay (41v2) γkhor daṅ bdag čag las scogs phas]_{ERG} [gcug lag khaṅ]_{ABS} brcīgs (PT 751)

In De-ga-g.yu-cal [of] the region Bkra-śīs Dbyar-mo-thañ, grand councillor žaṅ Khri-sum-rje, great žaṅ Lha-bzaṅ, [their] attendants, and ourselves, among others, built a monastery.

If we look for cognates of *rcig*, no lexemes appear to be straightforwardly related to the verb. However, CDTD proposes connecting it to the cEA verb *rceg/brcegs/brceg/rcegs* ‘¹to lay one thing on or over another, to pile up, stack up, build up; ²to tuck up’ (J: 440b).²⁰⁷ *rceg* is elucidated as a cEA verb with the basic meaning ‘to pile up, to heap up; to build by piling up

²⁰⁵ *gscal* attested in PT 367: v3 and ITJ 504: v2.2 should be read *gsal*. It is not related to the verbs discussed here.

²⁰⁶ *-d* seems to have belonged to the root. For instance, in the construction ‘V+/*par/ gnañ*’ ‘to allow/grant that V’, V always takes the v3 form. In the case of our verb, it is *scald*. It follows that *scald* was a v3-stem and *-d* formed part of the root.

²⁰⁷ Jäschke glosses *rceñ* as ‘to tuck up, truss up’ (J: 440b). It seems that the second meaning provided s.v. *rceg*, i.e. ‘to tuck up’, might have resulted from the confusion between the two verbs *rceg* and *rceñ*.

bricks, stones etc.’ in modern Tibetan dialects (cf. CDTD.V: 993). In addition, CDTD relates *rceg* and *rcig* to *gsog/bsags*, *gsog/bsogs*, and *γchag/γchags*. The word family of *rceg* can be reconstructed as:

The original meaning of the etymon \sqrt{sag} can be reconstructed as **‘to collect, to gather’**. Prefix *r-* of *rceg* and its specialised derivative *rcig* might have served to redirect the vector of the action from ‘horizontal’ gathering towards ‘vertical’ piling up, i.e. gathering things by heaping them up, one on the other. Thus: \sqrt{sag} ‘to gather’ > \sqrt{rceg} ‘to pile up’ > \sqrt{rcig} ‘to pile up bricks/stones etc.; to build’.

brcis (#625) TR [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ¹‘counted; ²counted up; ³calculated’

[C] *rcis*

The semantic range of the objects that *brcis* could take extends from concrete objects (tallies, beacon stations), through animate collectives (families), to abstract notions like deficiency or balance. Unfortunately, the full argument structure of the verb is not preserved in OLT documents. It can be reconstructed only on the grounds of later evidence; in the meaning ‘to count’ the verb is cEA in all modern dialects (CDTD.V: 990).

Apart from such obvious cognates as *rcis* ‘¹counting, numbering, numeration; ²account; ³estimation, esteem’ (J: 439b; see also s.v.) and *rcis pa* ‘mathematician, astronomer, soothsayer; accountant’ (J: 440a), *rci* seems to be also related to *chis* ‘prob[ably] secondary form of *rcis*’ (J: 448b), ‘the proper management of the affairs of the subjects by those in authority’ (Richardson 1969b: 256), ‘*čhis*, administration, management’ (Richardson 1985: 164), ‘method, plan, policy’ (Li and Coblin 1987: 103). The latter term is frequently found spelled as *čhis* in OLT, which might have resulted from palatalisation of *ch-* [tʰ-] before the front vowel *-i-* in spoken language.²⁰⁹

As demonstrated by (Imaeda 1980a: 132), in PT 986 Tibetan *chis/čhis* “corresponds to *yi* (yi 𑄎 – JB), *zhi* (zhi 治 –JB) ‘administer administration, govern’ in Chinese”. Neither *zhi*,

²⁰⁸ For /a/ > /i/ > /e/ before a velar obstruent compare: *lags* ~ *legs*, but Balti [ljaxmo], Kargil [tʃajmo], Tshangra, Nubra [lʃajmo], or *śag ma* ~ (g)*seg ma* ‘pebble’: *sag > *sʲag > 1. śag ma; 2. (g)seg. Since no palatalisation *s* > *ś* seems to have occurred in the word-family of *rceg*, we may assume that the derivation by means of the palatal /j/ was still productive after the full palatalisation yielding alveolo-palatals ceased. For the reconstructed stem \sqrt{seg} compare Chepang *sek-* ‘pick up, take or collect up, gather up (small objects)’ (Caughley 2000: 264a).

²⁰⁹ The lexeme is most commonly known from the compound *so čhis/chis* (sometimes also *so chigs*) ‘housekeeping, management of domestic concerns, husbandry’ (J: 578b), which might go back to the phrase *so nam gyi *chis/čhis*.

reconstructed as LH $\text{d}\bar{\text{a}}^{\text{C}}$, OCM *d-ləh (Schuessler 2007: 619) or MC *driH*, OC *lɾə-s (Baxter and Sagart 2014), nor *yi*, reconstructed as MC *ngjojH*, OC *ŋa[t]-s (Baxter and Sagart 2014), seem to be related to *chis* and *rci*. Tibetan *rci* has been subsumed under the PTH etymon *r-tsyəy count in STEDT (#2738). However, Lolo-Burmese, Karenic, and Chinese forms included in the same group seem to belong to different etymons.²¹⁰ From the remaining lexemes, only Tibetan and Rgyalrongic languages attest to the initial *r-*, but the Rgyalrongic forms suggest a borrowing from Tibetic.

As the OLT form *chis/čhis* indicates, the root initial was an alveolar affricate and *r-* should be analysed as prefix: *r-* + $\sqrt{\text{tsi}}$. *rci* and *chis/čhis* are derived from $\sqrt{\text{tsi}}$ by means of the prefix *r-* and suffix *-s* respectively. *chis/čhis* has been explained as an abstract term '(economical) affairs; management, administration'. The suffix *-s* derived abstract terms from verbs (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))). Taking into account the TH data, I deem it plausible to reconstruct the primary meaning of $\sqrt{\text{tsi}}$ as 'to count'.²¹¹ However, on account of the fact that scarcely any cognates of *rci* could be traced in Tibetan, it seems fruitless to speculate about the function and meaning of the prefix *r-* in the derived verb *rci*.

²¹⁰ The PLB etymon has been reconstructed as *rəy^{1/3} WRITE/COUNT (ibid.) and the Chinese as MC *srjuH*, OC *s-ro? 'to count' (Baxter and Sagart 2014).

²¹¹ As opposed to (Róna-Tas 1956: 169, fn. 37), I do not find any indications that *rci* or any of its cognates were ever used in connection with writing or incising letters. The term *rcis rdo riñ*, on which Róna-Tas based his hypothesis, is of much later date and might in fact go back to an intentional 'correction' made by the scribe to whom the OLT *gcigs* of the original was not known. Compare also the remark by Richardson: "The original sense (of *gcigs* – JB) seems to have become obscured in later Tibetan. In the *Rgyal po bkay thañ*, probably of the 14th century but drawing on earlier material, *gcigs* has been replaced by *rcis* – e.g. *rcis kyī rdo riñs* (f. 48a) where it appears to mean 'important'" (Richardson 1985: v). Although the compound **gcigs rdo riñs* does not seem to be attested in OLT, we find very similar phrases: *gcigs kyī rdo riñs* (PT 16: 34r1), *gcigs kyī mdo rdo riñs* (Treaty W 10–1; Treaty E 64–5), and *gcigs khrims rdo riñs* (Treaty E 70).

ch

choñ čhen (#480) ‘great exchange’

DTH: 31: un grand commerce; (Petech 1988a: 292) capo-esattore;²¹² (Dotson 2009b: 84) a great sale.

In OLT, *choñ* as a noun occurs most frequently with the light verb *byed* or *bya(s)* in divinatory texts, cf.:

(1)

γdron po la btab na myī γoñ // choñ byar (3v72) myī ruñ // mo γdī čī la btab kyañ ñan γo //
(ITJ 738; *apud* OTDO)

If [one] cast [divination] for a guest, [he] will not come. It is not appropriate to make a transaction. For whatsoever [one] cast this divination, it is bad.

(2)

choñ žig byas na khe phyīn // (ITJ 738: 3v77; *apud* OTDO)

If [one] did a transaction, profit will come.

It seems that the original meaning of *choñ* was ‘trade, trading, transaction, business’; for *choñ byed* compare Ger. *Geschäft machen*. In OLT, the following derivatives of *choñ* are attested: *choñ dus* (CT *choñ γdus*), *choñ pa*, and *choñ (d)pon*. The compound *choñ čhen* seems to be a *hapax legomenon*. *choñ čhen* is an attributive compound with the underlying structure **choñ čhen po* [N+A].

It remains unclear what exactly did *choñ čhen* denote. It is hardly imaginable that in a feudal society imperial Tibet was at that time, fields were sold and bought on the market. In PT 1288: 25 we read of preparing (*sbyard*) *choñ čhen* of fields. This event immediately follows after making sheaves of fields. (Dotson 2009b: 84, fn. 138) observed that the lord of the Ra-sañ occurs in connection with *Žañ-žuñ* in some other OLT sources as: *ra sañs rje* (PT 1286: 7; PT 1290: r4); *ra sañse rje* (PT 1290: v5); *ra scañ rje* (PT 1060: 64); *ra sañ rje* (PT 1060: 72). The subsequent clause of PT 1288 speaks of appointing Spug Gyim-rcañ Rma-čuñ as *mñan* – a fiscal official – for the land of the *Žañ-žuñ*. Both actions (preparing the *choñ čhen* and the appointment) were carried out by the same person – Mañ-po-rje, the king of the Dags-po. Considering that the events were taking place not a long time after the *Žañ-žuñ* have been conquered (644), we might think of a new apportionment of the land of the *Žañ-žuñ* by the conquerors. Accordingly, I propose a more general translation for *choñ čhen* as ‘great exchange’.

mchan (#540) ‘HON name’

In the OTA, *mc(h)an* is used exclusively with *bcan pos*: Khri Xdus-sroñ (ITJ 750: 92–3), Rgyal-gcug-ru *alias* Khri Lde-gcug-rcañ (ITJ 750: 185–6), and Khri Sroñ-lde-brcañ (Or.8212/187: 17). Since *mchan* belongs to the honorific register it might have developed the meaning ‘name’ in

²¹² Petech read *choñ čhen* as truncation of *choñ dpon čhen po*.

the course of metaphorisation. I deem it probable that ‘mark, token’ or similar was the original meaning of *mchan* that shifted towards ‘name’ when used figuratively.²¹³

γchald (#714) TR [EXP]_{ABS} [THEM]_{ABS} (v1 *γchal*, v2 *γchald*) ‘HML to request, to beseech’

[C] *scald*, *gsold*

Apart from the lexicalised phrase *p(h)yag γc(h)ald*, the verb *γc(h)al/γc(h)ald* occurs in the OTA also in the following clauses:

(1)

blon bcan (68) *sñas dru gu yul du drañste / ldum bu khri bśos khrom γcald* (ITJ 750)

Councillor [Mgar] Bcan-sña [Ldom-bu], having drawn to the Dru-gu land, requested the colonial province Ldum-bu-khri-bśos.

(2)

khu γdus can dañ rñegs khyi ma re dañ / γa źa gsum mčhid śags γchal źiñ / gnag (88) *nad čen pho byuñ ste /* (ITJ 750)

While the three, Khu γdus-can, Rñegs Khyi-ma-re, and the γa-źa, were pleading, a great cattle disease occurred.

(3)

blon skyes bzañ rgyal koñ blon čheyi (26) *γog dpon γchal γchal ba las gum /* (Or.8212/187)

Councillor Skyes-bzañ Rgyal-koñ, upon wishing [the position of] deputy of the grand councillor, died.

Exx. (2) and (3) present the argument structure of the verb as ‘HUMAN_{ABS} OBJECT_{ABS} *γcal*’. The complex verb *γchal γchal ba las* suggests that *γcal* could have been used in a durative meaning, i.e. denoted an action that was not punctual. This assumption is supported by the converb *γchal źiñ* (ITJ 750: 87) for the converbial clitic *źiñ* connoted duration (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))). The allomorph =*źiñ* is attached after *-l* but not after *-Cd*. It follows that the underlying form *γcald* was a v2 whereas *γcal* a v1-stem.

In modern dialects, the verb *γcal* is used only in a few idiomatic expressions the most popular of which is the equivalent of LT *phyag γchal* ‘to prostrate, to make prostration, to make obeisance to’, in which case the verb has the argument structure cEDA (A = *phyag*). In the OTA, the clauses with *phyag γchal* unanimously attest to the argument structure ‘HUMAN_{ABS} *pyag γchald*’. The HUMAN-slot is filled by the following phrases:

γa źa mañ po

ton ya bgo kha gan

če dog pan gyi

po ña

rgyaγi

pho ña

γeyu źañ śo

γbay da śi

rgyaγi

po ña

kam keñ

²¹³ See (Bialek 2023c).

<i>rgyaḡi</i>	<i>pho ña</i>	<i>yañ kheñ</i>
<i>ḡbug čor gyi</i>	<i>pho ña</i>	
<i>stod phyogs gyi</i>	<i>pho ña mañ po</i>	
<i>rgyaḡi</i>	<i>po ña</i>	<i>li coñ kan</i>
<i>rgyaḡi</i>	<i>po ña</i>	<i>cwa de pu</i>
<i>rgyaḡi</i>	<i>pho ña</i>	<i>čañ ḡdo sí</i>
<i>rgyaḡi</i>	<i>pho ña</i>	<i>li kheñ</i>
<i>ta čhig dañ dur gyis gyi</i>	<i>po ña</i>	
<i>rgyaḡi</i>	<i>pho ña</i>	<i>li žaň só</i>
<i>mywa</i>		<i>la kag</i>
<i>rgyaḡi</i>	<i>pho ña</i>	<i>ḡwañ ḡdo sí</i>
<i>rgyaḡi</i>	<i>pho ña</i>	<i>ḡeḡu jaň sí</i>
<i>rgyaḡi</i>	<i>pho ña</i>	<i>li žaň só</i>
<i>bru žaḡi</i>	<i>rgyal po</i>	
<i>rgyaḡi</i>	<i>pho ña</i>	<i>ḡwañ ḡdo sí</i>
<i>rgyaḡi</i>	<i>pho ña</i>	<i>qan da laň</i>
<i>mywa nag poe</i>	<i>po ña</i>	<i>la bri</i>
<i>rgyaḡi</i>	<i>po ña</i>	<i>kwag čuň laň</i>
<i>rgyaḡi</i>	<i>po ña</i>	<i>čaň ḡgwaň ḡge</i>
<i>dur gyis gyi</i>	<i>po ña</i>	

Except for two cases (*ḡa ža mañ po* and *pho ña mañ po*) the subject of the verb *ḡcald* has a single person as its referent, usually it is an emissary (*po ña*) of a foreign country or a king (*rgyal po*). The contexts leave no doubt that they come to see the *bcan po* at his court. The honorific *phyag* used as the direct object of the verb informs us that it was the *bcan po* to whom the action expressed by *ḡcald* was directed. Accordingly, the verb may be ascribed to the humble register.

Beside *phyag ḡchal*, the dialect of Southern Mustang attests to two other phrases with *ḡchal*: [jāwa ts^hāl] (LT *bśags pa ḡchal*) ‘to confess one’s sins’ and [t^hōljak ts^hāl] (LT *mthol bśags ḡchal*) ‘to beg for pardon’ (CDTD.V: 1027). As remarked in CDTD.V, LT *ḡchal* ‘to want, wish, desire, ask’ seems to be cognate with *ḡchol* ‘to seek, to search’. They might have developed from one root; *ḡchol* retained the concrete meaning ‘to seek’, whereas OLT *ḡchald* acquired the more metaphorical meaning ‘to beseech’:

The reconstructed root suggests that the verbs might also be cognates of the OLT TR-EAA *scald*. Due to the causative prefix *s-*, *scald* may be expected to require one argument more than *ḡcal*, which is confirmed by the attested argument structures of the verbs. The additional argument is the agent in ERG (see s.v. *scald*). *ḡcal/ḡcald* is a transitive, whereas *scald* a di-

transitive verb. Another cognate verb is *rcol* 'to endeavour' and possibly *rcal* 'skill, dexterity' < *'exertion' (?).

J

mjad (#628) TR [AGT]_{ERG} [PAT]_{ABS} 'HON ¹to prepare; LV *ɣgord mjad* to hunt; ²to organise; LV *rol mo mjad* to hunt'

In the OTA-I, *mjad* is used only with *bcan po* as its subject:

(1)

khyīyi lo la / bcan po rkoñ g.yug du ɣgord mjad čhīñ (PT 1288: 41)

In the dog year, the *bcan po* hunted at G.yug [of] Rkoñ.

(2)

byañ roldu gśegste / kho ñe du rur / g.yag rgod la rol mo mjade / (233) g.yag rgod sgrog du bčhug / (ITJ 750)

[The *bcan po*] went to the north; having hunted wild yaks at Kho-ñe-du-ru, [he] fettered wild yaks.

(3)

blon čhen po man čhad (306) bro scalte / bkay nan čen pho mjad nas (ITJ 750)

Having sworn [all] from grand councillors downward, [the *bcan po*] prepared a great instruction.

Only in the first passage is the subject explicitly expressed. In the remaining passages *mjad* takes a direct object in ABS: *rol mo* and *bkay nan*. Unfortunately the subject is not expressed. Neither does subject occur in clauses with *mjad* in the OTA-II or in the OLT inscriptions. According to modern dialectal data, nowadays the verb is cEA.

In the OTA-I, the verb is used exclusively with *bcan pos* and so clearly belonged to the honorific register. However, in the OTA-II it seems to have also referred to actions undertaken by grand councillors (see ex. (4)):

(4)

bod yul gyi pha los gyi [rcis] mg{o} mjad / (Or.8212/187: 1)

[One] prepared an initial account of the populace of the Bod land.

(5)

bod yul du mol čen / (58) mjade /// žañ lon čhen pho spo bleg mjade // (Or.8212/187)

[The *bcan po*], having organised a great conferral in the Bod land, made promotion-slates [for] grand aristocrats.

I put forward the hypothesis that *mjad* was derived from the verb *zad* by means of the prefix *m-*: *m-* + \sqrt{zad} > *mjad* *[mɔzad]. In accordance with Conrady's law ((Conrady 1896: 56); see also (Hill 2019b: §17)), *-d-* is understood as an excrescent consonant. Thus, the original meaning of *mjad* might have been *'to complete, to finish'.

W

Ž

žaň (#765) ¹maternal uncle; ²title bestowed on persons entitled to provide a wife for a *bcan po*'

(Benedict 1942: 318) < *zraň; p. 319: 'father's sister's husband'; p. 322: the especial bond between mother's brother (*žaň*) and sister's son (*cha*) is a feature of the avunculate. Under cross-cousin marriage, one's sister's son becomes one's son-in-law (man speaking); DTH: 132, fn. 7: *Fonctionnaire du plus haut rang, sorte de vice-roi*; (Tucci 1950: 58) usual meaning: uncle; when used alone, it seems certain that it applies to families from which the kings chose their wives; p. 61: the title given to officials related by marriage with the kings; (Richardson 1952a: 6) appears with regularity in connection with ministers who can be identified as relations of the royal family – e.g. Mčhims, Sna-nam, Che-spoň. It is not used with all the ministers. [...] The probability of *žaň* denoting royal kinship is therefore strong, but it was also possible for other persons to be given the rank of *žaň lon*; (Róna-Tas 1955: 266, fn. 41) should be considered a leftover of the avuncular system, and through it of the Old Tibetan matriarchy. The avuncular system still existed in Tibet in the 8th century; at the time it was already necessary to differentiate the veritable uncle on the maternal side (*žaň druň po*) from the rest of the nobility who also bore the title of *žaň*; the *žaň dbon* relationship between the Chinese emperor and the Tibetan king – that of uncle and nephew on the maternal side – essentially reflects the Tibetan avuncular system; the fact that this relationship was used to determine the mutual position of the two rulers is rooted in social history; the uncle on the maternal side, that is the representative of the queen's clan is in charge of the regency during the king's minority; it was not in Tibet alone that the term for the uncle on the maternal side had become the term for an office; such extension of the meaning is known also from the Orhon inscriptions and at the *t'u yü hun-s*; (Haarh 1960: 161) In the later or latest period of the dynasty, *žaň* became a more common title of prominent members of the leading clans, apparently of those that at some time or other had been related with the royal house by blood; (Richardson 1967: 9f.) The title, *žaň*, in certain clearly definable circumstances, signifies that the person so described or a member of his family was at some time in the relationship of maternal uncle to a king of Tibet; (Stein 1972: 94) as in China, the word for maternal grandfather or uncle also means father-in-law; p. 100: in ancient Tibet, the ministers were often the king's maternal uncles, or at least belonged to his mother's clan; (Richardson 1985: 21, fn. 12) *žaň* (in *žaň lon* - JB) is perhaps an equivalent of the Chinese *shang shu*, head of an office; and must be distinguished from *žaň*, maternal uncle, designating a marriage relationship between certain noble families and the Tibetan royal line; p. 92: the title was accorded to leading members of a clan from which Tibetan king had chosen a queen who then bore him an heir; the title *žaň* does not appear in the Tibetan Annals until 710 perhaps did not come to use until the ascendancy of the Xbro clan with the marriage to Maň-sroň Maň-rcan of the lady Xbro Khri-ma-lod; (Li and Coblin 1987: 122) the title of a high official from a family which had furnished queens to the Tibetan kings; (Yamaguchi 1992: 58) 'maternal grandfather', translated in Chinese as *jiu舅* ('maternal uncle', 'father-in-law', 'maternal grandfather'); pp. 65–6: the *žaň* did not have any important connections with politics during the reign of Sroň-bcan Sgam-po; (Nagano 1994: 105) maternal uncle; son-in-law; p. 111: *žaň* was not introduced in order to fill the gap left by the shift in the meaning of *khu*, but rather: ¹*žaň* was introduced as a term for 'maternal uncle' with a different meaning from *khu*, i.e., as a marked term; ²this term became influential, and therefore became unmarked so that it was used in general to indicate 'maternal uncle'; ³*khu* acquired the function of distinguishing between father and parallel uncles, which were previously undifferentiated in the lexical system; p. 112: WT *žaň po* may be interpreted as 'matrilineal relative'; the Sbraň clan was considered to be in *Žaň-zuň*, might it not be that *žaň po* had the meaning of 'people originating in *Žaň-zuň*, from *Žaň-zuň*' prior to acquiring the meaning of 'maternal relative'? The *žaň* in *Žaň-zuň* is exclusively used as a proper noun indicating place names, and does not occur as a common noun. It is known that *Žaň-zuň* was an important area of *gñen* 'relatives by marriage' for the Yarlung family; members of the Sbraň clan later (around the end of the 8th century) began to style themselves as *žaň rgyal* 'kings of the affinal tribes originating in *Žaň-zuň*'; p. 113: the core meaning of *žaň/žaň po* underwent the following semantic shift: 'people originating in *Žaň-zuň*' > 'affine from *Žaň-zuň*' > 'representative of affine' > 'maternal uncle'. Thus, a semantically marked lexical item with a special content ultimately became a common kinship term for 'maternal uncle'; p. 113, fn. 15: a minister who comes from a queen's family is designated as *žaň*; after Dunhuang manuscripts, *žaň po* is exclusively used for 'the tribes who have already provided a king's mother'; (Takeuchi 1995: 129) the Tibetan type name construction, namely, the combination of *rus* ('clan'), *blon* or *žaň* ('title'), *mkhan*, and *myiň* ('given name'); (Richardson 1998b: 187) maternal uncle. Title of noblemen whose family was related to the *bcan po* by marriage. They could be called *blon žaň*; (Dotson 2004: 75) the appellation *žaň* was lent to aristocratic clan when one of its ladies gave birth to a Tibetan sovereign (or upon his subsequent accession to the throne); the

title was retained for at least four generations thereafter; no-heir-producing marriage with a single maternal clan was permitted until a certain number of generations had passed since an earlier such union; p. 79–80: the term *żań* was commonly employed as an honorific in the compound *żań lon/żań blon*, which simply means ‘minister’. Only in very few circumstances does *żań blon* indicate ‘maternal uncles and ministers’ or simply ‘maternal uncle minister’, that is to say, a minister who is also a *żań*; p. 86: after the lady of a clan gave birth to a Tibetan emperor (*bcan po*), or upon his subsequent accession to the throne, the term *żań* applied to at least four descending generations of the clan; p. 90: the *żań* were a group of privileged maternal relatives with whom heir-producing marriages were contracted; parallel to this, there existed a proscription against reproducing the unions of one’s immediate forbears; p. 92, fn. 25: Aside from the obvious fact that the mother’s clan has control over the child in his infancy and youth, wife-givers in Tibetan societies nearly always hold a higher status than wife-takers; p. 94: during the period of the Tibetan empire, the appellation *żań* pertained to members of four Tibetan clans: *ǰbro*, *Mčhims*, *Ches-poñ* and *Sna-nam*; the term *żań* was also used as an honorific in the compound *żań lon/żań blon*, which simply indicated ‘minister’ or ‘ministerial aristocracy’, and did not necessarily imply any kin relationship with the Tibetan royal line; (Dotson 2009a: 224) *żań* can be applied not only to an individual father-in-law or bride-giver, but to his descendants as well; (Dotson 2009b: 59) bride-giving [clan]; p. 260: bride-giver in relation to bride-receiver (*dbon*); father-in-law, maternal uncle (mother’s brother); also used as a kinship term cum-title to refer to members of those clans with whose ladies the emperors contracted heir-producing unions: the *ǰbro*, *Mčhims*, *Ches-poñ*, and *Sna-nam*; (Samuels 2016: 309) Whilst *żań* is more generally associated with the ‘wife-givers’, *żań po* specifically denotes the maternal uncle/wife’s-brother.

For a detailed analysis of the semantic shift from a kinterm towards a classificatory title, see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming)).

żań dbon (#630) ‘uncle and nephew’

(Richardson 1967: 10) uncle and nephew; [relationship that - JB] existed between the Emperor of China of the King of Tibet as the result of the marriage of *Sroñ-brcan Sgam-po*, and later of *Khri Lde-gcug-brcan*, to Chinese princesses. There was a similar relationship between Tibetan kings, as *żań*, and the *ǰa-ža* chiefs, as *dbon*, through the marriage in 689 of the Tibetan princess *Khri-bańs* to the *ǰa-ža* ruler; (Gumiliov 1972: 375) stryj i synowiec; (Dotson 2009b: 116) bride giver and bride receiver; p. 261: = *dbon żań*

żań lon (#388) ‘aristocrat’

< **żań lon*, lit. ‘to receive the *żań*-[position]’. For details, see (Bialek 2018a: 2.451ff.)

żał če (#749) ‘sentence’

< **ża’i lče* ‘tongue/speech (of the face)’. For details, see (Bialek 2018a: 2.434ff., s.v. *ża lče*).

żig (#631) INTR/NC [PAT]_{ABS} ‘to collapse’

[C] *bśig*

An INTR counterpart of *bśig* ‘to destroy’ (see s.v.) derived from the root $\sqrt{\text{żig}}$.

żiń (#657) ‘field’

żugs loń (#481) ‘beacon station’

< **żugs kyi slan* ‘a brazier for charcoal’. For details, see (Bialek 2018a: 2.468ff.)

bži (#633) 'four'

bžugs (#482) INTR [THEM]_{ABS} [LOC]_{INESS} 'HON ¹to abide, dwell; ²to stay; ³to remain'

In the OTA-I, we can distinguish between two meanings of *bžugs*: 1. to abide, dwell (THEME: *bcan po*, *pho brañ*, *yum*, *yab*, *phyi*, *phyi sbon*, *sras*); 2. to stay (THEME: *spur*, *riñ*, *dpur*). In the first meaning, it is applied to the family members of a *bcan po* and to his court. In the second meaning, it is used to refer to the dead body of a *bcan po* only. The verb belongs to the honorific register.

I tentatively propose analysing *bžugs* as a lexicalised inflected form of another verb: *γjug/žugs* 'to enter' > **b+žugs* 'to have entered'. In a way, the derivation *bžugs* < *žugs* can be compared with *mčhis* 'to stay' < *mčhi/mčhis* 'to come'. Both *žugs* and *mčhis* originally denoted the result (-s) of an action of entering and going/coming. The meaning and function of the prefix *b-* in this derivation remain to be established, but we can speculate that it was added to distinguish between *žugs* and the new formation *bžugs*. Since *γjug* was formed later (it is not attested in OLT), *žugs* was primarily used for both imperfective and perfective (see (Bialek 2020a: 285, fn. 61)) and therefore the new verb must have been additionally marked.

bžes (#634) TR [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} 'HON to take'

The complete argument structure of the verb is not attested in OT. It can only be reconstructed on the grounds of modern dialectal data; the verb is unanimously glossed as cEA in CDTD: 1112.

Z

***zog** (#805) ‘(trading) goods’

[V] zag (Or.8212/187: 91)

The OTA-II-D abounds is scribal errors and misspellings. For this reason, I emend the attested zag with zog ‘goods’; the latter is the etymological form of CT zoñ ‘ware, merchandise, goods’ (J: 490a); cf. (Bialek 2021a: xvi).

zlugš (#635) ‘information’

Derived by conversion from v4 zlugš; √zlug v1 *zlug, v2 bzlugš, v3 bzlug, v4 zlugš (see (Bialek 2018a: 2.534).²¹⁴

bzuñ (#636) (v3 gzuñ) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [THEM]_{ABS} ‘¹to seize; ²to adopt; ³to take for, to consider (as [FUN]_{TERM})’

²¹⁴ In (Bialek 2018a: 2.534) I falsely reconstructed the v1-stem as *zlugš*.

Y

ya za rje (#733) 'lord of the Ya-za'

The rulers of the Ya-za acquired the hereditary title *dbon* 'nephew' after the marriage of the Tibetan *bcan mo* Khri-baṅs with a lord of Ya-za in 689/90 (ITJ 750: 102–3).

yog dpon (#713) 'deputy'

BTK: 130, fn. 7: *yog dpon te mčhan kheb. lag dpon. stoñ bu čhuñ lta bu layo* (s.v. *yog pon*); (Francke 1914b: 44) lower officer, subaltern officer; (Thomas 1933: 388) subordinate commander, second to the *chugs dpon*; DTH: 64: deputy; p. 70: assistant; (Coblin 1991c: 104) lower officer, deputy; (Takeuchi 1995: 322) an adjutant; (Richardson 1998h: 150) Assistant Minister; (Takeuchi 2004b: 51b) sub-commander; (Dotson 2009b: 130) deputy.

OLT sources record *yog (d)pons* of the following officials: *blon čhe* (PT 1071: r4; PT 1287: 106; Or.8212/187:25–6), *rgyaṅi to dog* (PT 1089: r10), *rce rje* (PT 1089: r11), and *gźis pon* (PT 1089: r42). The term apparently had a general meaning. From Or.8212/187: 25–6 we can infer that one had to be nominated to the function.

y

yan čad (#710) **POSTP** 'upward'

yab (#637) 'HON father'

(Benedict 1942: 330) The terms *yum* and *yab* are perhaps connected with *rum* 'womb' and *rabs* 'lineage', respectively. Initial *r-* ~ *y-* alternation is not typical for Tibetan yet may occur, e.g. Schmidt cites *ral ga* 'branch' for *yal ga*; (Hahn 2003b: 93) **ya pha* 'hoher Vater'; (Dotson 2013a: 130) patriarch.

yi ge (#638) ¹text; ²diploma'

J: 508b: in comp[ounds] *yig*; ¹letter; ²anything that is written, note, card, bill, document, inscription, title, letter, epistle.

DTH: 31: le texte; p. 144: lettre; p. 161: écriture; (Lalou 1955: 210) insignes des grades; (Stein 1972: 132) insignia; (Stein 1983: 153, fn. 13) = *yig chañ*, diplôme; (Li and Coblin 1987: 175) Officials in early Tibet held *yi ge* 'letters' of different precious or semi-precious materials, as indications or insignia of rank. The *yi ge* were alternatively called *yig chañ* in OT; (Coblin 1991c: 104) letter, text, writing; an insigne of rank; (Richardson 1998e: 138, fn. 6) Perhaps the letter, *yi ge*, was a diploma on a metal plate entitling the holder to wear the appropriate decoration; (Uebach and Zeisler 2008: 319) single specific certificates which form the group of the six insignia of rank; (Dotson 2009b: 61) insignia; p. 63: insignia of rank; p. 100, fn. 206: refers always to a specific insignia, e.g., turquoise or brass; p. 261: insignia of rank, epaulets; usually referring to a particular type of insignia.

In PT 1288: 30 *yi ge* is something that can be written down (*bris*) and contains laws (*bkaŷ grims*). Basically, the term can be understood in two ways: 1. a written work regarded as a physical object; or 2. a work regarded as a coherent unit of discourse. In the remaining contexts, *yi ge* seems to have denoted an official document (lit. 'letter') confirming the right of a merited person to a particular social rank. The word-formation of *yi ge* remains unknown.

yig gcañ (#800) 'insignia'

DTH: 39: écrit [d'alliance]; p. 71: = *yig chañs* 'documents, records'; (Demiéville 1952: 285) documents (for *yig chañs* – JB); (Tucci 1956b: 88) patents, diplomas; highest: gold, turquoise; middle: silver, silver inlaid; lowest: copper, iron; each may be higher and lower; (Uray 1960b: 50) diploma; fn. 37: Tucci has shown that the word *yig gcañ/cañ* in the 7th-9th century denoted the 'coloured letters', i.e. turquoise, golden, silver-gilt, silver, brass and copper diplomas and/or insignia of ranks, granted together with the different civil and military grades and mentioned in other sources as *yi ge*; (Stein 1983: 178, fn. 56) *yig chañ* 'insigne, décoration'; (Beckwith 1993: 61, fn. 41) charter; (Bellezza 2001: 66) commendation (for *yig rcañ*); fn. 42: this term seems to refer to royal awards; (Takata 2006: 164) diploma; (Bellezza 2008: 223) The *yig chañs* / *yig ge* / *yig* functioned as designations of the status of low-, middle- and high-ranking officials, whose use persisted throughout the imperial period. The ancient *yig chañ* appear to have been in the form of badges or tablets, as well as many other kinds of valuable objects; (Uebach and Zeisler 2008: 320) has survived to the day, but its meaning is different. It denotes the chancellery of the Tibetan government, and also offices in general; (Dotson 2009b: 100) insignia of rank; fn. 206: lit. 'pure letters'; p. 261: usually referring to the generality of ministerial insignia and not a specific type; may also be the origin of the later term *yig chañ*, used in the same way.

In OLT the compound is a dis-legomenon known only from the OTA:

(1)

glo ba ñe ba yig gcañ dañ bya sga scald / (ITJ 750: 130)

[The *bcan po*] bestowed those who were loyal with insignia and rewards.

(2)

sum ru pal po che yīg gcañ scal (Or.8212/187: 35)

[The *bcan po*] bestowed insignia on a bulk of Sum-pa Horn.

In post-imperial sources the term seems to have been readily confused with *yig chañ (pa)* (< **yig* ‘letter, documents’ + *chañ* ‘abode’) which apparently denoted an office or an official. Likewise modern scholars do not make any distinction between the two and also frequently treat *yig gcañ* as identical with *yi ge*. The OLT orthography is clearly *yig gcañ*. We observe that *yig gcañ* is bestowed collectively, whereas *yi ge*, modified by terms referring to precious materials (see OTD, s.v. *yi ge*), is given to concrete individuals. In both cases, the use of the verb *scal* indicates that *yig gcañ* and *yi ge* were bestowed directly by a *bcan po*. It follows that *yig gcañ* was a collective term, of which precious *yi ges* were instantiations.

I tentatively reconstruct the underlying structure of the compound as **yi ge gcañ ba*, lit. ‘stuffed letter’,²¹⁵ with **gcañ ba* being a nominalised v3-stem of *γchañ* ‘¹to press into, to stuff’ (J: 457b), ‘va. to stuff in, to squeeze in’ (Gs: 898b), Nurla [tʰaŋs] cA ‘to crown, to rush in, to squeeze in’, Tabo [tʰāŋ] cED ‘to force one’s way through (a crowd)’, Bathang [tʰō:] ‘to block up, to plug’ (CDTD.V: 1020).²¹⁶ *yig gcañ* would have denoted the type of official documents or distinctions made most probably by inlaiding (i.e. ‘stuffing’) a surface of the document with the respective precious materials.

The main problem with this etymology is that the verb itself is only sparsely attested and the stems provided by Jäschke (v1 *γchañ*, v2 *chañs*, v3 *bcañ* (?)) suggest that two conjugations might have been confused: an intransitive v1 *chañ*, v2 **chañs* and a transitive v1 *γchañ*, v2 **bcañ*, v3 *gcañ*, v4 **choñs*. The former is apparently identical with the well-known stative verb ‘to be complete’.²¹⁷ The basic semantic opposition was INTR *‘to be full’ vs TR *‘to fill, to make full’; the verbs were derived from the ambivalent root $\sqrt{\text{tsaŋ}}$.²¹⁸ The v3-stem *gcañ* might have very early gone out of use, losing the competition with the homophonous but unrelated *gcañ* ‘clean’. **gcañ* ‘stuffed’ survived only in the compound *yig gcañ* that itself fell into oblivion with the demise of the Tibetan Empire and its social and administrative systems.²¹⁹

yum (#639) ‘HON mother’

(Benedict 1942: 330) The terms *yum* and *yab* are perhaps connected with *rum* ‘womb’ and *rabs* ‘lineage’, respectively. Initial *r-* ~ *y-* alternation is not typical for Tibetan yet may occur, e.g. Schmidt cites *ral ga* ‘branch’ for *yal ga*; (Uebach 1997a: 57) in the Annals only mother of the emperor are addressed *yum*; (Hahn 2003b: 93) **ya ma* ‘hohe Mutter’; p. 94: Der Vokal *u* in *yum* erklärt sich leicht durch den Einfluss des folgenden labialen Nasals; (Dotson 2009b: 185) a heir-bearing queen.

²¹⁵ Cf. CT *khri nañ chañs čan* ‘a stuffed seat’ (J: 457b, s.v. *γchañ ba*).

²¹⁶ For the original use of v3-stems in attributive position, see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming)).

²¹⁷ The latter is related in CDTD.V to *rjoñ* ‘va. to stuff in’ (Gs: 1073b).

²¹⁸ For ambivalent roots, see Type 3c verbs in (Bialek 2020a: 281f.)

²¹⁹ A more straightforward etymology **yi ge gcañ ba* ‘clean letter’ lacks semantic motivation for me. Why should letters of distinction be called ‘clean’?

yul (#640) 'region'

yo byad (#769) 'necessaries'

From ITJ 750: 176, it appears that *yo byad* denoted objects immediately related to the expected arrival of *bcan mo khoñ čö*.

Its etymology remains unknown although CDTD: 7769 seems to suggest it might be related to *yod čhas* Dingri 'belongings, possession, object' (CDTD: 7783). A compound with the existential copula *yod* as its first constituent is rather improbable. Instead, either *yod čhas* is a folk etymology from **yo čhas* < **yo byad dañ čhas* or *yod* is a clipping from *yo byad* (**yo+-d*).

yos bu (#483) '(calendric) rabbit'

In CT and modern dialects *yos* is only a calendric term (cf. J: 516b & CDTD: 7799), whereas the animal is called *ri boñ*. In OLT, *yos bu* is the standard form of the term that is known in CT as *yos*. The diminutive suffix *-bu* suggests that it is a derivative of *yos*. In fact, one OLT passage makes it clear that *yos* originally denoted an animal:

(1)

- | | |
|---|---|
| <i>bya ro ro na mduñ gī rce rañ nig /</i> | In every bird a lance-tip stays on its own. |
| <i>yos ro ro na lham gyi goñ ra nig /</i> (PT 1287: 57) | In every hare a tip (lit. the upper part) of a shoe stays on its own. |

Here *yos* is juxtaposed with *bya* 'bird' and both occur in a context that suggests hunt. It follows that *yos* denoted a wild animal (by analogy with birds) that could be hunted and therefore should be rendered with 'hare'.²²⁰ The question is: what is the function of the DIM *-bu* in *yos bu*? Three distinct interpretations can be provided:

1. *-bu* originally denoted young hare and first later the whole formation *yos bu* started to denote a calendric unit;
2. *-bu* denoted another (smaller ?) species, i.e. rabbit, as opposed to *yos* 'hare'. Afterwards *yos bu* underwent specialisation to denote a calendric unit;
3. *-bu* from the beginning was applied in a metaphorical meaning to denote an abstract concept of a calendric unit.

In his comprehensive study of the CT diminutive *-bu*, Uray distinguished between twelve main meanings it could express (Uray 1952: 205–13). In this perspective only the first interpretation does not raise doubts. Although Uray also quotes one example in support of the second interpretation: *spreyu* 'monkey' < *spra* 'langur'.²²¹ To this Uray adds dialectal data for *boñ bu* and *byiyu* that should prove that "a species is denoted by the diminutive form, while the basis itself has assumed a specific meaning" (Uray 1952: 206). As I have shown s.v. *spreyu*, this interpretation does not apply even in the case of *spreyu*. Uray did not mention any

²²⁰ *yos* has replaced *yos bu* as a term for a calendric unit after a new term denoting the animal, i.e. *ri boñ*, was coined or gained on popularity.

²²¹ For a detailed discussion, see s.v. *spreyu*.

formation that would have developed its meaning along the lines proposed in the third interpretation above. However, if we restrict our analysis to the textual data at hand, we have to admit that *yos bu* does not occur in the meaning ‘a young hare’ or ‘a small hare’ in our sources.²²² In OLT, *yos bu* occurs always in the phrase *yos bu(yi) lo* leaving no doubt that it denoted a calendric unit. In the Chinese Zodiac the fourth year of a cycle is that of rabbit. *yos bu* might have been coined to denote an animal not known to Tibetans but similar to hare (although smaller). The lexeme has never found any application outside of calendric system. Thus, we may conclude that *yos bu* was coined under foreign influences and therefore the meaning of *-bu* does not concord with any other native diminutive formation. However, the syllable *yos* could be related to the PTH *b-yəw-n rat/rabbit/hare (cf. STEDT #2796).

g.yag rgod (#484) ‘wild yak’

The underlying structure of the compound can be reconstructed as *g.yag rgod po; cf. *bya rgod po* (ITJ 734: 3r96). The OTA do not use the more popular term *ybron* ‘wild yak’.

g.yu (#485) ‘turquoise’

g.yul (#641) ‘¹army; ²battle’

The OTA attest to a semantic shift in *g.yul*. Namely, in ITJ 750: 122 the verb *sprad* acquires an argument in comitative which expresses adversative. The latter argument is missing from ITJ 750: 253, while in PT 1287 it is marked with allative:

(1)	
<i>la boñ ni rje dañ skol /</i>	[Kag]-la-boñ, the lord and [his] subjects,
<i>blo čhe ni dkyel mkhas la //</i>	Of broad mind, experienced in overthrowing and
<i>rgal mkhas ni / (356) khoñ dpaṅ bas //</i>	Experienced in fighting, of brave heart,
<i>rgya rje nī bsam lañ la /</i>	Who committed a battle at a fortified encampment
<i>dgray bžer nī g.yul sprad čin /</i>	Against the Chinese ruler Bsam-lañ and
<i>dgra zīn nī gsar (357) spañs pas //</i>	Who renounced anew [his] enemies and allies,
<i>srid kyi ni mgo bzuñ zīn /</i>	The head of the dominion, that he had held, and
<i>pha skyabs nī sdug bcal paṅ //</i>	The agreeableness under the protection of the
	father (i.e. the <i>bcan po</i>), he was looking for,
<i>lha sras nī bcan la / (358) bcal //</i>	[He] tried to obtain from (lit. upon) the Divine Son,
	the <i>bcan po</i> .

The frequent use of *g.yul* in collocation with *sprad* might have led to the semantic change and the lexicalisation of the phrase as ‘to commit a battle’.

²²² The situation is different from that of *spreyu* which is attested in OLT as denoting an animal.

r

ra sañ rje (#377) 'lord of the Ra-sañ'

[V] *ra sañs rje* (PT 1288: 7; PT 1290: r4, v5)

(Chang 1959: 130) an official title; (Uray 1972b: 42) seems to be a title of councillors, presumably in Žañ-žuñ; (Bellezza 2008: 522, fn. 578) *ra sañs rje*, possibly a term for a councillor (minister) in the Žañ-žuñ language; (Dotson 2009b: 299) *Rid-stag-rhya*, *Ra-sañ-rje*, minister (associated with Žañ-žuñ); p. 84, fn. 139: a clan name.

A survey of OLT formations with the last element *-rje* has shown that these are always titles whose first constituents fall in one of four categories:

1. ethnonym + *rje*: *rgya rje*, *bru ža rje*, *ya ža rje*
2. clan name + *rje*: *skyi rje*, *rñegs rje*, *mčhims rje*, *ltam rje*, *drañ rje*, *nags rje*, *gnubs rje*, *bal rje*, *dbyes rje*, *rcañ rje*, *žoñ rje*, *γol rje*
3. administrative unit + *rje*: *stoñ bu rje*, *rce rje*
4. common word + GENDER CL + *rje*: *stag po rje*, *mañ po rje*, *mañ mo rje*, *ziñ po rje*

Whenever final, *rje* is a meaningful syllable: 'lord, ruler'. Since from the phrase *ra sañ rjeyi blon rid stag rgya* (PT 1288: 24) it occurs that the lord of the Ra-sañ had a councillor (*blon*), I consider Ra-sañ to have been an ethnonym; clans are not known to have had councillors. As time passed, *ra sañ rje* was re-analysed and used in the so-called 'catalogues of principalities' – stereotypical and formulaic lists of polities that presumably formed part of the Tibetan Empire. In these lists, the title is customarily related to the Žañ-žuñ polity and functions as a clan name of Žañ-žuñ councillors.²²³ The title is also found in connection with distinctly non-Tibetan, possibly Žañ-žuñ, names – *Rid-stag-rhya* and *Spuñ-rhye-rhya*.

rabs čhad (#486) 'extinct family'

< **rabs čhad pa*, lit. 'a cut off lineage'. For a detailed analysis, see (Bialek 2018a: 2.521f., s.v. *rabs čhad*).

ram γday (#487) 'support forces'

< **ra ma γday* 'to follow an advance guard'. For a detailed analysis, see (Bialek 2018a: 2.522ff.)

riñ (#491) 'HON dead body'

Jä: 547a-b: ¹lang vom Raum; ²lang v.d. Zeit; ³alt; J: 528b-9a: ¹long, high, tall; ²long, with respect to time; esp. of kings etc.: under a king; during the reign or life of a king; ³old; DSM: 883b: *pur ram ro la yjug pa yod de*.

(Lalou 1952: 352) *mort*; (Haarh 1969: 360) *bone, skeleton; dead body*; (Richardson 1985: 176) *life-time*; (Li and Coblin 1987: 459) *long (of time); long (of space); far distant; time, lifetime*; (Stein 1988b: 50) *cadavre (?)*; (Walter 1998a: 64) *riñ / riñs* in adjectival and adverbial phrases relating to duration means 'persisting through time/space'; p. 65: an abstract noun with the meaning of an *ongoing* or *enduring presence*; p. 66: the living presence of the emperor – his status – is his *sku*. Correlative to this is *riñ*, used when the writer needed to express his endurance through a stretch of time or space; *riñ* means *corpse* – providing it is understood here to be equivalent to *spur/dpur*, with the intention of describing the corpse as being, or containing the continuing presence of the

²²³ We can also speculate whether *rañ rjeyu* of the *Dbay bžed* (18v2) is not a clipped form of *ra sañ rje*.

emperor; p. 68: an extended meaning of *riñ* as 'sacred presence' was employed in Imperial Tibet. Originally, it referred to the sacral presence of the Tibetan emperor among his subjects beyond his physical lifetime. This concept was later used to convey similar beliefs about Buddhist enlightened beings in Tibet, while its original use, in connection with the bodies of the emperors was gradually forgotten; (Dotson 2009b: 261) royal honorific for corpse; also indicates the 'presence' of the emperor; (Hill 2011b: 8) reign; p. 15: duration.

For a thorough analysis of *riñ* '(dead) body' and its cognates, see (Bialek 2018b).

riñ khañ (#493) 'mortuary'

< **riñ gi khañ*, lit. 'a chamber for (lit. of) a (dead) body'. For a thorough discussion of the compound see (Bialek 2018a: 2.526ff.) Cf. *gduñ khañ* 'funerary chamber' in *Mñay ris rgyal rabs* (Vitali 1996: 63, l. 1).

riñ lugs (#492) 'messenger'

< **riñs par zlugs*, lit. 'to inform so that [it] is quick'. For a detailed analysis, see (Bialek 2018a: 2.530ff.)

ruñ (#770) [EXP]_{ABS} 'to be willing'

†reg zid (#792) 'notes'

DSM: 893a: skyud byañ ñam zin bris dañ bkas bčas kyi don la yjug ste; BYD: 534: zin bris; CM: 423b–3a: ¹reg zig. zin bris; ²skye mched bču gñis kyi yul drug gi nañ gses reg pañi chor ba (s.v. *reg*).

Sch: 551: das Studirte zu Papier gebracht od[er] aufgeschrieben, Excerpte gemacht (s.v. *reg gzig pa*).

(Bsod-nams-skyid 1992: 78): zin bris (s.v. *reg (zig)*); BDN: 214: zin bris dañ don gcig; STK: 394: zin bris zes pa'i don dañ mtshuñs.

(Simonsson 1957: 263) Notiz (emended the transmitted *reg zid* with *reg zig* – JB); (Taube 1978b: 179) Manuskript (for *reg zeg*).

Letters *reg zi* are the last ones visible in l. 11 of Or.8212/187 before the break of seven years in the narrative. *reg zig* is attested in the following passage:

(1)

rgya rje li yug / śa ču na mčhis pañi (20) che / nas khal brgyay dañ khre či khal bču nos pa / scañ dam žag gi rcis mgo / reg zig dañ myi sbyar žiñ / god scal par (21) žañ lon čhed pos gnañ nas / (PT 1111: 19–21)

At the time when the Chinese lord Li-yug was staying in Śa-cu, those who received hundred *khal* of barley and ten *khal* of millet were allowed by great aristocrats to be paid (lit. given) the loss while not having compared the initial account of the fixed grain with the notes taken.

However, the compound has a very unstable form already in the earliest sources:

<i>reg zi</i> [-]	Or.8218/187: 11
<i>reg zig</i>	PT 1111: 20
<i>reg bzid</i>	PT 1855: v1 (<i>apud</i> (Lalou 1939-61.3: 155))
<i>reg zid</i>	<i>Sgra sbyor bam po gñis pa</i> (<i>apud</i> (Ishikawa 1990: 127))

Whereas the final *-g* can be explained as resulting from assimilation to the preceding final *-eg* (cf. also CT *reg zeg* noted by Taube), no plausible explanation can be delivered for *-d > -g*. Therefore, I take the forms in *-d* as etymological. The loss of the word-internal *-b-* in *reg zid* can be attributed to its inter-consonantal position so that the etymological form of the compound seems to have been **reg bzid*. DSM glosses *ɣjid* as ¹ɣjin paɣam ɣčhañ baɣi don la ɣjug pa' (746b). I connect *bzid* to this verb as its v2-stem (cf. also *reg zin* glossed as 'reg zig' in BYD: 534b). The verb seems to be historically cognate with CT *ɣjed* 'to hold out or forth' (J: 466b), still amply attested in modern dialects. There is another compound with the second constituent going back to the same verb: *lhuñ bzed* 'alms-bowl' (J: 602a). For CT, *bzed* is also glossed separately as 'basin' (J: 496b), although it seems to occur mainly in compounds. The motivation behind and the time of the change *-id > -ed* in this verb cannot be established yet, but it seems to have led to a semantic specialisation from a more general *ɣjid* 'to hold' to *ɣjed* 'to hold out (to receive)'.²²⁴ Accordingly, the etymological meaning of *bzid* can be reconstructed as **'holder'*.

By analogy with *lhuñ bzed*, in which the first constituent is the underlying root of the verb *lhuñ* 'to fall', I identify *reg* as a verb root and put forward the hypothesis that *reg* is an inherited form of the verb *rig* 'to know, to understand' preceding Dempsey's Law: *-e- > -i- / _C^[+velar]*.²²⁵ Now, the etymological meaning of the compound can be reconstructed as **'holder for knowledge'* (**reg paɣi bzid*). The reconstruction makes *reg bzid* an archaic compound that has preserved lexical units otherwise not encountered anymore in free forms even in OLT.

I reconstruct **reg zid* in Or.8212/187: 11 for this form is closer to the etymological one. All later forms in *-ig* came into being through folk etymology and the re-analysis of the compound as based on the word **gzigs* 'to look at'.

rol (#655) **INTR**(?) 'to hunt'

rol mo (#629) 'hunt'

In OLT, *rol mo* seems to have had the most general meaning 'amusement, entertainment'; cf. CT *rol* ¹to amuse or divert one's self; ²to take, taste, eat, drink; ³to practice sorcery, to cause to appear by magic power' (J: 536b–37a). In the OTA-I, its meaning 'hunt' is suggested by the next clause (ITJ 750: 233) in which wild yaks are fettered.

brlag (#656) **TR** [**AGT**]_{ERG} (?) [**PAT**]_{ABS} 'to overthrow'

OLT passages attest to *brlag* as a v2-stem of *√rlag*. In this case, we have to reconstruct the v3-stem of the verb as **grlag* and assume that the cluster **grl-* was allowed in PT but not in OLT. As a consequence of this restriction in OLT, new forms were coined: v2 *brlags* and v3

²²⁴ As a matter of fact, *ɣjid* seems to have undergone two changes: 1. *ɣjid > ɣjed* resulting in semantic specialisation; and 2. *ɣjid > ɣjin* (**ɣjid+n*) derived with the present participle suffix *-n* (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))).

²²⁵ (Hill 2019b: 12f.)

brlag (CDD.V: 1212 gives as v2 two forms: *brlags* ~ *brlag*). The 'defective' inflectional morphology of the verb might be connected to the fact that *brlag* was a denominal derived from *lag pa* 'hand': *lag* > r+√*lag* (r-derivation) > √*rlag* (see (Bialek 2024 (Forthcoming))). For its potential TH cognates, see STEDT #5670 **lag* hit/beat/strike.

I

lan (#653) 'return'

lug (#643) '(calendric) sheep'

lo (#541) ¹'annual report; ²'year'

The meaning 'year' derived from 'annual report'. The bridging context was formed by the very form of imperial annals. A council that at first convened once a year²²⁶ prepared reports on the most important events of the year. The reports were written down on wooden slips, one wooden slip for a report. The regular temporal frame of the councils and thus of the reports caused a metonymy '(annual) report' > 'settled date of a report' > 'year'. The shift from '(annual) report' to 'year' might have been triggered by borrowing of the Chinese calendar. The reports certainly existed prior to that because they were indispensable for the administration of the growing polity. The definition of a year as demarcated by convening of the council might have come with the duodenary cycle, in which every year was given its own name. We may even speculate whether the formula ANIMAL_{GEN} *lo* was not originally devised to denote an annual report from the period of the respective animal: '(annual) report of the ANIMAL'; if every year was given a name, then there was no need to repeat that the time unit is 'a year'. Compare the construction X_{GEN} *khirms la bab* (PT 1072: 164, PT 1075: 29, 30, 31), lit. '[It] fell on the law of X'. In the same vein ANIMAL_{GEN} *lo la bab* could have originally been understood as '[It] fell on the (annual) report of the ANIMAL'.

The proposed etymology of *lo* can be juxtaposed with the Slavic *rok* 'year' < Proto-Slavic **rokъ* 'settled date' < **rekti* 'to say' (Boryś 2005: 517).²²⁷ The original meaning '(annual) report' can be juxtaposed with: Rongpo *lə-/lwə-* 'sprechen, sagen' (Zoller 1983: 322); Darma *lo* 'language' (Willis Oko 2019: 52); Tshangla *lo* 'language, speech' (Andvik 2010: 12); and Bunan *lot* 'to say' (Widmer 2017: 752); < **lo+t* (-t = verbalising suffix (Widmer 2017: 133)). Tibetan *lo* also seems to be the source of the hearsay marker =*lo*, in which Zeisler saw "a defective verb 'to say'" (Zeisler 2004a: 890), although no other traces of such a verb could be found in Tibetic thus far.

log (#651) INTR/C [AGT]_{ABS} ¹'to turn; ²'to revolt'

log pho (#652) 'revolter'

²²⁶ According to the OTA, the year 673/4 was the first to host two councils.

²²⁷ Stein's statement that "[o]ne and the same Tibetan word (*lo*) means both 'year' and 'crop'" (Stein 1972: 117) can be confirmed neither in OLT nor CT sources. I deem it possible that *lo ma* 'leaf' was derived from *lo* 'year'.

ś

śa (#379) 'dead body'

For an explanation, see s.v. *gñard*.

śa liñs (#494) 'game hunt'

I proposed reconstructing the etymological meaning of *liñs* as *'a spread- or a carpet-hunt' (Bialek 2018a: 2.230). For the lack of more detailed information on the nature of the hunt, I interpret *śa-* in most general terms as referring to game animals. Alternatively, the rendering 'a stag/deer hunt' could be considered. The underlying structure of the compound can be reconstructed as **śa bayi liñs* 'a spread-hunt for game animals'.

śid (#495) 'funeral ceremony'

As I argue s.v. *bkaγ tañ*, *śid* seems to be the correct reading in ITJ 750: 142; previous proposals to 'amend' it to *śiñ* are unwarranted.²²⁸ Analysing the compound *mdad śid* (cf. (Bialek 2018a: 2.191ff.)), I argued that *śid* was derived from *śi* 'to die' by means of the deverbial suffix *-d*.²²⁹ In OLT, *śid* is used in the following collocations: *śid bgyi(d)*, *śid btañ/gtañ*, and *śid byas*. *śid* is frequently paired with terms that refer to various funeral edifices: *rmañ*, (*γ*)*brañ*, or *mčhad*. Erecting edifices and preparing a *śid* are mentioned as acts indispensable after death. A complete funeral consisted of erecting an edifice (i.e. a tomb and maybe also some accompanying ritual (?) buildings) and preparing or carrying out *śid*. Thus, it appears that *śid* was a general term denoting ceremonies related to funeral. However, Schiefner translated *śid dag* as 'Begräbnisfest' (Schiefner 1877: 11) and it is conceivable that the original meaning was more restricted but for the lack of concrete data, I propose the general translation as 'funeral ceremony'.

śuld (#496) ¹'tracks; ²'absence'

In OLT the syllable *śul* occurs most frequently as the second constituent of a toponym (cf. *mčhims śul*, *dags śul*, *rñegs śul* etc.). In these instances it is an assimilated form of *yul* (after the etymological *-s* of the preceding syllable)²³⁰ and should be kept apart from the etymological *śul*. In the remaining cases, OLT *śul* (in the OTA-I *śuld*) can be identified with the CT *śul* ¹'an empty place, a place that has been left, that is no longer occupied; ²track, rut, way, road; ³any thing left behind by a person departed or by a thing removed' (J: 560b–1a). Its original meaning could be reconstructed as *'tracks', i.e. a mark or line of marks left by sb./sth. in passing. Further development can be sketched as follows:

²²⁸ For a discussion of previous interpretations, see s.v. *bkaγ tañ*.

²²⁹ Ibid., p. 195. There I have also provided the meanings proposed previously for *śid* as well as its various derivatives. I refrain from repeating this information here.

²³⁰ Cf. (Bialek 2018a: 1.216, fn. 1).

In OLT two basic meanings can be discerned:

I. ‘way’

(1)

bdag čag ñan pa la śul bstan nas / (PT 126: 131; *apud* OTDO)

[You] showed us, the humble ones, the way.

II. ‘empty, deserted place; wilderness’

(2)

gžan ni śul riñ por spyug go (ITJ 753: v23; *apud* OTDO)

Regarding the other one, [he] was banished to a remote wilderness.

The semantics of the verb *spyug* in OLT necessitated the goal to which one was banished to be conceived of as space. Therefore the reading ‘[he] was banished on a long road’, just like in English, would make little sense.

In PT 1288: 6 *śuld* has to be analysed as the direct object of the TR verb *pyuñ*; ERG in *bcan po khri sroñ rcan gyis* clarifies that *pyuñ* is to be identified with CT *phyuñ* (v2 < *ybyin*) and not with CT *byuñ* (v2 < *ybyuñ*), which was an INTR verb also in OLT. The literal meaning of the clause seems to have been ‘*bcan po* Khri Sroñ-rcan caused [his] tracks to come forth on the northern road.’ The very next line of the text relates that the *Ya-ža* and the Chinese paid tribute. Our clause was to express the fact that the *bcan po* set out on the road to wage war against the *Ya-ža* and the Chinese.²³¹

In ITJ 750: 243, *śuld* forms part of the phrase *śuldu*. The latter recurs regularly in OLT documents and was previously explained as: ‘en chemin’ (DTH: 47); ‘on the way (sometimes = in supplement?)’ (TLTD.3: 185), ‘on the way’ (Dotson 2009b: 116) & (Hill 2011b: 35). As I have argued s.v. *bkay gyod*, the latter term was used to denote accusation of an illegal activity directed against a *bcan po*. In ITJ 750: 243, we read that the *bcan po* left for the *Ya-ža* land. The clause ends with the converb *gšegste* that may suggest that the following event was in some way related to it. *śuldu*, apart from the already mentioned meaning ‘on the way’, could also mean ‘in empty place’, i.e. ‘in place (of), in replacement, in compensation’:

śul du ybul (Or.15000/380: 3; *apud* OTDO) ‘to give in place (of)’

śul du scald (Or.15000/90: 2–3; *apud* OTDO) ‘to give in place (of)’

Accordingly two alternative translations can be proposed for the clause in ITJ 750: 243–4: 1. ‘On the way Dbays Sum-po-skyes indulged in an accusation’; or 2. ‘In [*bcan po*’s absence] Dbays Sum-po-skyes indulged in an accusation.’ The second variant is in so far more plausible

²³¹ These campaigns were also recorded in Chinese sources, cf. (Bushell 1880: 443–4), (Pelliot 1961: 3–5), and (Lee 1981: 6–10).

as Dbays Sum-po-skyes is not mentioned as accompanying the *bcan po* to the Xa-ža land. Since *bkay gyod* resulted from an activity against a *bcan po* and since it is less probable that Dbays Sum-po-skyes would have undertaken such an activity when accompanying the *bcan po* on a diplomatic mission, I tend to favour the second translation. Moreover, *śul* in the meaning ‘absence’ is attested in a CT text, in a very similar context:

(3)

ñas kyañ za dgos bsams te / bcun mo med paḡi śul du / lde chab kyis sgo phyas nas nañ du byon pa dañ / (GLR D 27r6)

[The king], having thought “I have to eat [it] too”, in the absence (*śul*) of the queen, who was not there, opened the door with a spare-key and went inside.

śo chigs (#497) ‘dice code’

śog śog (#498) ‘sheets of paper’

DTH: 52: *śog śog*; (Uebach 2008: 64) the duplication of the word *śog* in the term *śog śog* cannot be explained with certainty. It may refer to ‘single sheets (or: pieces) of paper’, ‘a multitude of paper’, to ‘paper for each’ or to the material of paper in general; (Dotson 2009b: 124) paper; (Cairangsan Zhou 2022: 12, fn. 5) probably an onomatopoeic word [...] imitating the rustling sound that sheet of paper makes when someone touches it. [...] Another possibility is that the word for rustling sound *śog* was already there in OT, and duplicate *śog śog* was developed for paper.

I put forward the hypothesis that *śog śog* is a reduplicated form of *śog*, orig. ‘leaf’. After Tibetans had come into contact with paper via the Chinese, the latter lexeme formed the basis from which a new term for the newly introduced device was coined. Compare in this context Ger. *Blatt* that also encompasses both meanings ‘sheet (of paper)’ and ‘leaf’. As it seems, *śog* could refer to any flat and thin object for it came to denote ‘wing’ of birds too. I consider *śog śog* to have been originally coined with a collective meaning *‘a bundle of sheets’ and subsequently, via metonymy, started to be used as a general term for the material, i.e. ‘paper’. The latter semantic change might have occurred already in OLT as we find *śog śog* measured in *yug* (cf., e.g., PT 1078r: 1, 2; ITJ 1274: 1; *apud* OTDO). The popular CT term *śog bu* ‘paper; sheet of paper’ does not seem to be attested in OLT documents.

gśegs (#650) INTR [AGT]_{ABS} ‘HON ¹to go (to [DIR]_{TERM}); ²to come (to [DIR]_{TERM}); ³to depart’

As an intransitive verb *gśegs* always has an explicitly stated subject; in the OTA it is: {*b*}*can mo* Mun-čhañ koñ čo, *bcan po* Khri Sroñ-rcan, *bcan mo* Khri-bañs, *bcan po*, *pho brañ*, and *bcan po* Khri Xdus-sroñ. Therefore, there can be no doubt that *gśegs* belongs to the honorific register.

When used as a simple verb *gśegs* attests to the following argument structures:

$S_{ABS} DIR_{TERM}$ ¹to go to; ²to come to’
 S_{ABS} ³to depart’

Apart from its use as a simple verb, *gśegs* forms three idiomatic expressions:

dguñ du gśegs ‘to die’, lit. ‘to go to the sky’, used only of *bcan pos*;

čhab srid la gšegs 'to go in support of the foreign policy'²³²
bag mar gšegs 'to get married (to ALL)', lit. 'to go as bride'

In all these phrases, the original meaning of *gšegs* is still tangible.

Concerning the etymology of *gšegs*, due to it being an honorific, we may assume that the attested meanings came into being as a result of a metaphorical extension of another, primary meaning. Since *gšegs* does not have any overt cognates in OLT (or, for that matter, in CT) it is difficult to relate it to any other lexeme. However, it has an unusual v4 form: *šog*, and there is a dialectally attested superlative morpheme with the forms *šog* ~ *šogs* ~ *šos* (cf. J: 564a–b & CDTD: 8642), which I tentatively relate to the v4 of *gšegs*.²³³ It is feasible that the verb was originally transitive and its inflected forms were: v1 *gšegs*, v2 **bšags*, v3 **bšag*, v4 *šogs*. This would make it another member of the verb family of $\sqrt{\text{čag}}$ 'to split' (see (Bialek 2020a: 338, Fig. 3)).²³⁴ The verb might have undergone semantic specialisation towards **'to stride, to pace'*.²³⁵

bšig (#632) TR/C [AGT]_{ERG} [PAT]_{ABS} '1to destroy; 2to severe'

[C] *žig*

ITJ 750: 278 confirms the argument structure TR-EA. The verb, derived from $\sqrt{\text{čig}}$, is a transitive equivalent of *žig* ($\sqrt{\text{žig}}$; see s.v.)

bšos (#654) TR [AGT]_{ERG} (?) [COMP]_{COM} 'to live with'

²³² For a more detailed discussion of *čhab srid* and its collocations, see (Bialek 2022c).

²³³ The original v4 of *gšegs* seems to have been **šogs*. In OLT *šog* is unanimously connected with the form *šig* of the imperative clitic (see OTDO) which could be attached only to syllables with the final -s. The final -s is also confirmed by Balti *šoxs* ((Hill 2014c: 95); this stem is not provided in CDTD: 1262). The following development can be suggested: **šogs šig* > *šog šig* (elision of -s before another sibilant) > *šog* = v4.

²³⁴ The reconstruction of v2 **bšags* and v3 **bšag* was put forward by (Hill 2014c: 94ff.) on the basis of Balti form *faxs* (CDTD: 1262; Hill: *šaxs*). Since Balti verbs reflect OLT v2-stems, *faxs* attests to a final -s. The verb-family quoted in (Bialek 2020a: 338, Fig. 3) should be amended on this point in accordance with Hill's suggestion.

²³⁵ If this analysis is correct then the root of *gšegs* can be reconstructed as $\sqrt{\text{čag}}$.

S

†**sa ris** (#499) 'territory'

< **sayi ris* *'a division of land'. For a detailed analysis, see (Bialek 2018a: 2.575ff.)

ser po (#644) 'yellow'

so (#791) '†border'

so phyogs (#762) 'border region'

so so (#500) 'group of individuals/single items'

(Simon 1941: 386) reduplication of *so* 'place'; (Uray 1954a: 191) < *so* 'place'; (Wayman 1987: 52) respective; p. 55, fn. 5: skt. *abhinna*.

In (Bialek 2018a: 2.583, fn. 3), I put forward the hypothesis that *so so*, CT 'distinct, singly, individually' (J: 578b), is a reduplication of *so* *'spot'. I have reconstructed its original meaning as *'spotty, punctual'. Since *so so* can acquire case markers (cf. ITJ 750: 307), it was undoubtedly a noun. I assume that, as in the case of *śog śog*, the reduplication added the sense of collectivity: *so* 'spot' > *so so*, lit. 'a group of spots/single items'. The literal translation of *so sor* (ITJ 750: 307) would be 'as a group of individuals', i.e. 'separately'.

sog ma (#501) 'straw'

In (Bialek 2018a: 2.594) I argued that *sog rild* in ITJ 750: 209 is an error for *sog ma*, attested independently in ITJ 750: 211.

sog rild

See s.v. *sog ma*.

slar (#794) **Adv** 'back'

In the OTA *slar* can occur in two positions in a clause, either directly before the verb:

(1)

bcan po yab dgun bod yul du slar gśegs/ (ITJ 750: 282)

In the winter, the *bcan po*, the father, returned to the Bod land.

or before another argument:

(2)

bcan po dbyard mcho bgoe bol gañs na bźugs pa las/ slar bod yul du gśegste/ (ITJ 750: 248)

In the summer, the *bcan po*, upon abiding in Bol-gañs of Mcho-bgo, came back to the Bod land.

As in the above examples, the position may vary but apparently only with verbs of going if the respective clause also contains an oblique argument that expresses the direction of the movement. With other verbs (e.g. *γkhord*, *thob*, *log*) the adverb regularly takes the preverbal position.

In terms of its etymology, *slar* is derived from root **sla* 'hind part, back part' (see (Bialek 2018a.2: 367f.)) by means of the terminative clitic *-r*, but it is already highly lexicalised in OLT.

sras (#502) 'HON son'

(Hahn 2003b: 88) *cha* 'Nachkommen' + infix *-r-* + suffix *-s* > **ch-r-a-s* 'einer, der zum Nachkommen geworden ist, Nachkömmling' > *sras*.

In (Bialek 2018a: 2.152, fn. 5, s.v. *tho ras*), I put forward the hypothesis that *sras* is cognate with *γdra* 'similar, equal; ^{2.1}resemblance, likeness; ^{2.2}form, shape, appearance, phase' (J: 282a-3a) and *ras* 'shine, light, glare'. Its etymological meaning has tentatively been reconstructed as 'semblance' (ibid.). The shift to the honorific register appeared through the metaphorical extension of the basic meaning 'semblance' via '[one's] semblance' to '[one's] offspring' (Bialek 2023c: 316, Table 6). In the OTA, the word is used exclusively to denote a male offspring, in fact, a heir to the throne.

†sluñs (#763) 'stage station'

WtS.10: 219a: Poststation (s.v. *go bar*).

(Thomas 1933: 385) a tribal designation; the *Sluñs* were a people who had established an aptitude for police, camp-servants, camp-followers, etc; (Lalou 1955: 206) nom d'un district supprimé; (Macdonald 1971: 325) relais; (Hoffmann 1972: 199f.) it seems to be very probable, that *sluñs* in the Tibetan documents from Chinese Turkestan and *sluñs-se* in *Ž[añ]-ž[un]* are the same word, meaning not 'military police' but just 'corps d'élite of young men' who were recruited from the tributary *Žaň-žuň* people. Tibetan *sluñs* which occurs only in the 8th and 9th centuries' documents should, therefore, be interpreted as a *Žaň-žuň* loan word; (Uray 1984: 358-9, fn. 56) the Tibetan *kluñ rta/rluñ rta* is the translation of the Chinese 驛馬 *i-ma* 'post-horse'. Consequently the first syllables *kluñ* 'walley (sic!), river' and *rluñ* 'wind' both are spellings of folk etymology and they in fact substitute for Old Tibetan *sluñs*, which nowadays is not used independently, and means 'stage' or rather 'postmaster' according to Mme A. Macdonald's interpretation; BDN: 58: *luñ lam kluñs te yul dañ gnas kyi don*; (Dotson 2009b: 52, fn. 73) upper and lower way-station [officials]; p. 112, fn. 263: as a term for a unit of distance traversed by a messenger, constituted about thirty *li* (*le dbar*), or approximately fifteen kilometers. The intermittent stops are called *sluñs chañs*, and these are headed by *sluñs dpon*; p. 261: way station associated with the transport network; abbreviation for *sluñs dpon*; (Hill 2010a: 121b) ~ *kluñ* ~ *ltuñ* ~ *lhuñ* (s.v. *ltuñ*); (Dotson 2015b: 285) way station.

For a detailed analysis of the relay system of the Tibetan Empire, see (Bialek 2021b).

gsar (#647) 'new'

gsar bu (#648) 'young adult'

gsar bu is attested in Thebo with two meanings: ¹'adult; ²'young' (Lin 2014: 247a & 267b). In the given context of Or.8212/187: 23, the most appropriate translation seems to be 'adult; young adult, youth'.

gsum (#645) '1three; 2third'

gser khral (#646) 'tax in gold'

< **gser gi khral*, lit. 'tax of gold' (descriptive genitive), i.e. tax that is paid in gold.

gser zañs (#649) 'golden pot'

gsold (#715) **DITR** [AGT]_{ERG} [REC/BEN]_{ABS} [THEM]_{ABS} (v1 **gsold*, v2 *gsold*, v3 *gsold*) 'HML 1to give, to offer; 2to bestow'

In the OTA-I verb *gsold* is used with two distinct argument structures:

I. HUM_{ABS} O_{ABS} *gsold* '[one] bestowed HUM with O'

(1)

blon khri ybriñ gyis / dgun (Čhos-yphel) glagī pu čhuñ du bsduste / [bcan po]_{o2} khri (93) ydu{s} sroñ du [mchan]_o gsold / (ITJ 750)

[Grand] councillor [Mgar] Khri-ybriñ [Bcan-brod],²³⁶ having convened the winter [council] at Pu-čhuñ of Glag, bestowed the *bcan po* with the name Khri Xdus-sroñ.

(2)

ybon da rgyal dañ / blon chen pho khri gzī(185)gs gyīs / {ydun ma} lha gab gyī bye ma luñ du bsduste / [btsan poe mtshan]_o rgyal gtsug (186) ru las / khri lde gtsug rtsan du gsold / (ITJ 750)
dbon [Bcan-zuñ], the king of the Dags-po, and grand councillor [Dbays] Khri-gzigs [Žaň-ñen] convened [the council] at Bye-ma-luñ of Lha-gab; [they] bestowed the name of the *bcan po* as Khri Lde-gcug-rcan instead of Rgyal-gcug-ru.²³⁷

II. S_{ERG} O_{ABS} *gsold* 'S offered O (to an HON-person)'

(3)

bcan po dpyid že šiñ du gšegste / bcan mo khri mo lan gyīs / ston mo čhen po (63) gsold / ybon da rgyal khri zuñ gyīs / gser zañs čhen po gsold pha dañ / (ITJ 750)

The *bcan po* went in the spring to Že-šiñ. *bcan mo* Khri-mo-lan gave a great feast [for the *bcan po* whereas] *dbon* Khri-zuñ, the king of the Dags-po, offered [him] a large golden pot.

(4)

(83) *[bruñ pa lho ybriñ po rgyal sum sregs gyīs]_s / ñen kar du [ybul skyems]_o gsold (ITJ 750)*

At Ñen-kar, *bruñ pa* Lho Xbriñ-po Rgyal-sum-sregs offered a libation [to the *bcan po*].

²³⁶ In the preceding clause we read that councillor Mgar Khri-ybriñ Bcan-brod was appointed grand councillor but he is still called 'councillor' here as well as in the following two years: 686/7 (l. 94) and 687/9 (l. 97). First starting with the year 689/90 he is consequently referred to as 'grand councillor'.

²³⁷ Cf.: [---] *skyi yi lha luñ du y / bcan po mu cu brtan las // khri gcug lde brcan du mchan gsol pa [---]* (PT 1290: r2) 'At Lha-luñ of Skyi, [they] bestowed the *bcan po* with the name Khri Gcug-lde-brcan instead of Mu-cu-brtan.'

Ex. (3) consists of three clauses; the first one has *bcan po* as subject and the following two contain the verb *gsold* but do not mention the recipient which, due to the humble register of *gsold*, should be identified with the *bcan po*.²³⁸ The subject is omitted from the next clause, but the verb *bžugs* makes it clear that it is still *bcan po*. It appears that *bcan po* remains the pivot in four consecutive clauses:

S *gśegste*
 (IO) *gsold*
 (IO) *gsold*
 (S) *bžugs*

All verbs are marked for the register and the missing arguments have to be complemented pragmatically. The analysis of (4) is similar. At the beginning of the annual entry, we read that the *bcan po* was abiding in *Ñen-kar* – the place at which *bruñ pa* Lho *ᠬbriñ-po-rgyal* Sum-sregs offered a libation. In both quotations the recipient of *gsold* can be identified with *bcan po* due to the register of the verb.

In order to clarify the difference between the structures and to elucidate the semantics of *gsol* I quote several passages from the OLT inscriptions, ordered chronologically following the dating put forward in (Bialek 2021c):²³⁹

(5)
bod (13) *mgo nag poyi srid nī ḡkhrug du* (14) *byed pa las / klu khoñ gis / ḡbal* (15) *dañ / lañ glo ba riñs payī gtan* (16) *gcigs // bcan pho sras khri sroñ* (17) *lde brcan gyi sñan du **gsold** nas* (Žol S)

Upon [they] were plunging the government of the black-headed Tibetans into chaos, *Klu-khoñ* **provided** (lit. offered) evidence of *ᠬbal* and *Lañ*'s disloyalty to the *bcan pho*, the son *Khri Sroñ-lde-brcan*.

(6)
ñan lam klu khoñ gis // rgya yul gyī thild / rgya (54) *rjeyī pho brañ keñ śir / bod gyīs dmag drañ* (55) *baḡi bkaḡ gros gyī mgo čhen pho **gsold** nas* / (Žol S)

Ñan-lam Klu-khoñ started (lit. **offered** the beginning of) a council [that concerned] Tibetans leading an army to *Keñ-śi*, the centre of China [and] the court of the Chinese ruler.

(7)
de las (13) *mnaḡ kha dbud pa dag gyañ /* (14) *myi bgyī myi bsgyur bar / [ḡjīg* (15) *rten las / ḡdays pay dañ /* (16) *ḡjīg rten gyi lha dañ / myī ma yin* (17) *pay / thams čad gyañ*]_{ADD} *dphañ du /* (18) ***gsol** te / bcan po yab sras dañ* (19) *rje blon gun gyis dbu sñuñ dañ bro /* (20) *bor ro /* (Bsam)

Thereupon, the words of the oath (that had been pronounced (lit. set free)), were **presented** to all the gods that had abandoned this world and those worldly ones, as well as

²³⁸ The agents are *bcan mo* and *ḡbon da rgyal*, respectively. *gsold* leaves no doubt that a person of status higher than those is the recipient; thus, it must be the *bcan po* from the preceding clause.

²³⁹ I only quote clauses that are complete and provide us further information on the argument structure of the verb.

non-human beings as witnesses, so that [they] would not be fabricated nor changed; the *bcan po*, father and son, together with all the lords and councillors solemnised a vow and swore an oath [respectively].

(8)

gčen kar po nī / thog ma yas gśegs paḡī che // [mčhed gñīs kyī / sku bla gñan po]_{ABS} gsol ba dañ / (Rkoñ 6)

Regarding the elder brother Kar-po, when [he] first came down from above, [he] was **worshipping**²⁴⁰ the fierce tutelary deity of both brothers.

(9)

deñ sañ (10) du khab so dpon sna dagīs // khral gyī sna ḡchal te / gces sīñ mčhis na // nam duḡaṅ bde bar thugs bag mjad paḡī // gcīgs caṡ žīg čī gnañ žes (11) gsold nas // (Rkoñ)

“When nowadays the heads of *khab sos*, desirous of [different] sorts of taxes, come hassling, would [you] grant [us] a sole edict, that would pay regard to [our] happiness for ever?” Thus it was **requested**.

(10)

rgyal brcan gyī rgyud kyañ rabs čhad na // ñe ḡchams las // [kha čhems kyīs]_{ERG} [gañ]_{ABS} // gsol baḡī nañ nas // spus dañ (17) sbyard te // gañ ḡos pa gčīg scald bar gnañ ño // (Rkoñ)

It is granted that if also the lineage of Rgyal-brcan has become extinct, from among those from [his] close relatives (*ñe ḡchams*) who (*gañ*) had been **benefited** by [his] will (*kha čhems*), a suitable one (lit. the one who is suitable), being characterised by (lit. corresponding with) [good] qualities, shall be appointed.

(11)

spyīr [legs paḡī bka gros]_{ABS} gsol čīñ / las su byas pa (9) las scogs te / dpen pa byed byed sñīñ ñe ñeḡo // (Žwa W)

Doing what is beneficial – the **given** advice, that was generally good, and what [he] did as [his] works, among others, – [he] remained loyal.

(12)

kha čīg phan phun dañ / gdon scon pa dag (12) yod pa yañ / ban de tiñ ñe ḡjīn kyīs ñaṡ drod zin nas / [dpend (13) paḡī bka gros]_{ABS} gsold / khrag khruḡ myed par byas / (Žwa W)

ban de Tiñ-ñe-ḡjīn took the initiative against those who had triggered dissension and demons and **offered** counsels that were beneficial.

(13)

[ban de ñīd]_{ABS} rjes ḡbañs kyī (22) lugs dañ / dge sloñ ḡi chul ḡjīn čīñ / bka drīn myī nod par gsol gyīs (23) kyañ / žo śaḡi lan / bka drīn sbyin paḡī čhos yin pas // ñaḡī bkas / (Žwa W)

Even though it was **requested** that *ban de* himself, while adhering (lit. holding) to the manner of courtiers, as well as to the way of a monk, does not receive any favour, since

²⁴⁰ In this sentence *gsol ba dañ* is coordinated with *bgyīd kyīs kyañ*. Because the latter verb is v1, I assume *gsol* should be likewise read as v1. The meaning ‘to worship’ developed from ‘to make offerings’ < ‘to offer’.

the return for a contribution is the custom of bestowing a favour, by my order [this was decided].

(14)

[*de skad* (33) *čes*]_{ABS} / [*čhe čhuñ sus*]_{ERG} **gsold** *kyis kyañ* / *de ltar myi mjad do* // (Skar)

Even if somebody, great or small, **uttered** these words, one shall not act like that.

(15)

de las mnay kha (53) *dbud pa dag myi bgyi myi bsgyur bar* // [*γjig rten las γdas pa dañ γjig* (54) *rten gyi lha dañ myi ma yin pa thams čad kyañ*]_{ADD} / *dpañ du gsol te* // *bcan po* / (55) *rje blon kun kyis kyañ* / *dbu sñuñ dañ* / *bro bor ro* // (Skar)

Thereupon, the words of the oath (that had been pronounced (lit. set free)), were **presented** to all the gods that had abandoned this world and those worldly ones, as well as non-human beings as witnesses, so that [they] would not be fabricated nor changed; the *bcan po* together with all the lords and councillors solemnised a vow and swore an oath [respectively].²⁴¹

(16)

[*ban de ñid* (8) *kyis*]_{ERG} / *bkaγ drin myi nod par gsol nas* // (Žwa E)

ban de himself **requested** not to receive any favour.

(17)

ban de tiñ ñe γjin kyis / *ñayī ža sñar čhab srīd* (12) **gsol nas** / *ñayī sku riñ la* / *sku dañ čhab srīd la γphral* (13) *yun gñis su legs paγī bkaγ gros gsold čin* (14) *spyir dpen paγī las čhen po byas pa dañ* / (Žwa E)

ban de Tiñ-ñe-γjin **conferred** dominion on me. Thereafter, while **offering** counsels that were good to the person [of the *bcan po*] and to the realm during my lifetime in the past and in the future, [he] performed great deeds that were generally impeccable.

(18)

ban de ni gcigs (18) *sñar gnañ bas γchal te myi bskyed par gsol gyis* (19) *kyañ žo ša čhen poγi lan* / *bkaγ drin myi γpham bar sbyin paγī* (20) *rigs par* / *rje blon mol nas* / (Žwa E)

Even though *ban de*, having beseeched [me], **requested** that [it] should not be increased more than the previously granted edict, lords and councillors discussed that the return for a great contribution must be given so that the favour is not vanquished.

(19)

gcigs bčas pa γdī // (61) *nam žar myi γgyur bar* // [*dkon mčhog* (62) *gsum dañ* // *γphags paγī rnam dañ* (63) *gñi zla dañ gza skar la yañ*]_{ALL/ADD} *dpañ du* (64) **gsol te** // *tha chīg gī rnam pas kyañ* (65) *bśad* // (ST Treaty W)

Having **presented** this prepared edict to the Three Jewels, Noble ones, the sun and the moon, planets and stars as witnesses, so that [it] never changes, [they] explained [it] with a promise.

²⁴¹ This passage seems to be dependent in its wording on the above quoted fragment from the Bsam inscription (ll. 12–20).

Table 1 summarises the surveyed clauses with *gsol*. The clauses are grouped according to the semantics and the surface structure of the verb arguments:²⁴²

	Argument 1	Argument 2	Verb	Example
1.	REC _{ABS}	THEM _{ABS}	<i>gsold</i>	1
	THEM _{ABS}		<i>gsol(d)</i>	2
2.	THEM _{ABS/ADD}	REC _{ADD}	<i>gsol te</i>	7
	THEM _{ABS}	REC _{ADD}	<i>gsol te</i>	15
	THEM _{ABS}	REC _{ALL/ADD}	<i>gsol te</i>	19
3.	INSTR _{ERG}	REC _{ABS}	<i>gsol</i>	10
4.	AGT _{ERG}	THEM _{ABS}	<i>gsold</i>	3, 4, 5, 6, 17
	(AGT _{ERG})	THEM _{ABS}	<i>gsold</i>	8, 11, 12, 14

Table 1. Argument structure of *gsol*

Some of the passages (groups 1–3) lack the agent argument. In (1) and (2), the last explicitly mentioned agents are councillor Mgar Khri-ybriñ Bcan-brod, *dbon* Bcan-zuñ, and grand councillor Dbays Khri-gzigs Žaň-ñen. Their main duty was to convene a council. Because they held very distinct positions (councillor, ruler of a semi-independent polity, and grand councillor), we can presume that it was not a particular person responsible for bestowing the name on a *bcan po* but rather the collective summoned during the councils. Also the clause quoted from PT 1290 (see fn. 237), although possibly lacking some constituents, does not seem to have contained an agent; the preserved fragment starts with a locative adjunct (*skyīyi lha luñ duy*) that conventionally begins a clause and it would be highly unusual if the agent would have preceded it.²⁴³ Thus, all the clauses of group 1 lack underlying agents.²⁴⁴

Similarly in the clauses of group 2 no agent seems to be indicated. In my understanding, their theme arguments stand in absolutive and belong to the semantic field of UTTERANCE (‘words of the oath’, ‘edict’).²⁴⁵ All three clauses acquire an additional argument that is marked with additive. I interpret these as recipients of the words (= theme) because they denote the addressees of the activity expressed by the verb *gsol*. The first two passages have the recipient argument standing in absolutive but in the ST Treaty (the youngest of the

²⁴² In exx. (13), (16), (18), *gsol* takes a verbal complement, whereas in (9) *gsold* is a verb of speaking.

²⁴³ In the OTA-I, the order agent–adjunct–verb is possible only if the agent refers to a remarkable person such as a *bcan po*.

²⁴⁴ The general syntax of name-giving in OLT is discussed in more detail in (Dotson 2015a: 23ff.) Although the latter author states that “[i]n the *Chronicle*’s ‘primal scene’ of name-giving as coronation, it is the councilors who bestow the royal name” (ibid. p. 24) I could not identify any passage in which councillors were overtly the agent. Instead, the only instance in which agents of naming can be unanimously identified in the text is:

yul ñas po yi (188) *ybañs // dbays dbyi chab la scogs pas // bcan po yi mchan gsol pa //* (PT 1287)
Subjects of the Ñas-po land such as Dbays Dbyi-chab offered a name for the *bcan po*.

In the following passage *myi yoñs kyis* can but does not have to be understood as the agent of *gsol*, cf.:

myi yoñs (455) *kyis bkay drin dran žiñ chor bas // sroñ brcan sgam po žes mchan gsol to* (PT 1287)

Because all the people, while remembering [his] kindness, were aware (lit. knew) [of it], [they] gave [him] the name Sroñ-brcan Sgam-po.

²⁴⁵ For this interpretation of *mnaγ kha* see (Bialek 2018a: 2.234f.) OLT *gcigs*, lit. ‘edict’, is derived from *chig* ‘word’ (cf. also (Li 1955: 58), (Li and Coblin 1987: 85)).

inscriptions under discussion) the recipient is marked with allative. Authors who previously studied the inscriptions translated *gsol* in these cases as ‘to invoke’ (Richardson 1985: 31, , 81, 127), (Li and Coblin 1987: 80, 190, 328), (Doney 2014: 70), (Willis 2014: 251). They have also interpreted recipient as addressees. This interpretation could work in the case of Bsam and Skar, but in the ST Treaty the analogous argument is marked with allative that precludes its interpretation as theme. Hence, the rendering ‘to invoke’ is purely contextual and based on a flawed interpretation of the clauses. With no agent but with a theme and a recipient I understand the verb *gsol* in group 2 literally as ‘to be offered’, i.e. the words of the oath and the edict were presented (lit. offered) to various entities as witnesses because these entities were conceived of as everlasting.

In Rkoñ 16 (group 3), the context makes it clear that *gañ* must have had a human referent²⁴⁶ that has to be interpreted as the recipient argument standing in absolutive. Therefore, the clause lacks not only agent but also theme. This passage demonstrates most clearly the ‘defective’ character of *gsol* when compared with its classical and modern uses. Furthermore, the clause contains an instrument that is marked with ergative, lit. ‘by means of [sb.’s] last will’. This type of clause, with ergative originally marking Instrument, might have undergone reinterpretation from ‘by means of’ (the referent of instrument = [-ANIM]) towards ‘by’ (referent of instrument = [+HUM]). The change might have eventually led to the interpretation of *gsol* as a prototypical transitive verb with agent in ergative and theme in absolutive along the following lines:

THEM_{ABS} (REC_{ABS})²⁴⁷ *gsol*_{INTR} ‘THEM was offered (to sb.)’
 INSTR_{ERG} REC_{ABS} *gsol*_{INTR} ‘REC was offered by means of INSTR’
 AGT_{ERG} THEM_{ABS} *gsol* ‘THEM was offered by AGT’ > ‘AGT offers THEM’

The agentive reinterpretation of the last structure yielded a new understanding of the verb that now turned to a transitive one. It goes without saying that the change was not linear and a new structure did not just replace the preceding one but they all might have co-existed for some time.

A separate problem concerns the semantics of *gsol* that is once used to refer to an action of offering, once of requesting. The actions of offering and requesting have distinct vectors. In the first case, the subject offers sth. actively to sb., whereas in the latter, the subject requests sth. from sb. Their common denominator is the addressee of the action: in our passages it is always a person of respect, higher in social hierarchy than the agent. This confirms that we are dealing with one verb. The disagreement between the two senses of *gsol* might be patched up by recalling the etymology of the verb. I agree with CDTD (V: 998 & 1343) that *gsol* is cognate with *scol* (see s.v. *scald*) but I also add to these *ychal* and *ychol* (see s.v. *ychald*). *gsol* seems to have been derived from *scold*, v4 of *scol* (*g-* + *scold* > **gscold* > *gsold*). The

²⁴⁶ We can juxtapose *gañ gsol ba*, lit. ‘someone who was offered’, with *gañ γos pa gčīg*, lit. ‘the one who is suitable’ from the next clause of the same passage.

²⁴⁷ Recipient in this position, i.e. immediately preceding the verb, and accompanying another argument in absolutive is marked with additive, indicating here extended transitivity (see (Bialek 2023b: 5–6)).

etymological meaning of v4 *scold* (i.e. static passive) can be reconstructed as *‘is bestowed’.²⁴⁸ *gsold* took over the meaning after the v4-stems started to be used preponderantly in imperative constructions with *čig*.²⁴⁹ It follows that *-d* originally formed part of the stem, but was abandoned in v1 at some point by analogy with the intransitive conjugational pattern: v1 $\sqrt{\text{ }}$, v2 $\sqrt{\text{ }}+s$.

²⁴⁸ On stative passive interpretation of v4-stems, see (Bialek 2020a). But the opinions on the semantics of *gsol* especially taken in diachrony differ among scholars, cf.: “*gsol* primarily indicates an inquiry, a request submitted to a person of higher rank, but as a manifestation characteristic of the hierarchic relation of persons it is used secondarily also to denote any action or happening in which a lower-ranking person gives, passes on something a higher-ranking person or which a high-ranking persons (sic) receives or obtains something. Accordingly, the meanings of *gsol* could be summed up as follows: 1. ‘to ask (a person of higher rank)’; 2. A) in a transitive sense ‘to give, to hand over (to a higher-ranking person)’; B) in an intransitive sense ‘(a higher-ranking person) obtains, receives (clothing; food, drink, medicine; name; into his hands, [figuratively] in his possession)’ (Uray 1964a: 333); “the semantic range of *gsol* ‘take; eat, drink; wear’ can all be derived from an original sense of ‘take, accept’” (DeLancey 1998: 120f.)

²⁴⁹ See an analogous semantic development in Pol.: *zapraszać* ‘to invite’ is derived from *prosić* ‘to ask’. The latter verb was used in OPol. also in the meanings ‘*ugaszczać*’ (lit. ‘to offer (food or stay) as a host’) and ‘*częstować*’ (lit. ‘to serve up, to offer’); cf. (Boryś 2005: 484a–b) and <https://sjp.pwn.pl/doroszewski/prosic-l;5482034.html>; accessed 06.11.2023. The Polish lexemes derive from PIE *perk-/prek-/prk- ‘to ask, to beg’ (Boryś, *ibid.*) from which also Ger. *fragen* originates (Kluge and Seebold 2011: 313b).

h

lhag čad (#503) 'deficiency'

<*lhag par γčhad, lit. 'to be consumed so that it (i.e. the consumption) is exceeding'. For a detailed analysis, see (Bialek 2018a: 2.602f., s.v. *lhag čhad*).

q

Primary Corpus

PT 1288	<i>Old Tibetan Annals</i>
ITJ 750	<i>Old Tibetan Annals</i>
Or.8212/187	<i>Old Tibetan Annals</i>

Abbreviations and symbols

√	reconstructed verb root
[...]	passage left out
#123	lemma's number in the OTD
*	form/meaning reconstructed
†	archaic word or meaning
!	form not attested or blocked
>	'evolved into'
<	'developed from'
~	'alternates with'
3SG	third person singular
ABS	absolutive
ADD	additive
ADDR	addressee
Adj	adjective
Adv	adverb
AGT	agent
ALL	allative
AT	Amdo Tibetan dialect group
BEN	beneficiary
Bsam	Bsam-yas inscription
C	controllable verb
[C]	<i>gum</i> = cognates included in the OTD
[C]	<i>gum</i> = cognates not yet included in the OTD
cA	controllable verb/absolutive
cAD	controllable verb/absolutive-dative
cEA	controllable verb/ergative-absolutive
cED	controllable verb/ergative-dative
cEDA	controllable verb/ergative-dative-absolutive
Ch.	Chinese
CL	clitic
COM	comitative
COP	copula
CT	Classical Tibetan
CtrT	Central Tibetan dialect group
D	Sde-dge edition
DEL	relative

DEM	demonstrative
DIM	diminutive
DIR	direction
DIST	distal
DITR	ditransitive
DO	direct object
Dx.	Дуньхуан
E	east-facing inscription
EL	elative
Eng.	English
EOT	Early Old Tibetan
ERG	ergative
EXP	experiencer
<i>fig.</i>	figurative(ly)
FOC	focus
FUN	function
<i>gen</i>	genitive
Ger.	German
GO	goal
Gr.	Greek
HML	humble
HON	honorific
HT	Hor Tibetan dialect group
HUM	human
IO	indirect object
INESS	inessive
INTR	intransitive
IO	indirect object
INSTR	instrument
ITJ	IOL Tib J
ITN	IOL Tib N
Kh.	Khotanese
Khra	inscription on the Khra-γbrug bell
KT	Kham Tibetan dialect group
Lat.	Latin
Lčaṅ	Lcaṅ-bu inscription
LH	Later Han Chinese
LOC	location

LT	Literary Tibetan
Lw.	loanword
M	masculine
MAL	maleficiary
MC	middle Chinese
met.	metaphoric(ally)
MOT	Middle Old Tibetan
MT	modern Tibetan
N	noun
NC	non-controllable
ncA	non-controllable/absolutive
ncDA	non-controllable/dative-absolutive
NP	noun phrase
NW	North-western
O	object
OBL	oblique
OC	Old Chinese
OCM	Minimal Old Chinese
OHG	Old High German
OLT	Old Literary Tibetan
ONW	Old Northwest Chinese
OPol.	Old Polish
Or.	Oriental Collections of the British Library
ORIG	origin
orig.	original(ly)
OT	Old Tibetan
OTA	<i>Old Tibetan Annals</i>
OTC	<i>Old Tibetan Chronicles</i>
OTurk.	Old Turkic
PAT	patient
PIE	Proto-Indo-European
PLB	Proto-Lolo-Burmese
Pol.	Polish
POSTP	postposition
PP	postpositional phrase
PT	¹ Proto-Tibetic; ² Pelliot tibétain
PTH	Proto-Trans-Himalayan
PY	Pinyin

Q	oblique
QUOT	quotation
REC	receiver
RES	result
Rkoñ	Rkoñ-po inscription
RN	relator noun
RSFNL	reported speech final clitic
S	¹ subject; ² south-facing inscription
SEP	separation
Skar	Skar-čuñ inscription
Skt.	Sanskrit
SOUR	source
ST	Southern Tibetan dialect group
ST Treaty	Sino-Tibetan Treaty inscription
STIM	stimulus
TERM	terminative
TH	Trans-Himalayan
THEM	theme
Tib.	Tibetan
TR	transitive
trslr.	transliteration
V	verb
[V]	variant spelling
v1, v2, v3, v4	verb stems
VP	verb phrase
W	west-facing inscription
WAT	Western Archaic Tibetan dialect group
Žol	Žol inscription
Žwa	Žwa-lhayi khañ inscription

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